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1. PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF PRACTICAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF THE ACADEMIC LYCEUM OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
1-6 Ismailov Alisher Ulugbekovich
2. INFLUENCE OF SUNSHINE (IN HOURS) ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STROKES AMONG THE POPULATION IN SOUTHERN KYRGYZSTAN
7-11 Umurzakova G. I., Mamasaliev N. S., Baigashkaev E. S., Boljirova E. Sh., Ergeshova A. M., Chekirbajeva N. E., Argynbaeva A. T., Z. N.Mamasoliev
3. SOCIAL- PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERRELATION OF FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILD INTELLECT
12-15 Oimatova Dilorom Ruzimurotovna
4. USING INTERESTING METHODS AND OBSERVATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR ELEMENTARY CLASS PUPILS TO UNDERSTAND SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS
313-318 Bobomurodov Kupaysin Abduvayitovich
5. PRAGMALINGUODIDACTIC CHALLENGES: ENHANCING COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING
16-18 Khalifa Paluanova
6. PSYCHOLOGY OF CRIMINAL PERSONALITY
19-22 Ikramov Nizomiddin Nuriddinovich
7. EVALUATION OF THE LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL BALANCE AMONG PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS BY EDUCATIONAL COUNSELORS
23-41 A. P. Ashraf Saleh Jassim
8. IMPROVE THE BEE FOOD BASE BY PLANTING SAP AND POLLINATING TREES AND SHRUBS
42-46 Tolipova Kholidaxon Sherali kizi, Uktamova Zebokhon Nosirjon kizi, Okhunova Durdona Erkinjon kizi, Azizov Rahmatillo Olimjon ugli
9. DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS
47-51 Hamrayeva Aziza Farhadovna
10. FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN
52-56 Saidov Jur'at Sodirovich

11. PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN
57-66 Khamrokulov Rasul Abdusattorovich, Nuriddin Muradovich Karimov
12. THE PLACE OF MIRZO SIROJIDDIN IN MODERN MEDICINE OF BUKHARA
67-69 Ruziyeva Tamara Shukurboyevna
13. COMPARABLE LEARNING OF WORD ORDER IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES
70-73 Khidirova Nilufar Abdiyatovna
14. FACTORS AND IMPORTANCE OF FORMING PERSONAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY
74-79 Umarali Kadirov
15. METHODOLOGY OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION
80-84 Muslimova Rano Muratovna
16. PECULIARITIES OF CORROSION OF THE EQUIPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF PURIFICATION OF HYDROCARBON GASES FROM ACIDIC COMPONENTS
85-89 Murodov Malik Negmurodovich, Rayimov Zukhriddin Khayriddin ogli
17. CONCEPTS OF SECULARISM AND RELIGIOSITY AND THEIR SOCIAL IMPORTANCE
90-93 Merzaev I. B., Normamatov Khabibullo
18. CHEMICAL PROCESSES OF CREATION OF WORKS OF ART BASED ON THE GIYAK MUSICAL INSTRUMENT IN UZBEK MUSICAL ART
94-97 Umarov Bakhtiyor Shovkatovich
19. ON THE DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF MODERN SOCIETY AND EDUCATION
98-101 Rozieva Komila Ernazarovna
20. THE ROLE OF ORAL SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN THE LANGUAGE
102-106 Kenjabaev Jakhongir Abdisalimovich
21. HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SECONDARY RESIDENTIAL HOUSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CITIES OF UZBEKISTAN
107-108 Madaminjon Ergashev
22. FORMS AND METHODS OF THE COUNTRY STUDY MATERIALS' USED AT THE ENGLISH LESSONS
109-113 Usmanova Khumora Ahmadjanovna, Ergasheva Zilola Saydullevna
23. DYNAMICS AND PROSPECTS OF INCREASING THE INFLUENCE OF OPENNESS TO EXPERIENCE IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM
114-116 Shamsiddinova Elmira Mukhammadjanovna

24. STUDY OF INDUCTION AND DEDUCTION ISSUES BY PSYCHOLOGISTS
117-121 Sattarova D. E.
25. THE PLACE OF NATIONAL SONGS IN THE CREATIVE SINGING ACTIVITIES OF OUR TEACHER ARTISTS
122-124 Almatov Shuhrat Talipovich
26. IMPROVING THE FORMATION AND MECHANISMS OF COMPETENCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS
125-132 Mengliyev Bobur Normatovich
27. NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE
133-137 Shodi Bobomurodovich Umirov
28. METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING INTERACTIVE GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS
138-141 Tilavova Nargiza Turabovna
29. WAYS OF USING UZBEK FOLKLORE-SUB-GENRES IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS BY TEACHING THEM IN PRIMARY GRADES
142-144 Ruzikulova Nigora Kudratovna
30. DEALING WITH HETEROGENEOUS GROUPS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS
145-147 Sultonova Laylo Umidjon qizi
31. THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE SKILLS
148-150 Boqiyeva Muqaddas, Umarova Maftuna
32. VALIDITY OF PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS
151-156 Khurinisa Karimovna Qarshiboyeva
33. THE MOST IMPORTANT CHARACTER OF KHUVAYDO'S WORK
157-159 Zaripova Dilfuza Baxtiyorovna
34. FOUNDATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION MANAGEMENT: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORKS
160-167 Radjapov Komil Askarovich
35. ADVANCEMENTS IN EDUCATIONAL WEB RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT
168-173 Abdujabbor Abdurazakov
36. INFLUENCE OF THE INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT ON HIGHER EDUCATION: CONSTRUCTIVE AND DESTRUCTIVE FACTORS
174-178 Khalikulova Umida Rustamovna

37. COMPONENT ELEMENT OF USING WEB PLATFORMS
179-183 Kholikulov Bekzod Jovliyevich
38. POSSIBILITIES OF VISUAL ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL PUBLICATIONS IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATIONS OF BACHELORS IN THE FIELD OF SERVICE
184-189 Shaynazarov Ravshan Mamayusubovich
39. ANALYSIS OF EXISTING RISKS AND METHODS OF COMBATING THEM IN CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES
190-198 Shodiyev Rizamat Davronovich, Ergashev Nuriddin Gayratovich
40. IMPROVING THE BASE TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL OSMS BASED ON THE INFORMATION DESIGN APPROACH
199-204 Shukurov Akmal Uktamovich
41. TECHNOLOGIES FOR USING SOFTWARE PACKAGES TO TEACH DIGITAL RESOURCE MODELING IN HIGHER EDUCATION
205-209 Siradjev Salokhiddin Negmatovich
42. THEORETICAL BASICS OF PROFESSIONAL-CRITICAL APPROACH IN ORGANIZING MEDIA EDUCATION AND PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY
210-214 Kh.Kh. Nekboyev
43. CREATIVE THINKING AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO COGNITIVE AND SKILL ACHIEVEMENT IN HANDBALL AMONG SECOND-YEAR STUDENTS
215-230 Lecturer. Yasser Reda Qanbar, Lecturer. Imad Abbas Hussein, Lecturer. Mahmoud Abbas Hussein
44. THE EFFECT OF USING THE MASTERY AND COOPERATIVE METHODS IN LEARNING THE SKILL OF SHOOTING FROM A STANDSTILL IN BASKETBALL
231-251 M. M. Avin Fakhri Hawar, M. M. Sinan Akram Ali
45. ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INCREASING THE NATURAL FERTILITY OF SALINE SOILS
252-256 Kuralova Rano Mirzaalievna
46. SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYDROTOPONYMS, ZOOMORPHIC AND ETHNOPONYMS IN GERMAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES
257-259 Axmedova Dildora Jo'raxon Qizi
47. SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF PROVIDING HAVOC ON WEB-ORIENTED PLATFORMS
260-263 Zoxidov Jahongir Botirxonovich
48. THE ROLE OF PLAY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDS SPEECH
264-271 Matmusayeva Muhayo Azamovna

49. THE CURRENT ROLE OF ENGLISH AS A GLOBAL LANGUAGE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS LANGUAGE IN ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL TERMS
272-274 Turdaliyeva Shahnoza O'ktamovna
50. THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF DIGITAL ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS IN THE TRAINING OF ENGINEERS IN TECHNICAL SPECIALTIES
275-279 Tursunov Mirolim
51. STIMULATING DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH COMPETENCE WITH THE HELP OF DIDACTIC TOOLS
280-284 Jo'rayeva Mohira Yunus qizi
52. THE PLACE OF GRAMMAR IN TEACHING ENGLISH
285-289 Yusupova Lobar Xusanovna
53. USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN ESP SPHERES
290-297 Abdanbekova Nilufar
54. IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES
298-304 Sagdullaev Pulatbek
55. THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND PUBLIC HEALTHY SPORTS IN OUR COUNTRY
305-312 Nishonova Dilafuz, Kakhakhorova Madinabonu

**PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF PRACTICAL PHYSICAL TRAINING
OF STUDENTS OF THE ACADEMIC LYCEUM OF THE MINISTRY
OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
This article describes in detail the practical physical training of academic high school students.	Military power, spiritual force, border, powerful, training.

Introduction

The famous Russian theorist V.V.Kirillov interprets the military power of the country in this way: "The military power of the state is a realized part of all the combined material and spiritual forces of the state, its potentials, military organization, which are used to ensure the military and national security of the country as a whole."

In the World Ranking of Military Power (Global Fire power Ind), the armed forces of Uzbekistan occupy the 48th place out of 106 participating countries, second only to the armed forces of the Russian Federation (2nd emesto) and Ukraine (21st emesto) among the post-Soviet countries.

Indeed, of the Central Asian states bordering Afghanistan, Uzbekistan has the most powerful military potential. The country's military programs differ significantly from its neighbors. The military budget of Uzbekistan is about 5% of GDP, which exceeds the total defense costs in Tajikistan (20 times) and Kyrgyzstan (45 times) combined.

The results of the III Army International Games, which took place from July 29 to August 12 this year at 22 training grounds located on the territory of the Russian Federation, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan and China, also testify to the high military training of Uzbek soldiers. Over 150 teams from 28 countries representing Europe, Asia, Africa and Latin America took part in them.

Servicemen from Uzbekistan, who took part in these competitions for the first time, according to the results of 8 contests, took 5 prizes.

Representatives of the military teams of Uzbekistan took second place in the competition "Master gunsmith" and third places in the competitions "Excellent military intelligence" and "Highway Patrol".

In recent years, serious transformations of the armed forces have been carried out in Uzbekistan, aimed at creating a mobile, modern army. The system of operational and strategic management, organizational and staff structure was revised, the system of interaction between the branches of the

armed forces was improved, combat and training training and social support of servicemen were modernized.

Seven higher military educational institutions provide a sufficient level of training of command personnel, surpassing the similar level of neighboring states. In recent years, the term of military service has been reduced from one and a half to one year, and the course for a professional army continues.

Uzbek youth, unlike neighboring countries, want to serve in the army. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasizes the role of patriotic education: — "As everyone knows, patriotism is the moral basis for the viability of any state... That is why we must take concrete steps to form strong immunity among citizens against the negative impact of ideas alien to us and strengthen the sense of responsibility for the fate of the fatherland." He stressed that patriotic officers should become the basis of the army.

For this purpose, the reform of higher military education is envisaged. The reformed Academy of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan will have to deal with it. The new military educational institution will teach young people who have chosen a military career, and engage in retraining and advanced training. Young men who have chosen a military career will first study at lyceums and colleges specially selected throughout the country and only after that they will continue their studies at the academy.

In addition to the new system of officer training, Tashkent notes the need to create its own military-industrial complex in the country. In this connection, at the end of 2016, Uzbekistan signed a new military-technical agreement with Russia. A number of measures have also been taken to improve the social security of Uzbek army servicemen. They will be provided with housing at the expense of the state housing fund and preferential mortgage programs.

In the conditions of growing radicalism, the intensification of terrorism and religious extremism, the expansion of drug trafficking, the armed forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan are more fully able to protect the country and the people from most possible external threats and preserve peace and stability in the state.

Currently, within the framework of the implementation of the accepted concepts of military-patriotic education of youth and increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, large-scale work is being carried out to educate comprehensively developed, erudite, devoted to the people and the cause of serving the Motherland youth.

At the same time, in the conditions of accelerated development of globalization processes, increasing threats to national traditions, culture and identity of peoples, attempts to introduce alien ideas, the most vulnerable category of the population remains young people. The adoption of a set of additional measures in this direction is one of the urgent tasks.

In order to ensure the active and consistent implementation of state policy aimed at creating a system of education of a comprehensively developed, physically healthy and spiritually mature young generation with high intellectual potential with modern thinking and worldview, ready to selflessly defend the interests and sovereignty of the state:

1. To form fundamentally new military academic lyceums "Temurbeklar maktabi" (hereinafter - "Temurbeklar maktabi") as part of the Ministries of Defense, Internal Affairs and Emergency Situations, as well as the State Security Service and the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to Appendix No. 1.

Determine the main tasks of Temurbeklar Maktabi:

formation of students' deep respect for the spiritual and educational values of our people, their culture and customs, such high personal qualities as honesty, decency, patriotism, dedication, dedication and a sense of national pride;

educating students on the basis of the history and rich culture of our people, the priceless heritage of great ancestors, first of all Amir Temur, on the example of the heroism of compatriots of contemporaries who gave their lives in the name of freedom and prosperity of the Motherland, devoted to the people of Uzbekistan, with firm life views and active citizenship;

the development of students' broad horizons, intellectual potential, creative and analytical thinking, the formation of their solid knowledge of natural and exact sciences, foreign languages and modern information technologies, as well as instilling in them the initial skills of military affairs;

preparation of physically developed, hardy, brave and courageous defenders of the Motherland, having oratorical and leadership qualities, worthy candidates for admission to higher, higher military and specialized educational institutions of the country in order to form a personnel reserve for the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the civil service.

2. Approve:

The program of measures ("Road map") on the creation of fundamentally new military academic lyceums "Temurbeklar Maktabi" and the improvement of the educational process in them according to Appendix No. 2;

Regulations on the military Academic Lyceum "Temurbeklar maktabi" according to Appendix No. 3;

The standard organizational and staff structure of the military academic Lyceum "Temurbeklar Maktabi" according to Appendix No. 4;

The list of higher, higher military and specialized educational institutions assigned to the military academic lyceums "Temurbeklar Maktabi" according to Appendix No. 5.

3. Assign personal responsibility to the heads of the relevant ministries and departments, as well as military-administrative sectors, for ensuring the full and timely implementation of the measures of the approved Program of Measures ("Road Map").

4. To grant the right to the Ministers of Defense, Internal Affairs and Emergency Situations, the Chairman of the State Security Service and the Commander of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if necessary, to make changes to the organizational and staff structure of Temurbeklar Maktabi within the total number of troops of ministries and departments, respectively.

5. Determine that:

admission and training in the newly formed "Temurbeklar maktabi" begins from the 2020/2021 academic year;

the duration of training at Temurbeklar Maktabi is two years with an annual quota of admission of 100 people to each of them;

students of the Fergana Academic Lyceum with a military-technical bias of the Ministry of Defense, as well as the Tashkent Academic Lyceum of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan complete their studies according to the current curriculum until the beginning of the 2020/2021 academic year;

starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, the admission and training of students of special groups organized in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2017 No. PP-2738 "On the program of measures to implement the tasks of further reform and

development of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is suspended. At the same time, students in special groups complete their studies in accordance with the established procedure according to the current curricula.

See the previous edition.

Starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, the annual quota of admission to Temurbeklar Maktabi of the Ministry of Defense, the Ministry of Emergency Situations and the National Guard is 150 people. At the same time:

additional full-time units of military personnel under contract and employees from among civilian personnel for the military academic lyceums "Temurbeklar Maktabi" are allocated within the established maximum number of units (troops) Ministry of Defense, Ministry of Emergency Situations and National Guard;

The financing of the measures provided for in paragraph six of this paragraph is carried out at the expense of budgetary funds allocated annually to ministries and departments in the system of which there is a military academic lyceum "Temurbeklar Maktabi", and other sources not prohibited by law. (paragraph 5 was supplemented with paragraphs six to eight in the wording of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 3, 2022 No. PP—344 - National Database of Legislation, 03.08.2022, No. 07/22/344/0704)

6. Allow:

The Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan to suspend the activities of the Urgench Military Academic Lyceum with a military-legal bias and the Samarkand Academic Lyceum with a military-construction bias with the transfer of their buildings (structures) and adjacent territories to the khokimiyats of Khorezm and Samarkand regions, respectively, upon completion of the training of students enrolled in the 2019/2020 academic year according to the current curriculum;

The Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan to create "Temurbeklar maktabi" instead of a specialized academic lyceum at the Academy of the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the organization of which is provided for by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2019 No. UP-5706 "On the introduction in the Republic of Uzbekistan of a qualitatively new system of prevention and liquidation of emergency situations, as well as ensuring fire safety" and Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2019 No. PP-4276 "On organizational measures to further improve the activities of emergency departments".

7. To the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

within three months, transfer professional colleges and academic lyceum with buildings and structures to the State Security Service, Ministries of Internal Affairs and Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the rights of operational management, with full preservation of existing staff units, material and technical means, educational equipment and other property in accordance together with the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure timely employment of released workers and employees of professional colleges, academic and military-academic lyceums.

8. Establish that:

a) starting from September 1, 2019, the basic tariff rates of workers and employees of Temurbeklar Maktabi, as well as the Specialized Boarding School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are increased in the following amounts:

for the director and his deputies, teachers, employees of the educational department — 5 times;

for leaders of clubs (sections) and psychologists — 3 times;

for employees of the information resource center (library), department of informatization and communication, instructors and laboratory assistants - 2 times;

b) for military personnel serving in Temurbeklar Maktabi, starting from September 1, 2019, a monthly allowance of 50 percent of the official salary is introduced;

c) Temurbeklar Maktabi employees and employees are subject to the amounts and conditions of remuneration established for the relevant positions of secondary special educational institutions of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, and they also enjoy the rights and benefits provided for in the legislation. Temurbeklar maktabi employees and employees are also subject to the procedure for applying the percentage allowance for work experience established for employees and employees of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

See the previous edition.

d) graduates of Temurbeklar maktabi, upon admission to higher military and paramilitary educational institutions, are granted a benefit in the form of additional points in the amount of 30 percent of the points scored by them to the scores of an individual final interview or test tests conducted by the Agency for the Assessment of Knowledge and Qualifications under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and upon admission to other state higher educational institutions of the republic — 15 percent of the points scored by them;

e) graduates of Temurbeklar maktabi who have graduated with honors are granted the right to enter higher military or specialized educational institutions of ministries and the departments in charge of which the corresponding military-academic lyceum "Temurbeklar maktabi" is located, without passing test tests based on the results of successful completion of military-professional selection events.

9. Within two months, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan should develop and approve a comprehensive program to improve the infrastructure, educational and logistical base of the Temurbeklar Maktabi military academic lyceums, as well as ensure its timely and full implementation.

10. To the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

together with the Ministries of Defense, Internal Affairs, Emergency Situations, the State Security Service, the National Guard and the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the transfer of this resolution to the relevant ministries and departments of the relevant professional colleges and academic lyceums to make appropriate changes to their cost estimates;

annually, starting from 2020, according to the reasonable calculations of the relevant ministries and departments, to ensure the allocation of additional budget funds to strengthen the educational and logistical base of Temurbeklar Maktabi.

11. To determine that the expenses related to the implementation of the measures provided for by this resolution are carried out at the expense of budgetary funds allocated annually according to reasonable calculations to the Ministries of Defense, Internal Affairs, Emergency Situations, State Security Service, National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their extra-budgetary funds, by attracting state loans from foreign states and international financial organizations, as well as other sources not prohibited by law.

12. From August 1, 2019, to recognize the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers as invalid in accordance with Annex No. 7.

13. Ministries of Defense, Internal Affairs, Emergency Situations, State Security Service and National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

in order to ensure an effective educational process in Temurbeklar Maktabi, starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, to organize monitoring of the fulfillment of the tasks assigned to them, providing them with the necessary methodological and practical assistance on a systematic basis, as well as professional development of teachers;

together with other interested ministries and departments, within a three-month period, submit proposals to the Cabinet of Ministers on amendments and additions to the legislation arising from this resolution.

14. Control over the implementation of this resolution shall be entrusted to the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan A.N. Aripov and the Secretary of the Security Council under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan V.V. Makhmudov.

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**INFLUENCE OF SUNSHINE (IN HOURS) ON THE DEVELOPMENT
OF STROKES AMONG THE POPULATION IN SOUTHERN
KYRGYZSTAN**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
Acute cerebrovascular accidents (ACVA) occupy priority ranking positions in the structure of neurological pathologies. The differences and incidence of stroke may be due to climatic conditions that differ in different regions of Kyrgyzstan. The purpose of the study is to study the risk of developing cerebral stroke over 4 years under the influence of meteorological factors for the timely adoption of preventive measures.	Stroke, meteorological factors, sunshine, Kyrgyzstan

Introduction

Over the past decades, the unprecedented rate of global warming and climate change has been a source of concern. In recent years, climate change has been considered as one of the leading factors influencing public health and the formation of acute and chronic non-infectious diseases [1]. The occurrence of stroke is caused by a complex of factors, among which uncorrectable environmental factors occupy a large place. A generally accepted risk factor for the development of stroke is increased hemomagnetic activity and the influence of meteorological factors themselves. As is known, meteorological factors also take an indirect and/or direct role in the formation of non-communicable diseases. But even on this issue there are no clear opinions of modern researchers [3, 2, 1].

Material and Research Methods:

Using the method of retrospective epidemiological analysis, medical records of patients hospitalized with a diagnosis of stroke in the hospital of a medical organization in Osh from 2016-2019 were analyzed. The study volume included 382 stroke patients. We conducted a study using data from meteorological factors of the Kyrgyz Hydrometeorological Center in Osh, such as sunshine for a 4-

year period from 2016-2019. When statistically processing the obtained data, methods of relative statistics, Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Access programs, Spearman's rank method, paired and unpaired Student's t tests, parametric Wilcoxon test, sign test and methods for comparing the specific weight of characteristics, as well as covariance-regression analysis, variance and logistic regression analysis with determination of B-coefficients and odds ratios, using the IBM Statistics computer program, correlation coefficients (r), connections between the studied characteristics and the critical value of Student's t-test were determined.

The results of an analysis to study the detection of strokes against the background of fluctuations in sunshine (SS) according to prospective clinical and meteorological observation data are presented on Table 1.

Table 1. The influence of sunshine on the development of strokes among the population in the south of Kyrgyzstan (1st line - in absolute numbers, 2nd - in %).

Duration of sunshine (in hours)	Prevalence of various forms														
	Ischemic stroke					Hemorrhagic stroke					General stroke				
	2016y	2017y	2018y	2019y	2016-2019	2016y	2017y	2018y	2019y	2016-2019	2016y	2017y	2018y	2019y	2016-2019y.
9,2-10,4	34	14	33	8	89	10	6	15	3	34	44	20	48	11	123
	52,3	24,6	51,6	11,9	35,2	40,0	7,1	46,9	16,7	38,2	48,9	28,2	50,0	12,9	36,0
10,5-11,7	11	12	13	16	52	5	1	5	5	16	16	13	18	21	68
	16,9	21,1	20,3	23,9	20,6	20,0		15,6	27,8	18,0	17,8	18,3	18,8	24,7	19,9
11,8-13	4	15	4	12	35	4	0	5	3	12	8	15	9	15	47
	6,2	26,3	6,3	17,9	13,8	16,0	50,0	15,6	16,7	13,5	8,9	21,1	9,4	17,6	13,7
13,1-14,3	16	16	14	31	77	6	7	7	7	27	22	23	21	38	104
	24,6	28,1	21,9	46,3	30,4	24,0	100,0	21,9	38,9	30,3	24,4	32,4	21,9	44,7	3,-4
Bcero:	65	57	64	67	253	25	14	32	18	89	90	71	96	85	342
	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
r(+/-)					0,257					0,196					0,239
Mp(+/-)					32,4%					39,5%					34,2%
t					0,375					0,283					0,349
P					0,771411					0,824206					0,786330

From the data obtained it follows that the frequency of detection of strokes begins to increase from the level of sunshine (SS) >9.2-10.4 hours, and in its levels from 2.6 to 9.2 hours - there was no such pattern, it was noted and therefore they were not included in the statistical analysis.

At different intervals of fluctuations in sunshine, general stroke is determined with the following frequency: at 9.2-10.4 hours - 36.0%, <10.5-11.7 hours - 19.9%, <11.8 - 13 hours - 13.7%, <13.1-14.3h-30.4%. This trend was observed in all years of observation except 2019, when, as the duration of SS increases, the frequency of detection of cerebral stroke during the year increases from 12.9% (with SS <9.2-10.4 hours) to 44.7 (with SS <13,1-14.3h), i.e. the detection of patients with general stroke increases by 31.8% or 2 times (p <0.01).

From this we can conclude that the frequency of cases of cerebral stroke detection has a direct correlation with the duration and fluctuations of sunshine throughout the year. Apparently, to approve this concept, even more lengthy research in this direction will be required.

It was confirmed that ischemic stroke, only in some years of observation (2019), under the influence of this meteorological factor increases from 11.9% (with SS <9.2-10.4 hours) to 30.4% (with SS <13.1- 14.3), by 18.5% or 2.7 times ($p < 0.001$). During a 4-year observation, under the influence of sunlight, ischemic stroke is detected with the following prevalence: at levels of fluctuations in sunlight from 9.2- up to 10.4 hours-35.2%, at <10.5-11.7 hours-20.6%, at <11.8-13 hours-13.8% and at <13.1-14.3 hours-30, 14%.

Similar data were obtained for hemorrhagic stroke. The largest number of hemorrhagic strokes occurred during periods of sun exposure ranging from 9.2 to 10.4 hours. (38.2%) and 13.1-19.3 hours. (30.3%). A comparatively low frequency of GI is determined when the duration of sunshine is <10.5%-11.7 hours (17.8%) and 11.8-13 hours (13.5%). In general, it was revealed that there is a correlation or direct relationship between increasing fluctuations in the duration of sunshine and the number of hemorrhagic strokes in the climatic conditions of Osh.

Based on a statistical correlation-regression study of the development of strokes depending on fluctuations in sunshine in the south of Kyrgyzstan, the following was shown: the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.239. The relationship between the characteristics under study - the direct strength of the connection on the Chaddock scale - is weak. The dependence of the signs is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The coefficient of determination rr is 0.057, the average error of approximation is 34.2%.

The presented bar graph-histogram (Fig. 1) shows that the population frequency of all forms of strokes turned out to be higher with prolonged exposure to sunshine than among individuals who did not have such exposure to this meteorological factor.

Fig. 1. Development of strokes against the background of exposure and fluctuations in SS in the extreme continental climate of Osh

Conclusion

Thus, according to the data obtained, along with other factors or meteorological elements, sunshine can also contribute to the formation and more severe course of strokes in the conditions of southern Kyrgyzstan.

The identified results in this direction also, of course, have direct practical significance in developing the implementation of effective correction (with medical, social and economic benefits), treatment, rehabilitation and preventive programs among the population living in the climatic and weather conditions of Osh in the south of Kyrgyzstan.

These data, noted and recommended by us for practical use, are of great importance in optimizing the provision of emergency and rehabilitation medical care to stroke patients in regions with a sharply continental climate in the south of Kyrgyzstan.

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**SOCIAL- PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
INTERRELATION OF FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS TO THE
DEVELOPMENT OF CHILD INTELLECT**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>In fact, the education of young people, which is the foundation of our future, is formed first of all in the family. Character traits characteristic of a person, as well as ethnic characteristics characteristic of our nation, feelings such as respect for elders, respect for children, love for the Motherland, and duty are all formed in the family.</p> <p>Deviant behavior among children, such as crime, drug addiction, aggression, and suicide, which are foreign to our society, are caused by improper organization of interpersonal relationships in the family. In our young families, communication between children, teenagers, adults and other persons is not satisfactory, it is currently carried out through communication with mass media, as well as the concept of "we" and the attitude towards it are not sufficiently developed.</p>	<p>Personality, tradition, custom, attitude, parents, character, environment, upbringing, nuclear family.</p>

Introduction

The main factors that strongly influence the formation of a child as a person in the family are the direct environment and microenvironment. First of all, it is the team that develops the child's abilities and shapes his character, his parents, relatives, peers, preschool teachers, school pedagogues, etc.

The microenvironment has a two-sided effect on a person:

- stereotypes established by society, that is, through traditions, rules, norms and usual conditions in everyday life;
- also, as a result of the unique characteristics of the immediate environment, the family environment has the greatest influence as the most important factor in the formation of character traits in children. As the first President noted, "It is recognized that the eternity of family life is the center of education that ensures the continuity of generations, preserves our sacred traditions, and at the same time has a direct impact on how future generations will become human beings. we need to get From birth, a child lives and grows up in a family environment, family traditions, values, and customs form a teenager's personality. The most important thing is that children understand and feel the demands of society through the school of family life.

In fact, the education of young people, which is the foundation of our future, is formed first of all in the family. Character traits characteristic of a person, as well as ethnic characteristics characteristic of our nation, feelings such as respect for elders, respect for children, love for the Motherland, and duty are all formed in the family.

As we mentioned above, a number of components that influence the formation of character traits in children, together with the formation in the family, cause the formation of unique negative individual psychological characteristics in the behavior of children who are brought up in unhealthy family conditions. .

According to a group of psychologists, the emergence of new qualities of character and their strengthening requires a real situation. That is why there is an opinion that behavior creates habit, habit creates character and character creates destiny. Character is not some stable and unchanging feature. For example, in childhood, character traits usually appear in the form of "getting serious", "becoming more different", which begins to manifest as a result of social factors, i.e., the complexity of the attitude towards others, hormonal maturation. Inadequate consideration of personality changes leads to conflict and conflictual relationships. At the same time, accentuation features in the child's character, including the emancipation reaction to be "free" from the care of adults, the reaction of grouping with equals, the reaction of passion, the reaction of hobbies, etc. take precedence.

Deviant behavior among children, including crime, drug addiction, aggression, and suicide, which are alien to our society, are caused by improper organization of interpersonal relationships in the family. . In this case, parents are indifferent and indifferent to the education of their children, they do not establish a healthy lifestyle in the family, parents are taught the psychology of their children, their interpersonal skills. Due to the lack of knowledge about relationships, conflicting behavior is occurring in our society, as a result, it is necessary to reveal the psychological aspects of the relationship between parents and children based on science.

First, various events in the social environment directly affect the human mind and leave a deep mark on it.

Secondly, the person himself helps the influence of the external social environment to be deeper and stronger. It is known that children, according to their nature, are imitative from a young age. By directly imitating all the actions of adults, children imbibe these actions, good and bad qualities. Children closely monitor every action and interaction of adults in the family, on the streets.

True, due to the current globalization and integration processes, the national stability of the ethno-psychological characteristics of the family is weakening, and the trend of modernization is clearly visible. V. V. Boyko also agrees with this opinion and distinguishes the specific characteristics of modern families that influence character formation in children as follows:

- Firstly, as a result of the nuclearization of the family, that is, the fact that the family consists of a couple and children, unlike modern nuclear families with few children, creates a unique socio-psychological environment for the formation of a child's character. In such families, a short chain of interpersonal relationships often prevails, the means of mutual influence of family members are limited, and they are distinguished by the fact that models and situations for imitation are not well formed.

-Secondly, due to highly dependent and uniform relationships in the family, it increases the probability that children will firmly acquire the patterns of parental behavior. Due to the limited selection of

parents' behavior, children acquire socio-typical characteristics, which are not without the possibility of reflection of both microenvironment and individual characteristics.

Based on the cited scientific data, it can be noted that the characteristic feature of the modern family is the limited humanitarian experience for the young generation.

In some of our young families, the qualities of communicative tolerance (tolerance) towards children, teenagers, adults and other persons are not sufficiently reflected, sufficient information exchange between family members is limited, right or It is distinguished by the lack of development of the concept of "we" and the attitude towards it. As a consequence of many cases, children's "personification" at a high level, i.e., children's showing of their "I" in the family circle, asserting their right, setting themselves against parents It is manifested by acting against them, denying their value and reputation, and not fully using the advice they give.

This causes the emergence of some forms of alienation that are not characteristic of the child's character.

At the same time, the alienation of family members formed in the family causes children to be busy in other circles, that is, in different groups and for hours with the media. As a result of limited communication between family members and unsatisfied interpersonal relationships, we can observe that children are now meeting their needs, joining informal groups, and engaging in non-traditional activities.

V. V. Boyko interprets the occurrence of some negative situations in the process of interaction between such children and parents as follows.

The relations of the members of the family, which are strictly limited in the family, in this case, the extremely demanding nature of the fathers and mothers, cause defective character traits in the children. This, in turn, leads to the creation of more strict situations in the attitude of parents towards the child. As a result of the aggressive state of relations, indifference to each other, rudeness and neglect of parents arouse aggressive reactions in children and increase the cause of conflicts in the process of relations.

Consensus state of relations. In this case, the parent complex directs the child complex to life. For example, a parent's constant displeasure with a child, criticizing, fighting, insulting, and humiliating the child, in turn, creates a sense of guilt in the child, leading him to lack protective reactions at school and in extra-curricular communities, withdrawing himself from communication, leading to inability to defend oneself, inability to react quickly to an impact and loss of oneself quickly. This kind of behavior of children causes their parents and others to control them, to become dependent on others, to become attached, and to be unable to be independent. Non-consecutive relationships. In this case, the carelessness and indifference of parents in raising children is distinguished by the fact that they are not demanding in relation to the plague. Improper demands placed on children are either unjustified or overly lenient, and are the result of punishing one behavior and then ignoring it the next. In such cases, children do not think about norms of behavior, duty, sense of responsibility, and do not have certain ideas.

The above-mentioned methods and forms of education cause the following characteristics in child education:

"Difficult to educate" children are the result of pedagogical neglect. According to L.S. Vygotsky, "difficult" child's life is the result of wrong relationships. First of all, these are stubborn, whimsical children, attracting them to interesting activities is one of the main methods of educating them. A

certain part of them are undisciplined and rude children. It is possible to change their activity in accordance with the purpose, to influence them by giving them some rights. In psychology, there are several classifications of "difficult to educate" children.

The first group is children with socially negative, strong views;

The second group is children who imitate lawbreakers;

The third group is children who hesitate between positive and negative stereotypes of behavior and understand their mistakes.

The fourth group is the children who obey the willful children.

The fifth group is those who accidentally entered the path of lawlessness.

It should be said that the role of the environment in which they live, the family, the community where they study, and the class are very important for children with difficult upbringing.

So, in conclusion, it can be said that the use of different district education methods in the family should match the characteristics of the student, that is, it is appropriate for parents and educators to use the methods and forms of education, taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of children. Otherwise, the upbringing of the child in the character traits will cause undesirable manifestations such as change.

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**PRAGMALINGUODIDACTIC CHALLENGES: ENHANCING
COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>This study delves into the intricate landscape of language education, exploring the pragmatic, linguistic, and didactic challenges faced by educators in fostering effective communication skills. Pragmatic challenges, including politeness and cultural nuances, linguistic complexities encompassing grammar and vocabulary variations, and didactic hurdles related to teaching methodologies, constitute the focal points of analysis. The study advocates for a holistic approach, emphasizing the interrelated nature of these challenges and proposing innovative, adaptive teaching strategies. By addressing these multifaceted obstacles, educators can create inclusive, culturally sensitive learning environments, fostering proficient and confident language learners.</p>	<p>Pragmatic challenges, linguistic variations, didactic strategies, language education, effective communication, cultural sensitivity, inclusive learning, adaptive teaching methods.</p>

Introduction

Language teaching stands at the crossroads of diverse disciplines, requiring a nuanced understanding of pragmatics, linguistics, and pedagogy. In this intricate web of communication, pragmatic competence plays a pivotal role, allowing individuals not only to master the structural intricacies of language but also to navigate the unspoken rules of social interaction (Vygotsky, 2005). This competence is essential for effective communication, enabling individuals to express themselves appropriately in various contexts, cultures, and social settings (Vysochina, 2009). However, within the realm of language education, educators often grapple with multifaceted challenges related to pragmatic awareness, linguistic subtleties, and effective instructional methodologies (Karaulov, 2000). The landscape of language teaching is further complicated by linguistic intricacies, encompassing the nuances of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation (Apresyan, 1995). Language learners encounter these challenges as they endeavor to grasp the intricacies of different languages and their unique structural patterns. Moreover, didactic challenges add another layer of complexity, relating to the methodologies employed, curriculum design, and assessments within language education (Baryshnikov, 2002). Traditional approaches sometimes fall short in addressing the diverse needs of learners, necessitating innovative and adaptive teaching methods that resonate with the complexities of contemporary communication.

This article delves into the heart of these challenges, exploring the pragmatic, linguistic, and didactic hurdles faced by educators in the realm of language teaching. By dissecting these challenges and

drawing insights from seminal works in the field, this study aims to propose comprehensive and practical strategies to enhance communication skills in language teaching. Through a careful synthesis of theory and practice, educators can navigate these challenges and foster an environment where language learners not only understand the structure of a language but also harness the subtleties of its usage. By addressing these challenges head-on, educators can pave the way for a new era of language instruction, one that embraces the richness of linguistic diversity while nurturing effective and culturally sensitive communicators.

In the subsequent sections, this article will explore the specific challenges posed by pragmatics, linguistics, and didactics in language teaching, offering tangible strategies to enhance communication skills and create a transformative learning experience for language learners.

Pragmatic, Linguistic, and Didactic Challenges in Language Teaching

In the realm of language education, educators grapple with a multifaceted tapestry of challenges. Pragmatic challenges form the first layer, encompassing aspects such as politeness, indirectness, and cultural variations in communication styles (Pan-European competences, 2003). These subtle nuances often elude language learners, leading to breakdowns in communication and hindering effective language acquisition. For educators, addressing these challenges becomes imperative to facilitate meaningful linguistic development.

Moving beyond pragmatics, linguistic challenges add another layer of complexity to language teaching. These challenges arise from the intricate web of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation variations existing across different languages (Apresyan, 1995). Learners must navigate these differences, which can be daunting. Educators are tasked with developing innovative instructional methods that assist learners in overcoming these linguistic barriers, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the language's structural intricacies.

Simultaneously, didactic challenges present a formidable hurdle in language education. These challenges span diverse teaching methodologies, curriculum design intricacies, and assessment strategies (Baryshnikov, 2002). Traditional teaching approaches, while foundational, might not align with the needs of the increasingly diverse learner base. Thus, educators must embrace creativity, implementing innovative and adaptive teaching techniques. This adaptive approach ensures that the educational process is not only engaging but also tailored to meet the unique requirements of each learner, thereby fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Addressing these intertwined pragmatic, linguistic, and didactic challenges requires a holistic approach from educators. By developing strategies that simultaneously tackle these multifaceted issues, language teachers can create an immersive learning experience. Through innovative teaching methods and a nuanced understanding of cultural and linguistic diversity, educators can guide learners towards effective communication, bridging the gap between languages and cultures. In this symbiotic relationship between challenge and solution, language education can truly thrive, nurturing skilled and culturally sensitive communicators.

Enhancing Communication Strategies

To address the pragmatic, linguistic, and didactic challenges in language teaching, educators can adopt the following strategies:

- **Contextualized Learning:** Design activities that reflect real-life communication scenarios, enabling learners to apply language skills in context.

- **Interactive Role-plays:** Incorporate role-plays and simulations that encourage learners to engage in conversations, promoting pragmatic competence.
- **Cultural Sensitivity Training:** Raise awareness about cultural differences in communication styles, ensuring learners understand the context of language use in diverse cultures.
- **Feedback and Error Correction:** Provide constructive feedback and targeted error correction to guide learners in refining their language skills.
- **Technology Integration:** Utilize language learning apps and online platforms that offer interactive exercises, enhancing both linguistic and pragmatic competence.

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PSYCHOLOGY OF CRIMINAL PERSONALITY

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Abstract: The role of psychological knowledge is very important for the study of human activity in the field of law enforcement agencies. In-depth study of a person, his personality, basic psychological conditions, processes, is important in legal activity. To study the personality of a criminal, it is necessary to fight crime first. Psychology studies the mechanism of personal immunity in criminal situations and sets the main goal of crime prevention. Crime is a changing phenomenon that exists in human society. The fact that the state, level, and structure of criminality changes qualitatively and quantitatively during human development depends on the economic, social, and political legal changes in the society. In terms of quality, it is expressed in the method of execution, execution as an organized group, execution using modern science and technology achievements, etc.</p>	<p>Criminal psychology, psychology, crime, criminal community, crime, law, protection, crime, detective, investigation.</p>

Introduction

The fact that crime is a social phenomenon is that the subjects of crimes are individuals within the members of the society, who attack the social relations and members of the society in which they live. The circumstances and causes of crime occur due to social reasons. Crime, as a social phenomenon, is connected with economic, political, ideological, spiritual management, legal, etc. relations in any other social relations. Therefore, the growth of crime, its characteristics, and the interrelationship of social processes are determined by the scale of contradictions and criminological situations. Criminality is not a simple collection of committed crimes, but a system of crimes that constitutes a whole social phenomenon. It has its own characteristics and is associated with its social relations. Therefore, its reasons lie in these social relations. Since criminality consists of the totality of crimes committed in a certain area and during a certain period of time, the relationship between crime and criminality is based on general laws that have a commonality from a part to a whole, from individuality. The laws of criminality are determined not through separate types of crime, but by analyzing it as a whole negative social phenomenon.

It is impossible to express crime in simple numbers and reveal its meaning and essence. Accordingly, crime is expressed in criminology through qualitative and quantitative indicators. Quantitative indicators of crime are its level and dynamics, while qualitative indicators are changes in its structure and characteristics. During the transition of Uzbekistan to the market economy system, there was an increase in organized crime, illegal drug dealing, and corruption crimes. These are qualitative changes

in crime. The causes of crime are considered to be one of the most complex topics, and this negative social phenomenon has always worried the most advanced part of people in the history of mankind for thousands of years. Why do some people commit crimes? Where lies the reason for committing a crime? This problem has been the cause of serious discussions by experts in various branches of science, and even now scientists have not reached a consensus on this issue. Issues on the causes of crime are described in detail in Section III of the "Criminology" textbook, that is, in Chapters 5 and 6.

"Criminal personality" is a multifaceted concept and is the object of study of a number of disciplines. It is studied not only by psychologists, but also by lawyers as a subject. A number of psychologists (M.I. Yenikev, O.L. Kochetov, Yu.V. Chufarovsky, Yu.L. Vasiliev, etc.) have expressed their opinions in scientific literature about the psychology of a criminal person. This problem occupies one of the central places in legal psychology. The personality of the criminal is a set of the main intellectual and spiritual qualities, mental and physical condition of the criminal. Studying the identity of the criminal is crucial for providing a qualified assessment of the act committed by a person, including individual prediction. In order to have a comprehensive and deep picture of the criminal, the analysis should cover not only the time of the crime and the period of its investigation, but also the development of the subject. It is necessary to take into account both the hidden motives of the crime and the psychological and psychiatric characteristics. Since the identity of the criminal and the crime are interrelated, obtaining relevant information about the identity of the criminal within the criminal investigation is an important component of the investigation of the crime. Because according to Article 54 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the court must take into account the identity of the criminal, along with other circumstances, when imposing a sentence. In order to understand the inner world of a criminal, it is necessary to know his place in life, his attitude to the environment, people, society, state, law, work, etc. This cannot be done without studying his needs, spiritual directions and motives of his activity. That is, any criminal activity largely depends on the individual and psychological characteristics of the criminal. The Criminal Procedure Law requires determining the circumstances affecting the level and nature of the responsibility of the accused, as well as other circumstances representing the identity of the accused, when determining the subject of proof. Therefore, the main task of legal psychology is to develop the characteristics of the criminal that must be identified. When studying the personality of the criminal from a psychological point of view, it is necessary to analyze him in relation to the social environment. Because criminal behavior is not caused by a person or the environment, but by their interaction. The influence of the social environment on criminal behavior is complex. In other words, socio-economic, political and cultural aspects of society's life have an external influence on the formation of the modeled mechanism of crime, at the same time, the psychological characteristics of the modeled criminal constitute its internal content and shape it. The criminal personality is of special interest for both legal psychology and criminology, because it does not simply reflect certain external conditions, but is an active part of interaction. Therefore, in criminology, terms such as "criminal" and "person of the criminal" are interpreted as a category, that is, each of them is an independent concept. The concept of "criminal personality" uniquely expresses the social characteristics of the criminal, that is, it serves to reveal the "social image" of the person. The relationship between social conditions and antisocial behavior is complex, and on top of that, social conditions are always manifested in a crime through a specific person. In a number of cases, they leave a relatively stable mark on a person in the process of long-term social

interaction and create a stable illegal trend rather than some criminal actions. This direction is visible in the complex of crimes. The difference between antisocial behavior and legal behavior, in our opinion, comes from the system of values, views and social goals, that is, from the content-related side of consciousness. It is generally accepted that the direct causes of antisocial behavior should be sought in the value-normative systems of the individual and the social environment, and their interaction. The analysis of the literature on legal psychology also shows that much attention has been and is being paid to the study of criminal psychology. Nevertheless, practice shows that the theoretical research conducted on the psychological characteristics of criminals cannot adequately reflect the picture of criminal activity, that is, many questions (issues) remain "behind the scenes". For example, when choosing the method of committing a crime, in many cases, the criminal takes into account not only psychological characteristics, but also mental states. As you know, mental state is the subject of psychology. Psychological typing of a person is one of the ways to know this phenomenon, but the information obtained in the study of the personalities of certain criminals needs to be properly theoretically substantiated.

The mechanism of social determination of criminality requires combining two different approaches to the study of a person - social-typological and social-role approaches. In this sense, the personality of a criminal is a set of his typological characteristics that caused a certain type of criminal act committed by an individual. When studying a person who has committed a crime, it is necessary to determine his values, the content of his life and activities, his inclinations and views. Because criminals, realizing to a greater or lesser extent the true nature of their antisocial behavior, look for a system of motives and excuses that justify themselves and reject the values that prevent them from achieving their criminal goals. Avoiding responsibility and protecting oneself psychologically in order to justify one's actions is a psychological characteristic of most criminals. Exoneration of a premeditated and committed crime is carried out in various ways:

- exaggerating the guilt of the crime victim;
- devaluing social and legal norms against the rules of anti-social groups (gangs, gangs of thieves);
- putting the responsibility on others, justifying oneself with the situation, etc.

Being alienated from social values, the criminal, on the basis of mental decompensation (use of false "substitutes" that create internal mental balance), looks for the reasons for his criminal behavior not in his internal negative qualities, but in external situations and the actions of other people. Criminal motives are personal negative characteristics of the criminal

- is formed through a system of malice, jealousy, ambition, false views (misunderstanding of qualities such as duty, friendship).

The needs of persons who have committed crimes mainly have the following characteristics:

- that needs are narrow, limited, material-utilitarian in nature;
- lack of development of necessary social needs (needs for work, moral behavior);
- needs that are deformed, exceeding the average standard and the legal possibilities of satisfaction;
- violated needs.

In this sense, most offenders have hypertrophy of consumerism.

In today's conditions, the members of the lower-level group may not know their bosses (leaders). The former spotters' union can be considered as a source for the formation of organized criminal groups (communities). This may be due to socio-psychological reasons: the spotters who left the "big spot"

lost their internal reserves in the future, their inability to use their knowledge and skills in a certain profession, lack of financial support. allows them to become members of criminal groups.

Conclusion:

The organization of criminal groups creates criminogenic conditions in certain regions and countries. Many young men are attracted to this criminal world. The criminal team promises them large financial incentives, implements its criminal ideas using the "trapping" technique, and creates an opportunity for the team to expand and deepen.

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EVALUATION OF THE LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL BALANCE AMONG PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS BY EDUCATIONAL COUNSELORS

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>A sense of emotional balance is a basis for success, creativity and innovation at work, as it is a necessity of intellectual production for any individual in society, and at any age, always to creative work, and the positive evaluation of the individual by his sense of emotional stability pushes him to others to make the person aware of himself and evaluate it is a positive way, which makes him feel a sense of reassurance and security, but in the case of a lack of a sense of balance, and the feeling of fear increases in the human psyche, and the person who loses the sense of emotional stability, will tend to be insecure in all his other life matters, problems appear, troubles and mistakes abound, and therefore he works to destroy himself.</p>	

Introduction

Therefore, the current research aims to:

1. Evaluation of the level of emotional balance among principals and teachers by educational counselors.
2. Detection of the level of emotional stability among the members of the basic research sample. .
3. To identify that there are statistically significant differences in the average response of the members of the basic research sample in the level of emotional stability among the members of the basic research sample according to the gender variable (male, female).

For the purpose of achieving the objectives of the current research, it was required that the researcher build a tool to measure the level of emotional balance, and the scale consists of (20) paragraphs formulated in a way that suits the subject of the study, as it consists of (5) alternatives and the degree of correction for the positive paragraphs (1,2,3,4,5). The weights are reversed on the negative paragraphs (1,2,3,4,5) and the alternatives that represent the positive paragraphs are (never, rarely, sometimes, often, always). The alternatives that represent the negative paragraphs are (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never). The tool was applied to a sample of educational counselors working in schools, whose number reached (181) male and female counselors of both sexes, where the number of males was (80). The number of females was (101). Where they were chosen randomly. The results

showed that there were no statistically significant differences between males and females in the level of emotional balance among principals and teachers by educational counselors.

In light of this result, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Providing scientific, educational and recreational programmes, activities and events that contribute to achieving emotional balance and training in self-control.
2. Paying attention to educational and psychological counseling, especially educational institutions, following up on the various problems facing it and using the simplest solutions to overcome them.
3. The study concluded the issue of emotional balance in various fields, especially since the Arab studies that dealt with it were few compared to the actual history of the emergence of the concept and the amount of interest it received in foreign research.
4. Studying the emotional stability of principals and teachers in various educational situations, searching for the factors that lead to its increase in the field of education, and exploring them in the field.

Chapter One:

The problem of study:

Emotional balance is a clear turn in the human psyche and therefore you find some have the skill of mastering it and others can not master it and endowed with a mind and emotion that is not dictated by passions and is not based on the ground of its reality of imaginations (Al-Otaibi, 1999, p. 3).

That moderate emotions activate thinking and mental and motor processes and increase the tendency to continue to work The intense emotions paralyze the control of the will, and affect all mental processes negatively make the principal and teacher in a state of lack of control over his emotions, which results in behaviors and actions reduce his efficiency in the performance of the role entrusted to him (Al-Radadi, 1997, p. 2).

Emotional balance is one of the characteristics of a compatible personality that is characterized by courage in facing challenges, decisiveness in making important decisions, the ability to control, and control in expressing love and interacting with others based on his emotion and possession of an existence that does not cancel his privacy and uniqueness, and on his integration with others (CHRYSTAL, 2012, P:20).

The sense of emotional stability is the basis for success, creativity and innovation at work, as it is a necessity of intellectual production does not make a person realize himself and evaluate it positively, which makes him feel a sense of tranquility and security, but in the case of lack of sense of emotional balance and growing in the human psyche feeling of fear, and the person who loses the sense of emotional stability will work to be insecure in all other life matters, and problems appear and inconveniences and errors abound, and therefore he works to destroy himself (Jaber, 1986, p. 7).

Belonging to the working group provides its members with protection against negative administrative practices that occur in many educational institutions and organizations, and the same applies to members of the educational staff, as they join schools in order to achieve these needs and achieve themselves through work and teaching, and serving the school environment and society (Reitz, 1981, P: 7).

Iraqi society is witnessing an increase in the number of public schools. In achieving their goals, these schools depend mainly on qualified educational staff members. Attracting, maintaining, and developing scientific competencies in these schools is a matter that requires effort, time, and money. Competition is a situation represented by the transfer of some scientific competencies from one school

to another. Universities in general were created for various reasons, including the lack of a faculty member's sense of security, achieving emotional stability in his or her workplace, and the ability to control emotions within the classroom environment. This matter was reflected in the level of his job performance, despite the attempt of some schools to create and prepare the appropriate climate for an effective faculty member. In performing his teaching work, as it is at the forefront of the main jobs in educational institutions (Al-Zubaidi, 1997, p. 11).

What prompted me to research this topic is based on the importance of the role of the teaching staff member, and in order to raise the level of educational staff in schools and serve the community, it is necessary to pay attention to the safety and psychological health of teaching staff members; To perform the job tasks assigned to them with excellence and competence.

Due to the importance of the topic, the researcher was motivated to raise these questions:

- 1 . What is the level of emotional balance of principals and teachers by educational counselors?
2. Are there statistically significant differences in the average response of the members of the basic research sample in the level of emotional balance according to the gender variable (males, females)?

The importance of study:

The importance of tudys can be summarized as follows:

First: Theoretical importance:

1. The study is an extension of the research of some previous researchers who studied emotional balance and deepened it.
2. This study is an enrichment of theoretical knowledge in the subject of emotional balance, because the research sample are educational counselors who attach a lot of hopes to them in their communities.
3. It will shed light on the difficulties faced by some principals and teachers in order to detect weaknesses and work to remove them by specialists in the psychological and educational field.
4. The importance of the study lies in surveying the opinions of educational counselors and taking their suggestions and benefiting from their experiences as they are basic members and active participants in educational work.
5. Encouraging the establishment of similar research in the departments and directorates of education because of the clear impact of these researches for the purpose of concerted efforts to solve problems and obstacles.
6. Providing information to those concerned with this category and drawing their attention to study all the circumstances surrounding the principals and teachers in order to overcome the obstacles that stand in their way and that prevent them from performing their work well.

Second: Applied importance:

1. It refers to an aspect that can not be neglected in the analysis of the elements of the educational process, which is the emotional aspect as the sender is a human being and the receiver is another human being and the message as well can carry an emotional formula that may affect the way it reaches and receives.
2. The study hopes to draw the attention of educational and psychological specialists in the field of exploiting human energies and developing educational and guidance programs.
3. The results of the study can be used to develop appropriate criteria for the selection of principals and teachers entrusted with the task of preparing generations.

4. Trying to apply the abstract of research that dealt with emotional balance in the field of education in order to promote it in various fields after it proved successful in developed countries.

The Objectives:

The aims of study:

1. Evaluation of the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors.
2. Detecting the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors.
3. Identify whether there are statistically significant differences in the average response of members of the basic research sample to the level of emotional balance according to the gender variable (males, females).

study limits:

The current research is determined by the following:

1. The human field: A selected sample of educational counselors working in middle and middle schools of both genders.
2. Spatial area: Misan Governorate / middle schools.
3. Time field: for the academic year (2020-2021).

Definition of terms:

First: evaluation

- Abu Al-Haja, 2001 defined it: It is a process carried out by a person or group to determine the extent of his success or failure when he does something (Abu Al-Haja, 2001, p. 169).
- Al-Janabi, 2002 defined it: as making judgments and decisions about the validity and suitability of information to reach conclusions and decisions according to the quality, validity, and suitability of what we know and remember and what our thinking produces (Al-Janabi, 2002, p. 26).

Second: Emotional balance:

- Defined by Daoud and others, 1992: It is the individual's ability to deal with matters patiently and patiently, without being provoked or aroused by trivial events, and characterized by calm and sobriety, rational in confronting matters, and controlling his emotions (Daoud et al., 1992, p. 278).
- Arafa Kazem, 1994: It is the emotional characteristic that makes the individual able to deal with matters calmly, patiently, and rationally, not getting excited by trivial events, controlling emotions, and behaving well in stressful situations (Kazem, 1994, p. 33).
- Arafa Al-Zubaidi, 1997: It is a relatively stable emotional trait that represents the individual's control over his emotions, feelings, and motivations, controlling them, and his ability to deal with matters patiently, patiently, and rationally, and to face life with vitality, activity, and good conduct (Al-Zubaidi, 1997, p. 28).
- Arafa Al-Tamimi, 1999: It is a state of development and physical, intellectual, and emotional harmony of the individual with himself and the environment in which he lives, leading to enjoying a life relatively free of intense emotions (Al-Tamimi, 1999, p. 12).
- Arafa Al-Masoudi, 2002: It is one of the characteristics of a balanced person who is characterized by courage in facing the future, determination to make important decisions, his ability to control and control the authentic expression of his emotions, and his possession of an existence based on love and interaction with others, and this does not negate his privacy and uniqueness with them (Al-Masoudi, 2002), (p. 16).

- Yunus, 2004 defined it: It is the individual's ability to control and control his emotions, not to be excessively emotional, and not to be carried away by the influence of transient, emergency, and social external events, and by creating internal adaptation that enables him to face the circumstances without it costing effort (Yunes, 2004, p. 36).

- The procedural definition of emotional balance: It is the total score that the respondent obtains through the response of individuals from the basic research sample to the items of the scale prepared for this purpose.

Third: School Director:

- A person whose job is to supervise one or more employees, departments, or volunteers to ensure that certain duties are performed or that the goals of a specific group are met. Managers can be formal or informal. They are most common within companies, but can also be found when there is a need for a leader to head up individual projects (www.arabiainc.com).

Fourth: The teacher:

- He is the person responsible for distributing knowledge, providing students with it, and facilitating and simplifying information for them. The role of teachers is not limited to providing students with knowledge, but rather they are intellectual leaders who create opportunities for students to consolidate what they have learned and apply it in their practical lives.

Fifth: Educational advisors:

- Defined by Al-Hayali, 1990: They are one of the faculty members qualified to study students' educational, health, social, and behavioral problems, through information related to this problem, whether this information is related to the student himself, or to the environment surrounding him, for the purpose of enlightening him about his problem, and helping him to think. In the appropriate solutions to this problem or problems that he suffers from, in order to choose the appropriate solution that he accepts for himself (Al-Hayali, 1990, p. 10).

Chapter two

First: The theoretical background.

1. The concept of emotional balance:

- Rageh 1961 believes: Emotional balance is the individual's ability to control his emotions and express them in a mature, balanced way, far from childhood expressions and recklessness and impulsiveness. The individual's behavior is not characterized as panicked or under intense pressure, and his emotional life is calm and does not fluctuate or fluctuate for trivial reasons between joy and joy, and contraction, and between sadness and joy, and between laughter and crying, and between pride and submission, and between sensitivity and bullying (Rajeh, 1961, p. 101).

- Al-Hafni, 1975 sees: It is emotional stability or emotional stability and freedom from sharp changes or fluctuations in mood, which indicates that the individual's emotional control is excellent (Al-Hafni, 1975, p. 265).

- Al-Masa'id, 1977, believes: Emotional balance is the calmness of an individual's disposition, his control over his emotions and himself, the difficulty of arousing him, and his not suffering from various types of obsessions and anxieties (Al-Masa'id, 1977, p. 7).

- Camellia 1984 believes: It is the state in which a person is able to perceive the different aspects of the situations facing him, then link these aspects with his motivations, experiences, and previous experiences of success and failure that help him determine and determine the type and nature of the response that is consistent with the requirements of the current situation and allows for the

manifestation of an appropriate response that ends with the individual, to be compatible with the environment and contribute positively to its activity and at the same time give the individual a state of satisfaction and happiness (Camellia, 1984, p. 77).

2. Classification of emotions in terms of their resulting impact on the individual's personality:

- Emotions differ in terms of the feelings that accompany them, some of which are pleasant emotions accompanied by feelings of relief, such as emotions of joy and pride, and some of which are painful emotions accompanied by feelings of discomfort because they are linked to obstructing the basic needs of the individual, such as anger and rage.
- Emotions also vary in terms of the effect they produce. Some are tonic, such as joy and anger, and others are inhibitory, such as sadness or depression.
- In terms of the degree of clarity, we find some prominent emotions with clear signs and features, such as laughter and disgust, while we find other emotions whose meanings are unclear and blurred, such as the love of possession.
- The emotions may be occasional and temporary, such as rage, that is, they go away when their triggers disappear, or they may be chronic, for which the person does not realize the cause, such as anxiety and feelings of guilt, both of which are due to subconscious causes, or the result of traumas that befall the individual during his childhood.
- Emotions are either simple and primary and cannot be analyzed into simpler ones, such as fear and anger. Emotions may be derivative, and they are the ones that follow simple, primary emotions, such as despair or hope that follows fear, for example (Al-Meligy, 1982, p. 157).

3. Types of emotions and the impact of the environment and genetics on the personality of the individual:

The emotions are many and varied so that they can not be counted and they vary according to the individuals and the environment and the situations faced by these individuals and there are many divisions of emotions, for example divided (McDougall) emotions into three sections:

- Primary emotions: are related to instincts and appear in human life before others.
- Composite emotions: It arises from the mixing of two or more primary emotions as a result of the excitement of one or more instincts that do not oppose each other.
- Derivative emotions: emanate from a special desire (Hamdan, 2010, p. 92).

Some see their classification as follows:

- Emotions of an aggressive nature such as anger and hatred.
- Emotions with a blocking or disruptive character, such as fear and anxiety.
- Sarah emotions such as love and tenderness (Younes, 1978, p. 148).

Some of them are classified as follows:

- Initial or simple emotions: such as fear and anxiety.
- Complex emotions in their composition: It is based on the mixing of two or more emotions, such as jealousy and surprise (Al-Kinani et al., 2002, p. 409).

4. Benefits of emotions:

Moderate degrees of emotion achieve many benefits for the individual, including the following:

- The emotional charge associated with the emotion increases the individual's endurance and pushes him to continue working and achieve his goals.

- The emotion social value, in the expressions accompanying the emotion as we have already explained the value of linking the individual and increase their understanding of each other.
- Emotion is a source of pleasure, each individual needs a certain degree of them if increased affected his behavior and thinking, and if less bored .
- Emotions prepare the individual to resist autonomic nervous system stimulation defect (El-Sayed et al., 1992, p. 692).
- The balance of all the emotions of the individual in psychological integration linking the aspects of the situation and the motives of the person and his experience.
- The ability of the individual to live in social harmony and adapt to the surrounding environment and contribute positively to its activity in a way that gives him a sense of satisfaction and happiness.
- The ability of the individual to form fixed moral habits thanks to his control of his emotions and grouping them around certain moral topics (Abu Zayd, 1987, p. 227).

5. Disadvantages of emotions:

- Emotion affects the individual's thinking, preventing him from continuing as in the case of anger or making thinking slow, as in the case of sadness and depression.
- Emotion reduces a person's ability to criticize and make correct judgments.
- It also affects memory in relation to events that occur during the emotional period.
- In the event that emotions occur permanently and continuously, they result in many physiological variables, which leads to organic changes in the tissues and in this case arises the so-called psychosomatic or psychosomatic diseases (Al-Muzaini, 2001, p. 46).

6. The most important physical and physiological symptoms associated with emotions:

- Blood pressure and distribution: It usually occurs in the case of emotion high blood pressure and a change in its distribution between the surface of the body and inside.
- Rapid heartbeat: The heartbeat increases in the case of emotion and this is a general phenomenon experienced by the majority of people (dilated pupils: which is noted that the pupil narrows in the case of pain and turbulence, while widening in the case of calm and pleasure).
- Dry throat and mouth: affects the emotional disorder and drooling flows, as the amount decreases and dry throat and mouth in case of panic and anger in particular.
- Bowel and stomach movement: In the case of fear, the stomach is paralyzed from moving, and it is possible to observe this by examining with x-rays, and it happens in many cases that the individual is infected with the intensity of emotion with diarrhea or constipation.
- Change in blood chemistry: The analysis of blood in emotional states proves a chemical change. The level of sugar changes, as does the adrenaline and other elements.
- Change in the system of breathing (Zeidan, 1984, p. 85).

7. The characteristics of emotional balance in the individual are as follows:

- The ability of the individual to control his emotions and control himself in situations that provoke emotion and his ability to withstand and maintain calm neurosis and safety thinking about crises and adversity.
- That his emotional life is fixed and sober does not fluctuate or fluctuate for trivial reasons and stimuli.
- The individual should not be inclined to aggression and be able to take responsibility, carry out work, settle in it and persevere in it.
- As long as possible balance all the emotions of the individual in psychological integration links between the aspects of the situation and the motives of the person and his experience.

- The ability of the individual to live in social harmony and adapt to the surrounding environment and contribute positively to its activity in a way that gives him a sense of satisfaction and happiness (Abu Zeid, 1987, p. 227).

8. Theories that explained emotional balance:

- Ganet's theorem:

His theory is based on the assumption that the decomposition of the nervous system and weak communication leads to the separation of emotional activities and the separation of emotional activities results in isolation from each other, so it remains an excluded aspect of emotional life and becomes locked in the individual because the nervous system cannot carry out its task, forcing it to take wrong paths that appear in the form of turbulent emotion, and the disadvantages of this theory are that it is just an assumption of the decomposition of the nervous system lacks stability, as the human being is prone to emotion in special circumstances in which it seems the decomposition of the nervous system is far from explaining to us the phenomenon, as well as there may be evidence of a malfunction in the nervous system without the consequent emotional disorder of great significance (Faeq and Abdul Qadir, 1992, p. 222).

- WALLOON THEOREM:

This theory sees that the human being at the beginning of his life responds according to a primitive neural circuit, which is when the newborn since birth, which characterizes his emotion, but the growth of the upper levels of the nervous system and its control over the lower activities enters the human being in a higher nervous cycle. Valemotion is a regression in response under certain conditions of the nervous cycle to the primitive nervous cycle becomes an emotional response. However, one of the criticisms of this theory is that it has not shown us how and why emotionally provoking apostasy occurs (Faeq and Abdelkader, 1992, p. 223).

- Freud's traditional psychoanalytic theory:

Some psychoanalysts are interested in emotions on concepts such as anxiety, and aggression, although Freud has been interested in his writings anxiety and unconscious processes, but he neglected emotions and considered it a response process, in an article (1916) on the unconscious wrote: There is confidence that emotions fall within the feeling or consciousness (Mr. et al., 1992, p. 686).

Where Freud considered that sexual energy (Lapido) when hindered to reach its goal turns into an emotional charge that wants to discharge and wait for opportunities to take off, and in the first stage of life where awareness of the world has not grown characterized by the focus of the appearance on the body, which is what: Freud called it the stage (narcissistic Alliseed) and as a result of the child's friction with the world and increasing awareness of it launches a measure of this to appear on its subjects is constantly increasing Launch this Lyseeb expression (Layseem objective) and as a result of suppression of the objective Lyseeed becomes a starting Emotion is an expression of the narcissistic appearance in a hidden way and satisfying it in an imaginary way and depicting the old state of deprivation in a sudden and mysterious way (Faeq and Abdelkader, 1992, p. 19).

- Behavioral Theory:

This theory sees that emotion arises from the point of view of some behaviorists as a result of conflict provoked in the organism, which leads him to make inconsistent responses, as others explain emotions in the light of behavior disorder. Watson treated emotion as a genotype of response involving physical changes in the organism's body as a whole, Watson treated emotions in the same way he dealt with

unconditional responses that occur consistently to certain stimuli, and did not care about the physiological analysis of emotion, or the role of the nervous system (El-Sayed et al., 1992, p. 683).

Second: Previous studies.

1. Arab studies.

• Yunis 2004 study:

Titled “The relationship of emotional stability to levels of self-affirmation among a sample of University of Jordan students”

A- The study aimed to: reveal all levels of emotional balance and levels of self-affirmation, and find the relationship between them, among a sample of University of Jordan students.

B- Study sample: The sample consisted of (136) male and female students from the University of Jordan who were registered in the second semester of the academic year (2033-2004).

C- Study tools: The researcher used the emotional stability scale that he used (Al-Obaidi, 1992). To detect levels of self-affirmation, he used the Walbe scale.

D- Study results:

1. That there is a statistically significant difference at the significance level (0.05) or less in the level of emotional balance attributed to the gender variable.

2. There is a statistically significant difference at the significance level (0.05 or less) in the level of self-affirmation due to the gender variable, in favor of males in both cases.

3. The results of the statistical analysis, using the correlation coefficient to reveal the relationship between the level of self-affirmation and the level of emotional balance in the research sample, showed that the average level of self-affirmation clearly intersected with both the medium and high levels of emotional balance, and that there was a statistically significant relationship at the level of (0.05) or less) between levels of self-affirmation and levels of emotional balance, as the correlation coefficient reached (0.314) (Younis, 2004, p. 82).

• Ryan 2006 study:

Titled “Emotional balance and its relationship to both cognitive speed and innovative thinking among eleventh grade students in the Gaza governorates.”

A- The study aimed to: reveal the relationship between emotional balance and both cognitive speed and innovative thinking among eleventh grade students in the Gaza governorates.

B - Study sample: (530) male and female students from the eleventh grade in the Gaza governorates were selected from the scientific and literary specializations.

C - Study results:

1. There is no statistically significant correlation between emotional balance and cognitive speed among the sample members.

2. There is no statistically significant correlation between emotional balance and the ability to think innovatively among the sample members.

3. There are no statistically significant differences at a significance level of less than “0.05” between the average scores of those with low and high emotional balance on the cognitive speed test among sample members.

4. There are no statistically significant differences at a significance level of less than “0.05” between the average scores of those with low and high emotional stability on the test of the ability to think innovatively among the sample members.

5. There is no statistically significant effect of the interaction between emotional stability and student type on the cognitive speed test among sample members (Rayan, 2006, p. 81).

• Muhammad's 2006 study:

Titled "Measuring the emotional stability of students in teacher training institutes, male and female, whose families were subjected to raids, searches, and arrests by the American occupation forces, and their peers who were not exposed to them."

A- The study aimed to:

1. Measuring the level of emotional stability among students of teacher training institutes in general, whose families were subjected to raids, searches, and arrests by the American occupation forces, and also those whose families were not exposed to raids, searches, and arrests by the American occupation forces.

2. Identifying the differences in the level of emotional balance between those who were exposed and those who were not.

B- Study sample: (762) male and female students were selected from the Institute for Preparing Male and Female Teachers in the city of Mosul.

C- Tools: The researcher used the emotional stability scale that he used (Al-Masoudi, 2002, p. 34).

D- Study results:

1. The level of emotional balance among the sample members in general was high.

2. The level of emotional stability among students of teacher training institutes whose families were subjected to raids, searches, and arrest by the American occupation forces is lower than their peers who were not exposed to it, and that there are statistically significant differences between them (Muhammad, 2006, p. 64).

1. Foreign studies.

• Albright study 2008:

A - The study aimed to reveal stress and emotional balance among adult students. It also aimed to reveal the relationship between stress and emotional balance and their impact on the student's personality.

B - Study sample: (133) university students in the United States of America were selected.

T - Tools: The researcher relied on the experimental method, and the researcher built an emotional balance scale and carried out validity and reliability measures for the scale.

D - Statistical methods: including (correlation coefficient, t-test, Copy square, analysis of variance)...

C - The results of the study: Stress has a negative impact on the student's personality, which is reflected in his emotional balance, and thus directly affects his behavior and behavior (ALBRIGHT, 2008, p: 98).

• Henley 2010 study:

A - The study aimed to: train students on emotional balance through the method of self-control and acquiring its skills.

B - Study sample: (37) male and female students were selected in a school in the United States of America.

T - Tools: The researcher used two tools, namely a questionnaire and a guidance program to increase balance in personality.

D - Results of the study: When students possess self-control skills, they become more able to deal with others, and problems related to behavior began to decline, and students indicated that they felt self-confident after possessing these skills (HENLEY, 2010, P:2 26).

• Kumar 2013 study:

A - The study aimed: to reveal the level of emotional stability and its relationship to the social and economic level of students studying in public and private secondary schools in India.

B - Study sample: (100) individuals were selected from public and private secondary schools in India (50) male and (50) female students were selected randomly.

T- Tools: A special scale was used for emotional control and interviewing

D - Results of the study: The results showed that the level of emotional balance among the members of the study sample was moderate, as it showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of emotional balance among students who study in public and private schools, and the presence of differences in the general average of the social status of the emotional balance that they are distinguished by. , and economic demand (KUMAR, 2013, p: 137).

Chapter three

Methodology and procedures

This chapter includes a description of the procedures undertaken by the researcher to achieve the research objectives, which are summarized in describing the research population and how to select the sample, preparing a tool to evaluate the level of emotional balance among principals and teachers by educational counselors, verifying its validity and reliability, and then determining the statistical methods that the researcher used to reach research results .

Methodology

The researcher used the descriptive approach to measure the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors by building its own tool. This approach is one of the most common and widespread approaches in educational research.

Community

The research community includes (educational counselors and those continuing in service who graduated from the departments of psychological counseling and educational guidance and are distributed to middle and middle schools in Misan Governorate for the academic year (2021-2022).

The sample of study:

Since the current research aims to build a tool to evaluate the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors, the research procedures required selecting a sample of educational counselors, with a percentage of (53%) from the original population to be researched, which is (340) male and female counselors, where they were chosen. (181) male and female mentors (101) female mentors and (80) male mentors were chosen randomly, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1)

Explains the research population and sample

Number of female mentors	Number of mentors	Sample of study	Community of study
101	80	181	340

The tool of study

The researcher used the questionnaire to evaluate the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors, which he built as a tool to achieve the goals of his study.

Methods for verifying validity and reliability

The researcher used face validity to ensure the validity of the research tool. As for reliability, the researcher used the retest method as a means to verify the stability of the research tool. The reliability coefficient was (0.81), which is a high reliability coefficient that is acceptable for psychological tests and measures.

The tool application

After completing the preparation of the research tool and ensuring its validity and reliability, the basic application was carried out on the basic research sample of (181) male and female counselors, with the aim of assessing the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers from the educational counselors, and identifying the significance of the differences between them in terms of gender.

Fifth: Statistical methods

The researcher used the following statistical methods:

1. Percentage for the purpose of diagnosing the opinions of the expert committee regarding the validity of the tool's items.
2. Pearson correlation coefficient to find the relationship between the first and second application of the tool to calculate the reliability coefficient.
3. The weighted mean equation to determine the likelihood of the sample members' answers to each of the paragraphs.
4. Percentage weight formula for ranking paragraphs in general.
5. T-test. test to test the significance of the differences for two unrelated means and two unequal samples.

The chapter four

Presentation and interpretation of results

First: revealing the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors.

To learn about the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers from the educational counselors, the researcher extracted the weighted mean and percentage weight for each item in the tool, where the average score of the five-point scale was calculated (3) as a criterion for separating between achieved and unachieved items, as shown in Table (2).

Table (2)

It shows the weighted mean, percentage weight, and rank for each item in this scale

Percentage weight	Weighted mean	Paragraphs	Rank within the questionnaire	s
87,2	4,36	They feel calm and inner reassurance	1	1
80,6	4,03	They continue their work actively despite the obstacles	2	2
78,8	3,94	They do not feel shy when talking to others	17	3

87,4	3,92	They very much welcome interactive discussions and dialogues	4	4
78,2	3,91	They behave positively and naturally with strangers	18	5
74,8	3,74	If there is a problem they have that does not have a clear solution, they can find a solution for it	11	6
74,6	3,73	They can carry out their work under all circumstances	5	7
74,2	3,71	They are able to accomplish any work they aspire to	16	8
73,2	3,66	They are coherent when they are exposed to emotional shocks of what is around them	7	9
69	3,45	They arrange their work in an organized manner in terms of the plan and do not deviate from it	6	10
68,2	3,41	They are completely satisfied with their lives and themselves	3	11
66,2	3,31	They do not feel stressed when they are unable to face any problem they have	8	12
65,6	3,28	They admit the mistakes they make, regardless of the circumstances	19	13
65,2	3,26	They accept criticism, even if it is inappropriate	9	14
64,2	3,21	They feel afraid of imaginary things that have no truth in reality	15	15
62,4	3,12	They can easily ignore painful news	10	16
62	3,10	They easily deal with anyone who needs help	14	17
61,4	3,07	They have the ability to persuade and influence	12	18
60,2	3,01	They always seem to reconcile with their opponents	13	19
57,2	2,86	They take revenge on those who wrong them, no matter what the cost	20	20

The scale consists of (20) items, and from observing the table we find that all of them were verified. Their weighted means ranged between (4.36) and (3.01), while their percentage weights ranged from (87.2) to (60.2), except for Paragraph (20) is not met, as it obtained a weighted mean of (2.86) and a percentage weight of (57.2).

This is what was indicated by the results of the statistical analysis, where the paragraphs were arranged as follows - They feel calm and internally reassured, and they continue their work actively despite the presence of obstacles, and they do not feel shy when talking to others, and they very much welcome discussions and interactive dialogues, and they behave in a positive and natural manner with strangers, and if there is a problem they have, it is not it has a clear solution that they can find a solution to, and

they can carry out their work in all circumstances, and they are able to accomplish any work they aspire to, and they are coherent when they are exposed to emotional shocks to what is around them, and they arrange their work in an organized manner in terms of the plan, and they do not deviate from it, and they are completely satisfied with their lives and themselves, and they do not feel they suffer from stress when they are unable to face any problem they have, admit the mistakes they make regardless of the circumstances, receive criticism even if it is misplaced, feel afraid of imaginary things that have no truth in reality, can easily ignore painful news, and deal easily with anyone who needs help. They have the ability to persuade and influence them, and they always seem to reconcile with their opponents, while paragraph (20) (they take revenge on those who harm them, no matter what it costs them) did not obtain the required significance, and the researcher attributes the reason for this to the fact that the values that were formed in the personality of the teacher and the principal are strong, so they do not they can be neglected, and they are committed to Islamic values in this particular field

Secondly. Identify whether there are statistically significant differences in the average response of members of the basic research sample in the level of emotional balance according to the gender variable (males, females), to verify the validity of the hypothesis, the researcher used a t-test for two unequal samples, between the two gender variables (male and female), where the arithmetic mean value for the male variable was (352.43) with a standard deviation of (49.81), while the average value was (352.43) with a standard deviation of (49.81). The arithmetic for the female variable is (346.62) with a standard deviation of (46.52), and the calculated (t) value was (0.76), which is less than the tabulated (t) value of (1.960) at the significance level (0.05).) with a degree of freedom (179), and this result indicates that there are no differences between males and females in the level of emotional balance according to the gender variable (males, females), as shown in Table (3).

Table (3)

Shows the T-value (t) calculated according to the gender variable (males - females)

Statistical significance level: 0.05	Tabular t value	t value Calculated	standard deviation	SMS	Gender variable
Not sign	1,960	0,76	49,81	352,43	males
			46,52	346,62	females

The researcher attributes this to the fact that male and female educational counselors believe in the importance of equal conditions between principals and teachers in which they live and the social and economic situation in which they live within one country in which values, principles and morals prevail, which makes there no differences between them in terms of their emotional balance towards all the circumstances, situations and problems that arise. They go through it, both positive and negative.

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The appendix is in its final form

University of Misan

Faculty of Education

Department of Educational and Psychological Sciences

The mentor/guide the respected ones

The researcher is conducting a study on (evaluating the level of emotional stability among principals and teachers by educational counselors)

You have a set of paragraphs in your hands. Please read them and answer them accurately and objectively by choosing alternatives to each paragraph by placing a mark (√) in the appropriate place for each choice in front of each paragraph, taking into account not to leave any paragraph unanswered.

Thank you for your scientific cooperation with appreciation

Emotional balance scale

never	scarcely	sometimes	mostly	always	paragraphs	s
					They feel calm and inner reassurance	1
					They continue their work actively despite the obstacles	2
					They do not feel shy when talking to others	3
					They very much welcome interactive discussions and dialogues	4
					They behave positively and naturally with strangers	5
					If there is a problem that does not have a clear solution, they can find a solution for it	6
					They can carry out their work under all circumstances	7

					They are able to accomplish any work they aspire to	8
					They are coherent when they are exposed to emotional shocks of what is around them	9
					They arrange their work in an organized manner in terms of the plan and do not deviate from it	10
					They are completely satisfied with their lives and themselves	11
					They do not feel stressed when they are unable to face any problem they have	12
					They admit the mistakes they make, regardless of the circumstances	13
					They accept criticism, even if it is inappropriate	14
					They feel afraid of imaginary things that have no truth in reality	15
					They can easily ignore painful news	16
					They easily deal with anyone who needs help	17
					They have the ability to persuade and influence	18

					They always seem to reconcile with their opponents	19
					They take revenge on those who wrong them, no matter what the cost	20

IMPROVE THE BEE FOOD BASE BY PLANTING SAP AND POLLINATING TREES AND SHRUBS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on increasing the yield of fruits and obtaining high-quality honey by planting trees and shrubs that provide nectar and pollen, improving the food base of bees.

KEYWORDS

Bees, bee feeding, bee milk, bee wax, bee venom, pollen, flower.

Introduction

Beekeeping is one of the branches of agriculture, based on raising bees for the purpose of obtaining honey, wax and other products (bee milk, bee glue, bee venom, etc.), as well as for pollination of agricultural crops. The science of organization and management of beekeeping farms covers the legal and organizational aspects of farms that are developing rapidly in agriculture, the ways of using advanced technologies in raising bee families and increasing productivity and high-quality products. It is necessary to pay attention to the quality of food while using innovative technologies in beekeeping and to use modern methods. It is important to feed the bees with healthy food so that they do not get sick. Such food is given before the bees get sick. If the bees were infected with rot or nozematosis in the previous season, methods of adding protein food to the bee colonies in the next season will be necessary.

If bees are given 1-2.5 million units of biomycin, tetracycline, and streptocide drugs per kilogram of pasty food, they will not be infected with rotting disease. It is necessary to consult a veterinarian about which of the mentioned drugs and how much to add. If the bees in the apiaries are heavily infected with nozematous disease, then 4-8 g of fumagillin per kilogram of food is added (the amount to be added depends on how dangerous the bees are infected). Strong bee colonies consume one kilogram of the doughy food made from a mixture of honey and sugar syrup and added medicine for 7-10 days.

The bee family can be seen in 3 distinct periods in their spring development:

- 1 The period of replacement of overwintering bees
- 2 The period of rapid development of the Ari family
- 3 A period in which a large number of unemployed young bees accumulate

First period. After 1 month from the time when the mother bee begins to lay eggs, there is a period of exchange of places of bees that have come out of winter, this period extends to the period of intensive work of bees. During this period, the old bees that overwintered die, and their place is taken by the bees that were raised in the spring. The mother bee starts laying eggs in the southern regions at the beginning of spring, that is, in the first 10 days of February. In the first days, the mother bee begins to lay 40-80 eggs per day, and then 100-120. After passing the first spring flight and emptying the garbage accumulated during wintering in the hindguts, the egg-laying of the queen bee increases several times.

Second period. This period is characterized by rapid development of the bee family. There is a reciprocal relationship between the developing forager bees and the maturing larvae, and the mother bee lays eggs depending on the number of bees feeding the larvae. As the number of young bees in the colony increases, so does the mother bee's egg-laying rate. In the second period, the death of old bees in the family is not so much, on average, it is equal to the number of eggs laid by the mother bee 56-66 days ago (21 days - the day of raising worker bees; the day of bees' summer residence - 35-45 days; total $21 + 35 = 56$ days; $21 + 45 = 66$ days).

The development and growth rate of the bee family in the second period also depends on the quality of the bees that make up the family, the development of a bee family that has failed to hibernate in winter does not exceed 3-5% per day, and that of a strong bee family that has wintered well is 10-14% per day. How many days the second period lasts depends on the growth and development of the bee family, the weaker the family, the longer it develops, and vice versa.

Third period. The third period begins only after 2-2.5 kg of bees are grown in the bee family. This period is called the gathering period of unemployed young bees. This period lasts until the bees of the bee family reach 2.5-4 kg. In the third instar, the queen lays more eggs, but this increase still results in fewer larvae than the number of young bees produced, meaning that there is a significant disconnect between the number of nurse bees and the number of eggs laid by the queen. The stronger the colony, the fewer larvae the mother bee produces relative to her weight. The mother bee lays up to 2,000 eggs per day, and it takes an average of 43 seconds to lay one egg. She spends most of her time looking for empty, cleaned cells. There are slightly more young growing bees than dying old ones, and the family develops slowly. The stronger the family, the slower it develops. When strong bee families are long developed, the number of young bees produced in 1 day is equal to the number of old bees dying per day, and the development and growth of the family stops. During this period, the decline of old bees depends on the amount of sap coming from nature. residence time is slightly longer. Thus, there is a difference between the number of eggs laid by the mother bee and the number of worker bees, and the surplus of young worker bees in the family remains unemployed. In the third period, bees are not provided with work because there is no sap from nature.

The following changes occur in the family:

- 1) the average life time of worker bees in the family increases, a large number of young bees accumulate, and the strength of the family increases slightly;

2) as a result of the reduction of the physiological aging of the bees' body in the family, the bees of the family become younger, and the bees of the family accumulate energy and useful food units for living and working in their bodies.

The bee colony settles in the fall flat and around areas with early spring blooming, pollinating and nectar-producing plants, as the bees replenish the nutrients lost in their bodies during the long winter with pollen from early spring flowering plants. Beehives are placed with the entrance of bees facing the sun. The beehives should be placed one meter apart, and the rows should be 3-4 meters apart. They are installed on piles at a height of 40-45 cm from the ground. When the bees fly after the weather warms up, if after flying out of the hive their abdomens are swollen, they crawl and empty their hindguts inside the hive, then the bee family has been fed with poor quality food during the winter, that is, the food contains nozematous bacilli. lib, this indicates that he has an intestinal disease. If the bees leave the hive and fly slowly, then this means that the bee family is small or lacks food. will be In order to know when to feed or feed the colony, the beekeeper should watch for flowering nectar plants in early spring. For this, one medium strong bee family is placed on the scales and it is necessary to check whether the bees are producing juice or consuming the accumulated nectar in the house. If the weight of the bee colony has not changed, the bees will produce some juice and feed themselves. If the weight has changed, the bees accumulate a small amount of juice. Beekeepers do not give honey, sugar, juice to the bee family in both of the above cases.

The following plants can be planted to improve the bee food base.

Apricots bloom in March-April and provide bees with pollen and nectar in early summer. The color of the pollen is red. One apricot bush gives 7-8 kg of flowers. The color of honey is white yellow.

Apple - blooms from April to June. One bush gives 5-7 kg of flowers and pollen. The color of the pollen is yellow. Honey crystallizes very quickly, its color is pale yellow.

Quince is a smaller tree that blooms in May and gives 4-5 kg of flowers per bush. The color of the pollen is white and that of honey is light yellow.

Almond - blooms in March and April, one bush gives 5-7 kg of flowers. The color of the honey is light yellow, the color of the pollen is red.

Persimmon is a tall tree that blooms in May and June. One bush gives up to 10 kg of flowers and pollen. The honey of all date varieties is yellow in color, slightly bitter, but sweet and dark, and quickly crystallizes.

Pear - blooms in April. Each bush gives 5-6 kg of flowers. Bees also collect pollen from pears. The color of honey is light yellow.

Yantok - blooms in July-September. Each hectare yields up to 150 kg of honey. The color of the pollen is light yellow. The color of honey is light gray, it crystallizes quickly, and the crystals are small.

Oak acacia tree height 10-12 m. It blooms in May-June. The color of the flowers is white. Each hectare gives 300 to 500 kg of flowers. White acacia honey is one of the best honeys. The color of honey is white and it is finely crystallized.

Cherry blossoms in April and May. The flowering period is 10 days. The color of honey is light yellow. Gives flowers and pollen. Each bush gives 5-7 kg of flowers.

Mynchak is a perennial plant that blooms in June and July. Even during warm rains, bees visit the monkey flower. The flowering period is 40 days. Gives honey and pollen.

The color of the pollen is light gray. Each hectare yields up to 100 kg of honey. The color of the honey is light yellow.

Peach is a 6-7 m tree that blooms in March and April. The color of the pollen is red. One bush of peach gives 6-7 kg of flowers.

The color of honey is light yellow.

The color of honey is orange. It crystallizes quickly.

Lion's tail (pustirnik) - blooms in June and August. It also gives pollen. One hectare yields up to 300 kilograins of honey. The honey is pale straw in color and does not have a sharp taste.

Botakoz (vasilyok) is found among barley crops. St. John's wort - blooms in summer and autumn until frost. Gives nectar and pollen. Bees work hard. The color of honey is green-yellow. The honey is thick and smells of almonds. At the beginning, the taste is slightly bitter.

Old lady (lopukh) - blooms in June and July. One hectare yields up to 100 kg of honey. The color of the honey is dark-olive, the honey is fragrant and elastic.

Plum is a 10 m tall tree, it blooms 1-2 days before cherry in May and lasts for 10 days. It also gives pollen. Strong families can collect up to 1.8 kg of flowers per day. One bush gives 4-5 kg of flowers. The color of honey is light yellow.

Japanese safflower blooms in June and July. During the flowering period, bees work hard. The color of honey is cream color.

Coriander - blooms from June to July, gives pollen. One hectare yields up to 500 kg of honey. Honey has a sharp taste and a light yellow color.

Willow blooms in March and April, each bush gives 20-25 kg of flowers and pollen. The color of honey is golden yellow.

Tograyhan (dushisa) is a herb that blooms in June. The flowering period is one month. One hectare yields up to 100 kg of honey and pollen. Honey is fragrant and has a yellow-blue color. When it crystallizes, it turns into white small grains.

Krushina - blooms in May and June. One hectare yields up to 40 kg of honey. The color of honey is light yellow.

Kamchigul (gechikha) - blooms in July and August. The flowering period is 40-45 days. One hectare yields up to 150 kg of honey and pollen. The color of honey is dark reddish.

Emari - blooms in March and April. It gives a lot of pollen and honey. Bees collect dew from the leaves. It is not recommended to leave the honey in the village.

Conclusion:

In short, it is possible to get a high yield by planting nectar-rich plants on large areas, and by improving the food base for bees, high-quality honey can be obtained.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF
STUDENTS**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>The formal structure of the system of professional pedagogical training in higher education consists of a set of teachers, teaching aids, students and teaching technologies. This article discusses the importance of developing the professional competence of teachers.</p>	<p>professional pedagogical training, creativity, inquisitiveness, dedication, professional competence, pedagogue, teaching technologies, professional pedagogical activity.</p>

Introduction

The strategy and technologies of ensuring the quality of education require a clear definition and interpretation of such concepts as the professional formation, preparation of professional education and professional competence of the pedagogue. Modeling their systematic organization and studying the internal structure, functions or purpose of this phenomenon in the educational process helps to master these pedagogical events in the human personality.

The logic of professional-pedagogical education is represented by the system of the following concepts, which record the essence, direction and purpose of the main components of human creation: the professional formation of a pedagogue is a professional formation during the formative and subject effects characterized by the systematic and dynamic nature of human labor subject, personality and activity changes;

preparation for the professional education of a pedagogue is a specially organized professional process and mastering the subject's system of professional and pedagogical knowledge, technologies of professional activity, experience of creative implementation of activities and motivational-valuable attitude to the values of pedagogical culture. is the result and shows the level of preparedness and readiness of the pedagogue to perform his professional functions at work.

In the model of the professional competence of the teacher, it is necessary to have knowledge about all the components of the educational process (goals, content, means, object, result, etc.), about oneself as a subject of professional activity. It should also include the experience of implementing methods of professional activity as a combination of professional skills and the experience of implementing teaching methods as a creative component, such as changing and transferring them. As

Ye. I. Passov [128, 129, 130, 131] has stated. activity components are mediated by personality structure (activity, emotional-motivational and knowing/cognitive) and motivational-value and emotional/emotional-evaluative attitude to profession is reoriented by personal experience. Therefore, the activity-based component of professional competence is related to the structure of a person in a dialectical unity and is represented by professional-pedagogical skills.

Another point is that the proposed model should be filled with professional and pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills represent the sum of various actions of the teacher. These actions, first of all, are related to the functions of pedagogical activity, in many ways represent a set of very diverse actions that reveal the individual-psychological characteristics of the teacher and testify to his subject-professional competence [69, 70, 71, 72., 73, 74], on the other hand, competence is a general concept for all subjective characteristics that are manifested in activity and ensure its effectiveness [72]. Thus, determining the necessary range of professional-pedagogical qualifications, which represent the personality of the pedagogue and his subjective characteristics in interaction with students, is a sufficient basis for filling the professional-pedagogical competence meaningfully and operationally. The dialectic of the professional development of the pedagogue, who has defined the development of professional competence as his main goal, can be interpreted as a constant "acme" - the contribution of personal development to the qualitative transformations and the rise to the top of the profession, which determines the stage of promotion and the quantitative characteristics of professionalization.

Note 2. The development of professional competence (PK) as a constant "acme" (a; б; в) - reaching the peaks with personality (L) and stage characteristics; activity component (D), where the contribution of each vertex (a; б; в) as a private component changes the "acme" of the pedagogue to a qualitatively new state (see Figure 1.3):

Figure 1.3. Dialectic of teacher's professional development

The student's professional development is a complex, multifaceted process of a person's entry into the profession, which is expressed by the uncertain contribution of personal and activity components in the conditions of the leading role of the pedagogue's personality factor. The priority direction of professional education is to form the field of motivational value, meaning field of professional development in the logic of vertical and horizontal connections of this process.

The professional competence of a teacher can be considered as a set of private competences forming a new quality. Each level of professional development is sufficient within a certain stage of the profession (introduction, adaptation, integration, individualization, etc.).

We studied the psychological foundations of professional competence from the point of view of the pedagogue as a person, professional-pedagogical activity and subject of communication.

Coordination of professional trajectories and criteria in their vertical and horizontal connections necessarily leads to the development of optimal mechanisms of specialist training. The management mechanism based on the laws and principles indicated above serves as a condition for ensuring the continuity and consistency of the stages and levels of the professional formation of the pedagogue. The object of management in the professional education of a teacher is the process of development of his professional competence.

The specific features of professional-pedagogical activity in HEIs are distributed to all components of the professional competence of the future pedagogue:

person;

level of competence and preparedness: psychological, pedagogical and methodical knowledge arising from the purpose, content and technology of upbringing, education, development in higher education institutions;

professional-pedagogical qualifications, training: knowledge of a pedagogue is "implemented in his practical work, therefore they are inextricably linked with general pedagogical qualifications and skills. A teacher's practical skills are the form of application of his theoretical knowledge" [33];

in general, psychological-pedagogical activity: the process of communication and activity in higher educational institutions is considered to have a developing and educational nature that affects the results of educational practice in many ways.

Highlighting the specific features of these components is, in essence, substantiating the psychological-pedagogical features of the student's professional competence. The following factors cause the features highlighted:

objective requirements for the personality and activity of a specialist are recorded/specified in state educational standards[58], certification and qualification documents[132];

experimental studies in the field of the activity of creating a professionogram of student activity[132];

Existing concepts of professional training of students in HEIs [105];

In the higher education system, the goals and tasks of the teaching and educational process create the unique characteristics of the professional and pedagogical activity. In the process of professional activity, goal setting, content determination, student knowledge, activity management methods, student knowledge of the activity such important aspects as the choice of management tools, the design of the organizational structure, and the editing of the results emphasize the cooperative activity of the learner and the pedagogue.

Analysis of the requirements of the state educational standards for graduates of various pedagogical educational institutions allows to identify the following characteristics as invariant (unchangeable) characteristics: important psychological and personal qualities - benevolence (empathy), emotional stability, communicative, organizational qualities, professional and scientific-educational orientation (N.V. Kuzmina[96, 97, 98, 99], V.V. Karpov[98], L.E. Varfolomeeva[98]). Particular attention is paid to the communicative aspect of the student-specialist activity (S. Ya. Romashina [141, 142, 143, 144], I. I. Ridanova, N. V. Kharitonova [172] and others). "Communicative activity of a pedagogue is a unique activity that exists throughout the entire process of professional activity." as the thing that acts, it also acts as a universal form of activity" [187; p. 11]. S.G. Molchanov [123] distinguishes information-communicative, normative-communicative and affective-communicative functions of pedagogical activity as its main functions [123]. As noted by I.A. Zimnaya [69, 70, 71, 72., 73, 74], "it is for this age period that it is necessary for the teacher to demonstrate pedagogical functions such

as information, organization, control, etc., academic, it is required to implement all pedagogical skills based on didactic and organizational skills" [69, 70, 71, 72., 73, 74].

Summarizing the above, we can draw a conclusion about the specific characteristics and personal qualities of a student's professional and pedagogical activity: invariant requirements and characteristics are enriched by the specific characteristics of professional activity. The high level of emotional tension arising from the pedagogue's commitment to benevolent, person-oriented activities requires him to develop the skills of self-organization and self-regulation (N.P. Nevzorova [126]).

The identified psychological-pedagogical features of the student's professional competence allow a rational approach to studying its content based on a structural-functional approach. This technology is reflected in the work of S. Ya. Romashina[141, 142, 143, 144] in connection with the analysis of pedagogical activity.

The possibilities of the structural-functional approach in the study of the phenomenon of professional competence allow to master the studied object in a human person, to reveal its structural organization, educational parts and functional purpose. Such an approach can be considered as the operational level of the systemic approach. The results of applying the structural-functional approach to the study of student professional competence will be as follows: spaces and factors of student's professional development;

structural organization of the systematic phenomenon of "professional competence", which represents the sum of motivational, theoretical, technological and positive result/effective readiness of the student to carry out professional activity; is the logic of the functional purpose and interaction of structural components. Achieving the final result - a certain level of development of professional competence - is possible when developing its components in the following sequence:

1. The motivational-valuable and emotional-evaluative attitude of the student to the pedagogical reality is of decisive importance for the next stages; the purpose of this block is to form the psychological readiness of the pedagogue for work based on the relevance of the individual experience acquired in the following blocks.
2. The student's theoretical preparation determines competence - a set of knowledge about pedagogical facts, principles, laws, goals, content, technologies and the results of creating/forming a person; this block is intended to form preparation for mastering practical methods of activity based on knowledge.
3. Technological training is a set of skills that represent the experience of implementing certain methods and creative implementation of pedagogical activities, which assimilates the readiness of the pedagogue to perform professional functions and instills competence into the subject of work.
4. The purpose of preparing for a positive result as the ability to determine the productivity of one's professional activity and overall development and the property of giving a positive result is to develop a holistic image of professional competences in the sum of all its blocks and components; is the main factor in measuring the level of development of professional competence.

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**FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF
PRESCHOOL CHILDREN**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
The article is devoted to the modernization of preschool education spiritual and moral ducation and development of a child of preschool age. The article analyzes the problems, explains the possibilities of their successful solution precisely in preschool childhood; reveals the tasks, principles, content, forms and methods of developing interaction between adults and children, aimed at the spiritual and moral development of preschoolers, and the possible positive results of this activity.	Modernization, preschool education, spiritual and moral, upbringing, child development, preschool age.

Introduction

The relevance of spiritual and moral education and development of children is due, on the one hand, to the objective and continuous process of moral development of a person, which can be of different directions, and the objective interest of the human community in managing this process, the desire to pass on the culture of spiritual and moral life, a system of moral values as one of the conditions for the preservation and development of man and society.

Deformation of moral ideals, crisis of the value system in modern society; the spontaneously emerging understanding of "freedom" as "permissiveness", and "reasonable control" as "censorship"; uncritical borrowing of foreign experience and values that do not correspond to the mentality of the Russian people; as a consequence, the emergence of the phenomenon of lack of spirituality in society - all these are factors that enhance the urgency of the problem.

The modern education system in general and preschool education in particular does not fully implement the task of spiritual and moral education and development of a child for a number of reasons. The moral state of modern society does not contribute to the success of the work. Other reasons lie in the education system itself. One of them is the inconsistency, and often the incompatibility of various methodological positions in solving the problem, in particular, difficulties in establishing relationships, harmonizing the positions of Orthodox and secular education.

Obviously, it is necessary to combine the canons of Uzbek and religious education in an effort to preserve the purity of children's souls, clarifying the image of God in every child, from the point of view of Orthodoxy, and purposefully promoting the formation and development of the child's spiritual world in accordance with moral ideals and values adopted in society - from the standpoint of non-native education. The basis of such an integrative approach to solving the problem is, in our opinion, the presence of common positions in the understanding and interpretation of many problems of

personality development. One of the essential common positions lies in the understanding of personality development as self-development. That is, both Orthodox and national upbringing recognize the factor of self-development, self-construction, self-creation of one's inner world on the basis of free choice, reflection, self-correction of the "I" image in accordance with the system of value and moral guidelines adopted by a person as the main factor determining in the development of personality. The question is what values will be accepted by a person. Revealing, comprehending and practical implementation of these connections is one of the tasks and the theoretical basis for the development of substantive and methodological aspects of the integrated educational process. Another reason for the low efficiency of the educational process is the dominance of the knowledge paradigm in solving the problem and poor attention to the formation of the corresponding feelings and actions. This does not contribute to the holistic development of the child's spiritual world, introduces dissonance in the holistic development of the cognitive, emotional, volitional spheres of his personality and manifests itself in the mismatch of knowledge, feelings and actions of the child in behavior, in activity.

The low competence of adults in matters of spiritual and moral education and development of children is also evident; weak interconnection of the activities of different subjects of the educational process (parents, teachers, representatives of different social and religious structures); lack of a system in operation; insufficiently high level of spiritual and moral development of adults interacting with children (teachers, parents, etc.) The main resource condition for solving this problem is an adult, a competent teacher who introduces a child into the world of culture and contributes to his personal development. Thus, there is a contradiction between the acute objective necessity and the demand for solving the problems of spiritual and moral development of a person, favorable opportunities for this at an early age, on the one hand, and their superficial implementation in the preschool education system, on the other. The situation is aggravated by the poorly informative presentation of the problem of spiritual and moral education in modern normative documents on preschool education. The goal of spiritual and moral education and development of children: to promote the development of the foundations of preschool children, the basis of personal culture in relation to people, phenomena of social life, nature, the objective world, to oneself in accordance with universal human spiritual and moral values adopted in society.

Itual and moral values adopted in society. Tasks aimed at the spiritual and moral development of children:

1. To familiarize children with spiritual and moral values, the distinction between good and evil, as the basis for self-regulation, self-management of behavior and activities. To develop in unity and harmony all spheres of the child's personality: cognitive, emotional, volitional.
2. To form in children accessible systemic knowledge about the world around him: people, nature, man-made objects and the place of the child in this world.
3. To promote the development of the child's interest in his native land: its nature, history; folk and national culture (traditions, customs, art, holidays, etc.)
4. To promote the development of the emotional sphere in children:
 - 4.1. Feelings of various quality for the originality of the world around them (surprise, admiration, admiration, pride, reverence for shrines, reverence and respect for parents and other people, mercy, sympathy, sympathy, empathy, grief, rejection, indignation).

- 4.2. Cultures of their expression (verbal and non-verbal acceptable ways of expression, emotion management).
- 4.3. Ability to emotionally anticipate the consequences of their actions.
- 4.4. The development of emotional decentration (perceive, distinguish, respect the feelings of another, take into account in their behavior).
- 4.5. Formation and development of the prerequisites for civil and patriotic feelings.
5. To foster in children a proactive activity position towards the world around them, manifested in behavior (careful and caring attitude, mercy, the desire for goodness, accessible creation, the desire and ability to work, discipline, rejection and the desire to avoid bad deeds).
6. Create conditions for the gradual formation of the child's self-awareness: prerequisites for objective introspection, self-esteem, the emergence of the foundations of reflexive abilities, the desire for a positive image of "I", in accordance with moral values, awakening of conscience.
7. To promote the emergence and development of the prerequisites for respectful attitude to the originality of national characteristics, traditions, culture of other peoples, the emergence of the ability to enter world culture.

The principles of spiritual and moral education and development of children

1. The principle of developmental education, the purpose of which is the spiritual and moral formation and development of the child. In psychology, the category "development" is interpreted as maturation; - development as an artificial, specially designed "development activity"; - development as self-development "... as a fundamental human ability to become and be a true subject of his own life. And from this point of view, truly developing education can be considered that, and only that, which implements all three types of development, the central of which is self-development. " Specially organized education of children of early and preschool age should be natural, meeting the needs and capabilities of the child, at the same time meeting the needs of society and focused, if possible, on the development of the ability to self-education, self-development. In the field of spiritual and moral formation of the personality, the mechanisms of self-development are the main, key ones. Of course, in preschool age, the possibilities for conscious, purposeful self-development are limited, however, imitation of another, and the choice of a goal, means of achieving it, and elementary reflexive actions, assessment and self-esteem, gradually obey the rules, moral values adopted and implemented in the system of relations under conditions families, preschool educational institutions in child-adult, children's communities. With the development of general arbitrariness, the will, these opportunities for self-development increase, at the same time, arbitrariness and will are formed in spiritual and moral behavior.

2. The principle of social and pedagogical partnership of the subjects of the educational process. The unification and interaction of adults (social structures) participating in the educational process based on the knowledge and acceptance of spiritual and moral values by each participant, in accordance with which the child is brought up, concerned with the development of his own spirituality, capable of reflecting on their activities (from introspection and self-esteem to goodness) ...

3. The principle of integration of the educational process, which presupposes an integrated and systematic approach to the content and organization of the educational process. The systematization of the content of the work is based on the idea of developing the basis of personal culture, the spiritual development of children in all spheres and types of activity.

4. Person-centered approach assumes acceptance of the child as he is, benevolence, warmth in relationships, faith in his positive development; the adult's desire to be significant for the child, the priority of the subject is subject relations, dialogical communication.
5. Individual-differentiated approach. Individual approach to children, taking into account family, national traditions, etc.
6. The activity approach is realized in the development of the child in the types of activities specific to the preschooler; facilitating the appearance of a subjective position in moral behavior in a child in their conditions.
7. The principle of cultural conformity as following traditional Russian values in the process of spiritual and moral education and development, involves education using the material of folk pedagogy, folk culture and art, folk, including national, traditions.
8. The principle of compliance of tasks, content, forms and methods of upbringing with the age characteristics of preschoolers, the laws of their physical, mental and personal development.
9. The principle of identification - identifying oneself with a significant other, striving to be like him. Correlation of your own behavior with the norm, rule, etc.

The content of spiritual and moral education and development is designed and implemented in the main program, in all educational areas: "Physical culture", "Health", "Safety", "Socialization", "Labor", "Cognition", "Communication", "Reading fiction", "Artistic creation", "Music". The tasks of spiritual and moral education of children are solved in an integrated manner in the course of mastering all educational areas, along with tasks that reflect the specifics of each educational area. The solution to this problem is possible in various forms of organizing the educational process: directly educational activities, regime processes, independent activities of children in a family environment and in cooperation with the family, using developmental technologies and techniques. These are design, experimentation, classes of different types and types, story games and games with rules, TRIZ elements, problem situations, etc. All of them are focused on types of thinking specific for a preschooler (visual-effective, visual-figurative) and methods of cognition (sensory, play, experimentation, questions to adults in the process of communication), available methods of action, behavior, emotionality prevailing in preschool age. In connection with this feature, the ideas that stand out are interesting: in communication, the child learns not only cultural patterns, but also the motives of new types of activity. Value, motivational levels of activity are mastered only through another, through an adult. The method of transmitting new motives has its own specifics: through emotional infection, involvement, the creation of a common semantic field. The effectiveness of specially organized "development" activities in the educational process is determined not only by the optimal cultural content (selection of cultural content), but also by the ways of interacting with children, ways of organizing joint activities and determining the role, place, ways of including an adult in the process of this interaction. We believe that the term "joint activity" should be viewed in a broader context. It is also applicable to the child's independent activity, which also requires the reasonable, developmental participation of an adult. It's just that there are other ways of compatibility: indirect - purposeful creation of a subject environment by adults; establishing links between the independent activities of children with the content and forms of work of the entire educational process, for example, the use of children's drawings, handicrafts made in independent activities, in games, in other activities, etc.; help; cooperation as a response to the child's initiative activity, a positive response to the child's expressed need for cooperation: advice, practical help, encouragement, protection, etc.

The idea of integrating content, different forms, methods, joint activities of the subjects of the educational process also extends to the interaction of the preschool educational institution and the family. The educational process is not limited to the space of the preschool educational institution, if the parents are its equal subjects. We believe that the broad interpretation of the essence of joint activity is applicable to the characteristics of the educational process in a family environment. The only difference is in the social environment, the composition of the child-adult community. The child has other partners in the family, other subjects of educational activity.

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**PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE PHYSICAL
DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
The model of physical education of schoolchildren is considered as a set of forms of physical education united for one purpose and aimed at solving health and educational-pedagogical tasks.	Physical development, height, physical education technology, indicators of physical development, coordination abilities, health status of students, indicators of physical development and physical fitness, innovative approach to physical education of schoolchildren.

Introduction

The formation of pedagogy as a science stems from the need to prepare the young generation for life, to effectively implement their education. After the accumulated experiences regarding this need, there is a need to generalize those experiences, to develop laws and regulations about youth educators.

A number of pedagogic scientists believe that education provides communication between generations. Adults have taught the next generation the experiences they have gained during their life. The younger generation acquires knowledge and skills while finding solutions to new problems encountered during their activities, enriches the knowledge inherited from the previous generation and leaves it to the next generation.

As P.F.Lesgaft said, the task of physical education is to limit the disorder in a person's actions in order to consciously react to their actions in full with mental development and to perform their work with as little effort as possible.

Big changes are taking place in the life of our developing country, including in the school education system. A new general education school is being formed, the teacher's pedagogical activity aimed at comprehensive development of the student and independent development is being improved.

Yu.A. Yanson developed the structure of the modern physical education process of schoolchildren on the basis of his research work, which consists of six components:

1. Goal orientation of physical education (increasing and strengthening the level of health, all-round development of schoolchildren, forming the order of movement of students, personal physical education, preparing schoolchildren for life activities, forming a worldview in the field of physical education).
2. The physical education program (more than twenty programs have been developed recently), it should include 60-70 percent of the basic functional content based on the state educational standard, and 30-40 percent of the teacher's climatic and geographical conditions, ethnic characteristics, children's living conditions develops taking into account the socio-economic conditions of its conditions.
3. The model of physical education of schoolchildren, it is considered as a set of forms of physical education united to one goal and aimed at solving health and educational-pedagogical tasks.
4. Technology of physical education is a set of tools (physical exercises in the program), methods, forms of organization and conditions for engaging in movement actions. The basic model, technology is covered in the monograph.
5. The quality of physical education (objective and subjective indicators of physical development, movement readiness are determined, the ability to master movement actions is determined).
6. Managing the process of physical education.

According to E.A. Seytkhalilov, maintaining children's health in complex social, economic and environmental conditions is one of the most urgent problems of mankind.

P. Khadjaev emphasizes that the state of modern physical education is represented by a problematic situation, which is, on the one hand, the need to modernize it, and on the other hand, insufficient understanding of the value and spiritual orientations of the upcoming changes at the level of public and individual pedagogical consciousness, the content of physical education and education - depends on the weak development of effective mechanisms for achieving educational goals.

M. Barkoshev studied physical development indicators of 6-7-year-old schoolchildren. Regularly changing indicators of physical qualities and coordination abilities, their uneven and jumpy development have been identified. Therefore, according to the author, it is necessary to determine the standards of physical fitness of schoolchildren.

T.S.Usmonkhodzhaev developed and implemented the technology of testing the indicators of physical development and physical fitness, which determines the state of health of students, and used it in the comprehensive assessment of the quality of education of schoolchildren. Other authors also support this idea.

According to D.D. Sharipova and G. Shakhmurova, improving the quality of health of the growing young generation is possible only when measures are taken to find the criteria for early assessment of the functional state of all body systems.

While developing an innovative approach to the physical education of schoolchildren, a group of authors came to the following conclusion: currently, the intensity of the educational process in secondary schools is associated with an increase in the hours allocated for static subjects, the violation of the students' rest schedule and a number of other factors lead to the deterioration of the physical and mental health of students. is coming One of the most effective approaches in the current situation is to restructure the school physical education system taking into account the individual interests of schoolchildren and create conditions for the formation of a strong need for students to acquire physical education and healthy lifestyle values.

Sh.Kh. Khankeldiev developed a self-management training program for schoolchildren of younger age in the course of physical education-rehabilitation works. The program has the following structure:

1. The design block, which includes the target supply, which defines the main goals and objectives of the experimental program.
2. Content block, it defines the list of basic, additional and auxiliary means of physical education of children.
3. Procedural block, in which methodological recommendations on the use of physical education tools based on experience during research are described.
4. Control - accounting block, which includes the program for organizing the process of physical education of junior schoolchildren and evaluating their results.

M.S. Khaziakhmetova found out that 45% of school-aged children do not have the need for regular physical education and sports, and this condition has a negative impact on their physical activity. It is very important and necessary to form the need for physical education exercises and sports in an organized way, especially at the junior school age, because by the senior school age, the independent need for physical activity should remain in the students and be at the necessary level in the future.

Preschool education and training is a type of education aimed at teaching and educating children, developing them intellectually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education.

Preschool education aims to form a healthy and mature child's personality, prepared for general secondary education. This education is carried out in the family and in pre-school educational institutions until the age of seven.

Preschool education provides: strengthening and maintaining children's spiritual, mental and physical development; treatment and correction of children with disabilities , as well as creating a healthy environment for modern inclusive preschool education; determining the content of preschool education; raising children in the spirit of love for the Motherland, respect for the family, national traditions and customs, forming a conscious attitude towards oneself and the environment in them; formation of the child's personality, development of his creative abilities; ensure the child's social adaptation and readiness to continue education; implementation of social-pedagogical patronage of the family.

Children aged 6 to 7 years are required to be educated in preschool educational institutions and general secondary educational institutions according to the relevant educational program, which is the stage of preparation for general secondary education (grade 0).

Self-control requires comparing the results of performing and solving educational tasks with the expected result, result and its evaluation step by step during the process. Development of self-control and assessment skills in children is an important condition for the formation of mental independence and activity. The desire to achieve good results, which naturally arises during self-control and evaluation, encourages the child to look for new tools and methods of solving the task.

Pedagogical conditions for the formation of the ability to self-monitor and evaluate in the performance of educational tasks are as follows:

- 1) analysis of task performance by the tutor and comparison with the results obtained at the end of the training;
- 2) to set children the task of evaluating the results of training by identifying mistakes and shortcomings.

V.Loginova and P.Samorukhova in their work entitled " Pedagogy of preschool education " : "Specialists in different fields can determine children 's readiness for school . The pediatrician examines the child and determines his somatic development, if he has a certain physical and mental deficiency, he sends him to a psychological-pedagogical examination. Children with certain disabilities are sent to special schools .

In the study guide of K.Mahkamjonov and P.Khodzhaev, it is recommended to use the physical training program and standards developed for students of junior classes. It is shown here that 16 hours are allocated to gymnastics, 14 hours to athletics, and 38 hours to sports and action games. As we can see, the small amount of hours allocated to physical education in the annual study cycle does not allow to implement an individual approach to each child and to make sufficient use of the fitness direction of training, to use a rating system for evaluating physical development and physical fitness indicators, and therefore, to make objective corrections to the educational process.

It is known that the physical fitness of children and adolescents, their functional state and work ability are largely determined by somatometric indicators.

The analysis of the data representing the physical development of children made it possible to determine that they are approximately the same as the data of other authors on the physiometric indicators of children of educational institutions.

The age of 7 is associated with the transition from preschool age to school age, that is, a new routine, new physical and mental loads, etc. By the age of 7, the child should have such a development that the child should join the school life without difficulty, study successfully in the first grade .

The problem of interdependence of education and development is the main topic of research of a number of researchers, including A.I. Leontev, L.V. Zankov, Ch.S. Kostyuk and others.

The connection between upbringing and development is especially evident in the educational process. The teaching of the Russian scientist L.S. Vygotsky is especially noteworthy here. According to his concept, two stages play an important role in a child's mental development:

First, the child performs certain tasks independently. It can also be called a stage of development of the child's mental functions or an important stage of development. Through imitation, the child begins to understand and do more things together with adults. This is now the second stage of mental development. The difference between the second and first stage determines the child's future development area.

Physical development of children and adolescents is related to acceleration, i.e., rapid development, and is not related to genetic factors, but to the influence of the external environment.

Physical development is more influenced by the external environment, which can change the development process in a negative or positive direction. R. From Salamov's research, it became clear that the development of physical qualities in relation to age is uneven, that is, not the same.

The analysis of correlations between the main indicators of physical development shows that children who attended preschool educational institutions are more comprehensively developed. This is explained by the fact that in the conditions of preschool educational institutions, a system of measures formed in practice is carried out and they have a positive effect on the results of children's physical capabilities, which helps children to adapt to school conditions without undue difficulty.

Movement is a natural need of a child's body. It is a biological stimulant, a means of actively stimulating the child's growth processes and forming all his organs and systems.

The development of motor skills is related to biological and social factors: the natural biological growth of the organism is observed along with the increase in the child's movement opportunities, it is determined by social conditions, and the movement function participates as a pedagogical influence, a directed component.

The natural course of a child's motor development largely depends on his movement pattern, the content and methodology of physical education training. It is possible to influence the process of biological development of movement qualities through the selection of appropriate physical exercises during training.

This is confirmed by the results of many studies, the authors of which admit that regular exercise has a positive effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems after 2-3 months. In children, it is manifested in the decrease of the rate of heart contraction and the rate of breathing in relation to the gradually increasing physical load.

The positive effect of physical exercises is manifested not only in the increase of indicators of physical development and movement readiness, but also in the increase of working capacity. The effect of physical exercises is preventive and, to some extent, curative because children can be stopped with various exercises when they get sick.

By H.A. Meliev a pilot study aimed at determining the physical development of older preschool children showed that the indicators of physical development in 5-6-year-old children were around physiological norms (Table 1.1.1).

Descriptions of body length indicators of children of preschool educational institutions are one of the main parameters in the assessment of physical development.

Table 1.1.1 Age-specific changes in indicators of physical development of older preschool children

Age	n	Body length (cm)	Body weight (kg)	KQA (cm)
5	64	112.0±0.50	18.9±0.21	57.1±0.91
6	73	119.6±0.63	21.5±0.42	59.3±0.97

The change of this anthropometric indicator during the four-year life of children was of interest, and it was determined that this difference was equal to 5.7 cm and made 9.1 percent. This indicates that the physical exercises performed in the basic physical education classes in preschool educational institutions and the school education system had a positive effect, and this was positively reflected in the indicators of children's health, physical development, and movement readiness.

Experimental verification of anthropometric characteristics was carried out by M.S. Khaziakhmetova with a contingent of children of junior school age at the end of the 90s of the last century.

Research conducted by M.S. Khaziakhmetova in the 90s of the last century with children aged 7-8 years in the Fergana region revealed that the height of 7-year-old boys was 120.5 ± 1.24 cm, and at the age of 8, this sign was statistically reliable. It increased by 5.1 cm (4.17 percent) to 125.6 ± 1.63 cm (Table 1.1.2).

Table 1.1.2 Age-specific changes in physical development indicators in 7-8-year-old children in Fergana (according to M.S. Khaziakhmetova)

Age	n	Body length (cm)	Body weight (kg)	KQA (cm)
7	41	120.5±1.24	23.4±1.07	61.6±1.12
8	37	125.6±1.63	24.5±1.42	62.8±1.19

According to many authors, height indicators are the main factor for assessing physical development, which reflects the nature of the formation of the child's organism. Here, the annual growth of physical development indicators in junior schoolchildren increased by an average of 4.1 percent from year to year from 7 to 8 years of age.

The body weight of 7-year-old boys entering school was 23.4±1.07 kg, and at the age of 8, this indicator reached an average of 24.5±1.42 kg, which is 2.1 kg more than the indicator of 7-year-old boys (4.49 percent) was higher.

According to the information in the literature, when evaluating the external respiratory function of students in the younger age group, it was found that at the age of 7 it was equal to 61.6±1.12cm, at the age of 8 this indicator increased unreliably and reached an average of 62.8±1.19 cm. reached, the difference was 1.2 cm (1.92 percent). According to the data of KQA, the indicators of external respiratory function in the period from 5 to 8 years were 5.7 cm on average, which allows us to recognize that the physical education and health activities in the school education system have a positive effect on the body of young students.

Increasing the level of physical development of the young generation and, in connection with it, physical fitness is the most important and urgent pedagogical problem in the field of school physical education. Without knowing the capabilities of the growing child's organism, it is impossible to evaluate the results of the targeted pedagogical effects, and it is impossible to plan the process of improving physical qualities and movement skills.

It is of particular interest to consider the characteristics of physical fitness of children of preschool and junior school age, which is important for the consistent and correct organization of educational work on physical education in preschool educational institutions and general educational institutions.

Physical fitness is defined as the ability to perform various physical exercises with optimal movement qualities - speed, strength, agility, endurance, flexibility, coordination. Children's motor skills are evaluated using a complex of movement tasks. It includes the following basic types of movement: running, walking, jumping, throwing, climbing. It is also possible to evaluate children's motility based on the results of performing special control tasks that indicate the level of development of specific movement qualities.

The analysis of literature sources made it possible to conduct a comparative analysis with the indicators of other authors who conducted research in the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan in the contingent of children we are studying.

of 30 m, it was found that the performance of children aged 6 to 7 years improved by an average of 0.2-0.7 seconds.

This situation was also determined by standing long jump data. Public studies conducted to determine the level of physical fitness of children showed that the results of standing long jump in boys decreased by 6-15 cm compared to previous years.

In the analysis of the dynamics of physical fitness indicators of younger schoolchildren in the last 10 years, it is worth noting that there are more differences in the results shown by children at this age. This situation can be explained by the fact that intellectual and physical workloads in these children have increased significantly during the initial stage of education in the school education system. Studies of children's movement patterns show that a specially developed system of daily physical training allowed to improve the results of running 30 m by 0.4 seconds. Growth in standing long jump in 6-year-old boys was 20 cm, and 33 cm in 7-year-old boys. Relatively low growth of results in 6-year-old boys is probably related to natural movement activity.

The study of children's physical fitness made it possible to determine its dynamics under educational activities and targeted pedagogical effects, to determine the effectiveness of the used physical education tools and methods, to record the level of physical fitness that helps to successfully master educational and physical loads.

The analysis of the data in the scientific literature representing the physical fitness of children is evidence for the recognition of the decline of motor performance in the last 10 years.

Researchers have developed various tools, forms and methods that help to effectively improve motor skills and, in general, the primary school physical education system, and introduced them into the practice of school physical education.

Among the problems of physical education activities conducted at school with children of junior grades, there are also issues of reasonable movement patterns. For this purpose, various pedagogical experiments were carried out:

- analysis of the content of the action order;
- clarifying the structure of the physical education program in educational institutions, its content and normative requirements;
- special organization of experimental traffic procedures;
- taking into account the number of locomotions performed by children during the day, week, season.

As a result of the study of the effect of movement patterns on physical fitness, it was found that children's motor performance increased. Daily walks along difficult routes ensure high movement activity and an increase in physical fitness results. In order to optimize the movement pattern of children, the size of daily locomotions was determined, the activity of this movement in the examined children was around 12,000 to 15,000 locomotions, but its size can vary greatly depending on many factors.

The information available in the literature indicates that the high movement order organized with 7-8-year-old children in the structure of school activities has a positive effect on their physical development and movement readiness indicators. Under the conditions of reasonable movement patterns, the functional capabilities of the children's organism are reliably higher than the indicators of physical fitness of preschool children, because the movement pattern of preschool children was within the framework of the traditional educational scheme, which should be taken into account when organizing physical education activities.

The development of a reasonable order of movement is an urgent pedagogical task, which implies the presence of age-specific favorable periods for the education of certain qualities of movement in children.

Looking at the characteristics of the distribution of the main movement qualities in children according to age characteristics, it is worth saying that children of 6 years of age have strength indicators. Experts say that boys have a satisfactory level of general stamina at this age. It is recognized that pre-school age is a sensitive period, that is, the most favorable period for the formation of coordination skills, which can develop quickly in children of 7 years old only if they regularly engage in physical exercises.

The general laws underlying the development of children's movement qualities must be taken into account when organizing physical training sessions with children in the educational system.

From the information available in the literature, it is known that education of physical qualities of children of small school age is an important pedagogical problem, and it depends not only on the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the organism, but also on upbringing and education.

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THE PLACE OF MIRZO SIROJIDDIN IN MODERN MEDICINE OF BUKHARA

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
In the field of health, the doctor and poet Mirzo Sirojiddin from Bukhara, despite the difficult situation in the country, performs works that will cure the pain of his nation. Although some information about his life and activities have been reported by researchers in a scattered manner, his historical-popular and literary legacy, imbued with the idea of enlightenment, has not been studied in detail and has not been illuminated. The article analyzes this.	Treatment, Mirzo Sirojiddin, poet, method, research.

Introduction

The article of "Mirzo Sirojiddin Hakim - Bukhara developer and medical scholar" was published by T. Qayumov in the collection "Issues of Bukhara history: from the earliest times to the present" published on December 9-10, 2016 under the editorship of Sh. Hayitov" has important information about doctor. In his article, T. Qayumov highlights the work of Mirzo Sirojiddin Hakim in the field of medicine in Bukhara during the Emirate period. In particular, the article states the following: "Mirza Sirojiddin Hakim Bukhari (1878-1914) grew up in the city of Bukhara. Mirzo Siroj opened the first modern hospital in the Chelangari district of Bukhara city, where he began to treat diseases of the meda, rheumatism, and malaria in the European style. The procedure for drug distribution was introduced at this hospital. In general, this hospital worked around the clock. The poor were treated for free."

MATERIALS AND METHODS

U. Nizomiddinov touched on this issue much earlier. He published his book "Mirza Sirajiddin". In this book, the author provides the following information: "Mirza Sirojiddin discovered a method of treating ringworm, which is common among the people of Bukhara, by removing worms from the skin of patients. In one of the reports printed in the "Bukharai Sharif" newspaper, information is given that 300 patients were freed from bondage due to his efforts. Also, treatment works were carried out on the basis of humane principles, rich people received 5 coins from the body of each dead link, and 2.5 coins from average people. They did not take a single coin from poor widows and orphans, they treated them for free¹.

¹ Nizamiddinov U. Mirza Sirojiddin. - T.: Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2013. -B.5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

T. Kayumov's article also contains the following information: "Scientist Mirzo Sirojiddin believes that the majority of diseases in the Emirate period are caused by the disorder in drinking water and food consumption. "If water stays in one place for a long time, it becomes polluted, and living organisms (bacteria) and microbes appear in it, causing disease. Air pollution also promotes the appearance of germs. These microbes are added from the air when eating and drinking water, go to the stomach and lungs and make people sick. "Consequently, it is necessary to connect a water supply (fountain) to every location through a special iron (iron pipe) to supply and control clean water," the judge wrote in the article "Health Care". Mirza Sirojiddin wrote a work entitled "Tuhfai ahli Bukhara" (Gifts to the people of Bukhara)².

Mirzo Sirojiddin narrated what he saw and his memories during his long travels in a work called "Tuhafi ahli Bukhara" ("Gifts of the people of Bukhara") in a simple and fluent language. In 1910, the author completed a manuscript copy of the work, and in 1912, a lithographic copy was published at the Kogon printing house. A manuscript copy of the work was written in Persian on European paper. In total, it contains 193 pages, it measures 13x20, in good condition, complete with introduction and conclusion.

Mirza Siroj was not only a great poet and writer, but also a skilled publicist and journalist. He was one of the founders of the first Tajik-language newspaper "Bukhara Sharif", and published social poems and articles on its pages. This newspaper was published in 1912 in Kogon (New Bukhara) together with another enlightener from Bukhara, Mirzo Muhyiddin. Under the editorship of Mirjalal Yusufzoda, it was published once a week until July 14, 1912, and then four times a week. From July 1912, the newspaper "Turon" was published in the old Uzbek (Turkish) language as a supplement to "Bukharai Sharif". "Turon" was originally published twice a week as a supplement, and from September of the same year, it began to operate as an independent publication. Both newspapers were published in 2600 copies ("Bukharai Sharif" - 800, "Turon" - 1800). "Bukharai Sharif" newspaper will be closed a year later, after its 153rd issue. Mirzo Sirojiddin has been publishing articles under the pseudonym "Hakim Bukhari" since the first issues of "Bukharai Sharif". For example, in the article "Some benefits of the newspaper", it is revealed that newspapers are the most important tool for changing people's worldview, reading books, learning how to live, and being aware of world news and the condition of people. Mirzo Sirojiddin's poem "Yod bod" ("Remember"), written in Masnavi method, was published in 1913 in the 2nd issue of "Oyna" magazine. His poems and articles were published in Iran's "Navbahor" and "Tus", Turkistan's "Samarkand" newspaper and "Oyna" magazine. In his speeches, the author pays special attention to the issue of the formation of historical thinking. He seriously criticizes the decline of the prestige of science in Central Asia, the land of scholars, the shortcomings in making the population literate, and the problems in the education system. He stated that in order to be a generation worthy of our great ancestors, we should learn the right lessons from history, develop science, and read books. He also published more than 30 valuable articles on medicine and health under the title "Hifz-us-sihhat".

Mirzo Siroj got to know several modern figures, including Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdurrauf Fitrat, Abdulkadir Muhyiddinov, through the "Bukharai Sharif" publication.

² Kayumov T. "Mirzo Sirojiddin Hakim, a developer and medical expert from Bukhara" //Issues of the history of Bukhara: from the earliest times to the present. - Bukhara. 2016. -B.64-67.

Mirza Siroj traveled for the fourth time in 1913, but his illness worsened on the way, and on December 21, 1913, he returned to Bukhara from Rasht, Iran. He died of tuberculosis in the middle of the year. After the death of "Oyina" magazine Mahmudhoja Behbudi Mirzo Siroj, the editor-in-chief published the article "Ziya'i alim" ("Bitter loss") in his magazine, expressing his condolences. Also, on the occasion of the death of Mirzo Siroj, Sadridin Aini's sad lament will be published in the 14th issue of "Oyna" magazine.

CONCLUSION

In short, the enlightened views of Mirzo Sirojiddin, who lived and worked in the Bukhara Emirate at the beginning of the 20th century, and his work "Tuhafi ahli Bukhara" occupy an important place in the education of a perfect person.

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**COMPARABLE LEARNING OF WORD ORDER IN DIFFERENT
LANGUAGES**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
In different languages word order can be different, especially if they are not closely related to each other. Every language has own peculiarities making up sentence. So some languages can be seen more distinctive features rather than similarities. However, morphological side of three languages can be found the change of the verb and omission of the subject.	Typical word order, untypical word order, affirmative sentence, interrogative sentence, imperative sentence, special question, general question.

Introduction

Studying any language require to know some characteristics of languages which can be the determining factor in order to learn the target languages more easily. It helps to analyse how the languages are closely related to each other. This makes learners comprehend any grammatical structures and utilise them in a correct way. Comparative learning of word order and inversion in English, German and Uzbek languages can be estimated a bit difficult. Since these languages are not similar with one another, especially, using the words in different positions. However, when we learn grammatical structures in this way, it can be more understandable for learners since they know better about this construction in their source language.

While learning structures in the languages, it should be investigated thoroughly with the help of sentences to identify their peculiarities of orders of words. After comparing these languages, it can be clearly seen their distinctive and similar features of statements.

Literary Review:

In these three language word order are not considered closely associated, which English is inflexible in using words of the sentence, while German words is freely altered their position in the sentence, because it is typical for the German language to change word order through the sentence. When we look through Uzbek word order in the sentence we can identify that it is totally different from two other language.

As we know, the English language is considered fixed word order. It obeys strict rules in order to make up sentences. Its structure is S+V+O, followed in affirmative sentences:

The Professor looked at me. (“The Lost World”)

I have no choice. (“The Lost World”)

We cannot change the order of words in English. There are rules putting subject first, then predicate and after them secondary parts of speech in every sentence.

However, in German we can freely use the order of words. There are two types of word order: typical and untypical. We can choose which they are independently. These structures are: S+V+O or O+V+S.

Ihr erzählte das Unglück. (“Frau Holle”)

(You speak about misfortune.)

Es ging auf deiser Wiese fort. (“Frau Holle”)

(She continued to go to this meadow.)

or

Das Unglück erzählte ihr.

Auf dieser Wiese ging es fort.

In German untypical word order is mostly used form rather than typical one. So we can utilise more freely German words in sentences. The learners can be more confident exploiting words in the sentence

In Uzbek, like German words in the sentences are flexible. We can put words independently within sentence but word order is unlike two languages, the structure is like: S+O+V. Firstly we use subject, then secondary parts of speech and after that predicative. In this language words can also change its place and it is not considered wrong.

Bola jinoyat kodeksining moddasini aytdi. (“Alvido bolalik”)

(The boy said article of criminal code.)

Siz ham nasihatni yaxshi ko’rar ekansiz. (“Alvido bolalik”)

(You also like to admonish)

Interrogative sentence in English it is important to know how questions are formed. They should be followed the order in accordance with general and special questions, which in the former we add only auxiliary verb and in the latter we use question word and auxiliary verb before subject in the sentences.

Do you observe something there? (“The Lost World”)

Would you kindly look at this? (“The Lost World”)

Sometimes, when we make up interrogative sentence we can see some changes for the main verb.

Did you see any trace of life?

How did they come to be there?

We don’t put auxiliary or modal verbs before the subject when we pose a question about someone or something which did it.

Who said that?

What may be near us?

In German, interrogative sentences can be changed more easily from affirmative sentences, which questions are made up to put the main verb before the subject and other part of speech without any change, if they are general questions. If they are special ones we should put special question words before the main verb and the other parts of speech.

Habt ihr keine andere Tochter? (“Aschenputtel”)

(Do you have another daughter?)

Was willst du haben? (“Aschenputtel”)

(What do you want)

These statements in Uzbek are considered to follow totally different structure contrasting to the others. If a question is general, we can only utilise the suffix “-mi” at the end of the sentence, i.e. the predicate of the sentence by adding the particle to predicate verb or noun.

Bu yer joningga tegdimi? (“Alvido bolalik”)

(Are you fed up there?)

Kecha to’yda yaxshi tushdimi? (“Alvido bolalik”)

(Have you earned more in the wedding?)

However, if they are special ones, we should use a special word, which omitted in the sentence. We can put the special word in accordance with which of word left out, by putting them in the place where queried.

Endi nima bo’ladi? (“Alvido bolalik”)

(What is going to happen now?)

U qaysi yo’lga kiradi? (“Alvido bolalik”)

(Which way does he choose?)

In imperative sentences of the English language there are two types: positive and negative forms. For positive forms we can put the verb in the first position, since in it there is not any subject. So imperative sentences is to have only one form.

Let me remind you. (“The Lost World”)

Send for ropes, Massa Malone. (“The Lost World”)

In German there are four forms of imperative. They are: second person singular, second person plural, first person plural and polite form. They take “-e”, “-en” or without any suffixes to form them. They can be differentiated from one another, according to meaning and structures.

Bäumchen, rüttel dich und schüttel dich. (“Aschenputtel”)

(A little tree, shake over me).

In Uzbek there are four forms of imperative sentences, which are They are: second person singular, second person plural, first person plural and polite form. It is similar with the German language. To form imperative we can add some supplements to the verb such as “-ing”, “-gin”, “-aylik”, “-sin” or without any suffixes.

Ro’yxatingizda turuvchi barcha o’smirlar haqidagi ma’lumotni olib keling.

(Bring me information about all teenagers in your list.)

Siz charchabsiz, dam oling yoki davolaning.

(You have been tired, have a relax or look for cure.)

Looking through all communicative levels of these language, they do not have much similarities among them. However, when we investigate these structures, we come across resemblance to the predicative by adding or changing the verb of the sentence. So comparative learning of languages is to support our understanding about the source language and the target language, which can be very effective to teach learners.

Results

Based on the research, given sentences in these certain languages can be investigated various structures of the statements in word order. By analyzing various statements, the order of the words can play important role in every language, despite being different. While words in sentences are investigated through their peculiar order, they can be identified different types of characteristics of the

languages. The most common order for English can be fixed all the time, however, the remaining two languages are totally different opposing the former languages, they can be used freely in the statements changing the order of words. Through sentences we can analyze distinctive features of three languages.

Conclusion

While representing the peculiarities of fixed and non-fixed orders in the variety of languages can be stood differently in according with the characteristics of the language. Investigating this research by taken several examples in order to explore fixable and unfixable variation of the sentences is showed how different can be their features through the statements. It lead to a clear imagination of the word order in every chosen languages within given sentences.

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**FACTORS AND IMPORTANCE OF FORMING PERSONAL
CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This article is devoted to the modern meanings of the formation of individual consciousness in the information society, especially representatives of the vulnerable segment of the population in the socio-psychological provision of sustainable development of society in the era of globalization: In addition, the author gives scientific interpretations by foreign and Uzbek scientists of the concept of the information society. It is concluded that in the context of the expansion of the information space, the individual not only receives free access to information, but also becomes the object of information influence. Under these conditions, the danger of alienation of the individual from society and culture increases.</p>	<p>Information, formations, information society, personality, consciousness, psyche, society, globalization.</p>

Introduction

As a result of the emergence of a new form of information space in the world and the rapid development of computer technologies, the process of information exchange between people has been brought to a new level, which has also led to changes in human thinking. It should be noted that the endless expansion of mutual information exchange, the deepening and acceleration of socio-cultural integration create unique difficulties in the socialization of young people in society.

Information is a message, information. But such an interpretation of "information" is not enough to understand the entire mechanism of information exchange in society from a socio-philosophical point of view. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay attention to the aspects characteristic of any process in order to study the essence of the process of information exchange as a phenomenon, all the general features of information.

In the 21st century, people's activities are increasingly dependent on the possession of information on the one hand, and on the use of this information on the other.

At present, any specialist must be able to receive information through information and communication means, process and use it.

Recently, there has been a growing opinion that information is a factor that determines the strategic direction and level of development of a state.

Globalization has accelerated the transition of societies to the information society. The information market has provided consumers with all the necessary products and services that the information industry produces.

Uzbekistan is trying to be not only a participant and consumer in the global information market, but also a leading state in the production of information.

In particular, in the context of the "information war", new threats related to information security issues are emerging, and this is of urgent importance for the security of our state and our people.

It must be said that when speaking of a spiritual threat, it is necessary, first of all, to have in mind "ideological, ideological and informational aggression directed against the freedom of every person, regardless of his language, religion, and faith, with the aim of completely destroying the spiritual world."¹

In an informed society, the most important thing is information, the ability to own and manage it. The practice of managing, modifying and, if necessary, using the flow of information for short-term and economic benefits is now evident. Examples include hacker, derived from the English word (hacker, computer that gives systems the meaning of an intruder), spindocor, influencing the content of information and transforming it into a form convenient for the communicator.

According to V. Ustyanov, the informatization of everyday life and the emergence of a new information field surrounding the human soul are not without complications. The digital space of the individual, value goals and traditional relationships are changing. These changes are becoming more and more noticeable in all spheres, especially in the economic sphere. Because the exchange of information in organizations connected to the same network is fast, convenient and efficient. But there is another side to the informatization of society, i.e. the use of information by destructive forces to influence the minds of citizens of other states in order to create the basis for destabilizing the situation of a certain country or region.

Hacker attacks on portals and computer programs of Uzbekistan, as well as acts of information aggression carried out from the territories of various states, are examples of information wars waged against our state.

To date, the entry of the state into the world community is ensured not only by its military and financial might, but also by the ability to accurately apply the intellectual achievements of other states, moreover, preventing the cultural expansion of foreign countries, timely agitation and introduction of national spiritual values, the degree of development of public and personal consciousness.

From this point of view, it can be said that information is the political capital of a nation.

In the information society, one of the main factors ensuring the development of society and the state is the rapid informing of the population about the events taking place in the world.

The system of public education plays an important role in the formation of this factor. Despite sometimes opposing points of view, views (religious, philosophical, biological, medical) on the essence of consciousness, there is still no single definition of it.

But psychologists have studied and introduced its general features, and they can be of great importance in understanding (realizing) the managerial mechanism of human actions. This is:

1. A person's consciousness reflects the external world around him;
2. The consciousness of each individual is peculiar to him;
3. One of the main means of comprehension and analysis of the environment, the external world is thinking;
4. Consciousness is strongly connected by speech (verbal, written);

¹ Karimov I. High Spirituality – Invincible Force. – T.: Manaviyat, 2008.p.13

5. Man's consciousness plays an important role in determining his activities;
6. Consciousness plays an important role in determining the subject's attitude to various values (axiological aspect);
7. Consciousness expresses the sequence of symbols (signs, images) perceived by thought and sensation;
8. Physiological and social processes, as well as the environment and external factors are of particular importance in the formation of consciousness;
9. The circumstance that a person is aware of depends on assumptions and conjectures, as well as on the content of his activity at that time;
10. Processes related to the psyche and comprehension depend on the activity of the brain.

In this article, we consider the concept of "consciousness" not from the point of view of religion or philosophy, but from the point of view of medicine and psychology, which describe mental processes as thinking, speech, sensation, consideration (reason), representation (imagination), attention, thought, will, memory; as denoting the meaning of human activity.

Consciousness manifests itself as an argument (proof) of a person's empirical assessment of his knowledge of himself and the external environment, the motive of his behavior and actions.

For example, some Russian psychologists (mainly representatives of the St. Petersburg scientific school) do not include sensation, interest, and emotion in their work as part of mental processes. They are proponents of the study of sensation, desire, and emotion as psychic circumstances.

But analyzing mental processes in a completely different aspect, in contrast to the proponents of a separate study of emotional relations, the Russian scientist V. S. Deryabin in one of his works as early as 1927 emphasized that the study of a new disease – lethargic encephalitis – provided interesting information for the study of brain activity. In this disease, in most cases, the sensual-volitional area is damaged.

As evidenced by practice - psychological research, in most cases patients are not inferior to ordinary people in intelligence, but they do not have a feeling of sorrow, joy, hatred, hope, especially striving for a goal. They look like a living corpse.

The results of research show that sensuality has a central place in human activity, in his aspirations. "Reason without sensuality is nothing. It can be compared to a mechanism from which the spring has been removed. The mind is exclusively a working apparatus."

At present, when describing the initial stage of epidemic encephalitis (Japanese viral encephalitis), such mental changes in patients as impaired attention, thinking delay from mild mental retardation to a deep decrease in thinking abilities are noted. We believe that from this point of view it is expedient to evaluate, systematize, and study the mental state of a person.

An analysis of the concepts of "consciousness" and "thinking" shows that the concept of "consciousness" is the broadest and includes various functions. Thinking, in turn, is an integral part of consciousness. Thus, the understanding of reforming, changing thinking in the process of human management takes into account only mental operations (operations of thinking).

Such important aspects as speech, sensation, reason, attention, thought (imagination), will, and memory are left aside. When involving people in destructive groups, introducing alien ideologies into them, they effectively use the specific features of the brain.

For example, in the process of meditation, the ability to convey feelings in words and the sense of state, critical evaluation of behavior, is reduced. If we analyze this state from the point of view of

neurophysiology, then all kinds of meditation cause brain activity at different levels, gradually moving from the alpha rhythm to the theta and delta rhythms.

A person with closed eyes in a relaxed state is characterized by alpha waves, the frequency of which is 8-12 Hz. In the first stage of sleep, theta waves with a frequency of 7-8 Hz appear in the brain of a person sitting in an enclosed place (for example, in a cell). Delta waves with a strength of 0.5-3 Hz are observed when a person is immersed in a deep sleep. Beta waves of 13–25 Hz are typical for active brain function. Although a person is free from all content, if he constantly concentrates his attention on the right combination of sounds, tirelessly repeats different texts, then certain processes that inhibit the nervous system can reduce the influence of mental activity.

The main thing here is not the content of the text, but the tempo, timbre and number of repetitions. In this case, repeating the same text over and over again is nothing more than verbalized meditation. This gives special importance to what attracts a person's attention and directs him to the right object, to the goal, and at the same time it must be borne in mind that there is something that relaxes the personality and helps to isolate it from the outside world for a while. Electroencephalographic studies show that this state of a person is closer to the state of hypnosis. In addition to the accepted methods of observation of consciousness, various mechanisms that affect the psyche of people are effectively used for certain purposes.

The main mechanism is suggestion. Suggestion is a process that influences the mental state, in which the person, not fully aware of the content of the information offered to him, cannot treat it critically, consciously recognize it.

In spite of this, the person freely accepts the information offered or forcibly suggested. Suggestion can be carried out with the help of words, gestures, artificially created circumstances. A person can be indoctrinated in a waking, sleeping, and hypnotic state.

The effectiveness of this process depends on the suggestible person (on his willpower, attraction, superiority) and on the suggester (largely on the degree of influence). It is very difficult to "correct", correct, or turn into the right channel the consciousness formed or programmed by the influence of the information received as a result of suggestion.

The degree of suggestibility is a factor whose appearance depends on the position and characteristics of the personality. Such personality traits include the following: lack of self-confidence, low level of self-esteem, feelings of inferiority, submissiveness, dependence, cowardice, shyness, credulity, restlessness, anxiety, high emotionality, low level of logical thinking, extrovert (of course, typical extroverts are characterized by sociability, excitement, social adaptation, they have a lot of friends, love fun, entertainment, but they find it difficult to control You can also persuade educated, calm people.

In various emergency situations, especially during a fire, an earthquake, after the death of a loved one, the degree of protection of consciousness decreases. At such a moment, it is easier to perceive certain events, to perceive someone's thought.

Factors associated with a situation conducive to suggestion include such motives as an unexpected impact on a person, the absence of any information about the suggested material or the activity being carried out, limited opportunities for critical assessment of the situation, and the psychophysical state of the subject.

With the development of culture, representatives of humanity who have not received education and knowledge are deprived of the opportunity to use all the benefits of civilization. Any lack in the

educational system, including the lack of education for all segments of the population, is the cause of the mental, intellectual and cultural crisis of the individual, and this, in turn, has a negative impact on information security, and at the same time on the stable development of the state.

From this point of view, the Law "On Education" adopted in our republic in the new context is important because they, in accordance with the principles of organicity and continuity, are aimed at the formation of a new generation of personnel, with a high general and professional culture, creatively and socially active, with developed skills of independent decision-making in socio-political life, capable of promoting and solving promising problems.

Uzbekistan is successfully eliminating various threats to building an information society and taking its rightful place in the world market of high information technologies. Special attention is paid to this task in the educational institutions of our state.

Familiarization of pupils and students with the events, changes taking place in our republic and in the world at information hours and social and humanitarian classes is of great importance in patriotic education, the development of analytical thinking, and ensuring the information and psychological security of the individual.

In general, in the twenty-first century, in the process of globalization, states and societies face an important task of creating an information environment aimed at ensuring human interests, forming and developing personal consciousness. The individual, his consciousness, interests and needs, spirituality, and ideals are the tasks that are the focus of the state's attention in the policy of the information sphere.

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METHODOLOGY OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This scientific article explores the methodology of learning the Russian language in higher education institutions. The study focuses on the effective approaches and strategies employed to facilitate language acquisition, proficiency, and cultural understanding. The article presents a comprehensive approach that includes communicative strategies, proficiency-based instruction, integrated skills development, task-based learning, language immersion, technology-enhanced learning, and cultural integration. The findings emphasize the significance of a multifaceted methodology in equipping students with the necessary language skills and cultural competence for successful language learning in higher education.</p>	<p>Methodology, Russian language, higher education, language acquisition, proficiency-based instruction, integrated skills development, task-based learning, language immersion, technology-enhanced learning, cultural integration.</p>

Introduction

Learning a foreign language is an enriching experience, opening doors to new opportunities and fostering intercultural communication. In the context of higher education, the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language plays a crucial role in equipping students with the necessary language skills and cultural understanding. This article delves into the methodology of learning the Russian language in higher education, highlighting effective strategies and approaches that facilitate language acquisition and proficiency.

1. Communicative Approach:

The communicative approach forms the foundation of teaching Russian in higher education. This methodology prioritizes meaningful communication and interaction, emphasizing the practical use of the language in real-life situations. Students engage in activities such as role-plays, discussions, and collaborative projects, which promote active participation and foster language fluency.

2. Proficiency-Based Instruction:

A proficiency-based approach focuses on developing students' language abilities in the four main areas: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Language proficiency benchmarks, such as the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), guide the curriculum design and

assessment. By targeting specific proficiency levels, instructors can tailor their teaching methods and materials to meet the individual needs of students.

3. Integrated Skills Development:

Integrating the four language skills mentioned above is vital for effective language learning. Instructors design activities and tasks that require students to apply their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills simultaneously. For example, reading authentic texts followed by discussions or writing summaries reinforces comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and oral proficiency.

4. Task-Based Learning:

Task-based learning involves engaging students in authentic, goal-oriented activities that mirror real-life language use. Instructors design tasks that require students to complete specific objectives, such as planning a trip, conducting interviews, or presenting a research project. These tasks encourage students to apply their language knowledge creatively and develop their communicative competence.

5. Language Immersion:

Promoting language immersion environments is essential for fostering language acquisition and cultural understanding. Incorporating authentic materials, such as news articles, literature, films, and music, exposes students to the Russian language in its natural context. Additionally, arranging language exchanges, cultural events, and study abroad opportunities further immerse students in the Russian language and culture.

6. Technology-Enhanced Learning:

Integrating technology into Russian language instruction enhances students' engagement and offers additional learning resources. Online platforms, language learning apps, multimedia materials, and virtual communication tools provide opportunities for self-study, interactive exercises, and virtual language exchanges. Technology also facilitates access to authentic resources, online dictionaries, and language corpora, supporting vocabulary expansion and grammar acquisition.

7. Cultural Integration:

Understanding the cultural context is integral to language learning. Instructors incorporate cultural components into lessons, including discussions about Russian history, traditions, literature, and contemporary society. Exposure to Russian culture through art exhibitions, film screenings, and guest lectures further enriches students' understanding and appreciation of the language.

This teaching model of the distance course is descriptively variable, taking into account the selection characteristics, the number of blocks or sections of the course, their sequence, the purpose of the content, the needs of students, and the software may differ.

Organizational forms and means of teaching distance education, each model has its own methods. The main models of distance education, which have not lost their relevance and, on the contrary, are leading their importance to a new point of development, include:

- integration of full-time and distance education in the network;
- freedom of distance learning course;

- information and education delivery environment (virtual school, department, department, university);

- network education, case technologies and video conferences;

The leading component of the content of teaching the Russian language is not the basics of the subject, but methods of activity - teaching various types of speech activities: speaking, listening, reading and writing. The formation of communication skills (communicative competence) and the creation of knowledge about linguistic concepts and the language system are part of the purpose of teaching the Russian language.

The leading component of the content of teaching the Russian language is not the basics of the subject, but methods of activity - teaching various types of speech activities: speaking, listening, reading and writing. The formation of communication skills (communicative competence) and the creation of knowledge about linguistic concepts and the language system are part of the purpose of teaching the Russian language.

The difference between the subject "Russian language" and "Native language" is that the amount of speech practice is high (in the family, with friends, acquaintances, etc.) and communication in Russian is usually limited to the scope of practical seminars in limited weekly hours at the university. The Russian language is more effective. For teaching and learning, speaking skills should be increased in the volume of speaking practice, should be developed in traditional face-to-face training.

Using the possibilities of information and educational environment services from the Internet, independent work, special selection and systematization of educational material, interactivity, modern pedagogical technologies, attracting native speakers of Russian and organizing communication with them are the main features of distance education.

Current information based on reading texts and watching videos from Russian-language Internet resources, for example, the latest events in the world (sports, cultural, political, etc.), texts by native speakers of Russian (speeches of political figures at conferences, seminars, announcements by presenters), films, videos, electronic materials, libraries and other information allow you to work on enriching the language reserve. Actual forms the information and communication competence of students in the process of receiving information, increases the individual educational trajectory and motivation to learn the Russian language, and requires the development of tasks related to information, project, creative, research activities.

Pedagogical technologies that contribute to more effective learning of the Russian language during a distance course are important to take into account the educational material for the lesson content: discussions, role plays, project activities, etc.

In the modern world of information, it is possible to increase the intensity of speaking in Russian using various digital devices (mobile phones, smartphones, iPhones, tablets, computers, etc.) that are used for human communication. Currently, due to mobile education, which is developing as a concept, institutions are expanding due to the integration of specialized training (elective courses), formal and non-formal education, and the professional development of teachers, trainers, etc. is increasing.

Thus, it should be noted that the introduction of information and communication technologies in language teaching, the formation of communicative competence in learning the Russian language, student-oriented education, individualization and differentiation of educational activities, self-education and self-development of students is a motivating factor for distance education. In front of the science of pedagogy, specially developed online education for modern distance courses is related

to the selection of goals and models, methodical development of existing training manuals, research of new ones, selection of promising technical tools for teaching the Russian language, software opportunities for learning the Russian language in a distance course. and there are tasks such as improving the coordination of competences, teaching staff and network readiness and interaction of all participants of the educational process.

Conclusion:

The methodology of learning the Russian language in higher education is a dynamic process that combines various approaches and strategies. By employing a communicative approach, focusing on proficiency-based instruction, integrating skills development, embracing task-based learning, promoting language immersion, utilizing technology, and emphasizing cultural integration, instructors can create a comprehensive and engaging learning environment. Through these methodologies, students can develop their Russian language skills, cultural competence, and intercultural communication abilities, preparing them for global opportunities and fostering a lifelong appreciation for the Russian language and culture.

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**PECULIARITIES OF CORROSION OF THE EQUIPMENT OF THE
SYSTEM OF PURIFICATION OF HYDROCARBON GASES FROM
ACIDIC COMPONENTS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Today it is difficult to imagine various sectors of the national economy, including the oil and gas and chemical industries, without metal equipment. Equipment used in various industries is constantly exposed to external and internal environments, as a result of which metal equipment loses its original properties. This, in turn, leads to the formation of oxides and hydroxides of the metals used as a result of contact with the external and internal environment, and corrosion of metal equipment is observed. The article analyzes the causes of corrosion damage to metal equipment and equipment of devices for purifying hydrocarbon gases from acidic components.</p>	<p>MDEA (methyldiethanolamine), corrosion, pitting, pitting, solid-uneven, shell-and-tube heat exchanger, piping network</p>

Introduction

Chemical and electrochemical corrosion is one of the most common types of corrosion in gas processing plants. The main problem that arises in cleaning hydrocarbon gases from acidic components is the internal corrosion of heat exchangers, which mainly manifests itself in the form of corrosion cracks under the influence of various aggressive environments[1].

In the research of corrosion decay of devices, the data obtained as a result of continuous inspection of the device, as well as the analysis of the corrosion condition of the installed samples were used as a basis. The material design of devices for purifying hydrocarbon gases from acidic components, possible corrosion damage and their nature are considered using the example of the Gazli gas processing plant. For the first time, all possible types of corrosion degradation and zones of aggressive corrosion by current, by type of corrosive agents and type of corrosive environment were studied at the amine hydrocarbon purification plant[2].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In addition to general corrosion, pressure equipment and plant equipment are susceptible to various types of localized corrosion, including stress corrosion cracking and pitting corrosion (Figure 1).

The K-1 absorber is made of 09G2C steel. The inner surface of the device is covered with a 2-3mm thick corrosion-resistant material, which protects the shell made of 09G2S steel from the aggressive environment. Therefore, despite the fact that the environment in the K-1 absorber is very aggressive (H₂S, CO₂, CH₄, H₂O and MDEA), the corrosion process is relatively slow. However, in layers coated with anti-corrosion material and in welded seams of columns, tanks and condensation-cooling equipment, as a result of corrosion erosion, cracks are formed that spread to the surface of the base metal - carbon steel (the base metal does not “temporarily” weather)[3].

However, when carbon steel with low corrosion resistance is exposed to an aggressive environment, it results in severe corrosion of the base metal.

The separation of natural gas released from the bottom of the K-1 absorber and added to the saturated amine solution is carried out in the C-1 separator. Separator S-1 is made of steel 20YCh.

Figure 1. Calculation of corrosion-aggressive zones of an amine purification plant for hydrocarbon gases and the selection of proposed corrosion-resistant materials.

I-gas for cleaning; II-purified gas; III-hydrocarbon condensate; IV- H₂S; V-methyldiethanolamine solution; VI pairs; VII-water; VIII-inhibitor; IX - complex salt precipitate.

The composition of grade 20YCh steel consists mainly of 97% iron, in addition to aluminum, chromium, carbon, silicon, phosphorus, sulfur, and is used in the manufacture of the following parts:

- shells and flat flanges;
- corrosion-resistant oil and gas pipelines;
- parts and units operating in an aggressive environment containing hydrogen sulfide or carbon dioxide;
- Parts operating in the temperature range from -40°C to +475°C..

In addition to the above, 20YCh steel is used in the production of pipeline fittings and welded tanks for the oil and gas industry.

The saturated amine solution removed from the bottom of separator C-1 is heated by the heat of the reduced amine solution in heat exchanger T-1[4].

The T-1 heat exchanger is made of 09G2S steel. Contains 0.09% carbon, 2% manganese, up to 1% silicon and about 2.5% other additives. The most aggressive corrosive zone of the installation for amine purification of hydrocarbon gases is the T-1 heat exchanger, and the most vulnerable part of the installation to corrosion is the tube bundles. Their service life is 1.5-3 years, depending on the type of aggressive environment and temperature. The saturated amine solution removed from the T-1 heat exchanger is fed into the K-2 desorber at a temperature of 80 °C. This device is made of steel 16GS-3 with a carbon content of 0.12-0.18%, silicon 0.4-0.7%, manganese 0.9-1.2%, containing up to 0.3% nickel, sulfur up to 0.04%, phosphorus up to 0.035%, up to 0.3% chromium, up to 0.008% nitrogen, up to 0.3% copper, up to 0.08% arsenic and 97% iron. The reason for the corrosion process in the upper part of the desorber is explained by the high concentration of H₂S and CO₂. The corrosion process in the lower part of the stripping device, where the nozzles are located, proceeds faster than in the upper part of the device. The reason for this is due to exposure to high temperature and direct current[5].

The inhibitor is introduced into the system perpendicular to the MDEA-saturated pipe entering the T-1 heat exchanger. The high concentration of corrosion inhibitor in the T-1 heat exchanger blocks the corrosion process due to the formation of a complex compound with the metal surface in the corrosion-active zones of the device. The effect of direct current in the tubes of the T-1 heat exchanger causes the formation of a layer of complex compound formed by the metal surface over a certain period of time. In this case, instead of the migrated layer, the corrosion inhibitor constantly added to the medium creates a new layer. Extraction of the remains of the migrated layer containing complex salts is carried out in an O-1 quencher. The remnants of the migrated layer containing complex salts are removed from the tapered lower part of the O-1 clarifier, and the reduced amine solution, cleared of residues, is removed from the upper part.

The recovered amine solution is mixed with a new amine solution in container E-1 and sent to the absorption column. The purified gas is removed from the upper part of the absorber.

SUMMARY

When analyzing the corrosion process occurring in the equipment of a technological system for purifying hydrocarbon gases from acidic components, it was found that the corrosion rate is high in shell-and-tube heat exchangers.

When studying the corrosion process in a shell-and-tube heat exchanger, a certain number of saturated and regenerated MDEA samples were analyzed in the system and heat exchangers that failed due to corrosion. A number of experimental data have been obtained that reveal the reasons for the failure of heat exchangers.

In industry, shell-and-tube heat exchangers are used to transfer heat from one fluid to another. In this case, one of the liquids heats up and the other cools. The structure of the device is shown in Fig. 2. The device mainly consists of a housing and a set of tubes inside it.

Figure 2. The principle of operation of the shell-and-tube heat exchanger

The reasons for the decrease in the capacity of the shell-and-tube heat exchanger are the accumulation of foam, oil, salts and tars on the heat exchange surface of the pipes, as well as metal corrosion.

Performance characteristics of the studied heat exchanger:

- environmental parameters inside the pipes: saturated amine solution, $T = 50...80^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P=490\text{ kPa}$
- pipe size and material: $\varnothing 20 \times 2.0\text{ mm}$, steel 09G2S;
- parameters of the environment between the pipes: the recovered amine solution, $T=118...83^{\circ}\text{C}$; $P=910\text{ kPa}$
- pipe grid -12X18N10T;
- corrosion allowance: 3 mm.

There are three types of corrosion damage in shell-and-tube heat exchangers:

1. Corrosion of the connections between the network of pipes and barriers (Fig. 3)
2. Corrosion-erosive damage of the inner surface of the inlet and outlet nozzles of the heat exchanger
3. At first, uniform, uneven, pitting corrosion along the entire length of the heat exchange pipe (Fig. 4)

The most rapidly corroding part of the shell-and-tube heat exchanger is the tube set. Barriers are installed in order to make the device multi-way in the space between the pipes. Corrosion is observed at the junctions of pipes with barriers and pipe networks.

Figure 3. Corrosion of connections between pipes, piping network and barriers

There is completely uneven, pitted and pitted corrosion on the inner surface of the heat exchange tubes.

Figure 4. Corrosion on the inside of pipes

The intensity of corrosion processes occurring in shell-and-tube heat exchangers depends on the environment, temperature and flow rate.

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CONCEPTS OF SECULARISM AND RELIGIOSITY AND THEIR SOCIAL IMPORTANCE

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
In the article, the concepts of secularism and religiosity in the process of globalization today, its study by many scientists, thinkers and religious scholars since ancient times, the issues of the negative impact of the processes taking place in the world today, especially in the countries of the Middle East, on the mutual balance between religiosity and secularism are highlighted. shows that it has its influence not only in the Middle East, but also in countries with multi-religious and multi-ethnic populations.	Secularism, religiosity, world, Middle East, country, balance, influence.

Introduction

It is known that "the mentality of our people, who played a huge role in the development of the Muslim world, is literally based on virtues such as tolerance, nobility and goodness." Today, the analysis of the concepts of "secularism" and "religion" and their socio-philosophical content is one of the most urgent social-humanitarian problems. It is worth noting that the concepts of secularism and religiosity have long been studied by many scientists, thinkers and religious scholars as mutually exclusive and opposite concepts and aspects, they were understood as two conflicting principles. Religion recognizes the supernatural world as the eternal and real world and teaches that human life in the real world is a means of transition to the eternal world. Secularism, on the other hand, attempts to study and change the material world as an object. "The contradiction between religiosity and secularism will not disappear completely. As the main principles of science and religiosity, secularism and religiosity contradict each other, as in previous times, the struggle in some issues continues openly or secretly in various forms," says researcher A. Boboev. But in our opinion, this opinion of the scientist may be correct in relation to fanaticism or atheism, which are radical manifestations of religiosity and secularism, but not literally. It is no secret that the secular (philosophical, scientific) view of the world served as the basis for some religions' conceptions of existence for centuries, while the information and ideas in some religious books contributed to the development of secular knowledge.

For example, when a society is dominated by religious fanaticism, any secular principles are denied. At the same time, we have learned that Dahrism also considers religion to be an opium for society. In societies based on secular democratic values and principles, any form of tolerance, including religious tolerance, is an important value.

It is worth noting that the concepts of secularism and religiosity have long been studied by many scientists, thinkers and religious scholars as mutually exclusive and opposite concepts and aspects. However, the processes taking place in the world today, especially in the countries of the Middle East, have a negative effect on the balance between religiosity and secularism, which affects not only the Middle East, but also countries with multi-religious and multi-ethnic populations. The ISIS movement based on Islamic radical ideas, which emerged at the beginning of the 21st century, is revealing its heinous plans. It is also targeting Muslim-populated countries, trying to establish a religious state and fill its ranks with citizens who have no faith and are inclined to radical religious ideas. This situation proves that the importance of socio-philosophical analysis of the concepts of secularism and religiosity, their fine boundaries and complementary principles is extremely high. Religiosity and secularism, in a word, secularism is a multifaceted and comprehensive problem. It has political, legal, psychological, sociological, religious, moral and historical aspects and features. In today's environment, any private, special interpretation and analysis cannot claim to be a true scientific conclusion. Only a philosophical approach to the issue can provide a real comprehensive knowledge of its roots, causes, history, evolution, present state and prospects. Otherwise, the analysis of the conflict between secularism and religiosity will remain shallow and one-sided. This cannot be allowed in today's dangerous times. After all, the choice of secular and religious development determines the fate of millions of people, the state and the nation.

From this point of view, finding clear answers to the questions of what religion is, what are the theoretical-scientific foundations of religious teachings that have kept humanity from going out of the scope of moral values for long historical periods, in today's complex times, when a spiritual crisis is observed all over the world and the important work of developing our national democratic statehood is being carried out. It is facing us as one of the most urgent and difficult problems. It is well known to all of us that "our religion will continue to unite our people and serve as an irreplaceable tool for spiritual purification, peace, kindness, tolerance, mutual respect and harmony, regardless of nationality and language." However, the future of the society in such a situation will decline if the individual cannot clearly imagine to the outermost horizons of his spirituality. For this reason, we have been witnessing that the Western countries have been experiencing a spiritual crisis for a long time, and at the same time, they are using religion as an important means of gaining power in the whole world, especially in the countries of the Middle East. This situation puts the issue of deep study of the socio-philosophical nature of religion as an important issue not only for experts, but also for the whole public.

M. Weber (1864-1920), one of the founders of the science of sociology, limited himself to studying only its parameters related to social activity when analyzing the essence of religion. Because, as a sociologist, he was not interested in the fundamental essence of religion, but only in the influence of religious ideas on the life of society, and the tasks performed by it in society. In addition, M. It can be seen that Weber tried to justify the fact that the Protestant stream of Christianity was oriented towards the subjugation of man to the world.

According to French sociologist E. Durkheim, religion is a social institution created by man and serves to satisfy social needs in society. Therefore, he also looked at religion not as an essence, but as a means of maintaining order in society.

W. James (1842-1910), one of the founders of the psychology of religion, which emerged at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, focuses on the connection of religion with

emotions and recognizes the existence of theology, which is the supernatural source of these emotions. Although his understanding of religion is not so deep and concrete, it is much deeper than O. Comte, M. Weber and E. Durkheim. We believe that the reason for this is that the psyche is the object of study of psychology, which may have helped him to understand religion more deeply than sociologists.

But in the East, Z. Munavvarov, a religious scientist, expressed his following conclusion about secularism: "In our opinion, the secular path of development is connected with the fact that it does not fall into the mold of the former ideology, that is, it is neither secular nor religious. From this, it can be concluded that secularism is essentially a spiritual and cultural state located between the two opposite poles, because it does not deny either religiosity or spirituality, it recognizes both of them as objective social phenomena. The logical conclusion from this is that the concept of secularism is based on the principle of pluralism, that is, pluralism.

After all, today's world development trend is globalization, this is mutual convergence. Only worldly development can save humanity from mutual global threats (ecological, nuclear, lack of clean drinking water, food supply, risk of desertification, global warming). "Intensification of the process of globalization not only expands the possibilities of humanity, but also leads to the aggravation of conflicts and the growth of the gap between developed and backward countries. As a result of this, various acts of a transnational character are being committed, which undermine peace and stability." For this reason, it is epistemologically acceptable not to oppose religion to secularism in such a benevolent movement, but to make appropriate use of religion in secular development. It is dangerous to pit religion against secularism, to politicize it, it will divide humanity. A historically tested epistemological solution is democratic secularism. Its perspective lies in the fact that it literally guarantees the right and freedom of belief of a person.

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PROCESSES OF CREATION OF WORKS OF ART BASED ON THE GIJJAK MUSICAL INSTRUMENT IN UZBEK MUSICAL ART

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
This article has deeply studied and scientifically explained the issues of variety and practice of jizhjak instrument performance in Uzbekistan historically and in the series of the school of zhijjak teachers. An important aspect of the research is that the theoretically and methodologically enlightened instructions help to perfectly study the gizjak performance, distinguishing the teachers' school and regional styles during the performance.	Gjijjak, tablature, Martle, Spiccato, Pissicato, Arco, Flageolet, Nola, Molish, skills, performance schools, Andijan, Bukhara, Khorezm

Introduction

Music is the food of the human psyche, it is one of the only factors that can reach the depths of the human soul and control humanity with its power of influence. That's why we all have a musical inclination in our hearts. The place of the music (folklore) in the oral tradition, from the songs told by our mothers in our childhood to our classical music, statuses and oral tradition is incomparable. Uzbek music culture is rich in traditions and genres.

Our national music and art is developing year by year. In particular, in Appendix 1 of the decision of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated February 2, 2022 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" At least one of them is set to teach the skill of playing tunes. According to Appendix 4, preparing audiobooks in the series "Gift from the Creator You Love" by teaching well-known artists in special recording studios based on the best examples of Uzbek and world literature, creating scientific research and scientific-methodical resources in the field of culture and art. state support is also provided. This is a special attention for all artists and musicians. Every melody emanating from our national musical instruments, tanbur, flute, chan, rubob and other instruments, reaches the depths of the human heart. Especially Gjijjak has a special place in our national classical music due to its close to human voice, delicate and painful sound, rich in melodies. Like most Uzbek national songs, the gjijjak instrument is a widely used string-bowed instrument among the peoples of Central Asia, in particular, among the Uzbek, Tajik, Turkmen, as well as Caucasian Azerbaijani and Armenian peoples. The first guitars created were 3-stringed and had a different structure and tuning. In the 20s of the 20th century, the strings of the gjijjak began to be tuned in unison.

By the 30s, as a result of the improvement of Uzbek folk instruments by A.I. Petrosyants, four strings were introduced to the sound of the gijjak. The strings of the frets taken from the violin template were placed at intervals of fifths. Studies of musical literacy have begun based on the European musical notation introduced in the 20th century through improved Uzbek folk instruments. Central Asian peoples had musical tablature before. However, since this tablature was considered the private property of the palaces and khanates, the common people could not master these notes, and playing palace music among the people was prohibited. According to Alisher Navoi's work "Majolis un-nafais", it was a requirement for all court musicians to be able to play the djemjak. In the Middle Ages, artists such as Alijon Gijjaki, Khoja Uzbek Gijjaki were famous. Moreover, maqams were recorded on the basis of this tablature, and it was at the beginning of the 20th century that attempts were made to destroy classical art, saying that maqam art was "an old thing". Now European notation has become a very simple musical language, which is easy to learn for young students and performers. That's why skilled performers and musicologists began to use the European notation in order to illuminate their scientific activities and to convey unforgettable music to the next generation.

Among the national musical instruments of the Uzbek people, the gijjak is important because of its pleasant sound, melody, moaning and harmony with the human voice. Not only our classic Uzbek songs, but also the works of European classical composers can be performed in Gijjak. Interestingly, this song can even imitate the sounds of various birds and animals. In order to turn from an amateur into a professional performer, first of all, diligence, patience, energy, strong will, and musical intelligence are required from the student. Through the teacher, the student develops performance skills (positioning, technique, dynamics, position, appliqué, etc.) along with improving his musical literacy. Therefore, a professional performer should be able to quickly learn any notation, symbols and not lose sight of them during the performance, master the lines of different complexity played on the zizhjak instrument, and thus be able to perform works of various genres. It is necessary to develop skills. At the same time, it is a requirement for a professional musician to harmonize smooth, attractive and impressive sounds with the sound of each finger during the performance of the piece. We will consider these criteria separately on the example of professional representatives of this field. There are musicians who delight their fans with their work even after death, as they did in life. Shuhrat Yoldoshev, an honored artist in Uzbekistan, a lover of the gajik instrument, was one of the skilled musicians who was given the nickname "Uzbek Paganini" with the respect of the people.

Sh. Yoldoshev brought the performance of world classical composers' works on folk instruments to a heroic level. His performance skills captivated not only Uzbek, but also foreign listeners. Sh. Yoldoshev almost knew by heart the works edited by the world-famous violinists: J. Heifetz, L. Kogan, D. Oistrakh, A. Yampolsky, in which position they played the same piece, (position of fingers on the sheet), which fingers, (bo 'fingers on the game are correctly placed), what strokes (various movements of the bow on the string) and did not confuse the options. Of course, with such high achievements, one should not forget Obid Khalmuhamedov, one of the founders of the professional performance of the Gijak school in Uzbekistan, his teacher, associate professor of the department of performance of folk instruments. Shuhrat Yoldoshev's work was positively influenced by his hard work, knowledge, teaching style, ability to work with students.

Below are the conditions that are required to be regularly performed in order to coordinate the training and practical knowledge of professional performing teachers, the basic skills of becoming a skilled performer, the improvement of performing skills on the zizhjak instrument, and the formation of a complex of theoretical and practical activities. let's go:

- to know all the specific features of the sound of the zizhjak and to distinguish the sound timbres of their families;

- to be able to perform samples of technical, polyphonic and composers' works of various genres and complexity with artistic and technical perfection, understanding of the content;

- being able to be an accompanist solo and in an ensemble, to be able to read a musical piece from sheet music;

- describing the melody;

- to have an understanding of folk music heritage;

- knowledge of musical terms;

- to know the means of expression of music;

- to be able to distinguish performance types from performance sounds;

- knowing music genres and being able to distinguish them from the style of performance;

- knowledge of specific performance styles and musical instruments in each local style;

- Ability to perform folk tunes of Ferghana-Tashkent, Samarkand-Bukhara, Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya, Khorezm styles;

- listening to and distinguishing the local styles of popular and professional music genres of the Uzbek people in the practice of national music;

- To be able to perform examples of classical music of world nations and works of composers;

Master Bakhtiyor Yaminov was very responsible in these matters and loved his work. Bakhtiyor Yaminov paid special attention to the performance technique and appliqué in the gizjak soz. The word "Applikatura" comes from the German "aplikatur" and the Latin "applico" means to put, press. The methods of correct choice of appliqué make the composer comfortable, on the one hand, in mastering and performing technically difficult parts of the piece, and on the other hand, without moving from string to string of the right hand, or without excessive effort. provides a free exit from the situation.

In Murad Toshmammedov's work "Mastering traditional performance in G'ijjak", he explained about the expression of decorations by means of musical notes. These marks are played based on the playing style and position of the guitar, quite different from the mordent used on the piano. A future master musician who is taking lessons in Gjizhak soz should be able to use the following complex lines in the performance process: For example, Nola - supposedly vibrato. It is done by gently and quickly moving the finger, pressing the curtain in the sound of Gijjak. The traditions of the teacher and student also play an important role in the professional formation of Gjijjak sound in Uzbekistan. Each region has its own school performance style. The unique styles of Gjijjak performance are manifested mainly through the traditional schools of Andijan, Bukhara and Khorezm.

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**ON THE DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF MODERN SOCIETY AND
EDUCATION**

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ABSTRACT

The education of the 21st century is connected with globalization, digitalization, rapid economic development and changes in their processes, requiring many new highly qualified professional personnel.

KEYWORDS

Introduction

In this regard, new trends in education are observed in the world:

- informatization (information technologies);
- subject-oriented (personal activity);
- integration (projects);
- forecasts (future orientation);
- social partnership ("open school") involving real experts of various fields in the educational process;
- gamification in education, game technologies;
- use of innovative technologies;
- building individual educational directions.

The formation of the information society - is a new type of society.

devices - turned information into the main economic resource and showed the great importance of informatization and information processes, which are of fundamental importance at all levels of the educational process.

Informatization is the implementation of a set of measures to ensure full and timely use of knowledge by society in all types of human activity. At the same time, the use of information and information technologies in any field of human activity becomes the main factor of the development of society.

The most important direction of public information is educational information. It includes the development of information technologies for the optimization of educational processes and the intellectualization of activities. The main goals of education informatization: increase the effectiveness of education, formation of information space and development of information culture.

Improving the efficiency of education implies that informatization of education should lead to more effective implementation of the social education order, that is, to increase the efficiency of formation of competitive specialists in the labor market; increase the effectiveness of forming citizens of society with a basic value system. The construction of information space means that the informatization of education focuses on the flexibility and convenience of educational services in relation to changes in

the modern social educational order. The development of information culture should ensure the development of general skills in the use of information technologies to increase operational efficiency. The main goals of educational informatization are to implement the social order of modern society - to prepare for social, daily and professional activities in the post-industrial society, to develop the personality of the student, to activate, to increase efficiency and quality. about the educational process. In the educational process of modern informatization trends, there are a number of advantages over traditional teaching methods:

- 1) formation of continuous education system;
- 2) creation of a single informational educational space;
- 3) introduction of new means and methods of teaching, focusing on information technologies;
- 4) harmonization of informatization and traditional educational methods and tools;
- 5) creation of an advanced education system.

Informatization of education should ensure formation of new competencies, knowledge and skills, methods of activity necessary for education in all subjects of the educational process in a new information environment, including in conditions of widespread use of modern information technologies. education, as well as a new holistic worldview and informational worldview.

Modern culture and social practice have a subject-oriented character, which is ontologically predetermined by the fundamental idea that the determinism of the external world is dependent on the capabilities of the subject (inseparability) for the worldview of the post-industrial society. not to exclude the subject from the object, the subjective from the objective). The importance of subjectivity lies in the characteristics of modern reality:

- the emergence of the influence of knowledge as a new method of productivity, which has become the main source of productivity in modern reality; the impact of knowledge on knowledge is a subjectively determined process;
- branches of modern society; network structure is subjective;
- innovativeness of modern society development; innovation - subjective definition of innovative activity;

A number of features of modern reality prove the high importance of subjectivity in modern culture and social practice, which predetermines the subject orientation of innovative changes in the field of education and, first of all, in the pedagogical space. Pedagogical space that meets the requirements of modern reality should predetermine the subjective activity of the student. Subjective activity refers to the conditionality of the actions performed by the subject and the result of his actions, the specific characteristics of his internal state. Pedagogical space should represent a form of territorial-procedural unit of pedagogical interaction that provides the possibility of subjective activity.

The subject-orientedness of the pedagogical space and the subject content allow changing the semantic-axiological direction of the educational process from the object (what is learned) to the subject (who knows), which corresponds to the subject-oriented feature. In particular, modern education and modern reality in general, and thus creates the necessary conditions for the formation of skills, abilities and personal qualities that have a corresponding professional demand.

In the context of subject orientation, the necessary conditions for integration into the educational process are created. Despite the fact that there is no single definition of the concept of "integration" in education, integration is often understood as a developmental process, the result of which is the achievement of unity and integrity within a system based on the interdependence of individual

elements. The basis of creating an educational system in the modern world is the integration of education. Integration in education makes it possible to create a holistic view of the world, helps to develop creative potential and eliminates patchiness in mastering the knowledge system. The essence of the integration process is to qualitatively and effectively change every element of the educational system. As changes are made within the elements, their interconnection occurs.

Integration in the educational process lies in the comprehensive nature of the goals of educational activity and the integrity of achieving the planned results; synthesis of pedagogical tools; interdependence of different types of activities, strengthening of knowledge, skills and qualifications; in educational relations; in the flexibility and convenience of educational organization; in the introduction of new integrative courses, subjects, etc.; in combining pedagogical tools into complexes; in the interaction of all subjects of the process, educational institutions and society. Based on the above, integration can be divided into internal and external types. Internal integration directly describes the educational process in the educational institution, and external integration describes the interaction of the institution with society and other structures.

Today, education faces a fundamentally new task - the task of forming a comprehensive education of future specialists in order to increase their competitiveness in the labor market. The solution to this problem is possible by creating integrated general professional knowledge and intellectual abilities of the future specialist focused on professional mobility. Professional mobility is a movement that directs a specialist to the future, with or without changing the social position of a person or a professional group in the socio-professional structure of society.

Forecasts (future orientation) are considered in the context of macroeconomic development as a trend of modern education. Orientation to the future is becoming a strategic direction for the development of education, its trends are determined by strict market requirements for the quality of educational activities and labor productivity. There is a need for forecasting and perspectives, so the following areas of forecasting are highlighted:

- training of a professional mobile specialist focused on the application of innovative processes;
- classification of educational services based on humanization, activation and greening;
- multi-level oriented to the international labor market.

At this time, the need for forecasting is great, because it is necessary justify the choice of educational policy, which determines the prospects of educational development, the impact of the environment on the parameters of educational activity, the relevance of developing a new forecasting system.

The result of orientation to the future, in particular, is the prospective solution of educational problems in general and professional education, the creation of an innovative educational system, and the creation of programs for the development of educational sciences.

Forecasting in education is aimed at studying development prospects, determining improvement directions, long-term prospects, expecting results, ensuring continuity of activity and development. Focusing on the future allows you to quickly respond to changes, consider development perspectives, adapt, reflect requirements and coordinate forecast information.

Social partnership and the involvement of real specialists of various fields in the educational process ("open school") are firmly integrated into the educational system. Social partnership in any sphere of human life is based on voluntary and mutually beneficial cooperation aimed at achieving certain common social goals. Social partnership in the field of education, based on the same direction -

voluntary mutually beneficial cooperation to solve common problems, is based on similar principles of mutual cooperation between parties, using only what is sufficient to achieve the goals: equality, mutual respect, interest in efficiency, freedom to discuss problems, voluntary commitment, responsibility.

The composition of partners in the field of education is formed depending on the level of the educational institution - for example, vocational education institution - state bodies - employers - employment services. Educational institutions are most susceptible to changes in the labor market, which leads to the need for continuous self-improvement. Information on changes is based on forecast data on the demand for certain professions and long-term plans for the development of regions; applications from employers; current information of the employment service; requirements of students for certain professions.

The optimal relationship between the state of the labor market and the employment opportunities for newly trained specialists is determined by a timely and comprehensive analysis of the identified trends. The lack of such an analysis can create a situation where graduates are not in demand and unfilled vacancies in other specialties may appear in the labor market when focusing only on students' requests for future professions. That is why the role of the state in creating and managing a flexible education system is of particular importance.

Social partnership in the field of education is carried out in accordance with special rules that allow it to attract a sufficiently wide range of people. As the degree of emergence of cooperation increases, the share of participation of third parties in it increases. One of these organizations was the "open school".

Open education has so far been implemented in the "School Without Walls" experiment. His idea lies in the parallelism of education in the ordinary school and beyond. School buildings, as well as the territory of firms, enterprises, etc., are used for lessons. Students can be in classrooms, science laboratories, museums, theaters, etc., where they perform specific educational tasks. As a result, the city becomes a center of knowledge. According to the initiators of "School without Walls", such an organization brings diversity to the student's life and increases interest in learning.

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THE ROLE OF ORAL SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN THE LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Oral language development involves more than learning words. It also entails the development of speech skills that enable children to express themselves clearly and effectively. Verbal expression gives way to creative communication, which also boosts self-esteem. Communication is the act of interacting and exchanging ideas with other people. Basically, when communicating, people send and receive messages. There are two primary forms of communication: verbal and nonverbal. With verbal communication, people express their thoughts, ideas, and feelings through spoken or written language. Nonverbal communication uses other methods, such as body language including facial expressions, gestures, and other body movements. We are going to discuss both of these forms of communication and give verbal and nonverbal communication examples to help you understand them better so as to improve your information transfer.</p>	<p>Non verbal, express, communication, understand</p>

Introduction

Supporting young children’s language and literacy development has long been considered a practice that yields strong readers and writers later in life. The results of the National Early Literacy Panel’s (NELP) six years of scientific research synthesis supports the practice and its role in language development among children ages zero to five.

The NELP was brought together in 2002 to compile research that would contribute to educational policy and practice decisions that impact early literacy development. It was also charged with determining how teachers and families could support young children’s language and literacy development. Outcomes found in the panel’s report (2008) would be used in the creation of literacy-specific materials for parents, teachers, and staff development for early childhood educators and family-literacy practitioners. Through its work, the NELP uncovered a set of abilities such as alphabet knowledge, oral language, or phonological awareness present in the preschool years that provides the basis for later reading success.

It also found that measures of complex and discourse- level skills are particularly strong predictors of reading success – a finding that is consistent with the fact that language is a complex, multidimensional system that supports decoding and comprehension as children learn to read. In our book *Early Childhood Literacy: The National Early Literacy Panel and Beyond*, we explore the NELP report, as well as newer research findings and the effectiveness of specific approaches to teaching early oral language development to establish a solid foundation for later reading comprehension.

Below we expand on concepts to help educators understand how oral language relates to reading comprehension, word reading, and language development; where Common Core State Standards factor into the equation; and what teachers can do to foster literacy development.

Laying Down the Building Blocks

Through its research, the NELP discovered that the more complex aspects of oral language, including syntax or grammar, complex measures of vocabulary (such as those in which children actually define or explain word meanings), and listening comprehension were clearly related to later reading comprehension, but that simpler measures of oral language (e.g., the widely used Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test) had very limited associations with reading comprehension.

Put simply, readers must translate print to language and then, much as in listening, they must interpret the meaning of that language. Numerous studies support this approach by showing that word reading and language comprehension are relatively independent skills, but that each contributes significantly to reading comprehension. Simple measures of vocabulary in which children simply point to the picture of a word or name a picture are not strongly connected with later reading comprehension. Nevertheless, many studies have shown that vocabulary plays an important role in fostering reading development in the years before and during formal reading instruction.

The role of vocabulary is likely two-fold. The words, and the concepts that they represent, are obviously of functional importance in comprehension, and vocabulary might also support decoding or the translation of text into language. The NELP established phonological awareness as a key contributor to children's ability to learn to read. Of course, phonological representations are part of the linguistic system and the ability to gain access to these representations may in part be a by-product of early vocabulary development (Metsala & Walley, 1998). Reading comprehension depends on language abilities that have been developing since birth. Basic vocabulary and grammar are clearly essential to comprehension because each enables understanding of words and their interrelationships in and across individual sentences in a text (Kintsch & Kintsch, 2005).

However, children who comprehend well go beyond word and sentence comprehension to construct a representation of the situation or state of affairs described by the text. In some theories, this is referred to as a "mental model" (Kintsch & Kintsch, 2005) and it involves organizing a text's multiple ideas into an integrated whole, using both information from the text and the reader's own world knowledge. To do this, successful comprehenders draw upon a set of higherlevel cognitive and linguistic skills, including inferencing, monitoring comprehension, and using text structure knowledge. Take the following story for example: "Johnny carried a jug of water. He tripped on a step. Mom grabbed the mop."

The literal representation of the individual words and sentences does not enable the reader to integrate their meanings and construct a mental model. Successful comprehenders understand narrative structure and couple it with their knowledge to infer that Johnny spilled the water. They then understand why Mom grabbed a mop.

They also monitor their comprehension of stories-either written or spoken-and realize the need to make an inference (that Johnny spilled the water) to make sense of Mom's response. High-level language skills used to create mental models of text are not exclusive to reading. In fact, children begin developing these language skills well before formal reading instruction in a range of language comprehension situations. For example, young children rely on knowledge of narrative structure to

do things like follow a set of instructions, share their daily activities around the dinner table, or understand spoken stories, cartoons, and movies.

Assessing Early-Stage Development

The skills needed for reading comprehension come into play as students progress. In the early grades, for example, reading comprehension depends heavily on emerging word-reading skills. As children accomplish the ability to automatically and fluently read printed words, language comprehension begins to contribute more to individual differences in reading comprehension. Most children who score poorly on reading comprehension tests have difficulty decoding words and understanding language.

Those with poor word-reading abilities (i.e., poor decoders) lag behind their typically developing peers on reading comprehension measures in the early grades, even if they have good language development. However, those with poor language comprehension, in spite of relatively proficient word-reading ability, usually do not lag behind their typically developing peers on reading comprehension tests until they have had one or two years of reading instruction (Catts et al., 2005). It's important to point out that what appears to be a decline in reading comprehension for poor comprehenders is not the result of declining language skills. In fact, these students' language skills were already poor compared with their typically developing peers at the onset of schooling.

People use verbal communication to express themselves in many ways during discussions, speeches, and everyday conversations. Just how effective this style of communication is can vary. It will depend on the receiver's listening skills, as well as a number of verbal communication skills, such as the volume of your voice, the tone you use, the clarity of your speech, and the caliber of the words you use. You'll probably get some idea of how effective your communication is through the feedback you receive.

You can help improve the effectiveness of your communication by considering your target audience and how you can adjust your message so they will pay attention to you and understand you. With verbal communication, you have a lot of control over adapting your message if you feel it is not effective.

In order to do this, you should first ensure that you have expressed your intended message. It's possible for the people to whom you are trying to communicate to misunderstand your words or the intention behind those words.

Whether or not your communication is effective depends on the listener as well as yourself, and you can't control the listener—but you can try to make your message as clear as possible. This can be particularly helpful if the person you are speaking to is not an active listener. To do this, you also need to consider nonverbal communication.

Nonverbal communication involves communicating without using words. Instead, individuals use nonverbal behaviors to communicate. These types of nonverbal communication can emphasize spoken words, or contradict them.

The three main aspects of nonverbal communication are tone of voice, body language, and eye contact, each of which has an impact on how people receive your message.

- **Tone of Voice:** The volume, pitch, and pace of your voice display your feelings. It can help other people determine whether you're upset, confident, angry, etc.
- **Body Language:** Body language is probably the clearest type of nonverbal communication. It can tell a person a lot about how you feel. If someone sees that your arms are folded while

speaking to you, they will likely feel you are not very receptive to what they have to say, whereas if you face the speaker with your arms at your sides, you will appear more interested.

- Eye Contact: Making eye contact lets a speaker know you are interested in their message. It can also help you stay engaged in the conversation and better understand the speaker.

Do these verbal and nonverbal communication examples make sense to you?

Nonverbal communication skills are a crucial part of articulating your message. People often rely primarily on nonverbal cues to derive the meaning of the message. This makes it vital that you work on improving your nonverbal communication skills.

Conclusion

Communication skills are critical in all aspects of life, whether verbal, nonverbal, or written communication. Improving your communication skills requires understanding the differences between verbal and nonverbal communication. Simply understanding communication cues, such as maintaining eye contact and using body language that shows you are interested in what the speaker has to say, can go a long way toward achieving effective communication.

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**HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SECONDARY RESIDENTIAL
HOUSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CITIES OF UZBEKISTAN**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>The history of the development of medium-sized residential houses in the construction of cities in Uzbekistan is a fascinating journey that reflects the evolving urban landscape of the country. Over the years, the architectural style and construction methods have been influenced by various factors, including culture, technology, and social changes. This article aims to shed light on this historical process and provide insights into the evolution of medium-sized residential houses in Uzbekistan.</p>	

Introduction

Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage and diverse historical influences have shaped its architectural development. The country is located in Central Asia and has been a crossroads of civilizations throughout history. As a result, its architectural styles have been influenced by Persian, Arab, Turkish, Russian, and Mongol cultures, among others. These influences can be observed in the design elements and construction techniques of medium-sized residential houses.

The inception of medium-sized residential houses in Uzbekistan can be traced back to ancient times. The ancient city of Samarkand, known for its magnificent architecture, played a vital role in shaping the urban landscape. Some of the earliest medium-sized residential houses were made of clay and had flat roofs, reflecting the simplicity of architectural styles at that time.

During the Islamic Golden Age, which occurred in the 8th to 14th centuries, Uzbekistan experienced a boom in architectural development. The emergence of cities like Bukhara and Khiva saw the construction of medium-sized residential houses with more intricate designs. These houses were characterized by decorative motifs, vaulted ceilings, and intricately carved wooden elements. The use of locally sourced materials, such as adobe and clay bricks, was prevalent during this period.

The arrival of the Russian Empire in the 19th century brought about significant changes in the architectural landscape of Uzbekistan. The Russian influence led to the introduction of new construction techniques and materials, including the use of fired bricks and cement. This period saw the construction of medium-sized residential houses with more Westernized designs, featuring larger windows, balconies, and multiple stories.

However, it was during the Soviet era that the development of medium-sized residential houses reached its peak. The Soviet government implemented massive urbanization programs, resulting in

the construction of numerous apartment blocks. These medium-sized residential houses were mainly constructed using precast concrete panels and were often part of larger housing complexes.

In recent years, with the newfound independence of Uzbekistan, there has been a renewed appreciation for traditional architectural styles. The government has implemented policies to preserve and restore historical buildings, ensuring their integration into contemporary cityscapes. This shift has seen a renaissance in the construction of medium-sized residential houses that blend modern amenities with traditional design elements.

Today, medium-sized residential houses in Uzbekistan reflect a fusion of historical influences and modern architecture. They typically exhibit features such as terraces, courtyards, and distinctive ornamental facades. Contemporary construction methods, such as reinforced concrete, are often used to enhance durability and structural integrity.

As Uzbekistan continues to experience rapid urbanization and economic growth, the development of medium-sized residential houses will undoubtedly remain an essential aspect of urban planning. The country's rich architectural heritage will continue to shape the construction of sustainable and aesthetically pleasing homes, balancing modern needs with traditional design elements.

In conclusion, the history of medium-sized residential houses in Uzbekistan highlights the rich tapestry of architectural styles and influences that have shaped the country's urban landscape. From the simple clay houses of ancient times to the grandiose designs during the Islamic Golden Age, the evolution of these houses reflects the changing cultural, technological, and social dynamics. Today, Uzbekistan embraces its historical heritage and combines it with modern construction practices to create homes that are both functional and visually appealing.

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**FORMS AND METHODS OF THE COUNTRY STUDY MATERIALS'
USED AT THE ENGLISH LESSONS**

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ABSTRACT

Various forms and methods of work with the country study material at the English lessons are considered in this article. In the opinion of this article author, when conducting English lessons, the following should be used: texts oriented to country studies through language, authentic letters, and proverbs, idiomatic expressions. The above listed forms of introducing the materials on country study and country studies through language have a beneficial effect on the foreign culture understanding by students and facilitate in their involvement in dialogue between cultures and develop the general learning skills of students.

KEYWORDS

Country study, country study through language, competence in cultural linguistics, authentic letters, geographic letters and calendars, proverbs, idiomatic expressions, communicative, information

Introduction

The modern technique of training in foreign languages proclaimed in quality defining personal and activity orientation contents and process of training in a foreign language. Such orientation assumes search and creation of optimal conditions for linguistic cognitive activity of the personality.

Result such activity the linguoculturological competence in studied is foreign language. Competence – set of knowledge, abilities, formed in the course of training in a foreign language (1, page 28).

Training in communicative behavior has to be carried out to a dress with training in actually language skills of foreign language skills in receptive and productive aspects. Communicative and sociocultural development of pupils is carried out due to the correct realization language learning through study of a country's approach at lessons. Such approach provides assimilation of language in close connection with the culture of the countries of the learned language, which includes informative data on history, literature, country archeology, her customs, traditions, household features.

The main objective of training in a foreign language consists in development the identity of the pupil capable and the person interested to participate in cross-cultural communications.

Proceeding from goals in contents to training to regional geography at lessons of English the following joins components: language learning through study of a country's including knowledge, understanding realities (the words designating objects of national culture) and their ability to use and also background lexicon, phraseological units, proverbs as source of national cultural information; knowledge of regional geographic subjects, connected with the general knowledge of the country; text material which is contained in textbooks and a training material on regional geography it is also general an educational component. (1, 87)

The teacher's task according to realities of time consists in providing conditions for familiarizing of pupils with foreign-language culture and them to preparation for participation in transfer of spiritual wealth of the people of the country target language, in particular in enrichment of the subjects offered for studying on regional geography that everything worked for cross-cultural communication.

Within education there is only a training type out of language environment. In the conditions of lack of the real language environment, compressed framework of a lesson and lack of regional geographic material the teacher faces with objective difficulties in the solution of a difficult task of formation versatile sociocultural competence of pupils, therefore presence in this or that type of components of attributes of the language environment of the country target language at lessons it is necessary. On efficiency of formation sociocultural competence, the personality has significant effect teachers, his style, experience and ability to build the relations with a class in time occupations and after hours.

Work with language learning through study of a country's texts

As we already spoke, the quality of training in many respects depends on ability teachers to pick up language learning through study of a country's and regional geographic material. Texts of regional geographic character figure prominently in process training in a foreign language. The contents of such texts have to be significant for pupils to have for them novelty.

Textbooks of English contain material of regional geographic character which allows to provide realization of sociocultural component, offering information on Great Britain and English-speaking the countries, developing abilities of pupils to represent the country in comparison with other countries. Students learn to build speech and nonverbal behavior with accounting of features of culture of a target language when understanding uniform systems of ethnic values of the people. The training material is represented and it is fulfilled in the tasks modulating situations of real daily applications of language. According to us, regional geographic material in textbooks not there is enough for fuller understanding of history, culture, life, etc. the studied country. Therefore, it is necessary to enter additional texts. The picked-up relevant and interesting materials about life in these countries, informative texts, photos and illustrations do them fine addition to traditional school textbooks on the one hand. With another – the system of additional texts is designed to expand and deepen the language learning through study of a country's information obtained by students at lessons English. (2, 300 p)

Forms of control can be in the form of question-answer work on contents of the text, stay in the text of offers which can serve as confirmation of illustrations, short retelling of the text, in the form of any conversation of the teacher and the pupil in the read text, justifications by the pupil of the point of view. Sometimes depending on problems of a lesson it is possible to combine traditional and nonconventional forms of control. As a rule, at the end of texts tasks of lexical and grammatical character are given, for example, when studying the text about the royal family the training in oral

speech of phrases with use of possessive case, in others – definition in texts of the English equivalents, drawing up questions with use of new lexical units, etc. is supposed. (2, 355 p)

Work with authentic letters

In work with letters the following problems are solved:

- to teach it is correct to make out the letter in English, it is correct to sign an envelope.
- to teach to understand and to correctly comprehend contents of texts.
- to teach to express the opinion on the basis of information which is contained in the text, to conduct a conversation, to argue the point of view.
- to learn to apply the gained knowledge in writing in situations, close to real. Authentic letters differ from usual texts the simple daily language. At the same time to students interestingly literally all: from the image on marks, envelopes and cards, finishing with handwriting, not to mention contents. The authenticity of correspondence is a powerful tool of motivation of students in their aspiration to seize skills of writing of letters.

Different types of letters are studied: the letter gratitude, the letter invitation, the letter of apology, the cover letter to a parcel, the letter - request for health, etc. The structure of the personal and business letter is without fail studied, examples of introductory phrases, greetings (address), final phrases are learned by heart, the approximate scheme of the sequence of statement of events in the main part of the letter speaks. Though correspondence takes the insignificant place in the maintenance of a training material, but according to us its studying is capable to recover, diversify traditional lessons of English and to maintain the interest of students to its studying.

Work with nonverbal forms, proverbs, idiomatic expressions

Materials of similar orientation not only give a deep idea of language and the culture of the countries of a target language, but also that is more significant, "Do English to the most English". It is no secret that easy even to determine by the used English lexicon in the interlocutor Uzbek the speaking representative. When studying the above-stated material there is the greatest possible approach to a target language, "introduction" in a mentality of British. The fact that we hear, not always what we are told. There is a verbal loss of information therefore nonverbal means of communication which sometimes tell more are so important, than it is possible to put into words (tone, shout, a timbre), including a sign language.

We will give some examples.

Standing with hands on hips - Readiness, aggression

Sitting, legs apart - Open, relaxed

Arms crossed on chest - Defensiveness

Rubbing the eye - Doubt, disbelief

Stroking chin - Trying to make a decision

Some English, Uzbek and Russian proverbs have a general meaning and can literally be translated from one language on another. For example, "There is no smoke without fire" has the Uzbek and Russian equivalent "Smoke without fire doesn't happen".

In other cases, the value of one proverb can be translated different in the ways: "Once bitten, twice shy" can be expressed in Uzbek and Russian "Having burned on milk, you will blow on water" or "Frightened crow of a bush is afraid". (A burnt child dreads the fire, once bitten twice shy)

The cognitive interest of students is attracted by studying of value of some and the same words having different value in British, American and Australian English. For example, Barbie-barbecue, roo-kangaroo, mozzie-mosquito, chook-chicken, tellie-TV.

As it was specified, above, approach to the culture of the country studied language is impossible without acquaintance with its folklore, proverbs, etc. that is an obligatory component of language learning through study of a country's material.

It would be desirable that when studying English to this aspect it was given bigger value.

Work with authentic announcements, newspapers, magazines, cards, household objects, attributes

Presently it is possible to receive enough above-stated objects which can be used as when carrying out lessons of a subject when studying the corresponding subject now, and on class hours, and when carrying out week of English.

All listed forms of introduction of materials of regional geographic contents promote transfer of English-speaking culture to school students, promote their involvement in dialogue of cultures, develop their creative and informative abilities, raise and maintain interest in a learning of foreign language.

In the course of training it is necessary to consider possibilities of students and degree of complexity of a training material. Lessons are under construction so that the student showed the intellectual opportunities, felt interest in improvement of the individual abilities. Training material it is offered on model "passed + given + new".

The analysis of the interesting problems of students of an average and senior link shows that as the main there are four blocks of educational subjects when studying regional geographic material: youth problems; fashion, leisure; education; about and the world around.

Studying of these subjects is directly connected with a content of the lesson which includes the following components:

1. Language learning through study of a country's component:

a) Knowledge, understanding of realities (the words designating objects of the national cultures) and ability to use them and also background lexicon (antonym, homonyms); phrase logical units, proverbs, aphorisms and as source of national and cultural information. As a rule, it is acquaintance lessons with culture on the basis of texts about holidays, symbols, traditions.

b) Knowledge of the regional geographic subjects connected with the general knowledge of England and its stories (English humour, history and traditions of the royal family, famous King Arthur, etc.). One of types of work on the history of England there can be an evening of the English poetry, or performances according to works Mark Twain, Shakespeare.

2. General and educational component:

a) The educational and organizational abilities connected with formation at learning students of ability to work in various modes (the student-teacher; student-student; students-students; group students and others), objectively and it is correct to estimate the activity and activity of the companions. It lessons presentations, projects when the group of students of 3-5 people chooses subject, prepares the message, and then protects it before a class. Obligatory condition is - to ask questions about a subject, to estimate in English.

b) The educational and intellectual abilities connected with formation of ability to compare, compare, analyze, systematize and to generalize the studied material. In this plan works are interesting students on such subjects as "Subculture", "Policy", "Generation gap" in the form of the presentations, reports, an interview, meetings.

c) The educational and communicative abilities which are shown in the cultures of communication i.e. in abilities to listen and hear the partner in communication, to prove the point of view. Lesson forms various: lesson travel, lesson teleconference, lesson magazine, lesson excursion, lesson quiz, etc.

All above-mentioned forms of introduction of materials regional geographic and language learning through study of a country's contents promote transfer to students foreign-language culture, promote their involvement in dialogue of cultures, develop it is general educational abilities of students, their creative and informative abilities, increase interest in a learning of foreign language in general.

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**DYNAMICS AND PROSPECTS OF INCREASING THE INFLUENCE
OF OPENNESS TO EXPERIENCE IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION
SYSTEM**

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ABSTRACT

In the article, in the twenty-first century - the age of intelligence, teachers and their learning of scientific research in education, the master of their profession, Pedagogical skills, Spiritual and ideological maturity, loyalty to their profession, considering it as the meaning of their lives, patriotism, national pride, inclination to science, knowledge, organization , open relations such as politeness, communicativeness, and the ability to attract students to themselves, arouse their enthusiasm, inculcate the idea of national modernity, and inspire them to national-educational tasks.

KEYWORDS

Education, research, pedagogical skills, spirituality, ideological maturity, profession, patriotism, national pride, inclination to science, knowledge, organization, politeness, communicativeness, openness, education.

Introduction

In fact, our observations and analyzes today show that today the school itself should be a center of skill improvement. Every school should have a high level of access to lessons, observation, analysis, wide introduction of new innovative methods, exchange of experience, public supervision, study and popularization of advanced pedagogical practices, in a word, life in the school should be "boiling". A teacher's learning of scientific research is an important factor in his work on himself. Of course, if he writes articles for periodicals, participates in projects, grants, lectures at scientific conferences, his skills will undoubtedly increase. Previously, the teacher was involved in forced labor and did not have time to work on himself. Now that is over, there is time and opportunity to work independently. Teachers who understand this correctly are learning to work on themselves. This situation should be fully supported.

Today's pedagogue, along with being a master of his profession, should be an example to others with his lifestyle. The most influential factor in education is a personal example, an example. The inspirational words of the head of our state, "Teachers and trainers are role models for us, the embodiment of high human qualities", confirm that the teacher is literally a model of our spirituality. Today, due to their care for teachers and coaches, who are the owners of honorable professions in Uzbekistan, their position and respect is increasing today. Thanks to the care provided, the teacher's love and devotion to his profession increased, inspiring him to work even more on himself.

It is necessary for today's teacher to deeply understand the historical roots of our spiritual past and to be able to instill it in the minds of young students. For example, he told the students that after the death of our great master grandfather Amir Temur, the feudal disunity in our country escalated, and later three khanates appeared in the country, and due to mutual disagreements between them, kindness increased to a certain extent, and Tsarist Russia took advantage of this and invaded our country, and thus national and spiritual he must convince us that it is impossible to make historical mistakes that have damaged our values. It is the teacher's duty to explain to our people, to the young generation, that the historical wisdom "If you don't have your own idea, a foreign idea will rule your country" was proven during the period of more than seventy years of communist tyranny.

The communist idea did not originate in our country. There was no inclination towards it in our people. This idea was brought here from Europe, in other words "exported". It is necessary to properly explain to our youth that this artificially introduced false idea led to the split of nationality, the impoverishment of our culture and spirituality, the introduction of evil ideas, and the violation of our values. At the same time, having a national ideology of any independent state, in other words, the main task of the teacher should be to deeply instill in the people, especially the young generation, that there is no future for the society and the state. This should be done by all teachers, not only those who teach social and humanities. The idea of "from national recovery to national rise" should be conveyed to the minds of every citizen.

Today's teacher is completely different from yesterday's teacher. Now the responsibility of teaching is higher and more honorable than ever. This responsibility means developing a person of the 21st century. Considering that the twenty-first century is recognized as the age of intelligence, we realize how important the responsibility of the teacher is. Teaching our children to think freely, forming an independent worldview in them is the content and essence of a teacher's activity.

The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoev, very aptly quoted from the legacy of our great thinker Yusuf Khos Hajib, "In the world, two different people are considered real people: one is a teacher, the other is a learner" [1]. The responsibility of the teacher is great in the teacher-mentor, learner-student relationship. A good teacher means a teacher with high professional skills.

Pedagogical skills indicate the moral superiority of the teacher. The word "pedagogy" means "I lead a child", so a pedagogue is a person who leads a child. But what does it take to be able to lead a child? - It takes skill! Why did the Japanese or Koreans advance in development? Because they put pressure on education and boldly introduced new pedagogical technologies. They preferred teaching children to read rather than teaching them. In other words, they taught the child not only to eat fish, but also to catch fish. Pedagogical skill becomes a part of the teacher's spirituality, so he can form free thinking skills in the student.

Spiritual and ideological maturity, devotion to one's profession, considering it as the meaning of one's life, patriotism, national pride, inclination to science, knowledge, organization, politeness, communication should be the personal qualities of today's teacher. "To be able to attract students, to arouse their enthusiasm, to inculcate the idea of national modernity, to inspire them to national-educational tasks; to consciously prepare and improve oneself in the image of a "perfect, modern Uzbek intellectual"; pure, clear, expressive, impressive, melodious speaking in Uzbek; public speaking and acting skills; to be able to increase the effectiveness of one's speech through facial expressions, eye, hand, and body movements; ability to control emotions; being able to have a direct and parallel influence on students, etc. [2] are important signs of pedagogical skills.

From this point of view, today the teacher should stand at the forefront of spiritual propaganda. While teaching secular sciences, he asked, "What have I done for the prosperity of the country?" he should place the feeling in the consciousness of himself and the students. It is necessary to inculcate the example of patriotism in the bodies of our youth in the form of Spitamen and Shiroq, To'maris and Muqanna, Jalaluddin Manguberdi and Temur Malik, and to explain that the blood of masters Amir Temur, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirzos is running in the veins of generations.

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**STUDY OF INDUCTION AND DEDUCTION ISSUES BY
PSYCHOLOGISTS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>In the article, the role of induction and deduction in the education of today's youth, the question of the role of thinking methods in knowledge, the fact that the problems of thinking have been out of the view of psychologists for a long time due to their complexity and the main reasons for this, the importance of the fact that philosophers and logicians think about the issue, the role of induction and deduction in the thinking process and the known Issues such as the emergence and solution of a problem, a problem, a puzzle are covered.</p>	<p>Thinking, induction, deduction, human, consciousness, cognition, object, abstract, Psychology, physiology, experiment, speech, idealization.</p>

Introduction

It is known that Scientific schools are a group of professionals and scientists formed as a result of studying the direction of scientific activity of a certain person, a scientist, in which activities are carried out in harmony within the framework of a certain scientific idea and theory. On the part of scientists, Scientific schools ensure succession in the development of science, that is, they manifest systematic development in science. Paradigmatic and local levels of scientific schools differ. If the scientific schools of I. Newton, A. Einstein, N. Bohr, I. Prigozhin show the paradigmatic level, the scientific schools operating in the country, individual higher education institutions or scientific research institutes reflect the local level. The paradigmatic level of the scientific school, in turn, constitutes a set of local level scientific schools with their own leaders. Academic schools may have one or more leaders. In the scientific school, specific scientific innovative mechanisms are used, their emergence is always formed in the struggle with opponents who put forward the opposite idea to the implementation of new ideas. According to some scientists, new ideas are more practical than old ideas, and the protection of the representatives of the scientific school is the guarantee of its implementation. In a scientific school, the teacher's leadership skills, scientific potential, and scientific responsibility are important. Scientific schools are manifested in the form of a set of scientific ideas aimed at the development of theoretical concepts. Scientific schools differ in the scale and importance of the ideas advanced. A characteristic feature of scientific schools is the ability to generalize ideas. A method of conducting individual scientific research is formed in scientific schools. When we analyze the problems of induction and deduction, it is known that this is a way of thinking. Thought is a generalized indirect reflection of existence. Therefore, the first important sign of thinking is

generalization. As a result of thinking, a person acquires such information that this information consists of a large amount of processed data from various objects and a summary of the most important properties of these objects in a short "condensed" form. Thinking creates an ideal image of them in the form of a subjective psychic phenomenon unique to a person.

The second important feature of thinking is the indirect reflection of existence. This means that thinking allows the analyzers to identify and understand things that do not directly affect them and can only be understood through indirect signs.

Thinking is a form of generalized and abstracted reflection, which ensures the presence of complex, comprehensive connections between things and events, which are considered objects of knowledge of the human mind. The problems of thinking have long eluded the attention of psychologists in their complexity, it was considered a matter for philosophers and logicians to think about. The German scientist Wilhelm Wundt, who is considered the father of psychological science, also divided psychology into two parts - physiological psychology (a science that studies the processes of cognition experimentally) and the psychology of peoples. He considered it only. These conclusions actually indicate the complex nature of thinking and thought processes. But even so, it is worth noting:

- firstly, thinking and thinking processes are cognitive processes;
- secondly, they are also a form of reflection of existence by a person, a form of generalization and indirect reflection;
- thirdly, these processes are also studied by experimental psychology;
- fourthly, thinking is the highest and highest form of knowledge.

The organ that allows us to think is our brain. All calculations, from planning the most basic actions to proving complex abstract theorems, take place in the brain. That's why when you are very tired, if you ask a person to express his opinion on a more difficult issue, he will answer: "I have a headache now, I am very tired, come to myself for a while, and then we will think about it." So, brain activity and thinking activity are inextricably linked. The thinking ability and capabilities of our brain are so important that some scientists believe that the laws of its operation are not the computers we use now, but are close to the operation of complex, extremely "intelligent" computers that will appear in 100-200 years.

All thoughts that occur to us are thoughts. It is impossible to imagine a normal person without thoughts, every moment, every minute, the human brain is busy with some thoughts. Sorting them out, focusing on them, solving them through internal or external speech is a process of thinking.

The thinking process actually appears when you need to solve a certain issue, problem, or puzzle. Thinking must always give several solutions about something, if the solutions are too many, it can turn into another process - imagination, fantasy. In the absence of a thought, idea, or clear solution, the human brain's reflection of the essence of things and events in existence is called imagination, etc. That's why, when there is an argument about a problem in the circle of friends, they look at the child who says something that comes to his head due to lack of clear knowledge or idea and say, "You're so good at running away, but you're a dreamer."

A set of knowledge acquired through logical observation, they are the following: analysis - separating the object into its components in practice or thought;

synthesis - to reassemble the whole from the parts in the same way. As a result of synthesis, a completely new object is created.

In the process of analysis (the activity of analysis), thought moves from complexity to simplicity, from coincidence to necessity, from diversity to specificity and unity. The purpose of analysis is to know the

parts as elements of a complex whole and to determine the relations and laws between them. However, the analysis leads to a separation of the essence, so that the unity that remains in the abstract is not yet revealed as a unity in diversity. Synthesis, on the other hand, consists of the process of uniting the parts, properties, and relationships separated by means of analysis into a single whole. Synthesis is directed from unity to difference and diversity, and unites commonality and individuality, unity and diversity into a certain living whole. Analysis and synthesis are closely related.

Abstraction is the process of thinking away from several properties and proportions of the phenomenon under study, at the same time separating the properties (first of all, important, general properties) that are of interest to the researcher. Various "abstract objects" are obtained as a result of this process. In this case, "abstract subjects" mean separate concepts and categories ("development", "contradiction", "thinking", etc.) and their systems. Mathematics, logic, dialectics and philosophy are the most developed systems.

Determining which of the properties under consideration are important and which are secondary is the main problem of abstraction. This issue is solved in each specific case, first of all, depending on the nature of the studied subject, as well as specific tasks of the research.

Generalization is the process of determining general properties and characteristics of the subject, which is closely related to abstraction. In this case, any general (abstract-general) or important (specific general, law) signs can be distinguished.

Idealization is a concept that represents the mental formation of concepts of objects that cannot be realized in practice in principle, but are their representatives in the real world ("point", "ideal gas", "absolute black body", etc.).

Idealized objects, ultimately, appear as objective objects, reflections of real processes and events. Concepts formed with the help of idealization can later be used as a reflection of a real object in conducting research, reasoning, and creating abstract schemes of real processes.

Idealization can be scientific or non-scientific, real or abstract. The distinguishing feature of scientific, real idealization from abstract idealization is that the objects of idealization created in it, individuals are idealized under certain conditions, that is, can be interpreted using the terms of real objects.

Induction-thinking from particular (experience, evidence) to general (summarizing them and making a conclusion); the rise of the deduction-cognition process from the general to the individual. Induction and deduction are interconnected and complement each other. Since experience is always infinite and imperfect, inductive conclusions are always problematic (probabilistic). Inductive generalizations are generally considered empirically known truths (empirical laws).

Among the types of inductive generalization, mass induction, incomplete induction, complete induction, scientific induction and mathematical induction are distinguished. In logic, there are inductive methods of determining causal relationships - the laws of induction (Bacon-Mill rules of inductive research). These include unique similarity, unique difference, similarity and difference, dependent variable methods, and method of residuals.

The peculiarity of deduction is that the researcher creates specific knowledge about each of them from the general knowledge about a class, a genus, a group of things or events by means of deduction. It is known from human cognitive experience that if a property is common to all things or phenomena of a category or genus, then this property is also characteristic of every thing or phenomenon belonging to that category or genus.

deductive method - implies the creation of a system of hypotheses that are deductively related to each other. Conclusions about empirical evidence are ultimately drawn from these hypotheses. This method is based on drawing conclusions (deduction) from hypotheses and other hypotheses whose true meaning is unknown. Consequently, the conclusion drawn using this method will inevitably have a probabilistic character.

The general structure of the hypothetico-deductive method:

- getting acquainted with the material that requires theoretical explanation and trying to explain it using existing theories and laws. If this is not possible:
- to make assumptions (hypotheses, guesses) about the causes and laws of these events using various logical methods;
- to evaluate the validity and seriousness of hypotheses and to choose the closest to the truth among them;
- drawing conclusions from the hypothesis (usually by deduction) and clarifying its content;
- experimental verification of the consequences derived from the hypothesis. Here, the hypothesis is either experimentally proven or disproved. But the fact that some consequences have been proven does not guarantee the validity (or falsity) of the hypothesis. Based on the results of the investigation, the best hypothesis becomes a theory.

The movement of knowledge from the specific to the abstract means the movement from the particular to the general. Logical methods such as analysis and induction lead here. Elevation from abstract to concrete feeling is a process of movement from some general abstractions to their unity, to a particular general. Here the methods of synthesis and deduction lead. Such a movement of knowledge is not a formal, technical procedure, but a dialectical conflicting movement that reflects the contradiction in the development of the subject, its transition from one level to another in accordance with internal contradictions. According to psychologists, when solving any problem, a person can only imagine its conditions in several options. coming If we connect with perception, the figure becomes the background, and the background becomes the figure, their places change, and so on. The individual difference is that some children come to a solution directly on the basis of a figure, while others come to a decision after considering several options. Someone thinks very quickly, someone very slowly. That is why two children sitting next to each other in the process of solving the test will determine the same solution, but the ways of arriving at that solution will be unique for each of them. The psychology of induction and deduction, which is a method of thinking, studies exactly how this process takes place. The solution to the problem sometimes appears suddenly, shining like a bright star. Such a psychological state is called insight in psychology. A person does not even know when clarity and insight appeared in such thoughts. It is surprising that even the most talented and intelligent scientists paid attention to the laws of their thinking and could not find an answer to when and in what way a new idea appeared. Therefore, this issue is a problem that should be studied even today.

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THE PLACE OF NATIONAL SONGS IN THE CREATIVE SINGING ACTIVITIES OF OUR TEACHER ARTISTS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of national words in the creative activities of our mentor artists. Also, detailed information about status art and national words is provided.

KEYWORDS

art, ceremony, education, perception, music, sophistication, education, heritage, composer, poet, creativity.

Introduction

The meaning of human life is measured by its creative output. If a nation has a long past, a rich spirituality, and an endless heritage, then this nation has great prospects, and the future generation is perfect. For example, creativity is a blessing that beautifies life, reveals the secrets of the universe, and expresses human thinking. It is divided into many broad sectors. But all of them are based on one main criterion, that is, nature and the attitude towards it. And on his land, love, sophistication, trust and thinking reach a unique harmony and discover their miracle in the living process. It is no exaggeration to say that music is also a wonderful art and one of the fields of creativity with rich aesthetic possibilities. It is impossible to talk about a spiritually mature person without developing a sense of beauty. A person is a person because he can feel the beauty around him through artistic creation. Music is derived from the Greek word mousihe - the art of the muses, and is an art form that reflects human emotional experiences through sounds (tones, melodies). Music is a wonderful art and one of the fields of creativity with rich aesthetic possibilities. Its content consists of musical and artistic images that express changing mental states. Music embodies various human moods (enjoy, sadness, pleasure, fear, etc.).

Music affects the human mind and emotions. It is of great importance in forming a person's moral and aesthetic taste, developing emotional feelings, and stimulating creative abilities. The art of composition and performance has existed in the peoples of Central Asia since ancient times and is an ocean of creativity that has been developing. Its place in the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people is incomparable. Today's time has come and the process of revival of our national values, that is, requires a

comprehensive study of our cultural heritage, including our artistic heritage and traditions formed over many centuries. Our national songs, which are the priceless spiritual property of our people, are one of the important and valuable resources, and the issue of their large-scale research is of particular importance at present. In particular, a great creator of composition and performing arts, a comprehensive study of history and deep research in this regard, opened wide opportunities to convey to our people.

The art of music is very multifaceted. However, in terms of features, it was formed, created and developed in two main directions. The first direction is related to international life criteria, conditions, and reality. The second direction, the fruit of special thinking - compositional creativity, that is, with specific forms and styles, is called classical music. Examples of classical music named after the great, corrupt, glorious (Khusravani) works from the legendary Borbad times (6th century), the art of composition, which has developed in different periods, passed from generation to generation, embodying unique traditions. It is necessary to admit that Bukhara "Shashmaqom" as a bright product of past compositional creativity was created in the form of a monumental collection of large works. In each period, they developed on the basis of their traditions and legal systems. The art of composition began in the Middle Ages, and the works of past scholars such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Sayfiddin Urmawi, Zaynulbiddin Husayni, Najmiddin Kavkabi Bukhari, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navai, Darvesh Ali Changi gained importance in his work. In the sources created by them, musical genres of the time such as naqsh, amal, and alhon are mentioned. In ancient times, performers of works based on poems of Uzbek folk music were called differently: singer, hafiz, singer, singer, yallachi, big singer, laparchi, interpreter, makomkhan, savkhan, bakhshi, poet, zakir, mughanni, mutrib, yrovchi, like a goyanda. These performers are divided into several groups. Maqam performers are called maqamkhan, hafiz, khandan, savtkhan, in the performance of dostan music they are called bakhshi, poet, dostanchi, yirovchi. The naming of singers in this way is largely related to the variety of genres and forms of Uzbek national music art. This shows that each performer has excellent experience and high level in his chosen field. Among the people, they were directly called "Savtkhan", "Yallachi", "Katta ashulachi", "Talqinchi", "Poet", "Bakhshi". performance and professional level are indicated. For example, it is known that a bakhshi never says maqam or a great singer never says lapar. For many centuries, poets have written about the art of music, its creators - singers, musicians, musical instruments, the influence and power of status on the human soul, the art of dance performed with music, the use of music in battles, royal palaces, who have expressed their place in various parties and performances in their works. Just as the singer created under the influence of the poet's poem, the poet also created poems inspired by the performance of singers and musicians. Singers and musicians who have been famous since ancient times are preserved in historical sources.

In the traditional singing heritage of the Uzbek people, there are mainly four singing schools and styles, which are named as follows:

1. Bukhara - Samarkand style of singing.
2. Khorezm singing style.
3. Fergana - Tashkent singing style.
4. Surkhandarya - Kashkadarya singing style.

Bukhara and Samarkand, which have long been considered the cultural center of Central Asia, have almost different characteristics of Uzbek music. These features apply to heritage themes and genres as well. An important difference between the characteristics of the local style of Bukhara and Samarkand is the division of musical heritage and performance into two types - professional art and folklore in the oral tradition. In addition to skilled representatives of musical folklore, professional artists - musicians and hafiz occupy a large place here, they are known as knowledgeable performers of maqam and other professional music genres. Performers of dance-play songs with diverse content that form a certain series of Kiyalik form- the musicians also have a wide attention.

These ancient cities were characterized by a wealth of musical instruments and a variety of ritual songs, as well as regular music and poetry evenings with the participation of the best singers and musicians. Maishat, the urban way of life allowed singers, dancers and ensembles of musicians to develop in their own way. Uzbek music folklore in Bukhara and Samarkand regions has a certain degree of commonality with Tajik music in many respects. is the heritage of music. "Shashmaqom" is a vivid example of our idea. "Shashmaqom" is a series consisting of six statuses, which are named as follows: "Buzruk status", "Rost status", "Navo status", "Dughoh status", "Segoh status", "Iraq status". Maqam is an Arabic word meaning place, place, space, curtain. The strings of the tanbur are tapped with a fingernail or a natural fingernail. In this instrument, other major instrumental tunes are played on the maqam path, and in addition, the task of accompaniment for the hafiz is performed. In addition, in Bukhara musical practice, the musical ensemble consisting of tanbur, flute and doyra has a traditional character. Ustosh hafiz sing the songs of maqqams. The classical poetic examples sung in them show the tradition of bilingualism.

Each of the six statuses has its own sound veils, on the basis of which composers create instrumental melodies and chants. Each maqam of the six maqqams consists of two major sections - the instrumental and the vocal tracks. Such works can be performed only by professional musicians and singers who studied at the master-apprentice school. Among the professional instruments, the tanbur is widely used. It consists of a pear-shaped, carved bowl and a handle attached to it, made of mulberry wood. The number of strings in a tanbur can be from three to six. However, in the performance practice of the present period, 3-stringed tanbur is used more often, and Uzbek hafiz sing mainly on the basis of examples of poetry in the Uzbek language. Poems of such poets as Navoi, Lutfi, Sakkoki, Mashrab, Babur, and Muqimi are widely used. Domla Halim Ibodov, Father Jalal Nasir, Father Ghiyas Abdugani, Haji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Levi Bobokhanov were skillful performers of the status series.

Fergana-Tashkent style of music is rich in the creativity of women, among them, singing side-by-side, singing various songs, yor-yor, which is a wedding ceremony song, greeting the bride, and their singing is public. received Among them, especially the yallas are performed more often. Yalla is a catchphrase that is sung while dancing. A soloist dances to the accompaniment of a djoyra and sings the verses, and the chorus is sung by those present in the circle. A singular speaker usually follows his statements with a dothar or circle. The Yallachilar ensemble consists of 2-3 women and sings only to the accompaniment of a circle. The repertoire of yallachi who are present in the women's circle is composed mainly of songs, lapar, yalla and wedding ceremony sayings. Hadyakhan Hamdamova, Lutfikhanim Sarimsokova, Rahimak Mazohidova and Oyimqiz Tokhtaeva are skilled performers of the art of hair weaving.

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**IMPROVING THE FORMATION AND MECHANISMS OF
COMPETENCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION SPECIALISTS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The modernization of physical education content provokes it refocusing not only on the subject competences, but also metasubject, personal, social, communicative, gnostic, projecting, informational and others competences. This contributes the increase in requirements to the system of professional development of physical education teachers who need to successfully meet the educational objectives, showing the completeness and effectiveness of their personal and professional characteristics, the activity of pedagogical thinking and possession of an integrated system of professional skills with a high level of professional competence. Creating the motivational space, initiating individual work of students and assisting them in developing their individual trajectory of self-improvement were the basis of the developed model.</p>	<p>Professional competence of physical education teachers, organizational and pedagogical predictive model, the components of activity, the diagnostic tool.</p>

Introduction

In the conditions of modernization of education, there is an increasing need for teachers who are able to take a personal and humane position, organize the educational process based on modern educational paradigms, and educate a person of culture. In this context, the process of development of society and personality cannot be complete without the progress of physical culture. This type of activity contributes to the spiritual and physical development of a person, forms values of general cultural significance.

The improvement of educational paradigms leads to a change in the status of physical culture as a humanitarian educational subject. This makes it necessary to update the content of physical education and thereby significantly changes the view of the quality of professional and personal positions of the teacher, requiring a rethinking and restructuring of the nature of his professional activity.

The teacher of physical culture becomes the bearer of the updated content of education, the organizer of pedagogical conditions that ensure the effectiveness of activities. In this regard, the problem of its modernization by strengthening the humanistic contexts of pedagogical activity of a specialist in physical culture and sports, who is called upon to build his individual pedagogical activity on the value-semantic foundations, to the fore among the urgent problems of modern additional vocational education, is the problem of its modernization by strengthening the humanistic contexts of

pedagogical activity of a specialist in physical culture and sports. Have professional and personal competence.

At the same time, no more than 20% of physical education teachers rely on the idea of democratization and humanization, 5-10% implement an activity approach, and up to 10% of teachers use psychological-pedagogical and psychological-physiological theories. New approaches to assessing students' academic performance, focused on qualitative criteria, are carried out by 10 to 20%, use a variety of creative methods and forms of teaching, with an emphasis on motivating students, up to 20% of teachers, use computers and other new technical means of teaching in classes no more than 5% of teachers.

Innovative directions related to the renewal of professional education of specialists in the field of physical culture and sports on a humanistic, value-semantic, personality-oriented basis are reflected in the works of a number of authors (I. P. Andriadi, V. K. Balsevich, S. N. Begidova). Recently, there have been many studies devoted to the problem of professional development of specialists in physical culture and sports in the conditions of updating the content of education (V. U. Ageevets, E.

R. Akhmedzyanov, A. N. Bleer, O. B. Dmitriev, S. P. Evseev, Yu. A. Kashirtsev, N. N. Kiseleva, V. K. Kuznetsov, S. A. Loktev, B. E. Losin, N. I. Nikolaeva, P. K. Petrov, K. L. Chernov, Yu. K. Chernyshenko, L. V. Yaroshenko).

At the same time, research related to the search and development of professional development systems based on humanistic foundations and aimed at improving the professional competence of physical education teachers, in our opinion, is still insufficient.

Among the many contradictions, we single out one related to the increased need of the modern school for a professionally competent personality of a physical education teacher and the insufficient development of pedagogical models for organizing the process of professional development, built on competence-based, activity-based principles.

The strategy of developing the model can be represented as a system of step-by-step unfolding actions-elements:

- Analytical understanding of the content, facts and factors of the functioning of the educational system;
- Identification of contradictions that make it difficult to achieve a qualitative result in the system of professional development;
- Selection of methodological bases of the model;
- Building a system of goals for improving the professional competence of physical education teachers in the process of professional development;
- Building an integral educational space of the professional development system that initiates the improvement of the professional competence of physical education teachers;
- Determination of criteria and levels of professional competence of physical education teachers.

Developing the logic of the above, we chose the following as a methodological basis:

1. Provisions on the integrity of the pedagogical process, considered in a sequence of interrelated stages (N. G. Abramova, I. Ya. Lerner, M. N. Skatkin);

2. Provisions on a systematic approach to the organization of learning processes in the context of its integrity (V. G. Afanasyev, G. I. Gerasimov, A. Ya. Danilyuk, V. S. Ilyin);

3. The theory of step-by-step formation of mental actions (P. Ya. Galperin, N. F. Talyzina), suggesting the need to create conditions that provide a certain system of actions of students in the context of the commonality of internal and external human activity;

Thus, the problem was determined - the task is to organize a holistic pedagogical process of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers. At the same time, we followed the provisions developed by V.S. Ilyin on the integral properties of the process and its influence not only on individual functions and properties of the personality, but also on the personality as a whole.

When developing a pedagogical model for organizing the process of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers on a competency basis, we chose the system of personality-oriented components of professional pedagogical education proposed by M. M. Levina as the substantive basis of design.

The personal-motivational component, which assumes the motivation of educational activities: the formation of the personal meaning of educational and professional activities; the development of professional orientation of the individual, personal and professional self-determination and self-realization; the development of self-organization in educational activities and self-regulation of behavior; the development of self-assessment of their professional readiness.

Cognitive creative component involving the implementation of a culturological approach: the formation of a scientific worldview based on the consistency of scientific knowledge and professional practice;

-subordination of the subjectively perceived objective function of the educational process with the value-objective function of professional development; comprehension of educational goals in the aspect of personal and professional self-determination development; mastering by students of the areas of subject professional and psychological- pedagogical education; awareness by students of the importance of personal information readiness for professional activity, free selectivity of professional actions, improvement of professional knowledge and skills; development of professional systematic thinking, flexibility, criticality, creative activity, development of creative individuality;

-formation of professional reflexivity and self-correction;

-formation of self-organization based on motivated goals and conditions of activity, self-regulation of the individual in conditions associated with overcoming educational and professional difficulties, based on the adequacy of self-assessment.

Professional and social component (civic orientation), involving the development of normative, moral, legal and moral culture: education of moral and political beliefs and feelings that determine professional and personal behavior. Formation of a professional role function based on personal and professional goals and social values, social adequacy of the teacher's personality; development of ethical norms of behavior during the exercise of professional functions; education of personal and professional responsibility for the implementation of value-oriented interactions and regulation of students' self-development; formation of civil, legal and moral responsibility in the process of professional activity.

We have identified the stages and components of the structure of the organizational and pedagogical provision of the pedagogical model of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers in the process of professional development.

The approximate design component is mutually dependent on the value-semantic and motivational-target component, since it serves:

- 1) the development of personal professional experience based on a dialogue of models of formative, developmental and personality-oriented education in the field of physical culture;
- 2) professional orientation and self-determination in modern models of concepts of upbringing and education in physical culture;
- 3) building an internal individual model of improving professional competence.

The practice-oriented and personality-oriented orientation of the listener's activity in the context of the first two components is manifested in the performance and performance-evaluation component, which is expressed in the ability to:

- 1) to model and design individual and group models of education in the field of physical culture;
- 2) carry out external and internal expertise of the proposed models, analyze their project activities and their results;
- 3) present individual pedagogical projects developed in the course of advanced training courses.

The results of diagnostics of the initial level of formation of professional competencies of physical education teachers, using six diagnostic techniques, served as the basis for determining the content of the subsequent stages and components of the prognostic model that ensures the improvement of the professional competence of physical education teachers.

The mechanism of giving the process of professional development a personality-oriented orientation was not only the content of the educational program, the principles of its implementation, but also the technology of its construction. Thus, each curriculum included in the educational program is a logically constructed educational module. The content of the educational modules gives dynamism and mobility to the learning process and reflects the specifics of the professional activities of physical education teachers.

Experience shows that the most effective forms of education from the point of view of interdisciplinary integration are those that provide an opportunity for the students of the courses to combine both educational and professional pedagogical activities. This is achieved by modeling situations based on professional actions that require the teacher to analyze and reflect on the scientific and practical content of the studied disciplines. Such forms of training contribute to the development of students' ability to demand and use the methodologies of the studied disciplines as a technological means of solving professional problems. This approach promotes the activation of students' learning activities, stimulates interest, and hence motivation to learn. This is how the problem of relevance is solved – the correspondence of the educational reality of the content of professional development to the objective needs of listeners.

The modular technology of teaching in the modern educational situation is recognized as the most relevant for the transformation of psychological and pedagogical provisions of science directly into the activity of a teacher, it takes into account all the features of the system of professional training of adults as much as possible.

Having decided on the choice of a system of principles, we chose the appropriate technologies for its development, giving the content of the learning process a personality-oriented orientation.

This allowed us to develop approaches to the content, as well as tactics for conducting the third stage of educational activity – constructive and procedural.

The specificity of this stage, which includes substantive and procedural modules, was found in the approbation of the innovative curriculum developed by us "Methods of teaching the subject "Physical Culture".

As a technological support, we have chosen pedagogical design, game modeling, the method of an educational project using information computer technologies as forms and methods of improving the professional competencies of physical education teachers.

Upon completion of the implementation of the model of organizational and pedagogical support for the process of professional development of physical education teachers and providing this process with specific pedagogical technologies, it became necessary to identify the level of development of professional competencies of students.

Thus, the final result of measuring the level of self-assessment of existing difficulties in the implementation of professional skills on a five-point scale (0-5 points) significantly increased (respectively, the level of difficulties in the implementation of skills decreased).

Skill level:

1) to use computers in the educational process, which in the input questionnaire was estimated by teachers at 0.91 ± 0.06 points, increased to 2.46 ± 0.11 points, while $t = 12.4$, $p < 0.001$;

2) use other technical means of training (video and tape recordings, etc.) 3.86 ± 0.11 , with an input result of 2.74 ± 0.06 , $t = 8.96$, $p < 0.001$;

3) organize training on new pedagogical technologies 3.45 ± 0.11 points, which increased by 0.39 points compared to the input result, $t = 3.12$, $p < 0.01$;

4) analyze advanced pedagogical experience and use it in your work 3.77 ± 0.06 , with an input 3.70 ± 0.06 points, $t = 0.88$, $p > 0.05$;

5) to anticipate the results of their pedagogical activity, at the input diagnosis it was 3.73 ± 0.06 points, increased to 3.94 ± 0.11 , while $t = 1.68$, $p > 0.05$;

6) to ensure the level of training of students that meets the requirements of the state educational standard of 3.95 ± 0.11 points, which increased by 0.13 points compared to the initial result, $t = 1.04$, $p > 0.05$;

7) to activate the educational and cognitive activity of students, when studying the initial level was 3.83 ± 0.06 points, significantly increased to 4.14 ± 0.09 , while $t = 2.14$, $p < 0.05$;

8) to diagnose students' knowledge and skills using tests, questionnaires and assessment methods increased from 3.85 ± 0.06 to 4.22 ± 0.11 points, $t = 2.96$, $p < 0.01$.

The survey was conducted on a representative sample that determines the characteristics of the general population of physical education teachers. When comparing the results of the input and final stages of the diagnostic examination, the dynamics of qualimetric indicators for all diagnostic tools was traced. Thus, the positive role of the developed and tested pedagogical model of improving the professional competence of physical education teachers in the system of professional development is revealed.

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**NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL
CULTURE**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
The article provides an overview of the Uzbek national wrestling Quresh: the history of the development of kurash, as well as the rules for evaluating kurash competitions.	Kurash, wrestling, the art of wrestling, glasses, penalty points.

Introduction

The period of formation of belt wrestling as a national sport began in the 5th - 3rd century BC. Moreover, it is believed that it originated 5,000 years ago. This is confirmed by the above-mentioned ethnographic event (wrestling between girls and boys) recorded by the Greek scientist Herodotus during his expedition to Central Asia in the period from 455 to 447 BC. The national sport of wrestling was introduced during the reign of the Timurids (455-447 BC).

The centuries-old sports history of our people shows that in the eyes of our ancestors, belt wrestling was revered primarily as an example of the versatile maturity of wrestlers. A special place is occupied not only by the physical strength, height, fighting spirit and agility of the wrestler, but also by his behavior in a wide circle, his moral and spiritual appearance, attitude to rivals and the environment. It has always been a kind of memorable tradition to look at heroes who have never been on earth as mentors, to receive their advice and parting words. A vivid example of our idea is embodied in the image of Pahlavon Mahmud, the famous poet and fighter of Khorezm. That is why this nobleman was once awarded the high honor of Prior vali (hero among heroes). It happened when Pahlavon Mahmud went to India. The day before the wrestling tournament was to be held in this country, he, according to his custom, went on a pilgrimage to the shrine. He saw a crying woman and turned to her with a plea. The mother said: "God, please raise my son's hand tomorrow. If my son loses to the warriors of Horatimia, what will happen to our survival? All our hopes depend on this battle." Pahlavon Mahmud understands that this woman is the mother of the young man who is fighting with him. The next day, he deliberately challenges his opponent to a duel and loses. From this story we learn that Pahlavon Mahmud was a noble and noble man, that he was not called Pahlavon or Prioribal for nothing, and that his sacred grave has been a shrine for many centuries.

As the years passed, courage did not lose its popularity, remaining one of the most beloved and revered traditions among the peoples of Uzbekistan and never left the borders of Central Asia. That is why no attempts have been made to systematize or summarize all the information about kurash.

And so, in 1980, the master of kurash, judo and sambo Komil Yusupov, having carefully studied the millennial traditions of folk wrestling for ten years, created the universal rules of kurash. Then, on their basis, weight categories, terminology and gestures, the duration of the fight, the form for wrestlers and judges were determined – everything that was necessary in order to turn the ancient folk fun into a modern sport.

The form for kurash wrestling was determined, which includes wide white trousers and a spacious shirt, a mandatory cloth belt used for the convenience of capturing an opponent, its length is 180-220 cm, and its width is 50-70 cm.

The basic rules of kurash are quite simple. The only position is a standing position. The main task: to throw the opponent on his back – such an outcome in kurash is considered a clean victory. To perform this task, it is allowed to use only throws and sweeps, which are evaluated by the judges. Kurash is a safe and simple type of martial arts, as it prohibits any painful, shock and suffocating techniques, grappling below the belt. Despite this, the fights look very dynamic and spectacular.

Kurash embodies a centuries-old philosophy and values such as respect for the opponent and humanism, honesty and the ability to go to the end. This type of martial arts is one of the youngest international sports and is beginning to gain popularity around the world.

The first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov at a meeting with Komil Yusupov (a master of kurash wrestling, who researched and popularized kurash) in 1992 fully supported the idea of making kurash an international sport, and through it to acquaint the world with the rich and ancient history, traditions, philosophy of the Uzbek people.

The first-ever World Championship among adults was held in May 1999 in Tashkent, where representatives of 48 countries of Asia, Africa, Europe and Pan America came to the capital of Kurash's homeland to participate.

The second World Cup was held in Antalya (Turkey) in 2000, the third – in Budapest (Hungary) in 2001, the fourth – in Yerevan (Armenia) in 2002, the fifth – in Tashkent (Uzbekistan) in 2005.

The African Kurash Union and the Kurash Association of Swaziland successfully held the XVI African Championship among Adults and the VIII African Championship among Juniors in Yaounda (Cameroon) in 2017. The African Championship brought together a large number of kurashists and officials from countries such as South Africa, Botswana, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, etc.

The first African Continental Kurash Championship was held in 2001 in South Africa, since then, continental championships have been held every year under the auspices of the African Kurash Union in various parts of Africa, in countries such as South Africa, Morocco, Madagascar, Mauritius, Zambia, etc.

The XII Kurash World Championship among adults will be held in Chunju, Republic of Korea, from August 30 to September 5, 2019. It will be held as part of another prestigious multi-sport event - the World Martial Arts Workshops.

Today, physical culture and sports are important tools for organizing the most comfortable, active, empowering daily life of schoolchildren and students, preparing them for the defense of the Motherland, educating a harmoniously developed generation in sports schools of schoolchildren and students.

Physical education of students plays an important role in the formation and improvement of many practical competencies related to moral, independent and aesthetic education. In addition, the period

of study in children's and youth sports schools is very convenient for achieving high sports results in the main sports.

Therefore, students master various sports of their choice in accordance with individual interests and abilities.

Kurash is a sport in which two athletes compete one-on-one in accordance with an established rule. The art of wrestling has been known to many peoples since ancient times. Wrestling is especially common in Greece and was a regular element of the ancient Olympic Games. Various forms of national wrestling exist in Greece, Italy, Japan, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Russia, Uzbekistan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and other countries.

The basic rules of modern wrestling were developed in several European countries in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. In 1912, the International Amateur Wrestling Federation (FILA) was formed (now 144 countries, Uzbekistan has been a member since 1993). Greek wrestling, freestyle wrestling, judo, sambo and other types of wrestling are widespread in the international arena. In recent years, Uzbek kurash has also gained international recognition as a separate sport.

Courage is one of the means of educating strength, dexterity, endurance and will of a person. Kurash can be practiced from the age of 12 under the supervision of doctors. Archaeological finds and historical manuscripts confirm that wrestling has long been an integral part of the Uzbek way of life. Cylindrical Bronze Age ceramics found in ancient Bactria (southern Uzbekistan) depict two wrestlers, one of whom is fighting the other. Another archaeological find from the same period shows the wrestling of wrestlers. These unique finds indicate that the kurash was part of the lifestyle of our ancestors even 1.5 thousand years ago. According to the Greek writer Claudius Elianus (II-III centuries) and other historical figures, the daughters of the Saxon tribe who lived in this area chose a groom, fighting with young men. An example of this is the conditions of Barchin in the Uzbek folk epic "Alpomish".

In the IX-XVI centuries, kurash was spread among the Uzbek people. During this period, the popularity of kurash increased among the tribes of Pahlavon Mahmud and Sadik Polvon.

There is also a type of individual struggle of the Uzbek people, called belt wrestling. Many archaeological finds and historical manuscripts are associated with it. A statue found in ancient Mesopotamia 5,000 years ago depicts wrestlers competing in belt wrestling. Ancient Chinese Manuscript

"Tan-shu" says that weddings and holidays in the Fergana Valley would not have taken place without kurash competitions. Ahmad Polvon, Khoja Polvon and others became famous in this kind of Kurash (late 19th - early 20th century).

In 1991, Kamil Yusupov, a member of the Kurash dynasty and an international master of sports in several types of kurash, developed the following rules of Uzbek kurash in accordance with international standards:

1. Wrestlers must compete standing on a blue-green kurash carpet with markings.
2. The winner will be determined based on the methods used and the assessment of their behavior on the field.

Strangulation in wrestling, the use of painful techniques is not allowed, one of the wrestlers is wearing a blue jacket, the other a green jacket (women have a white T-shirt inside the jacket), a belt 4-5 cm wide.

Men compete in the category 60, 66, 73, 81, 90, 100 kg and more than 100 kg, women – in weight categories 48, 52, 57, 63, 70, 78kg and over 78kg, children, teenagers, the elderly and girls also compete in weight categories taking into account their age.

The Congress of the International Wrestling Association (IKA) in Tashkent in 2003 set the official time of the competition at 3 minutes, so that each match was held vigorously.

In accordance with the applied methodology, the following types of assessments of the struggle are applied: "incomplete", "lateral", "clean", and for illegal actions - "warning", "dhaka" (strict warning), "deception". If a wrestler gets a score of "clean" or if his opponent is punished with a score of "cheating", it means that he has won. Getting a "sideways" score twice or punishing an opponent twice with a "dhaka" score also means victory. Taking into account the "incomplete" scores, the victory is awarded to the wrestler with the highest number of points, if the number of points and penalties of the opponents is the same, then the loser is the wrestler who received the penalty point last. If the wrestlers have an equal number of points and there are no penalty points, then the winner will be announced by a majority vote of the judges.

In 1992, the Kurash Federation was established in Uzbekistan, and in 2001, the Kurash Belt Federation was established in Uzbekistan. In September 1998, representatives of 28 countries (USA, Bolivia, Great Britain, the Netherlands, Russia, Uzbekistan, Japan, etc.) became the founders of the International Kurash Association (IKA) in Tashkent. In 1999, the first Uzbek Kurash World Championship was held in Tashkent, and an international women's tournament was held in Bryansk (Russia).

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**METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING INTERACTIVE GAMES IN
PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS**

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ABSTRACT

In our republic, a number of tasks related to the education of the mature generation are being implemented, and this process is preparing the ground for the education of young people with all-round developed intellectual potential. Formation of a mature generation is carried out first in the family, and then in the preschool educational organization. By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 «On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021» The program for 2021» was approved, and among the main objectives and directions of this program are to improve the quality of preschool education, to radically improve the quality of children’s preparation for school in preschool educational institutions, to introduce the educational process widely used in world practice. tasks of introducing modern educational programs and technologies are defined.

KEYWORDS

Introduction

The evidence presented above is the implementation of innovative technologies in the educational process of preschool educational organizations, the use of interactive games and multimedia tools during training, the formation of computer literacy of students, teaching them to use a computer in an elementary way, and school education. shows that preparation for liming is one of the urgent tasks. In a number of regulatory documents adopted in our republic, it is noted that the use of new innovative technologies, including multimedia technology, in the field of education is an urgent issue. Currently, multimedia-based electronic textbooks, manuals and various electronic didactic tools are being created and used in the field of education. However, preschool educational organizations have insufficiently developed opportunities to use multimedia technology in the educational process and, on this basis, to implement innovative methods in the course of training. Finding, developing and implementing innovative technologies in preschool education, which is the first type of continuous education system, is an urgent task today. Educational multimedia technology is one of the innovative technologies of preschool educational organizations intended for use in the educational process. Multimedia technology is one of the rapidly developing directions of modern information technology and consists of the following components: text, table, graphics, music, decoration, animation, audio, video. According to the author, the method of using interactive games, multimedia technology and tools in education was called the «multimedia attack» method.

Educational multimedia technology has its own style, just as each pedagogical, educational and other technology has its own style. The «multimedia attack» method is intended for use in the educational process, and when using this method, the teacher first prepares a multimedia interactive software product related to the studied material. If the child's brain is exposed to the educational material in the form of text, audio, video, graphics, music and animation at the same time, the acceptance and retention of the material increases. This is the main content of the «multimedia attack» method. «Multimedia attack» method is used in the training part of teaching new material. The advantage of the «multimedia attack» method is as follows:

- a multimedia didactic tool has an attractive, impressive, dynamic (dynamic state) effect;
- both hemispheres of the child's brain work simultaneously as a result of the presentation of educational material in a multimedia format;
- as a result of multimedia attack, children's attention stabilizes, their thinking increases, and educational materials are more accepted;
- the activities of children in groups increase;
- a certain amount of time is saved due to the multimedia didactic tool interactive software product, the opportunity to provide additional information to the child is created due to the saved time. In our opinion, multimedia technology for preschool children differs from traditional technologies in the following ways:
 - psychological aspects of children;
 - children's age (6-7 years old);
 - duration of computer training (15 minutes);
 - suitability of the material for children (in the form of multimedia);
 - size of the material (for 30 minutes);
 - the level of complexity of the material (simple materials are chosen for children);
 - their activity levels.

In the variant of multimedia computer technology created for preschool children, the technological approach is as follows: in order to facilitate and facilitate the mastering of the studied material by the pupil of preschool educational organizations, the material is divided into interrelated parts, fragments, and then in order to obtain the intended result, it is envisaged that the actions will be carried out in sequence and the planned work will be completed. Most importantly, the material studied in this technology is presented on the basis of multimedia. As a result of such a «multimedia attack» on the child's brain, the child's mastery level increases and the training efficiency increases. As a result of computer processing (technological process) of the above multimedia components, their placement in one package (disk) reflects the content of multimedia technology. In educational multimedia technology, the educational process is carried out on the basis of the «multimedia attack» method, that is, in this process, the brains of students of preschool educational organizations are influenced by at least three multimedia elements - audio, video and animation. consists of being done. Accordingly, we can consider educational multimedia technology as an innovative technology intended for use in the educational process of preschool educational organizations.

Multimedia didactic tools are aimed at developing the pupil's thinking, increasing his mental activity, stabilizing his attention, and activating his perceptions. Children should be taught to enjoy the beauty of nature, to keep the surroundings clean and tidy, not to harm animals and birds, not to destroy flowers

and grass, not to break tree branches, not to destroy bird's nests and ants' nests. . Paying attention to updating the content, form, tools and methods of education in recent years, searching for innovations related to preschool education, introducing it into the educational process and the pedagogical activities of educators is of great importance. In particular, the implementation of advanced pedagogical technologies in the pedagogical process, the introduction of innovations, the use of modern methods, and the equipping of teachers and educators with skills and qualifications are carried out as part of the tasks set before the professional development system. There is an important issue that needs to be implemented in the field of pedagogy, and that is to ensure that educators organize the pedagogical process in a methodical way, based on modern methods, purposefully, systematically and by being able to predict the results. It should be recognized that interactive game methods are currently a priority aspect of educational reforms and their role in solving pedagogical problems, as well as important factors ensuring the effectiveness of education. An important aspect of the theory of pedagogical technology is determined by the ability of each pedagogue to effectively use interactive methods in the educational process in order to increase educational activity, taking into account the unique characteristics of learners of different ages. Currently, as world psychologists have noted, «indigo» children perceive events happening in the world faster than adults. Therefore, today's educators face a number of urgent tasks. One of them is the use of interactive methods in the educational process. «What interactive game methods can Preschool education organization educators use?» a legitimate question arises. «...We demand that the pedagogue give our children modern education. But in order to provide modern knowledge, first of all, the coach must have such knowledge» Teaching educators to use interactive methods rationally, according to goals and conditions, based on didactic principles, is one of the important issues of modern pedagogy today. Educators of Preschool education organization have been applying modern methods to their activities by studying scientific articles, brochures and local best practices related to preschool education. Sometimes, they use interactive methods without fully understanding their essence and purpose. Therefore, if an interactive learning environment is created in the process of professional development, and educators become its direct participants, that is, if they master each interactive method directly by themselves, adapt these methods to preschool education and put them into practice. so easy and convenient. Interactive methods such as «Brainstorming», «Role house», «Working in small groups», «Debate», «Walk to the gallery», «Cluster», «Boomerang», «Energizers» can be used in preschool educational organizations. It is advisable for the teacher to use the brainstorming method at the beginning and at the end of the educational activity in order to clarify the understanding of the children on the subject and to strengthen the acquired knowledge. «Working in small groups» is based on children's interaction and exchange of ideas. In this case, a given topic is developed based on analysis and verification in the group. In «Rolly Houses» children are given a problem situation. Children use this method to recreate real life situations. In the debate method, children are given a topic the day before. Children find answers to questions by asking their parents, and the answers to the given questions are conducted on the basis of «discussion». Currently, although there are clear concepts and ideas about pedagogical technology, pedagogues of preschool educational organizations have problems such as not being able to distinguish technology from methodology. However, there are significant differences between them, theoretical information about them is given below. Pedagogical technology is a process that guarantees teaching a child to be independent, learn, and think. Methodology is a set of teaching methods and ways that are convenient for a certain person, a

pedagogue, depending on the knowledge, skills, abilities, personal qualities, and temperament of the pedagogue. It is divided into separate methods. The science of pedagogy studies the laws of teaching certain academic subjects. For example, methods of languages, methods of arithmetic, etc. It is necessary to understand the difference between methodology and pedagogical technology and be able to effectively use both in practice. The differences between them are listed in Table 1. The concept of «pedagogical technology» refers to pedagogical technologies at the private level, corresponding to the concept of teaching methods of private subjects and local levels. In technologies, more procedural, quantitative, and calculation components are represented, while in methods, the goal, content, quality, and variant guiding aspects are represented more. Technology differs from methods by its reproducibility, stability of results, lack of many «ifs» (if the teacher is talented, if the children are talented, if there are good parents...) is different. That is, the technology differs from a very individual method in that it can be restored and used by all specialists who have the appropriate training. In conclusion, it can be said that various comments on the effectiveness and quality of education can be the basis for us to think again. The use of modern interactive game technologies is a modern requirement, and it is advisable to use it regularly. Of course, all of the above will not happen by itself. At the root of these works and achievements is deep research and hard work. These are said not for gratitude, but for the purpose of correct assessment of the situation.

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WAYS OF USING UZBEK FOLKLORE-SUB-GENRES IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS BY TEACHING THEM IN PRIMARY GRADES

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>In this scientific article information about the ways of using Uzbek folklore-sub-genres in the education of students through the teaching of Uzbek folklore-sub-genres in primary classes are highlighted, and methodical recommendations on the importance of folklore are given in it.</p> <p>The purpose of writing this article: to show the importance of using Uzbek folklore-sub-genres in the education of students by teaching them in primary grades.</p> <p>Methods and Games: "Find the name of the fairy tale", "Salad from fairy tales", "Find the video".....</p> <p>Results: educating the young generation in the spirit of understanding the essence of Uzbek folklore.</p>	<p>folklore, imagination, fairy tale, proverb, riddle, thinking</p>

Introduction

The main task of the education system of our republic today is the formation and development of a scientific worldview, the ability to think logically, mental development, and self-awareness potential of the younger generation, of national and national significance. The role of samples of folk art in primary education in the formation of universal human values, the development of morally perfect people, and the ability to take a worthy place in society is incomparable. Today, the rapid development of science, technology and production, information and communication technologies requires raising the quality of education in educational institutions to a higher content level. It is clear to all of us that examples of folk art play a special role in the development of children's imagination and fantasy. In particular, every child from an early age learns about the world by listening to fairy tales. Each story told leaves a new impression on children. Children try to be like the heroes of fairy tales, want to have magical things or dream of becoming wizards and having unlimited powers, like a hero. With the help of fairy tales they travel through the deserts of good and evil, through the mountains. From this period they begin to understand what is good and what is bad. Growing up, children tell their younger ones fairy tales, urging them to be smart, restrained, and stop being stubborn and capricious. They also act as little educators. Therefore, in primary education, folk art is considered a complex of wisdom for

both young and old people. Despite the fact that centuries pass and issues of education are artistically expressed in the works of our great scientists, folklore works, which are a product of popular thought, continue to acquire universal significance from a spiritual point of view. Proverbs reflect all the virtues, philosophy, wisdom, worldview, high diligence and attitude of an Uzbek to various life situations.¹ Love for a cause and the feeling of love in a person are expressed in songs as the most beautiful inner experiences. Fairy tales show the highest dreams and passions of our people. The younger generation who gets to know them will understand how sacred the concepts of Motherland, people, family, work, science and pride are for Uzbekistan. Primary education is a stage that consolidates the mental education of a child, is carried out in inextricable connection with other areas of education, expands the volume of knowledge and worldview, and most importantly, ensures successful learning in high school. Thanks to this, all subjects taught in primary school, their sections, each topic and concept are selected with special attention. In primary education, materials that ensure the growth of the student's mind in accordance with the level and level of knowledge are used in everyday life practice, convey the essence of events and incidents that happened in life. For this purpose, the topics included in the content of each subject are selected separately by specialists and scientists. In this process, as we said above, samples of folk art also acquire special significance. The spiritual and moral development of primary school students occurs under the influence of school, family and society. It is not only the responsibility of parents, but also of the whole society to notice, educate and realize the abilities and talents of every child, and every pedagogue is in a special place as a responsible person. For this, a pedagogue must be active, inquisitive, demanding, creative, and most importantly, a knowledgeable specialist, who knows the examples of folk art. In addition, the use of interactive methods is also effective.

"ERTAKNING NOMINI TOPING" O'YINI. BUNDA O'QUVCHILARGA ERTAK RASMLARI KO'RSATILADI VA ULARGA JAVOB TOPILADI.

"Salad made of fairy tales" method. A salad of fairy tales involves combining the plots and main characters of various fairy tales, and on this basis a new story emerges. Example: Little Red Riding Hood meets Mittaway in the forest (from this place their adventures intertwine and take a new direction - add plots).

"Find video" method. Currently, in pedagogical activities, special attention is paid to the organization of the educational process with the help of various media (computer, television, radio, copier, slide, video and audio tape recorders). Teachers are faced with the task of appropriate and purposeful use of various media in the educational process. In folklore, special attention is paid to the issue of educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism, patriotism, hard work, and honesty. Riddles are one

of the ancient genres of folklore that teach children to think and be resourceful. The teaching of folklore also arises in the process of pedagogical experience and practical activity. Its content is determined by pedagogical knowledge, skills and abilities, personality formation. Certain criteria should be used to identify advanced pedagogical practices in primary education. The most important criterion is the advanced forms and methods of education used by the teacher in his pedagogical activity. This is an important feature that distinguishes him from an ordinary teacher. In short, at the moment of strengthening national education for primary school students, education and in the conditions where changes are being made to the content of education, there is no doubt that the examples of folk oral creativity will give positive results in the spiritual and moral education of children.

O`zbek xalqida bir maqol bor

Ilon quvsa, o`rga qoch,
.... Quvsa g`orga qoch

Ilon o`rga, ya`ni tepalikka yaxshi o`rmalay olmas, shuning uchun maqolning ikkinchi qatoridagi hayvon uncha-munchaga quvlamaydi, ammo bir quvish qilsa, jahl otiga minsa, undan qochish amri maholdi.

Savol: Ikkinchi qatordagi hayvon nomi nima?

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DEALING WITH HETEROGENEOUS GROUPS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
An analysis of the needs of representatives of heterogeneous groups of students is presented. Particular attention is paid to the needs of three categories of students – gifted, socially disadvantaged, and with disabilities. Recommendations are given for the development of vocational training and retraining programs.	Gifted students, students with disabilities, growth needs, communication needs, subsistence needs, socially disadvantaged children.

Introduction

In the last decade, in the philosophical, sociological, psychological and pedagogical literature, there has been interest in the problems of teaching heterogeneous groups. Most authors are inclined to understand a heterogeneous group as a heterogeneous group that includes a certain number of people with different characteristics (nationality, age, gender, intelligence, characteristics of physical and mental development, etc.), connected by common interests, subordinated to some or a common meaning and being fully dependent on each other. Despite the fact that certain aspects of these problems are widely presented in the works of domestic and foreign researchers, one cannot speak of a sufficient level of development of the problem of preparing teachers to work with heterogeneous groups of students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data obtained were interpreted on the basis of the theory of existence, connection and growth (ERG - Existence, Relatedness, Growth) by K. Alderfer, who, noting the lack of clarity in distinguishing some groups of needs in the theory of A. Maslow, identified not five classes (groups) of needs, but three: the needs of existence, connection and growth. Existence needs include two groups of needs in A. Maslow's pyramid - safety and physiological. Communication needs reflect the social nature of a person, his desire to be a member of a family, to have colleagues, friends, therefore this group also includes the needs for belonging to a certain social group, for recognition and respect, associated with a person's desire to occupy a certain position in the world around him, as well as that part of the security needs of A. Maslow's pyramid, which is associated with group security. Growth needs are similar to the needs for self-expression in A. Maslow's pyramid and also include the group's

needs for recognition and self-affirmation, associated with the desire to develop confidence, self-improvement, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gifted Students

In this study, a gifted student is understood as a person who stands out for his bright or hidden achievements (or who has internal prerequisites for such achievements) in one or another type of activity - practical, cognitive, artistic-aesthetic, communicative, spiritual-value, etc.

110 teachers, 78 parents, 93 school students and 99 university students took part in our study of the needs of gifted students.

Analyzing the needs of the existence of this group of students (in pedagogical support, logistics and special learning conditions), we came to the conclusion that there is dissatisfaction among schoolchildren and students with what educational organizations now offer them.

The majority of school students (54.8%) have the opportunity to study individually with teachers. However, students practically do not have such an opportunity: 44% of students indicate that they consult only sometimes, and 16% do not have such an opportunity at all. Nevertheless, with complex questions, the majority of students (57%) and students (65%) turn to the teacher (teacher). About a quarter of respondents (29% of students and 22% of undergraduates) answered that they solve complex issues on their own.

Despite the available support from the teacher, the majority of students surveyed (64.5%) believe that teachers do not or do not always take into account their individual characteristics and interests; 38.7% of school students cannot count on teacher support in solving a difficult personal problem.

Only 25% of parents note that their children have the opportunity to attend clubs and sections at school. Teachers have the same position: 22% of teachers consider the school's sports facilities to be sufficient and accessible.

A significant number of pupils (39.8%) and students (45.5%) would like to develop their talents in clubs and sections at their school/university; 15% do not know what the school currently offers them. Half of the children surveyed cannot engage in research activities, and 41.4% of students do not have the opportunity to choose courses to study at an in-depth level. At the same time, 68% of students and 61% of students consider themselves to be quite independent and agree that they can study effectively at home.

A study of another group of needs of gifted children - safety - did not reveal an urgent need to maintain health, which can be explained by the absence of serious health problems in this category of respondents. However, an unmet need for psychological safety was discovered. Gifted children experience serious emotional stress, they experience breakdowns and unstable states. About 85% of children and 87% of students noted that they are faced with situations where no one understands them; 67% of children and 68% of students cannot control their emotions and feelings; about 45% of students and 43% of students believe that they are assessed unfairly or inadequately. As for parents, they indicate that they have to participate in resolving conflicts between the child and peers (42%) and teachers (36%).

In our opinion, students in this category especially need psychological support from their families: only 50% of children and 54% of students believe that their parents evaluate them fairly; 48% of children claim that their parents understand them; 61% of children and 47% of students will turn to

their parents for help. At the same time, 41% of parents would like to receive help from teachers and psychologists in raising their children. But only 53% of teachers do not experience difficulties in communicating with parents.

Analyzing communication needs, we studied the needs for approval (recognition) and social status (our own, parents). Satisfying the need for approval, in our opinion, is an important aspect of the life of gifted children: they often speak publicly (at Olympiads, contests, competitions) and seek increased attention. The majority of children (63.5%) and students (75.8%) believe that others are interested in their original ideas, while 13% of children and 11.1% of students indicated that their ideas are critical. 7.5% of schoolchildren and 2% of students say that their ideas are not noticed.

The results obtained during a sociological study of the needs of various groups of children are important for the effective organization of the pedagogical process at any level. The teacher needs to know and understand the needs of the audience with whom he works, to master the technologies of working with groups (classes), in which children may differ in their abilities, needs, and capabilities. The results of the study help to determine the needs of students and clarify the specifics of interaction with them in a heterogeneous environment. Understanding the problems children currently face stimulates the formation of an inclusive environment in educational organizations in the region.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed the main trends that can form the basis for the development and implementation of the concept and innovative model for training teachers and educational managers to work with heterogeneous groups of students, namely:

1. Children of different groups are ready and willing to study together with other children, which makes the creation of an inclusive environment a necessary condition for the successful socialization of students.
2. To increase the effectiveness of the educational process, children in heterogeneous groups (classes) need to be provided with opportunities for growth, manifestation of their abilities, and self-realization.
3. Students need psychological and pedagogical support both from the family and from qualified specialists in educational organizations.
4. The specifics of working with heterogeneous groups (classes) require professional training (retraining) of the teaching staff of schools (universities).
5. Creation of special conditions (availability of special benefits, equipment, etc.) and improvement of the material and technical base of educational organizations will help optimize the educational and cognitive process, and for disabled children will be a real step towards obtaining an education in a peer group.

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**THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE ON FOREIGN
LANGUAGE SKILLS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
A competency-based approach to teaching a foreign language, according to the author, is one technique to boost students' enthusiasm to learn the language, enhance activity and creativity, and strengthen their learning activities. The best practices for teaching foreign languages to students are outlined in this article, with a focus on competency-based learning.	communicative competence, foreign language, communication.

Introduction

The shift in the sociopolitical climate, the rise of international contacts in all fields, the consolidation of these contacts, and worldwide integration have increased the role and relevance of authentic foreign language communication skills and talents.

Rapid socioeconomic advancement necessitates high standards for the quality of foreign language teaching in educational institutions, as each new generation of students must achieve a better level of foreign language proficiency. Changes in the socio-cultural environment of a foreign language, as well as new student aspirations for fluency in it, entail a qualitative shift in teaching.

One of the most critical issues confronting educational institutions in conjunction with the modernization of domestic education is the establishment ofFor the first time the concept of "competence" appeared in the 60s. XX century . in the United States of America, where it was used as part of activity education, the purpose of which was to prepare professionals who are competitive in the labor market. Initially, it all came down to automating the acquired practical skills within the framework of the behavioral approach, which was clearly insufficient for the development of the creative and individual abilities of the trainees. In this regard, it was proposed to distinguish between two concepts: competence and competence (competence and competencies). Competence began to be considered as a personal category, and competencies turned into units of the curriculum and constituted the "autonomy" of competence.

Speaking of competencies, it is necessary to clarify the concept of "competence" - a set of competencies, that is, observable manifestations of successful productive activity. Competence is a complex personal resource that provides the possibility of effective interaction with the outside world in a particular area and depends on the competencies necessary for this.

What is meant by competency -based approach? The competency -based approach in education is understood as a teaching method that is aimed at developing students' abilities to solve a certain class of professional tasks in accordance with the requirements for personal professional qualities: the ability to search, analyze, select and process the information received, transmit the necessary information; possession of the skills of interaction with other people, the ability to work in a group; possession of mechanisms for planning, analysis, self-assessment of one's own activities in non-standard situations or in conditions of uncertainty; knowledge of methods and techniques for solving problems that have arisen.

The competence -based approach imposes certain requirements on students and their level of foreign language proficiency. In this regard, a distinction is made between basic and advanced competencies in students.

At the basic level, language proficiency is assumed as a means of communication (a certain vocabulary, knowledge of basic grammatical structures, knowledge of the laws of language functioning, familiarity with the cultural environment, etc.).

The advanced level assumes that students will use a foreign language to solve practical problems, for example, to find the necessary information on the profile of their specialty. This level is interdisciplinary in nature and is assessed by the result achieved, and not only by the correct use of certain grammatical structures and active vocabulary.

The main means of forming key competencies in the study of a foreign language are various technologies, forms and methods of teaching. These forms and methods include: the teacher's monologue; frontal-individual survey; informing conversations; independent work with the textbook on the instructions of the teacher; film demonstration; traditional test.

Researchers of the competency-based approach to learning propose three important competency classifications:

1) value-semantic, 2) general cultural, 3) educational and cognitive, 4) informational, 5) communicative, 6) social and labor, and 7) personal growth.

A competency-based approach to foreign language teaching necessitates a creative approach to organizing and structuring the educational process, so establishing conditions for the formation and development of practical skills and abilities in foreign language communication. As a result, it is vital to attempt to establish such settings in the classroom, where students assimilate linguistic information in a natural manner, and in the process of communication between the teacher and students in life scenarios that we mimic in many ways.

The development of pupils' capabilities is dependent on their

First of all, students need to understand the nature and content of competency-based approaches.

Students need to acquire certain intellectual, creative and communication skills.

This means that you must be able to manipulate texts (highlighting main ideas, finding the necessary information in foreign language texts), analyzing information, making generalizations and conclusions, working with various reference materials, etc.

It means that.

Leads the discussion, listens to the opinion of the interlocutor, defends the opponent's point of view, supports it with strong arguments, is able to compromise with the interlocutor, expresses one's ideas concisely.

Additionally, students must be able to work in a variety of organizational formats: pairs, groups, and teams with clear role divisions (e.g.

boss, secretary, etc.).

Practical knowledge of a foreign language requires students to master specific programs and vocabulary/grammar materials, to be able to engage in correspondence in a foreign language, and to be able to independently compose various documents in Russian and foreign languages.

not.

Manage business deals in foreign languages.

Thus, for the competent use of the competence -based approach, considerable preparation is required, the creation of a solid language base for students, which is carried out in the education system.

In turn, the high quality of learning a foreign language contributes to the competitiveness and professional mobility in the field of professional activity and communication of the future specialist. The acquisition of foreign language competence by students consists in mastering a foreign language at a level that will allow it to be used to meet professional needs, implement business contacts and further professional self-education and self-improvement.

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**VALIDITY OF PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS
TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
The article analyzes the issue of the need to evaluate the work of primary school teachers.	Knowledge, teacher education skills assessment activities.

Introduction

In the world education system, the process of innovative development is currently taking place at a rapid pace. The main goal is to focus on imparting knowledge to students in convenient and acceptable ways, based on effective technologies, and introducing the latest innovations into the education system. International educational programs and educational structures of the United Nations serve as a program for our country in the implementation of these works. In this regard, the activities of this organization aimed at the development of the world education system by UNESCO and UNICEF organizations are of great importance in the world education system. As a result, it should be noted that the influence and responsibility of the greatest profession holders - teachers who carry out education is increasing based on modern requirements.

Primary education is an important stage in the world school education system. Because it is the primary education system that fulfills the task of forming the literacy of students, introducing them to the world of knowledge, and implementing the initial education and training process. Today, in the educational system of the countries of the world, the stage of primary education has begun to fulfill the task of preparing students for the next stages of general secondary and specialized education. Therefore, the process of increasing the authority of primary school teachers around the world, strengthening their responsibility, and almost all countries' educational systems are moving towards quality education based on the results of research and evaluation of the activities of primary school teachers. special attention is paid to issues of achievement. Especially in this regard, the main attention is paid to the evaluation of the activities of elementary school teachers and the development of the basis of development based on research results based on international assessment programs such as TALIS, EGMA, EGRA.

We all know that the education system in our country, including the primary education stage, is undergoing strategic reforms in line with these processes. That is why the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" program set the task of achieving quality education in our country. According to this program, evaluating the activities of primary school teachers is one of the important bases for

achieving quality education. In this regard, it is especially important to be based on international assessment programs with greater effectiveness.

Today, in the educational system of the countries of the world, researches are being carried out to study the activities of teachers based on a number of international evaluation programs. One of them is the international assessment program TALIS (Creating conditions for teachers based on international requirements). On the basis of this program, starting from 2021, with the participation of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, intensive preparations are being made for evaluating the work of teachers in our country. Because in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 987 of December 8, 2018 "On measures to organize international research in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system", the TALIS international evaluation program of teachers' activities in our country on the basis of which the task of learning is determined.

The TALIS international assessment program focuses on studying the following issues:

- 1) studying the activities of teachers working in general education institutions;
- 2) studying the working conditions created for teachers;
- 3) studying the educational environment.

The TALIS international evaluation program is of great theoretical, methodological and practical importance in evaluating the activities of elementary school teachers in our country and improving their effectiveness. All this requires a special study of the methodological features of the assessment of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program.

"On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, "On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026" dated May 11, 2020 gi, Decrees of December 21, 2022 "On Measures for the Implementation of New Uzbekistan Administrative Reforms" and "Evaluation of the Quality of Education in the Public Education System" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks set in the Decision "On measures for the organization of international research in the field of

U. Begimkulov, R. Jorayev, Sh. Mardonov, R. Safarova, Sh. In the researches of Olimov and others, important theoretical views on the study of teachers' activities have been described.

Uzbek scientists G. Muhamedov, S. Matchonov, U. Khojamkulov, Kh. Muradov have developed practical recommendations for studying the educational environment and developing the educational environment based on them.

Foreign pedagogic scientists K. Rogers, N. Bernstam, A. Khomeini formulated recommendations on the methods of evaluating the educational activities of the countries of the world based on international programs.

At the moment, the problem of methodological features of the assessment of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program has not been studied as a special study. Therefore, it is necessary to study this problem in a special dissertation form.

One of the main issues indicated in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan is the achievement of quality education in the country. This issue is directly based on the effectiveness of teachers. In the education development programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks of evaluating the work efficiency of teachers are set as a means of studying the activities of teachers. In particular, in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, the 2nd direction of the state program "Year of attention to

people and quality education" "Social reforms" is defined as "one of the main tasks of increasing the prestige of the teaching profession in society and improving their conditions". . All this requires regular evaluation of the work of primary school teachers. We draw your attention to the analysis of the need for evaluation. [2, 4 b].

Evaluating the work of teachers is to study their knowledge, skills and qualifications. But "teacher performance evaluation" does not mean "teacher performance inspection", it should be distinguished. Because assessment is based on the learning method, and inspection focuses on the teacher's performance. This approach is based on various learning tools, methods and criteria for evaluating teachers' performance. For example, it is important to be based on the following requirements when evaluating the activities of primary school teachers:

1. The need to assess professional knowledge. According to it, the level of professional knowledge of primary school teachers in practical activities is evaluated according to the following criteria:
 - based on the scientific foundations of professional knowledge;
 - theoretical basis of professional knowledge;
 - enrichment of professional knowledge with information.

The teacher's professional knowledge with scientific foundations is the basis of becoming a mature specialist. For example, it is required that a primary school teacher has a scientific understanding of the basics of primary education subjects, and the professional knowledge of a primary school teacher has a theoretical basis. Because a teacher should be aware of the theory of education. Also, it is required that the professional knowledge of a primary school teacher has various information on specific, natural and humanitarian educational subjects. Therefore, when studying the level of professional knowledge of a primary school teacher, his scientific-theoretical concepts as a specialist are determined. Various methods and tools are used in this work. Recently, the use of the Test method consisting of a special questionnaire in this regard has become popular, and such tests reflect the questionnaires that clearly show the level of professional knowledge of the primary school teacher. Karl Thomson, a foreign pedagogical scientist, developed a test to determine the level of professional knowledge of specialists, and the countries of the world are based on this test in most cases. Pay attention to the following questions of this Test as an example:

1. What is a scientific concept?
 - a) proven fact
 - b) reasoned opinion
 - c) I don't know
2. What is a scientific hypothesis?
 - a) proven opinion
 - b) prediction
 - c) I don't know

It is clear from this sample that the main focus of K. Thomson's test is on determining the scientific understanding of teachers. In fact, the basis of the teacher's profession is scientific knowledge.

2. Assessment of professional skills. To evaluate the performance of primary school teachers, the following are taken into account when determining the level of their professional skills:

- that the teacher has his own style;
- ability to work individually with students;
- professional activity of the teacher.

In the theory and history of pedagogy, the fact that primary school teachers have their own style is fully justified. In this, the teacher should rely on the most effective methods in the process of teaching and education. Because a primary school teacher has his own style throughout his career. In addition, a primary school teacher should be able to work individually with each student. Today there are certain complications in this matter. Because there are more than 30 students in each class, the teacher does not have enough time to work with each of them individually. Taking this into account, the state program "Year of attention to people and quality education" set the task of setting the number of students to 20, which allows the teacher to work individually with each student. The professional activity of a primary school teacher is determined by the interestingness of the teacher's training, the work with additional information, and the formation of an independent fiction in each student. [3, 5 b].

A special approach should be taken to the evaluation of the professional skills of the primary school teacher. This makes it possible to correctly evaluate the basics of the teacher's activity.

3. Evaluation of the competence to work on oneself. When evaluating the performance of a primary school teacher, in order to study his competence to work on himself, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- the ability to work with textbooks;
- the ability to work with additional information;
- the ability to share one's experience.

A primary school teacher must have the skills to work with textbooks. Today, more than ten textbooks are used in primary education, and the teacher is required to work according to these textbooks.

When conducting research on this issue, it is appropriate to set the following tasks:

- To study the theoretical issues of evaluating the activity of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program;
- Development of a regional method for evaluating the activities of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program;
- Creation of a central method for evaluating the activities of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program;
- Conducting pedagogical experiments on the effectiveness of evaluating the activities of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program and formulating recommendations based on their results.

As a result, the theoretical issues of evaluating the activity of elementary school teachers based on the TALIS international program are studied on the basis of the views, approaches and methodological directions put forward in pedagogical scientific research, the basics of the regional evaluation method of the activity of elementary school teachers based on the TALIS international program, forms and mechanisms will be developed and the evaluation of the educational system will be presented to state organizations.

A central method for evaluating the activity of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program has been created, and its modeled form is recommended to republican state management institutions for evaluating the effectiveness of education.

On the basis of TALIS international program, pedagogical experiments on the effectiveness of evaluation of primary school teachers are conducted, and based on their results, recommendations on the solution of the problem are formed.

Therefore, it is possible to come to the following conclusions regarding the issue:

1. In the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan and its state program "Year of attention to people and quality education", quality education by means of raising the authority of teachers in society, creating suitable working conditions for them and increasing the effectiveness of teachers' activities limit is reached.
2. The necessity of an honest assessment of the activities of primary school teachers is determined by assessing their professional knowledge, skill levels and self-efficacy. It is important to be based on the rules and requirements of the TALIS international program.
3. The goals and objectives of the TALIS international program are to evaluate the activities of teachers, their working conditions and the educational environment at school, which requires the study of the working conditions and qualification level of primary school teachers working in the educational system of our country.
4. Based on TALIS international program, it will be possible to develop new development programs in this direction by evaluating the activities of primary school teachers. All this shows the importance and relevance of the scope of theoretical issues of evaluating the activities of primary school teachers based on the TALIS international program.

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THE MOST IMPORTANT CHARACTER OF KHUVAYDO'S WORK

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>This article explores the poet of Huvaydo, a major representative of mysticism poetry, exploring the thematic wealth, linguistic nuances and emotional power that define his lyrical style. It concludes with reflections on the impact of Huvaydo's lyricism and suggestions for further research.</p>	<p>Huvaydo, lyrics, thematic wealth, linguistic nuances, emotional strength, influences, inspirations, creative process.</p>

Introduction

Huwaydo pseudonym; real name Khojanazar Kheyibnazar son (born 1704 — in Osh-died 1780/81, in the village of Chimyon, Fergana province.) is a poet, a major representative of mysticism poetry. Huwaydo has composed in almost all genres of classical poetry. Huwaido's poems were posthumously brought to devon by his grandchildren. It included 351 ghazals, 28 ruboiyas, 41 quatrains, 3 mukhammas, 1 musaddas, 1 musamman, 1 mustazad, 3 masnavias, as well as the “Rohati dil” manzuma of Ahly-didactic content.

Huwaydo continued the traditions of didactic prose and epic writing in our classical literature, creating “Rohati dil” and “Ibrahim Adham”. Humanity is led by loqaydism, ignorance, ignorance into degradation. Away from the good. Condemns to spiritual poverty. That is why representatives of our classical literature considered it an important task, duty, to educate a harmonious person. Contemporaries were guided by maturation, spiritual treasures. In particular, Huwaydo dedicated the epic” Rohati dil " to the same problems. His epic, written on a Masonic road, is popular with the people. He complements, teranizes the content, idea in his poems. The poet devotes a special little chapter to the reason for the writing of the epic. From him we will learn information about the genealogy of the poet, his place of birth, his name sharifi. In addition to being a work of a philosophical and mystical spirit, the epic” Rohati dil " also has a number of interesting places for the poet's translator. The reasons for the writing of the book are also understood from the epic preface:

The book of my father is “the pleasure of the heart”

Every word of Erur is unaware of its reprimand...

Hence, the poet's purpose in writing” pleasure dil " is to awaken his contemporaries from spiritual ignorance. He originally wrote the work in prose. Later, taking into account the demands and suggestions, he recreated it through nazm. The Epic is written in Turkic language, due to the fact that the inhabitants of the city of Chimyon, where the poet lived all his life, were turkigos. The saga

consists of 30 chapters and the story of Abraham Adham. The work traditionally began with praise to Allah and NA't to the prophets. Then the description of the instructive activities of the chahoryors - Abu Bakr Siddiq, Umar, Uthman and Ali-is given. Sharia law-rules, requirements commented. After that, a number of pandoma stories are listed. "Rohati dil" is conceived by themes such as enriching the inner world of man, consciously following the Ruks of Islamic sharia with deep faith. One group of images in them are images that evoke faith, purity, honesty, purity, humanity, and the second group is anger, hatred. Thus, manzuma is a work dedicated to influencing the people through literary means, images, poetry of Sharia instruction, which has been described and promoted in our centuries-old literature. "Rohati dil" is a religious-didactic work in which the universal ideas of Islam and the doctrine of mysticism are analyzed through the medium of instructive narratives. Anger in the world, the consequences of being a slave to the soul, the glory of learning, the glory of the people of science; fulfilling the duty of childhood to the parents and obtaining their consent; the consequence of kindness of the neighbors to each other; the fact that a couple places affection, self-esteem on each other; the virtue of human nature, such as hypocrisy, betrayal, condescension, arrogance, hypocrisy-that defects stand at the center of the work. Each of these problems is explained in a simple, understandable language in a folk style in short voluminous stories. This work is aimed at raising a perfect person. A person is encouraged to know himself, to lose his defects in nature. The work does not have a holistic plot line. But there is a single generalization in it that unites thought, idea, content - the question of perfect human upbringing. The epic "Rohati dil", as mentioned above, consists of 30 chapters, beginning with praise and Naat. Then comes the "coffin of Gabriel". The story says that Gabriel brought a coffin to Muhammad Mustafa, saying that it was a sign of death. Then, while the Prophet believed in the truth of death, I am with all the vagabonds of this world. I cannot leave them in disgrace and go to the throne by myself, I must intercede for them, I must go to the right path in this exam-duyodin passage, which answers in its content.

"Rohati dil" is a work aimed at studying the history of religion through literature, which has existed in our centuries-old literature. Unfortunately, this saga with zamana zailey has not been published in time. In this book, the philosophical worldview of man, the most subtle linguistic feelings for the creator, as well as the best human qualities that every Muslim child knows, such as sobriety, prayer, honesty, truthfulness, purity in faith, are sung, both obligatory and borrowed. While the work is not lined up in the lines of a special holistic plot and composition, the interconnection in the stories, or rather, the one-by-one exposition of each narrative, inextricably linked in content, indicates the harmony of content with the form. The work has a plan that keeps thought-ideas umulized and United. He is a question of perfect man. In the center of the work lies the servant - man, created by Allah in the Muslim world. All stories, themes, thoughts in the work are aimed at illuminating the essence, conditions, signs of perfection. In the Muslim world, it is a sacred tradition that every noble, charitable work performed by amalgam begins with the divine sentence "Bismillohir-rahmonir rahim". In the Eastern Epic, in the Middle Ages, all Saras began with the praise of God. Huwaydo also begins his epic with the praise of Allah, following this tradition. In it, the poet described with great pleasure the fact that the God who created everything, from heaven and the sun, every particle, all plants, and the animal world, the Society of man, guided by his high mind, his love for each person, moved, connected and intertwined. For God's kindness, everything in the universe thanked him for every particle and praised him.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, the peculiarities of Huvaydo's lyrics lie in the convergence of thematic wealth, linguistic nuances and emotional strength. His ability to draw from countless influences and instill his personal experiences in his AARs sets him apart in his competitive poetic industry. Hoover's lyrics not only entertain, but also provoke thought and constantly affect the audience.

As Huvaido continues to develop as a poet, cultural, historical and philosophical influences can be explored further into his work. In addition, research carried out in collaboration with literary experts can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of his lyrics. Future research can also add a socio-cultural dimension to analysis by studying the perception and interpretation of Huwaydo lyrics by different audiences.

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**FOUNDATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION
MANAGEMENT: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL
FRAMEWORKS**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>In contemporary times, the efficacy of any endeavour hinges significantly on the adeptness of its management. Amidst heightened competition, the imperative to continually refine leadership practices transcends every domain. Today's leaders are compelled to embody qualities of independence, creativity, and entrepreneurial acumen within the confines of legal frameworks, courageously shouldering accountability for their decisions. The essence lies in the ability to tactically assume calculated risks while upholding the principles of a law-abiding, disciplined society, all while unequivocally respecting universally recognized human rights and freedoms. The pressing need of the hour is the theoretical evolution of a unified model for modern leadership, an imperative that permeates through various sectors, particularly in educational institution management. This paradigmatic shift necessitates a reevaluation and consolidation of theoretical and methodological frameworks, striving towards an amalgamation that caters to the complex demands of contemporary leadership. The quest for this unified model persists, aiming to synergize diverse leadership tenets into a cohesive, adaptable structure capable of navigating the multifaceted landscape of educational institution management. Aim: to encapsulate the essence of contemporary leadership requisites and the pressing need for a unified theoretical model, particularly within the sphere of educational institution management. Adjustments can be made based on the specific focus or emphasis required for your piece.</p>	<p>Leadership Development, Management Theory, Educational Institution Management, Modern Leadership, Legal Compliance, Accountability, Entrepreneurial Leadership, Human Rights, Unified Leadership Model, Methodological Frameworks.</p>

Introduction

In today's competitive landscape, the efficacy of any venture is profoundly intertwined with the calibre of its leadership. The current era demands an evolution in leadership methodologies across various sectors. A contemporary leader must embody attributes of independence, creativity, and entrepreneurial spirit while adhering to legal boundaries and embracing accountability for their decisions. The capacity to navigate calculated risks within the framework of a law-abiding, disciplined

society, all while upholding fundamental human rights and freedoms, defines the essence of modern leadership [1,2].

Amidst these dynamics, the quest for a unified theoretical model of leadership becomes increasingly crucial, particularly within the realm of educational institution management. This pursuit necessitates a critical reexamination and consolidation of theoretical and methodological frameworks. The aspiration is to forge a comprehensive, adaptable structure that harmonizes diverse leadership principles into a cohesive model capable of addressing the multifaceted challenges inherent in managing educational institutions. This endeavour underscores the pressing need to synthesize varied leadership paradigms into a cohesive framework, aligning with contemporary demands and aspirations for effective educational institution management. Experience shows that one of the main causes of deficiencies in children's education is related to management psychology. But it is often not paid attention to. Therefore, it is important to study the management of educational institutions from a psychological point of view, to develop socio-psychological ways of its successful management [3,4].

To successfully manage an educational institution, it is necessary to study the composition of the team, correct its shortcomings and form it as a real pedagogical team. The purpose of the study is to study the social psychological features of management of educational institutions based on modern management approaches.

Literature Review

I.Ansoff, T.Bush, B.R. from foreign scientists on the management of the quality of education, organization of management activities of the educational system and professional development of the heads of various departments, directions and problems of improving their qualifications. Clark, F. A. van Vught, P. Hallinger, E. L. Horng, J. W. Valentine, R. Bolam, L. Cuban, J. Lauglo, K. Leithwood, P. Sammons, R. Webb and others have carried out several scientific studies [5,6,7].

Heads of educational institutions on some aspects of management activities and the problems of introducing strategic management in educational systems from CIS scientists Yu.A. Konarzhevsky, G.A. Balkhin, V.A. Gurtov, Ye.A. Pitukhin, L.M. Serova, T.I.Shamova, P.I.Tretyakov, E.D.Dneprov, G.I.Maltseva, T.M.Davydenko conducted scientific research [8,9,10].

Management, management of the educational system in Uzbekistan, problems of training, retraining and professional development of managers in it. Researched by Ikromov, A.S. Kucharov, D.S. Kasimova, L.V. Peregudov, M.Kh. Saidov, Sh.E. Kurbanov, E.A. Seitkhalilov, M.M. Mirqosimov, R.H. Djuraev, S. Turgunov, N. Akhmedova and others [11,12,13,14].

Also, U.I. Inoyatov, R.Sh. Ahlidinov, J.G. Yoldoshev, S.A. Usmanov and others in the direction of developing the theoretical and methodological foundations of the management of the educational system and institutions, improving the effectiveness of management activities of the heads of general secondary schools, and the management of the quality of education who conducted scientific research [16,17].

Methodology

Today, the large-scale reforms implemented in our country require the study of the importance of management in the training of management personnel and employees in the field of management. The result of the reforms aimed at building a socially oriented democratic, free civil society today remains

integrally dependent on such mature leaders and management specialists. This, in turn, shows the need to rely on the principles of democratization, renewal of society, modernization and reform of the country, and strengthening of its economic and political independence to realize the goals, interests and aspirations that are manifested in various ways in this direction.

At this point, the question arises, what periods does the history of the development of management correspond to? What has it looked like so far? We know that in ancient times, people lived as a tribe, and at that time there was a need to protect the tribe from external military invasions, to defend their land, to conduct internal and external relations of the community, and to hold discussions on various issues. To fulfil these tasks, the members of the team agreed to appoint a leader from among them. In this way, the development of social and economic relations led to the separation of people who deserve special respect and attention in society. They were not constantly engaged in the production process, but only exercised control and leadership over social and economic life. It should be emphasized that the first states appeared between ancient Egypt and two rivers (Tigris and Euphrates) 5 thousand years ago. Then the state system was formed one after the other 4-3.5 thousand years ago in the regions of Greece, Asia Minor, Iran, South Caucasus, India, China and Central Asia. A certain share was added to management in ancient times, 400 years before our era, Socrates formulated the principle of universality of management [18,19,20]. In 325 BC, Alexander the Great established a headquarters for the first time as a centre for directing military operations. Old organizations had a certain structure, in which the levels of management were separated. Large political organizations also existed, and kings and generals were their leaders. There were also managers, warehouse keepers, freight drivers, work supervisors, regional governors and treasurers who helped to ensure the activities of these organizations [21]. As a result of the above-mentioned factors, the social and economic basis of management was formed. Territorial functions of management have existed since ancient times, and these functions arose from the need to control and manage the relations of rural communities, districts, and regional residents. It can be seen that the foundations and principles of management in Uzbekistan have a deep history. Many modern researchers say that the emergence of the concept of "management" in the world of science is connected with the formation of market principles in the economic sphere. This scientific concept was mentioned for the first time at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. "Management" in its original meaning means managerial activity. Management is a type of human activity, which is the management of production using a system of management principles, methods, tools and forms developed and applied to increase production efficiency (to achieve the goal) [22].

Management as a broad concept, as one of the theorists of management and its organization in the world, Peter Drucker, said, "is a special type of activity that transforms an unorganized chaotic mass into an effective and productive group focused on one goal, a society, and encourages social change. "is a stimulating element" [23]. The concept of management was defined by foreign scientists as a process of planning, organization, motivation and control [24]. And RFDrucker assessed management as "a special type of activity that transforms a chaotic crowd into an effective and productive group" [25]. Academicians M. Sharifkhujayev, SSGulomov, a member of the Academy of Agricultural Sciences SSGulomov, professors Sh.M. Zaynudsinov, Yo.A. Abdullaev, K.A. Abdurakhmonov, who contributed to the development of management theory and practice in our country, professors Sh. Studying the research and scientific works of J.G.Yuldoshev, R. ShAkhlidinov, E. Seytkhalilov, M. Kuronov, L.V.Peregudov, M.X.Saidov, U.L.Inoyatov, X.F.Rashidov and other scientists in this field

is especially important. For example, S. Ghulomov gives the following definitions of management in his book "Fundamentals of Management":

1. Management is a special type of management related to the economy, based on market relations.
2. Management envisages revenue and profit based on economic management methods.
3. Management is a purposeful management method or management aimed at the efficient organization of work.
4. This is a management that sees product quality and labour productivity as its mission.
5. Management is highly skilled management. This is a type of organizational activity, an important part of which is a comprehensive and accurate analysis of specific management conditions, development of new projects, tactics and strategies of organizational development, as well as others.
6. Management considers itself a flexible and flexible management system, capable of timely restructuring, market conditions, competition, and social development factors.
7. Management is an activity that involves the art of preparing, organizing and directing human actions [26]. By M. Qasimova: -Management is the planning of relations and activities in achieving the organization's goal, organization of effective use of resources, reasonable coordination of labour distribution, fair application of the mechanism of inclination among employees and control of their implementation. For this purpose, information about events, processes, relationships and services is sorted, processed, analyzed, studied, management solutions are adopted, and leaders lead" [27].

M. Sharifho'jaev and Y. Abdullaev: — "Management is the process of management, management of resources, people, effective activity and knowing how to get profit, increase it. From this point of view, management is a choice that requires a certain high art and skill, making decisions based on this choice and controlling its implementation. Management is ownership and leadership of an organization, realizing a goal through management, learning how competitors behave, forming a new management mindset, and finding solutions to problems in organizing the organizational structure of management based on the requirements of the market situation. This, in turn, is manifested in the organization, planning, control, coordination of interaction in the work of the organization, implementation of work through the use of the potential of the organization." - described as.

Management is an important influencing force not only within the enterprise but also the entire society, leading the state to its chosen path, goals and aspirations, turning it into a strong, stable working mechanism in the development of the economy [28]. The main goal of management is to ensure harmony in the development of the organization, i.e. to ensure the coordinated and efficient operation of all external and internal elements of the organization [29]. Management should be studied by connecting it with the economic base of the society, taking into account its two aspects: organizational-technical and socio-economic.

Organizational and technical management is characterized by the division of labour and cooperation in imparting knowledge to obtain a sufficient level of educated mature specialists. Socio-economic management is related to existing institutional relations and defines management goals. Organizational and technical management consists of a type of activity that allows to creation of conditions for the increase of labor productivity and efficiency of education. The goal of socio-economic management is to create conditions for workers to work effectively, to form a reliable national system of social protection for them, to ensure employment and to support the disadvantaged sections of the population. Management has its objects and subjects, just as each science or each

direction has its object and subject, and in general, management consists of the cooperation of two objects aimed at the goal, where one of them is in the place of the subject of control, and the other is in the place of the object of control. The following are typical for this interaction:

Management subject means a legal or physical entity arising as a result of the influence of the administration. The governing authority of the subject of management, its economic and moral-ethical influence is the basis of the management process will be informed)

Management objects and can be a physical-economic system and processes directed by the administration subject under the influence of the administration. One structure of the organization can be both the subject and the object of administration [30]. (They carry out all the orders given by the subject of management and act following them). So, we can take as examples of management objects labour teams and employees, and management subjects as institutions and their leaders.

Management methods encourage people to fulfil the requirements of objective socio-economic development laws of society. They represent a specific method, method, and way to achieve the goal. We can say that the management style is the coordination of the activities of workers and employees in the process of achieving the goal set for the management object in general. Management methods can be divided into administrative-organizational, economic, social-psychological and legal forms according to the specific characteristics of influence.

The skill of management consists of having the ability to master all methods, to use them correctly, to find the most effective one in each specific situation. Currently, the movement of a scientific approach to the management of a single pedagogical process has increased. This is very important for the formation of personnel with high intellectual potential.

Management is of great importance in the social development of labour teams. Because the fate of all our work and plans depends to a large extent on the level of improvement of team relations, and on the health of the "social microclimate". In this respect, the goal of management is to improve public administration and turn it into social self-management.

Management of society and the spiritual development of individual members is another major type of management. In the age of scientific and technical development, management of the sphere of spiritual production is of great importance. This form of management includes management of educational institutions, public education bodies, science, literature, art, culture and health care.

Management is compared to the human brain, in which the creative potential of a person is embodied, from which instructions are given for the manifestation of his creative ability. In fact, management is a very complex process and requires a lot of effort and energy from a person. There are established methods, instructions, and theories in management, in which the aspects of management and the laws of management are clearly shown.

If we talk about the theoretical aspects of management, its main tasks are as follows:

- study the theoretical foundations of management;
- study and practice the main methods of management in the conditions of the market economy;
- acquisition of professional knowledge in the field of management activities;
- provide an understanding of management principles and functions;
- formation of communication skills and their use in the management process;
- providing knowledge about the style and culture of professional skills in leadership activities;
- study and analysis of the management system in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- These include studying foreign experiences, teaching and learning based on their comparison.

Since management is mainly the management of people and society, organization of work, creation of workplaces and conditions, control over the performance of specified tasks, application of efficiency indicators in the evaluation of activity results, and in addition, the psychology and culture of the leader in management requiring them to have a unique style and studying them is the basis for the development of management theory. The following can be cited as specific methods of seeking to coordinate the activities of the employees of the organization in the process of achieving the goal set for the management object in general:

1. The system method is used in solving management problems and is based on the system as a whole. In developed countries, there are systematic complex, systematic content, systematic functional, systematic communication and other concepts.
2. A complex method of research involves events and their interrelationships
3. communicate not only with this method of science but with other sciences dealing with the same phenomena.
4. The structural method of research consists of dividing complex phenomena into parts.
5. A situational approach is to determine the optimal methods of management activities depending on internal and external conditions.
6. An integrative approach is a method of searching for other methods

It is management based on the accounting of suppliers.

7. Modeling is a method of managing a controlled object using various schemes, graphs and drawings, and preparation of sketch materials.
8. Mathematical approach-Mathematical methods and computers are widely used to make optimal decisions.
9. The observation method is a method of collecting information about the object of management on a planned, scientific, and organized basis.
10. Apply proven methods to a controlled object. In addition, the most basic cognitive method of management is the dialectical method, which helps management to reveal the essence of the studied social phenomena. The skill of management consists of having the ability to master all methods, evaluate them correctly, and find the most effective one in each specific situation.

Conclusions

Based on the above-mentioned scientific and theoretical information, management is being formed and developing today. In the course of the reforms implemented in our country, great attention is being paid to the improvement of leadership, reform and development of the management system. Management is to make people interested in conscious work and entrepreneurship, to control their responsibility for work, to ensure that their knowledge and skills have a positive effect on their activities, and to organize incentives. The subject of this science consists of a set of theoretical and practical principles that represent the forms and methods of organizing management at all levels of economic management. A leader who has mastered management methods and can effectively manage this activity has a great influence not only on production but also on the development of the entire economy. The most important task of today is to "create a new thinker in all areas of our life, especially in management, at the republican level, in the management of regions, districts, villages and neighbourhoods, and in the management of network nodes, who can take responsibility in difficult

times, with life. it is to find people who can keep pace, have pure faith, are knowledgeable, and are business people, and to express trust in them.

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**ADVANCEMENTS IN EDUCATIONAL WEB RESOURCE
DEVELOPMENT**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>With the pervasive integration of contemporary information, communication, and pedagogical technologies, including electronic textbooks and multimedia tools, the educational landscape in the country's schools, vocational colleges, academic lyceums, and higher education institutions is experiencing a profound transformation. This concerted effort aims at a fundamental elevation of educational quality. Central to this endeavour is the strategic enhancement of educational and laboratory infrastructures through the infusion of cutting-edge educational and laboratory equipment, alongside state-of-the-art computer resources. Simultaneously, concerted efforts are directed towards cultivating an effective system aimed at materially and morally incentivizing the dedicated efforts of educators and instructors. This article delves into the intricate process of creating electronic information educational resources. It outlines their diverse types and structural elements while elucidating the stringent requisites for their development. Emphasizing the significance of these resources, the discussion navigates through the nuances of their creation, offering insights into their intricate design and delineating the requisite criteria for their seamless development. The aim is to encapsulate the essence of the article, emphasizing the transformational impact of modern technologies on educational institutions and shedding light on the process and significance of creating electronic information educational resources. Adjustments can be made based on the specific emphasis or details required for your piece.</p>	<p>Electronic Textbooks, Multimedia Tools, Educational Technology, Information Resources, Pedagogical Technologies, Educational Infrastructure, Laboratory Equipment, Computer Resources, Teacher Incentives, Educational Quality Enhancement.</p>

Introduction

Today it is inappropriate to talk about the popularity of the Internet. The Internet has become a part of our life, we are used to using its services every day. At present, a voluntary person can imagine that web technology has penetrated the food, commerce, politics, entertainment, and business sectors of human life and becomes a witness user of it. The Internet is bringing different people together with a common goal. Everyone tries to get some kind of information from the Internet.

There will come a time when the ability to print a document on the Internet, as well as to use a typewriter, is within the reach of every person with even an intermediate level of education. Good

memory ability, clear thinking, and a high level of mental thinking are considered important for mastering web programming languages. However, the diversity of people's worldview does not affect the uniqueness of intellect and cognitive processes. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, great changes took place in the field of education. In particular, problems related to the introduction of information technologies into the educational system, the study of the possibilities of computer technologies, and the creation of modern web resources for higher educational institutions and academic lyceums are urgent issues.

Significant results are being achieved with the application of information technology software, the Internet, the development process, and other areas. For example, A. Abdukadirov, A. Abdullayev, M. Boltayeva, V. Vergasov, P. Galperin, S. Godnik Aripov M.M., Yakubov A.Kh., Sagatov M.V., Irmuhamedova R.M. Shamis V.A. In the work of Borland and others, the pedagogical and psychological foundations of independent learning of pupils or students were studied.

Requirements for the creation of electronic information educational resources

Pedagogical requirements for the creation of electronic information educational resources are as follows.

- enriching with audio files, animation, emotional impact, etc. in order to ensure easier assimilation of the studied course material, unlike textbooks in paper version;
- compliance with the level of knowledge and professional competence of the listener;
- created taking into account the emotional and physical potential of the listener;
- visualization of the topic with the help of animation or other similar audio-visual means (trigger the visual receptor) as much as possible in accordance with the content of the lesson;
- free of large calculations;
- paying more attention to the content of the studied subject, creating conditions for solving problems and examples;
- to create an opportunity to control oneself in the cross-section of topics at any stage of the studied subject;
- create the possibility to transfer the written work prepared on the studied subject to any information carrier, to present it using a disk or other information carrier;
- use keywords, additional literature, hyperlinks, and help functions as much as possible in studying the subject.

Educational and methodological requirements are also set for the creation of electronic information educational resources. They are:

Educational and methodological requirements for the creation of electronic information educational resources (EIER):

- analysis by solving a large number of problems or changing primary data;
- use of graphic interpretations;
- creating conditions for the teacher to conduct the lesson in the form of an independent lesson, in this case participating in the role of a listening consultant;
- providing an opportunity to control the level of knowledge acquired by pedagogic learners with the help of tests of different complexity (formulated according to the level of complexity);
- creating an opportunity to prepare for lessons in a way convenient for the pedagogue (slides, text,

presentation, video material, etc.).

EIER must be able to perform certain functional tasks. Therefore, functional requirements are also imposed on their creation. Before elucidating the functional requirements for the creation of EIER and their essence, it is desirable to understand the dictionary meaning of the concept of "functionality".

Functional requirements for creating an EIER:

- content– similar to a paper version of a book, it is searchable by keywords, enriched with additional information that complements the subject;
- Flexibility(depending on the student's level of mastery, returning to the subject, working on the subject at an individual pace);
- multi-terminal-static data analysis availability of opportunity;
- ability to analyse the listener's frequency of using EIER, test results, correct and incorrect answers, in which questions he made more mistakes;
- interactivity- imitation of natural communication (having the opportunity to feel the presence of the pedagogue using a questionnaire, verbal, non-verbal, voice, etc., establishing a dialogue between the EIER text and the listener);
- control and analysis (EIER's ability to understand the essence of questions asked by listeners, to help them understand, to create an opportunity to control the level of successful learning of the training module);
- providing feedback and individuality(creating an opportunity to correct mistakes and shortcomings made by the student in mastering the educational module with the help of complementary and advisory programs during the educational process).

Therefore, the following are the functional requirements for the creation of the EIER:

According to NAMuslimov, EIER, which is the most common type of EIER, must meet the following requirements:

1. able to meet the requirements for the publication of the curriculum and educational-methodical works (confirmed by the scientific-methodical council of the Higher Education Institution);
2. EIER is prepared as an electronic version of a methodical manual that is being presented for the first time or previously published in a specific field and is related to a general or special course in terms of content;
3. possession of a volume that allows to reveal the content of a certain educational course (or its part) and to achieve educational and methodological goals;
4. OPossession of visual elements that help to achieve teaching-methodical goals (possibility of using the computer's multimedia capabilities to the maximum extent);
5. taking into account the feature of viewing the material on the monitor screen and placing it on the network;
6. of hyperlinks in the text existence, in the present tenseDisplay of web resources and management information resources;
7. the presence of control questions that allow the listener to independently assess the level of mastery of the material;
8. working in many languages and creating special conditions for disabled listeners.

EIER is created based on a pedagogical script that is goal-oriented, designed for the development of the individual, and has methodological consistency of pedagogical methods and technologies to

achieve the educational goal. The structure of the educational material and its placement in the educational staff is carried out according to the script.

Conclusions

Therefore, it is appropriate to take certain circumstances into account when developing the EIER scenario. Taking into account the following situations when developing the EIER scenario will make it possible for the listener to use it easily and comfortably:

1. all educational material should be logically completed, one topic should be covered in each module, each lesson should consist of theoretical and practical parts, a section of exercises for the test, and a homework section;
2. those who make up the theoretical part displayed in the window and placed in the frame, visual multimedia material should not be overlooked that it is of great importance in enhancing the perception, understanding, memorization, and mastery of the studied materials, compliance with the requirements of ergonomics in the placement of visual materials ;
3. that the textual materials placed in the frame are complete in content;
4. free movement of knowledge and topics (in this way, the listener can repeat previous topics or look at the material ahead of him in order to know what awaits him), use of hypertext content following sections and topics;
5. The EIER textbook consists of content, control questions, exercises and assignments for each section that determines the uniqueness of a specific academic subject, and the active use of interactive dialogue with the electronic textbook in these sections (the section is made up of exercises or should not be replaced with a set of tasks, on the contrary, the proposed control questions are directly related to the text of the main educational material that the listener is currently studying and serves to master this material well, as well as the listener's section the time of addressing one or other questions, exercises and tasks should be determined according to the pedagogical script);
6. Having search systems that allow quick access to basic concepts, terms, and definitions in EIER;
7. easy access to the directory from any page of the EIER;
8. EIER to conduct the trainee's current and final control test which provides a system, the student's reference to the tests should be specified in the pedagogical script;
9. EIER fully meets the rules and standards specified in "General sanitary and hygienic requirements for educational electronic resources". Creation of EIER takes place in a certain process, in several stages, like the creation of any product. At the current stages, specific tasks are solved taking into account the pedagogical, educational-methodical and functional requirements for creating EIER. The systematization of the stages of the creation of EIER ensures that the creative activities organized in this way are solved in a certain consistency, in a sequence, based on a specific goal. In addition, the stages of the creation of EIER prepare the ground for the formalization of this type of intellectual product and its recognition by the relevant responsible bodies.

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**INFLUENCE OF THE INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT ON HIGHER
EDUCATION: CONSTRUCTIVE AND DESTRUCTIVE FACTORS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This article examines the modern external information environment as a dynamically developing sphere that determines the conditions for the development of modern society. The author draws attention to the two-sided nature of the information environment, including constructive and destructive aspects. The basic properties of the information environment are studied, such as volatility, complexity, dynamism, interactivity, interconnectedness of factors, globality and openness. Particular attention is paid to fluctuation and its connection with the uncertainty and unpredictability of changes in the modern information environment. The complexity of the information environment, consisting of many subsystems, and its changes as a result of the development of communication and computer networks are also considered. The author emphasizes that the rapid growth in the volume of information and increased information uncertainty require the user to process a large amount of data to obtain the necessary information.</p>	<p>Information environment, activity, information consumption, constructive factors, destructive aspects, fluctuation, interactivity, complexity, dynamism.</p>

Introduction

The modern external information environment is not only the most dynamically developing sphere of human life, but also practically independently determines the conditions for the development of modern society. From this point of view, any activity requires initial conditions—the consumption of initial information; on the other hand, it constantly creates new information and carries out continuous information interaction [1].

The external modern information environment is very contradictory, as it has both constructive capabilities and destructive aspects. In dictionaries, the word “destruction” is interpreted as a violation, destruction of the normal structure of a system. It should be noted that destructive activity in the information environment can be directed by a person to other people, social structures or society as a whole, the natural environment, architectural monuments, historical memory, various objects .

LITERATURE REVIEW

Constructive and destructive factors of the changing information environment stem from its basic properties: volatility, complexity, dynamism, interactivity, interconnectedness of factors, globality, openness. Let's try to look at these relationships in more detail.

Fluctuation as a leading characteristic of the information environment means that changes in it occur with a high degree of uncertainty and unpredictability. In everyday understanding, uncertainty is usually associated with characteristics such as unpredictability and randomness. If the factors influencing decision making have these properties, then it is impossible to talk about any specific outcome of the alternative. In such conditions, it is necessary to take into account all possible options, or at least the most likely of them. Therefore, when analyzing a particular decision, several potential outcomes must be considered, namely the values of the performance indicators used to make decisions. The XX century brought significant qualitative changes to the information environment. Technological changes are happening much faster than in previous periods, and all of them are revolutionary in nature: first electronicization, and then computerization, mediatization and internetization. A qualitative leap occurred in the historical process when information began to circulate on a global scale. During this period, the volume of information production grows exponentially every year, and information processes also change significantly. At the same time, the transmission speed and the volume of transmitted information increased. This leads to an increase in the number of its consumers. Thus, uncertainty, unpredictability and instability of the external information environment determine the objective nature of the emergence of risk factors that complicate the process of individual adaptation to ongoing changes.

METHODOLOGY & EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The complexity of the information environment lies in the fact that it, as a system, consists of many subsystems that are self-organizing and exist in various relationships with each other. Currently, the information environment is changing depending on the development of communication and computer networks. According to some estimates, the amount of data stored on Internet servers is doubling every year. With the advent of the Internet, such an information infrastructure is gradually being formed against the backdrop of the use of network information technologies, the expansion of satellite communications, the implementation of their integration with cellular communications, the integration of user interaction with a computer, virtual environments, etc. Consequently, a fundamentally new, complex, highly automated, information-rich information environment is being created. The rapid growth in the volume of information, increased information uncertainty, and the inability to determine the correspondence between the volume of information and the number of its sources lead to the fact that the user is forced to process a huge amount of different data to obtain the necessary information.

The dynamics of the information environment is expressed in the following points: firstly, the environment must adapt to changing conditions, and secondly, changes in its state depend not only on a specific moment, but also on its previous states and external influences, which is a random process. The dynamics of the environment are associated with the acceleration of events associated with changing situations, and the user will have to transfer more and more information to adapt to changes. It should be noted that since the mid-20th century, the dynamics of the information environment have increased significantly, and the increase in documentary flows has led to an information "explosion".

Sometimes it can be very difficult to understand the quality and reliability of the information received, causing disorientation for users who do not have special skills in working with information, not only in the information world, but also in reality.

The interactivity of the information environment is defined as the active interaction of participants in the educational process among themselves and with network information resources supported at the technical and methodological level. Interactivity is the ability to exchange information processes, and this is not only the exchange of messages, but also the exchange of knowledge and ideas. The external information environment, which represents a separate sphere of people's lives (social networks, online games), allows a person to communicate with many people located in different parts of the planet. But, on the other hand, this virtual environment can completely change real life: virtual communication is increasingly replacing real life, and the emotional component of communication is decreasing. The ability and ability of a person to exist in a new information environment is one of the norms of modern civilization.

RESULTS

The next characteristic of the information environment is the relationship of factors. The most important factor in regulating the information environment is the educational sphere, on which the formation and development of science depends. Education is informational in nature, since the cultural information accumulated by previous generations is transmitted to subsequent generations. The information environment arises in the interaction of educated, intellectually developed people, and systemic knowledge has long been associated in society with education. In this case, "the educational information system must implement an advanced mechanism of reflection, modeling information scenarios of the future, which will help manage the future from now on" [7, P. 3]. Thus, the changing information environment, in turn, becomes an important factor in the development and education. Consequently, the constantly changing external information environment places special demands on the user's personality and the characteristics of his competence [8]. After all, changes in information flows, which constitute the essence of the teacher's interaction with the external information environment, require users to know the specifics of this type of mega-environment, perfect knowledge of the techniques, methods. In addition, updating the corresponding set of knowledge and skills must occur independently constantly. This, in turn, requires additional motivation, time, etc. Unfortunately, it should be noted the low level of information technology readiness of users to carry out such activities [9].

The next factor in the development of the information environment is information globalization, which is determined by the increasing volumes of information, obvious in modern conditions, and new technological capabilities for its creation and dissemination. This allows information to dynamically penetrate people's minds. In general, globalization is not a "natural" process that occurs spontaneously; a means of enhancing information exchange is technological progress, carried out primarily through the development of microprocessor technologies, digital technologies, telecommunications and the Internet. Large-scale implementation of the latest information technologies leads to a radical restructuring of the information environment. It goes beyond localism and regionalism and becomes the communicative basis of globalization. Globalization, which is one of the factors in the unification of humanity and the expansion of interaction between the populations of different countries, gives rise to a new unified culture. However, firstly, the quality of this new

culture is questionable, and secondly, it may lead to the loss of national culture. This, in turn, leads to a loss of self-identity and personal identity.

Openness, as a property of the information environment, manifests itself in different ways: as visibility, as the ability to see the interaction of subjects in a virtual environment; as access to the environment, as an opportunity to establish information interaction; as self-change in the process of development. One of the concepts for the development of modern education is open learning, which allows for the free development of the individual, and most importantly, provides the most important type of personal freedom - freedom of thought. The open learning model can be presented in the form of a cognitive environment focused on the individual, capable of self-organization and development of abilities based on the acquisition of knowledge and the development of methods for using it in everyday life and professional activities. Open education has a number of global consequences for the development of education systems in all countries of the world, provides free access to information resources and wide freedom to choose an educational strategy. This education system presupposes a personal orientation of the process: each subject of the educational process, no matter where he is, will have the opportunity to independently build an educational trajectory that fully corresponds to his educational and professional abilities and needs.

CONCLUSIONS

However, the lack of direct personal communication between students and the teacher, which can emotionally diversify knowledge, is a negative point for the educational process. With distance learning, it is difficult to create a creative environment in a group of students. In addition, the main problem remains the issue of knowledge testing, since difficulties arise with user authentication. These and other problems limit the use of distance learning in education. Thus, the modern changing information environment can have both constructive and destructive effects on a person. It is important not only to take into account its creative or destructive nature, but also to master methods of combating the negative impact of the information society.

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COMPONENT ELEMENT OF USING WEB PLATFORMS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
In article is that the current level of development of science and technology, as well as the orientation of the world educational space for openness, massification, individualization, mobility, use of multimedia in education activate the task of creating a new type of educational focus environment is an electronic educational environment.	Electronic, educational, environment, education, media, technology, mobility.

Introduction

E-learning means information available in the database and used during the implementation of educational programs, information technologies and technical tools that ensure its processing, as well as the transfer of relevant information along communication lines, students and educational process organized by the use of information and telecommunication networks that ensure mutual cooperation of pedagogical staff is understood. Along with this concept, its analogues “e-learning”, “e-education” and others are found in the literature. Mazkur sohaga tegishli atamashunoslikda bir ma’noli yondashuvning yo’qligi elektron o’qitish nazariyasining muhim muammolaridan biri sanaladi. Bu masala bo’yicha har tomonlama umumlashgan pozitsiyani It was put forward by a team of scientists and researchers of the University of Catalonia. In particular, they highlighted the following approaches to understanding the essence of e-learning:

- e-learning as a technology - the use of new multimedia technologies and the Internet in order to improve the quality of teaching with a means of facilitating access to resources, remote exchange and collaboration;
- e-learning as a content delivery system - the widespread use of a collection of programs and applications designed to “deliver” professional learning to the consumer;
- e-learning from the point of view of communication - implementation of education using modern means of communication;
- as a paradigm of electronic education - implementation of an innovative approach to the educational process. This approach envisages the creation of an interactive open environment with an educational orientation using the resources of various digital technologies .

The fourth approach to defining the concept of “e-learning or e-learning” integrates the above positions and is the most appropriate approach for us. Because it expresses the uniqueness and problem of our research.

The aspect that created conditions for the integration of e-learning into the international educational practice is the use of e-learning technologies of the world's leading universities and the creation of open e-courses. Examples of this are: MOOC (Massive Open Online Source), Coursera, Universarium, etc. Digital Britain, Degreed, Global Education, Second Life and others are among the most productive projects in the field of electronic education.

At the same time, as mentioned above, the introduction of e-learning into the educational system is characterized by the lack of theoretical considerations and the absence of comprehensive methodological support. In this regard, informative didactics of pedagogy; computer didactics; multimedia didactics; electronic didactics; New departments such as e-didactics are emerging and developing.

As a research subject of these departments, educational environments created with the help of the application of information-communication, distance and electronic education technologies will appear.

The following types of environments created and working on the basis of these technologies are described in the psychological-pedagogical literature: “information-educational environment”, “adaptive (adaptive) educational environment”, “electronic educational environment”, “electronic informational educational environment”, “multimedia educational environment”, “virtual educational environment” and others. The diversity of the cited concepts naturally raises the following question: is this definition synonymous? As mentioned above, the researched field of didactics is still new and the categorical apparatus is not unambiguous, so there is no single point of view on this issue. Accordingly, we had to analyze many definitions. Based on them, we came to the following conclusion: the studied concepts have different meanings. We will analyze the specific aspects of each of these concepts.

The content of the concept of electronic learning environment to a large extent reflects the essence and uniqueness of the environment aimed at satisfying educational needs in accordance with the modern trends in the development of the educational system. Its uniqueness is the use of electronic learning technologies and the intensification of computer networks for the implementation of educational activities. It should be noted that this concept is quite broad in terms of its scope. First of all, this is explained by the wide range of possibilities of electronic teaching technologies, their pedagogical potential. Perhaps, in order to organize the training of future engineers on the basis of mathematical and natural sciences at a higher educational institution, it would be appropriate to review the environment in which the component of the electronic learning environment is considered.

Adaptive learning environment is focused on individualization of the educational process, and this environment allows taking into account the uniqueness and needs of each learner. In this situation, information-communication, distance learning technologies and electronic learning technologies can be seen as one of the means to achieve the set goal. At the same time, this type of environment can be implemented without using a computer or the Internet.

The concepts of “open educational environment” and “multimedia educational environment” are divided on the basis of qualitative characteristics - openness and multimedia. In this situation, openness means the possibility of using educational and methodical materials in a free and convenient mode; for teachers, it is an opportunity to change and enrich the content-methodical and organizational-technological structure of the educational process. “Multimedia” represents the informational technological spectrum that uses various programs and technical tools in order to have a positive effect on the user. Therefore, these features can be implemented in all types of environments seen above.

A distinctive feature of the virtual learning environment is the leading type of interaction - virtual communication. In this case, the teaching process is built mainly by using distance learning technologies

and electronic learning technologies. In our research work, we study the mixed type of interaction of the subjects of the educational process.

The analysis of the characteristics of various environments organized and functioning on the basis of modern educational technologies made it necessary to evaluate the electronic didactic environment as a phenomenon of pedagogical science.

“Computer Supported Intentional Learning Environment” is also studied in the research works of foreign researchers.

As evidence, the concept of “computer learning environment” needs to be clarified and expanded in accordance with the important idea of our research.

The analysis of psychological-pedagogical studies provided an opportunity to identify theoretical and practical aspects that point to the existing differences between the concepts of “computer educational environment” and “electronic educational environment”. The first include the following: the leading concept and the relevant stage of information society development; the functional function of the latter is derived from the used teaching tools, communication methods and the level of interactivity and openness. Leading concept. The creation of the computer educational environment required the technologicalization of the educational system, its computerization. The stage of development is the nineties of the twentieth century. At the beginning of the twenty-first century, due to the openness of the educational system, its popularity, and the openness of the expansion of the Internet, the paradigm of electronic and mixed learning (ye-learning, blended-learning) began to dominate. It is noted in psychological and pedagogical studies that the electronic revolution is one of the reasons for the emergence and development of educational electronic environments. This argument was crucial in distinguishing the functional characteristics of computer and e-learning environments. It should be noted that in the previous teaching process, the computer was used only to perform an illustrative function, and also helped to perform various operations in an automated manner. As technique and technology progressed, so did its possibilities. In modern works on the problems of computerization of education, it is stated that it is not allowed to use the computer only as an additional illustrative teaching tool.

To a large extent, this is due to the wide range of tools used for teaching. If in a computer education environment - the tool is the computer, then in the e-learning environment interactive whiteboards, educational panels, multimedia tools, social services, remote desktops, touch pads, etc. are possible tools. possible Foreign researchers express the principle of diversity of teaching tools as "bring your own devices". Approving their opinion and position, we believe that the use of e-learning technologies paves the way for creating a special environment in the current educational space. This environment should not be limited to the computer as the main teaching tool.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the current scale of the development of science and technology, as well as the orientation of the international educational space to openness, mass, individuality, mobility, the transition to the use of multimedia tools in the field of education, a new type of environment with an educational orientation - electronic education is advancing the task of creating a lim environment. This argument is important in the context of the education paradigm of Long Life Learning. In its framework, mixed learning (blended-learning) has become widely popular. This type of education provides for the optimal combination of daytime and distance interaction between teachers and students. At the same time, as mentioned above,

the electronic educational environment that we are considering is considered a structural element of the electronic informational educational environment.

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**POSSIBILITIES OF VISUAL ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL
PUBLICATIONS IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL
QUALIFICATIONS OF BACHELORS IN THE FIELD OF SERVICE**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
Of great importance is the electronic presentation, which reflects the recent achievements of the main activities of digital education, the collection of large volumes of digital data, the production of Science, Technology, Engineering. During the study, we noted that many teachers used inappropriate information presented on the screen using pedagogical electronic products.	E-learning publication, visualization graph visualization method, didactic feature, e-learning publication development tamails, etc.

Introduction

The main activities of digital education consist in the collection, collection, processing and storage of large amounts of digital data. The provision and implementation of relevant e-learning information in mutual cooperation in the network should be carried out at the highest level.

The results of various (educational, scientific and other) digital activities carried out by students in the information and educational environment are based on the integration processes that take place in a digital society. These processes initiate the dynamic development of Science and production, intellectualize Educational, Labor and scientific activities, increase the level of Information Service open to all members of society.

Of great importance is the electronic presentation, which reflects the latest achievements of Science, Technology, Engineering Production.

In this regard, the formation of professional qualifications of Service bachelors implies the filling of the educational process at the institution of higher education with electronic educational publications, as well as pedagogical products presented in the form of audiovisual technologies.

A number of authors have developed and substantiated the terms for the design of safe and expedient electronic publications used in education. In their opinion, the consequences of psychological and pedagogical influences with digital technologies, emotionally saturated and filled with information, are especially negative⁴⁷.

We will consider the capabilities of e-learning publications as a programmatic implementation of didactic capabilities of information and communication technologies at all stages of the educational

process, starting with the formation of cognitive tasks, the design of content, the generalization of their knowledge on their basis, the implementation of the educational project, the planning of further stages of educational activity, the construction. In addition, e-learning resources ensure the completeness and continuity of the process of formation of professional qualifications of Service bachelors, who must be ready to provide theoretical material through electronic educational publications with a qualimetric supply, to carry out their training activities, as well as to use mathematical and imitation modeling with computer visualization elements.

During the study, we noted that many teachers used inappropriate information presented on the screen using pedagogical electronic products. These are:

educational information that exhausts students due to the excessive capacity of information and the emotional richness of the moment;

educational information that does not correspond to the individual characteristics of students in terms of its structure and quality;

full-level study data that does not provide a positive psychological background of student interaction with virtual reality objects;

the general inconsistency of the visual environment, color and sound background with the requirements for electronic educational publications.

In the modern educational process, the number of quality electronic publications is growing rapidly and accounts for more than 40% of all educational and methodological developments.

Currently, there are not many such electronic publications, since the didactic possibilities of applicants for this name are very limited. In addition, in our study, we note that many higher education institutions are not provided with modern technical means, which makes it difficult to use electronic publications in the educational process.

All electronic publications used in the educational process must undergo an appropriate multifunctional examination in order to eliminate the negative consequences of the use of EO.

Let's consider the following main positions of expertise::

implementation of didactic capabilities of the use of information technology in the sphere of pedagogical feasibility;

compatibility of educational content taking into account the age characteristics of students;

the educational and methodological feasibility of electronic publications, as well as the justification of the methodological foundations of the component of the electronic educational manual; ensuring the necessary Organization of training of students, the use of interactive methods and forms in the educational process, ensuring the appropriate pedagogical monitoring of the quality of mastering the educational material by students;

the necessary sanitary and hygienic and ergonomic conditions are created for the placement of educational information, the correctly provided visual and color background of the information field, clarity, logic and visual reading of the screenshot, correctly developed text format, character characteristics, sound parameters, artistic image parameters, multimedia, hypertext, technological features of hypermedia;

changing educational opportunities using electronic publications;

the process of installation and deletion, compliance with the technical characteristics of the reliability of the operation of electronic publications.

From the above, the need to develop completely different levels of electronic publications, which are effectively used in the preparation of Service bachelors using graphic visualization methods and 3D-technologies, was determined, on the basis of which the educational activity was not formalized in the process, including using interactive models of studied objects or processes, visual design programs in HTML, which allow solving creative issues in modeling certain components of activities of an informational-technological nature, allowing interactive communication through language forms that accccre natural for a person ,programs for the development of 2D and 3D graphics (Adobe PhotoShop, Adobe Illustrator, etc.), programs for obtaining animated constructs (3ds Max, With software-based tools such as Adobe Flash, etc.), it will be possible to achieve an imitation of students solving issues of high complexity 48. All of the above makes it possible to determine the main prospects for the development of electronic publications and their use as a didactic tool of relevant information training of Service bachelors.

The development of electronic publications requires: 1. Improving the legislative framework, which allows you to assess the quality of electronic publications, as well as create a basic framework for protecting the intellectual property and information security of the user. 2. Modeling digital activities in the study of objects or processes through interactive communication. 3. Design an electronic publication in accordance with the instructive-methodological base used in the information and educational environment of the higher education institution. 4. The presence of non-formalized creative tasks. 5. Training of scientific and pedagogical personnel in the field of examination of electronic publications. 6. Introduction of a system of methodological support for the use of electronic publications in additional educational programs, a system of examination of the educational process of secondary and general educational institutions and the quality of electronic publications. 7. Improvement of information competence in the field of application of information and communication technologies in professional activities (for science teachers). 8. Increase the level of development of information and communication technologies (for students). The development of the structure of e-learning publications requires separate approaches, to which we will dwell. Hypertext technology used in e-learning publications requires teachers and programmers to address the following key issues.

First, the first electronic product that we develop is a textbook, a teaching manual, a chrestomy, a reference, a dictionary, an encyclopedia, assignments, lectures, etc. Secondly, the e-learning Edition must have been developed and tested by the author on a conceptual basis, and only then will it have a teaching significance. This applies to the internal structure of the hypertext system.

In addition to the internal structure, the basic principles that apply to conceptual design and include a visualization structure that defines the links between the individual elements of the course remain relevant49.

In this case, students will have the opportunity to use a special navigation map or module pointer in the content. Within the framework of research activities, it is possible to use a special technique, that is, to hide the entire structure of the science from students, in which case the student must complete the task by developing a structure based on his accumulated knowledge or instructions.

It will be a R & D system for design design, that is, the organization of conditions by the author that determine the capabilities of the information system and the possibility of building his own individual research trayetory based on his educational interests. At the same time, it is a problem that is difficult to determine the universal structure of the transmission of educational information in various fields of science.

Now we actualize the problem of the influence of various plan factors on the development and presentation of a system of educational information in a hypertext electronic publication. In this case, as educational practice shows, a large part of the requirements for electronic textbooks are to some extent opposite, mutually exclusive and difficult to match.

One of the factors is the field of science. In our study of General Technical Sciences, the presentation of information is fundamentally different from the humanities, which work in much larger textual volumes, characterized by a low level of formalization, universal conceptual definitions and the absence of solving problematic and other issues.

Studying such subjects as “theoretical mechanics”, “machine parts”, “engineering graphics”, “computer graphics”, “Multimedia technologies”, “Auto Service” and others using electronic educational publications, i.e. multimedia technologies, requires visual display of objects on the computer screen. Therefore, when developing these electronic publications, a variety of demonstration materials should be included along with the main text.

Comparison of electronic textbooks with printed editions involves actualization of the value of the pictorial material presented in the text. “Clean” texts without such material will only have information about texts and will be used only with the help of texts. Subject indicators should be mandatory included in the composition of electronic textbooks, which give students the opportunity to start with the conceptual and meaningful foundations of the educational publication when working with educational information. This creates the conditions for students to quickly search for relevant educational information and make a comparative analysis of a certain number of electronic textbook articles, taking into account the same concept.

When developing electronic publications of a humanitarian orientation, it is advisable to include in their composition various schemes, photographs, tables for various purposes, high-quality presentations (for example, for the “Persons” Section).

The development of electronic publications on foreign languages requires the active use of multimedia technologies, since they undoubtedly have educational advantages.

The design of the structure of multilevel non-linear information systems should begin with the development of a holistic system of first high-level nodes, and then the expansion of additional nodes of other quality levels.

The solution of EON educational problems in the physical profile is carried out using special tasks, various forms of pedagogical control in the conditions of laboratory and practical training. At the same time, training tasks can be classified as calculating and qualitative. In the specified plan, structural communications provide free access to all information subsystems and determine the construction of the necessary hierarchy of nodes, the content of which is expressed in one or another theoretical, practical and test material.

Structural communications fall into three categories:

1. Connecting links, which are used by users to obtain detailed training information, which is located on various information nodes and provides clarification on specific training issues.
2. Clarifying links that provide the correct semantic relationship between the text structure of an electronic textbook and the images, videos and other software corresponding to this text.
3. Associative relations. Such connections allow the use of compact information that occurs together in an informational nature. The study of the “engineering graph” course of study involves drawing up the described material in separate modules. In the practical implementation of the formation of the

structure of the hypertext learning system, it will be necessary to prepare the content on a modular basis through qualimetric provision.

In such electronic textbooks, associative links are directed to the article "persons", which creates the necessary conditions for students to receive meaningful information about short biographical information when mastering educational material.

At this stage of the practical construction of the hypertext learning system, the following didactic measures should be taken:

formation of individual self-sufficient educational information modules by differentiating and detailing the overall structural area of the curriculum;

development of reference works of various functional objectives necessary to ensure the systematic integrity of associative links;

to develop a list of additional materials of auxiliary importance. Such materials can be, first of all, a variety of images, videos and other materials necessary for the detailed description of informational clarifying communications;

development of a system of thematic cards reflecting the general information structure of each training module. Each such card should contain a detailed list of contacts and links for all the didactic materials above.

The development of the course in hypertext decoration requires a meaningful filling of all updated components. This is reflected in the preparation of detailed lecture sessions and the correct adaptation of students to the possibilities of their effective perception in electronic form. In addition, the development of the course requires different examples, the choice of test assignments of different levels of complexity, etc.

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ANALYSIS OF EXISTING RISKS AND METHODS OF COMBATING THEM IN CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This article provides an analysis of current threats and mechanisms in cloud technologies. In addition, clouds name, computer systems, all of the computers within the same network, are analyzed in clouds to display information within it. Each computer is not considered as an independent unit, but a whole system. In general, the user is provided directly to work directly to work. All network resources available through servers are illuminated.</p> <p>Modern information technologies often play a major role in the success of all areas. There are a number of means and options that allow us to use full power of cloudy technologies. The concept of cloudy technologies is really important because it can become a turn point of doing business and take it to a completely new level. This means that it can bring income not only for businesses, but also for the state.</p>	<p>Cloud, Cloud ACCESS Security, Saas (Virtual-AS-Service, DOS (DENAL-AS-Service, DOS (DENAL-USER), Hypervisor, Cloud Security Alliance (CSA)) and others.</p>

Introduction

Cloud computing security is a set of technologies and strategies that help protect cloud data, applications, infrastructure in organizations as well as meet standards [1].

Identity management, privacy, and access control are especially important for cloud security. Because cloud systems are generally common and are available on Internet sources. Since it is typically used for continuous daily activities from cloud computing and public cloud providers, security measures related to cloud computing as well as vulnerability mitigation should be prioritized [1].

Cloud computing security processes must take into account the security measures provided by the cloud service providers, and organizations must understand the distribution of responsibility between the cloud service provider and the cloud user. In order to prepare for a possible breach of cloud security, it is necessary to ensure the continuity of the business and standardize the processes for the backup of cloud data.

Purpose

Cloud computing security-cloud security belongs to the lower categories of computer security, or network security in the broader category of Information Security. Cloud security is concerned with a set of policies, management tools, or security measures developed specifically to provide data, applications, and infrastructure in the cloud. Cloud Access Security, on the other hand, can be defined as a topic that takes into account where the data in the cloud security context is located and the right to access it through the cloud. Most often, it deals with the provision of an identity management system for cloud users.

Literature Analysis

One of the technologies that we are developing today is Cloud computing. The idea of such calculations was first proposed in 1961 by John McCarthy (John McCarthy). That is, its computing power is provided to users as a service [1].

In 1963 year J.S.R.Licklider began to study the idea of the global existence of a computer network. In his opinion, a global existing network allows a person to access computer programs and information from anywhere in the World [2]. He formulated the oldest ideas of the global computer network. As a result, the network space appeared, where today there are cloud services.

Theoretical Basis

Cloud security is a sub-branch of emerging computer or network security that works with cloud content security tools through a variety of management and infrastructure. Cloud-based security, however, has nothing to do with cloud-based security measures and vulnerability management software provided through a cloud-based antivirus or security service. It is segmented into the challenges that cloud security providers and cloud customers face. Cloud providers are responsible for delivering software, platform, or infrastructure as a cloud-based customer service. Cloud service providers need to make sure that their customers' applications and data are protected. At the same time, it is the responsibility of the customer that the service provider takes the right measures to protect the information. Cloud security challenges are divided into three main categories. That is, security and privacy, compliance and legal issues. To ensure data security and its confidentiality, a number of measures such as data protection measures, identity management systems, physical and personal security measures, high level of assurance measures, application-level security measures and data masking measures are used. To ensure compliance, service providers must comply with many data storage regulations, such as the PCI DSS (payment cards industry safety standard), HIPAA(Health Insurance capability and Liability Act), and the Sarbanes-Oksley act. They require regular inspection and reporting procedures. When it comes to legal and contractual issues, there should be agreements between providers and customers on liability, intellectual property and terms of service termination. Cloud access security. Cloud access security can be defined as the Lower Zone of cloud security. This is due to who is allowed access to this information. Access security is a very important issue in public clouds, where many service providers provide shared services. Identity management systems are mandatory in any cloud. These systems can be either client identification management systems connected to the cloud, or systems provided by the service providers themselves. If one access technology is used between different SaaS (Software-as-a-Service) providers, the user can use the same credentials when accessing all systems. To eliminate the great risk of abuse of access rights by

service provider administrators, customers can install event logging monitoring tools.

What is the difference between Cloud Security and Cloud Access Security? Cloud security is an area of computer security that deals with protecting cloud content using a variety of policies, controls, and infrastructures. Cloud security is divided into different sizes, and cloud access security is one of its most important dimensions. Cloud access security is concerned with ensuring cloud content protection. Ensuring cloud access security is critical to ensuring cloud security. Because it eliminates the possibility of unauthorized, unapproved users accessing data in the cloud and compromising the security and privacy of the data stored in the cloud.

When we say threat intelligence to cloud technology is compromised, cloud management and control are understood as the main security challenges. In cloud technologies, all resources are under constant control by virtual machines. This is considered a high-profile threat, it is associated with Cloud Management, serves as a single Information System, and it will need to build its overall protection at a high level.

For this, of course, it will be necessary to apply risk probability management models in the cloud infrastructure. On the basis of physical security, it would be necessary to have strict control over access to the server and network infrastructure. With regard to physical security, network security is in the first place. This model incorporates security against threats and eliminates them through the firewall. The firewall acts as a filter and restricts the use of the data center network. In this case, separate servers, that is, from those that are allowed to be used on the Internet, or servers within the network. Virtualization as a platform plays the main role in cloud computing.

Results and Discussion

We analyze the most common threats to ensure data integrity and security in cloud computing. There are several challenges in deploying cloud servers in cloud computing. The security requirements of cloud computing are no different from the security requirements of a data center. But the virtualization of the data processing center and the transition to the cloud environment cause new threats to appear. Controlling computing power over the Internet is one of the key characteristics of cloud computing. In many traditional data centers, engineers use servers that are controlled on a physical scale, and in a cloud environment, they operate over the Internet. System-level provisioning of access-controlled restrictions and transparent changes is critical protection.

Dynamics of virtual machines. Creating a new car, stop and restarting can be done in a short time. They can interfere with physical servers. Such changes make the system difficulty processing the security integrity. However, the vulnerability of the operating system or apps is uncontrolled in the virtual environments and begins to quickly spread in a certain period of time (for example, backup. In a cloudy computer environment, first of all, correct the system security status, it should be taken into account that its status and storage should not depend on it.

Vulnerabilities in the internal virtual environment. Cloud computing servers and local servers use the same operating system and applications. Remote hacking or malware threats are common to cloud systems. Parallel virtual machines increase the risk of attack. Protocol-based threats and mitigation protocols must detect malicious activity at the virtual level.

Protection of unused virtual machines. When the virtual machine is not active, the risk of damage is greater. Access to stored images on Virtual machines will be enough. On a virtual machine that has not started, it is impossible to start the software security, in general. In this case, not only should

internal security be implemented on the virtual machine, but also at the level of the hypervisor(the hypervisor is the computer that manages one or more virtual machines).

Zone security and network restriction. When using cloud computing, the zone network slows down or disappears from sight altogether. As a result, security is not at a high level, and the network part determines the overall security level. In the cloud, virtual machines will have to provide their own security when limiting segments to different levels of reliability.

Attacks carried out through cloud technology and their elimination. Traditional attacks on software this operating system, the vulnerability of network protocols, are considered traditional threats. In order to ensure protection, problems can be solved by installing a firewall, antivirus, IPS and other components[5]. It should be taken into account that such a way of protection should also work effectively in the development.

Functional attacks on Cloud Elements. This type of attack is multipathli with the cloud due to a common security printzip. On cloud security, the following can be obtained as a solution: when protecting against functional attacks, the following sources of protection should be placed on each cloud partition: DoS for proxy(Denial-of-Service-temporary suspension of the activity of the attacking server), ensuring effective protection from attack, controlling the integrity of pages for the web server, for server applications - applications on-screen, DBMS (Data Base Management System) for SQL(Structured Query Language)Protection, data storage system to give the right back-ups (backup), restrict access, etc. The above listed protections have been produced, but they have not yet been assembled together to provide cloud-based protection. Therefore, at the time of creation of the cloud, integrating them into a single system will be an impetus to the solution of the problem.

Many customers use the browser when connecting to the cloud. One of the attacks is Cross Site Scripting, “stealing” passwords, capturing web sessions, and so on. The only correct and protection from such an attack is mutual authentication with clear authentication and encryption of connections (SSL-Secure Sockets Layer). But such a method of protection is much more inconvenient and time-consuming to the creators of the cloud.

Attacks on the hypervisor. Hypervisor is one of the key elements for virtual systems. One of its main functions is the distribution of resources to virtual machines. An attack on the hypervisor can result in the fact that one of the virtual machines can take advantage of the memory, resources of another virtual machine. It can also capture utarmak traffic, absorb physical resources and stop the virtual machine from running through the server. They recommend the use of the necessary specialized products in the virtual environment in the implementation of standard protection techniques. Integration of host servers with Directory Services Active Directory(a bright database and a suite of services and tools that deploy devices to connect to a specific network), as well as standardize the procedure for using host server management tools. At the same time, denial of Service, which in most cases is not used, for example, virtualization web access to the server.

Attacks on the control system. Many virtual machines used in the cloud require separate system administration. Disrupting the control system in the virtual machines - it causes malfunctions, and by blocking one virtual machine, it makes another virtual machine guilty.

One of the most effective security solutions in the cloud industry, Cloud Security Alliance (CSA), was referred to by the public, in which the following data were analyzed:

Data storage. Encryption is one of the most effective methods of data protection. The provider, which allows access to the data, must encrypt the client data stored in the data processing center, and when

it comes to the use, delete them without a return.

Data security in transmission. The transmission of encrypted data can only be carried out after authentication. Reading or changing data, their use is carried out through reliable connections. Such technologies are very well-known algorithms and reliable protocols AES(protected form of information encryption), TLS(ensuring the confidentiality of information), Ipsec(security of the internet protocol).

Authentication. Password protection. When ensuring reliability, attention is paid to tokens and certificates. The provider should act transparently when passing authorization with the identification system. It uses LDAP (Light Directory Access Protocol) and SAML (Security Association Markup Language) protocol.

Consumer insulation. Individual use of Virtual machines and virtual networks. The following technologies should be introduced in Virtual networks. VPN (Virtual Private Network), VLAN (Virtual Local Area Network) and VPLS (Virtual Private LAN Service). Providers often isolate consumer data from each other because of code changes in a single application environment. Such an approach is considered dangerous, it is able to find a way out of a non-standard code and use the data of the client.

Key techniques in securing data protection in cloud technologies.

1-picture. Key in providing data protection in cloud technologies techniques.

Legal techniques. Legal techniques include the production of regulatory acts, including ensuring the safety and regulation of information relations between participants and normative - methodical documents, provision of Information Security, etc.

The most important activities of these include:

- timely amendments and amendments to the state legislation, regulations in the field of Information Security;
- elimination of conflicts related to international treaties;
- establishing responsibility for violations;
- limitation of powers in the field of Information Security;
- development and adoption of regulatory and legal acts.

Organizational and technical activities. Such techniques include the following:

- creation and modernization of information security system;
- effective use of tools in production, information protection and control techniques;
- to identify the risks arising from technical devices and applications in ensuring information security;
- certification of information security tools;
- control of personnel behavior in protected information systems;
- formation of system monitoring indicators and information security characteristics;

Economic activity. Economic methods include the following security:

- development of information security plans;
- financing of system improvement works together with organizational rights and

organizational and technical techniques.

Service level adaptation. Currently, legal normative acts, the absence of rules for the regulation of cloud resources, adaptation to the level of Service, are considered one of the most important criteria of cloud computing providers[7]. Unfortunately, at the moment, many providers make the adaptation at the service level so that they receive little responsibility for themselves as a result. Proceeding from this, before using confidential information in cloud computing, it is necessary to choose providers that are well adapted to the level of service.

Set up a cloud security channel up to the system. When communicating with the system in the cloud, the channel is encrypted. When installing security channels, VPN (virtual personal network) technologies are used. Nevertheless, that is, the presence of lower bounce reliability of telecommunications in the network, and the confidence in the channel remains high. Depends on the use of cryptographic tools (encryption, authentication, open-key infrastructure and the Prevention of changing the data being sent). This method is the simplest and most reliable. It protects against MITM (Man in the middle) attacks. But this method only protects the system and channel communication in the cloud. Information passing through the entire system is considered open.

Protection technology. Cloud protection strategy in the IT(Internet technology) industry allows to ensure a very high level. At the same time it is considered to have the highest standards of protection of personal data. "Cloud computing " allows you to determine the requirements for each structural level, setting the area of participants at all times. Today, measures for the implementation of such requirements are being found. The main emphasis should be on the use of reliable distribution and operation software.

The most common risks in cloud environments are theft of virtual machines from a state of running state, modifications to the network topology of the IT infrastructure using only application parameters, such as direct access to network protections in IT-related attacks. This risk is reduced due to the protection of the virtual environment at all stages of its construction. That is, they are: within the framework of virtual infrastructure, system administration and storage, hardware, system software graph (hypervisor), etc.

Provide customers with hardware and software. Until now, the consumer will not come up with any problems in the approach of software and hardware tools for encrypting IP - streams over SSL protokol at work. Speed, processing can output up to a dozen Mbit/t. Currently, theififikatsiyles frirme, which provides such services, is considered sufficient. The keys in consumer operating systems and the protection of personal information in the corporate cloud are one of the major challenges in ensuring information security. An electronic lock is installed on the consumer's personal computers. Such locking can be controlled not only by the consumer, but also by the company's information security service. But all this is only available in the private cloud, and the social cloud does not have these opportunities.

Hypervisor, as a software tool, manages hardware resources and allocates resources between guest operating systems. It is therefore the most vulnerable part of the virtual environment. Any broken status of it, the guest will cause a malfunction in the operating system. Taking advantage of the hypervisor brings in its place a variety of opportunities to evil-minded individuals. From a data point of view, such access provides an opportunity to control all information flows that pass through the hypervisor. Such opportunities give the right to general use of the virtual environment, namely: the administrator of the virtual structure will have the right to use any information without restriction.

Therefore, the security of information resources can be solved in a virtual environment. Logical virtual infrastructure does not differ from physical infrastructure. Accordingly, the threats in the first are considered relevant in the second. Then the media should be able to provide virtual infrastructure protection, optimization of hardware resources. The use of information protections for rational purposes in multi-volume virtual infrastructures helps to build at the hypervisor level. The main risk probability in the cloud occurs through actualization specification, the emergence of new entities - the cloud management system and the system actualization. Compromising one of them is equivalent to risking cloud security. Virtual machines on physical servers in a Virtual environment can be quite a lot. Virt if a simple antivirus is installed on the operating system of the upgraded server, 100 copies of the antivirus on one physical hypervisor will occur. Each copy will have its own antivirus signature, legal guardian: all this must be updated on time on all virtual machines. This results in a new extra weight being added to the hypervisor, and physical server resources are beginning to be wasted inefficiently.

Conclusions and Suggestions

The above solutions do their job by checking communications between virtual machines and analyzing traffic from attacks occurring at the hypervisor level. Therefore, in the trading market, new products that are produced for the actualization environment begin to appear. Undoubtedly, they work very efficiently and have the most stringent facilities in management.

Regardless of the location of the cloud-based technology, it allows users to collaborate with an ever-growing circle of users. These technologies deliver information in an economical and reliable way and are characterized by Ease of distribution and updating. Cloud-based technologies that allow information to overcome existing barriers, these are geographic, technological, social, etc.

The introduction of cloud technologies not only reduces the cost of purchasing the necessary software, but also increases the quality and efficiency of the production process, as well as the openness of data.

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IMPROVING THE BASE TRAINING OF STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL OSMS BASED ON THE INFORMATION DESIGN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>On the basis of the information design approach, the technical OSM should take into account the information technologies used in the analysis of strengthened cases of structures in the industry and in design projects to improve the base training of lari students.</p>	<p>Information, Communication, Technology, Project, approach, Foundation, OSM, student, base, prepared, improvement, society, education, technical, modeling, training, research, component, adaptation.</p>

Introduction

In the context of informatization of society and education, the requirements for a modern specialist for him in order to successfully and effectively operate in the professional field have significantly changed. Specialists must have comprehensive knowledge, a high level of competence, quickly adapt to new situations, easily find direction in the modern information space, competently and responsibly solve professional problems, realize their potential (knowledge, skills, experience, personal qualities), use the latest achievements of ICT, take responsibility for the results of their activities. It is these qualities that make the engineer competitive in modern economic conditions, and the educational system that ensures their formation, acceptable.

In technical universities, the educational process is aimed at qualitatively mastering the content of individual subjects, solving sample issues and performing accounting work. The student's activity is determined by the study of the phenomena and laws of the studied field of science, formed using mathematical apparatus, in a clear form. The student must be able to solve problems, analyze solutions (situations) represented by mathematical models, determine the free (variable) and free (constant) parameters of the issue and the connections between them, learn to obtain the necessary scientific information from interconnected fields of knowledge. It teaches the student not only to solve issues, but also to put issues in relation to the aspects that are known and that need to be identified, to analyze whether it can be solved, whether the solution is uniform, and also allows you to move on to another, more extended issue, where there are more opportunities to find a rational solution. The student should

be trained not only to analyze, but also to synthesize, to actively submit the solution to the desired result. In this case, it is required to harmonize mathematical and Physical Modeling.

In the system of higher engineering education, the search for optimal solutions of base and professionally oriented training based on informatization is underway. This requires changing approaches to training specialists in terms of the use of Information Technology in various disciplines. The main directions for the development of informatization of education and training are presented below.

1. Methodology and strategy of the selection of educational structure and content, methods and organizational forms of education and upbringing, corresponding to the tasks of developing the personality of a student in the conditions of an informed society today.
2. Design of pedagogical technologies aimed at the development of the student's intellectual potential, the formation of skills for independent acquisition of knowledge, the implementation of various independent types of activities in the collection, processing, transmission and development of educational information.
3. Study by dividing the possibilities of using ICT tools in the process of acquiring various fields of science.
4. Realization of the possibilities of educational-information interaction as the basis of a single information educational space and the potential of a distributed information resource of local and global networks.

Engineering education implies a certain specialization in a specific narrow scientific field. Frequent phenomena in each field of science consist of a certain system, in which it is necessary to highlight, among other things, the theoretical aspects, the supporting part that takes into its own rich the laws of problem solving, their development and decision-making. It is this part that makes up the science content of Education.

State standards set requirements for the level of knowledge in mathematics and Natural Sciences for training in OTMs. These requirements are designed to" expand the possibilities of continuing education and academic mobility, meet the needs of the individual, society, state, have an instrumental pedagogical organization based on strictly defined criteria for each stage of Education.

The requirements of the OSCE for the organization of the educational process in technical OSMS and natural educational subjects (mathematics, physics, etc.) the school curriculum is complicated by incompatibility.

The degree of knowledge of applicants in the natural sciences (mathematics and physics) does not meet the requirements of the OMS.

As evidence of this, we present among first-year students the data of testing the level of knowledge necessary for mastering the curriculum in the first year of technical universities in the main sections of mathematics in a five-point system, which are published in the report provided by technical universities.

In order to effectively conduct lectures and practical classes in these academic disciplines, a large part of the first-year students will have to undergo additional training ("pull"). In the form of mass education, it turned out to be practically impossible to teach all students their natural sciences in the same way. The organization of training" at different levels", as a result of which there was a need to develop appropriate methodological support, new models of training organization. These situations lead to the search and development of new teaching methods and technologies.

From the above, it follows that the internal structure of the state educational standards of higher education is left with the “structural” disadvantages of the current state educational standards of Higher Education.

There is a need to radically revise the traditional concept of studying basic learning subjects. Due to the development of ICT in the course system of the existing training in technical OSMS, it is necessary to establish logical and meaningful connections with the studied academic disciplines of the base block and with the laws and peculiarities of the most general Natural Sciences of the future professional activity. It is also necessary to develop a didactic concept of the integrity of the Educational Sciences of the base block, that is, interdisciplinary integration, based on the requirements of the state educational standard of Higher Education, the achievements of scientific and technological progress in the professional field. The student will have the opportunity to study the subject of study in a dialectical spiral: first he will get acquainted with the narrow theoretical problem of the studied science, and then learn to apply the theory at the conceptual level in various fields of science, then more broadly and with the necessary (necessary) accuracy in solving direct engineering problems. Then engineers will be able to effectively use theoretical knowledge in various fields of Science in their professional activities.

The choice of educational content in the first year of technical OSM should be built in such a way that the logical structures of all subjects are easy for students to understand.

That is, education allows the student to:

- a system of knowledge about nature, society, thinking, techniques and methods of activity, the assimilation of which ensures the formation of the foundations for the targeted activities of people;
- a system of general intellectual and practical skills and competencies that are the basis of many specific types of activities and provide the ability of the younger generation to maintain culture;
- experience of creative activities that provide the ability to further develop culture;
- experience of emotional-volitional interpersonal relationships, which are the basis for the formation of a worldview.

The effectiveness of teaching in Higher courses, consequently, the professionalism of the future specialist, will depend on how purposefully and correctly the content of teaching for first-year students is selected, compiled and organized. The success of training at a technical OSM is determined by the principle of continuity of training at any stage in the consistent development of educational programs. Taking into account these factors, the improvement of the base training of students of engineering and construction universities in the ICT conditions should be based on the basic theoretical training, taking into account logical and meaningful connections in various departments of basic educational sciences and practical training, taking into account the peculiarities of the construction industry.

The components of theoretical preparation are determined by:

- formation of the goals and objectives of the studied topic;
- diagnostic analysis of student knowledge and formation of motivation to acquire new knowledge;
- drawing up a scheme of basic knowledge on topics;
- construction of an ICT input algorithm for the learning process;
- disclosure of the topic: presentation and explanation of the conceptual rules of the theory, as well as its practical application, using logical-meaningful connections of science;

- Independent replication and consolidation of learned knowledge using ICT.

The components of practical preparation are determined by:

- motivation to set a professionally significant educational task, to solve it;
- clarification of the goals and objectives of solving the task, taking into account the Integrative logical-meaningful connections of science;
- identification of ICT functions in the decision-making process;
- implementation of software information;

independent assessment of work, improvement and correction of practical work, formalization of results.

The implementation of ICT capabilities stimulates the emergence of new tools, organizational forms and styles of teaching, as well as the improvement of existing ones that have proven themselves well. This leads to an expansion of the goals of teaching science and a change in the criteria for choosing the content of educational material: they are based on the acceleration of teaching, the development and self-development of the student's personality, the absorption of skills for the formation and independent separation of knowledge, the differentiation of laws, the use of ICT tools as.

The use of modern ICT tools in the educational process makes it possible to solve the following tasks:

- the teaching process is carried out by the students themselves with the specific tasks of the initial stage (knowledge, research, design, etc.) formulation and solution orientation;
- changing the role of the teacher from informant (supervisor) to coordinator.

All this provides the necessary conditions for the creation of an effective system for the training of engineers and builders and the improvement of its main educational components.

In our opinion, it is necessary to take into account the following components when improving the base preparation in the ICT conditions of students of engineering and construction universities.

1. Motivational – includes the need for self-realization in the use of information technology tools for solving professional tasks, the need for continuous independent education using ICT tools, the desire to make professional and research activities acceptable.

2. Project – The ability to justify the choice of ICT tools, the possibility of designing the technological process of solving their educational (later professional) tasks using selected tools, to assess the accuracy of the results obtained before completing the project.

3. Organizational – information and communication is expressed in the skills of organizing self-knowledge activities in the context of the science environment.

4. Research – the search and selection of professionally relevant information includes the ability to use ICT for its effective analysis.

5. Adaptation – includes the ability to adapt existing tools and technologies to solve a specific task, correct information technology.

6. Constructive – includes the skill of using base information and communication tools to develop its own project and manage its implementation.

Among the priorities for the development of the engineering education system is the formation of a basic professional level of Education. This, in turn, necessitates the creation and development of ICT-based scientific and methodological foundations, new forms, methods and pedagogical technologies. The backbone of the training and training of an engineer-builder is the mechanics of deformable rigid bodies (DQJM), which consists of training courses in construction mechanics, theory of elasticity and plasticity, resistance of materials, theoretical mechanics. The DQJM organizes the educational process with the completion and protection of the diploma project in the period from the first year to the fourth year of the baccalaureate, with access to doctoral and post-graduate education in the two-year graduate stage. The first two courses study wet (theoretical and practical mechanics, including training courses on the resistance of materials), which determine the base, systematizing part of the DQJM. It is worth noting that most textbooks and tutorials on NM and MQ are scientific and informational publications, mainly aimed at presenting final results, due to the abundance of information, which can also leave them behind the process and ways of obtaining results. There are practically no textbooks and teaching aids that make up a system in the specialty of technology, as well as textbooks and teaching aids of an interdisciplinary type.

In technical OSMS, NAM provides the theoretical foundations of general engineering preparation, an invariant core of the base preparation of the engineer-builder, which prepares him for professional mobility, activity in constantly changing conditions of engineering activity.

In technical OSMS, by the basic educational sciences, we understand a set of Educational Sciences that adequately represent the basic laws, logic and structure of the relevant disciplines that ensure the integrity of education in the chosen specialty, combined with interdisciplinary ties and connected with professional competencies (CCS).

Conclusion

The basic training of students of technical ICT should take into account the information technologies used in the construction industry in the analysis of strengthened cases of structures as well as in design projects. To do this, it is also necessary to add information competence to the base training goals. When creating a methodological system for teaching students of engineering and construction universities of educational disciplines that determines base training, it is necessary to take into account the extended educational goals, through which it is necessary to ensure the continuity of information and professional training as well as the connection between fundamentalism and professional orientation in training, which in turn leads to an increase in the level.

The content of informatization of the educational process consists in activating the cognitive activity of students during their independent work, ensuring the interactivity of the student's interaction with the educational material, ensuring an individual trajectory of its assimilation, activating the “student-teacher” feedback. The use of information technology will help to significantly expand the possibilities of individualization and stratification of Education.

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**TECHNOLOGIES FOR USING SOFTWARE PACKAGES TO TEACH
DIGITAL RESOURCE MODELING IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>In this article, special attention is paid to how, when choosing didactic and technical means of education, these tools help to organize the activities of students in order to know in this or that field of knowledge. Also, within the framework of an active approach to education, the concept of "activity" is often associated with the concept of "knowledge", that is, it is argued that in order to form knowledge as an element of the consciousness of an individual, it is necessary to organize cognitive activity of the appropriate type, level and size.</p>	<p>Information, visualization modeling, teaching methods, forms and tools, software packages, etc.</p>

Introduction

Currently, in pedagogy, there is no unambiguous explanation of the concept of "educational tool" and a single multifaceted classification of educational tools. An educational tool can be understood as a material or ideal object used by a teacher and a student to acquire new knowledge. In that case, all objects and processes (material and materialized) that serve as a source and means (actually means) of educational information for learning the content of educational materials, development and education of students can be said to be educational tools. It should be noted that education is effective when material and ideal educational tools are used to complement and support each other to achieve the goals of the educational process [1].

In addition, the content of education at each level has characteristics specific to that level. But if each level has its own content, the means of mastering them should also have their own characteristics. As the content of education changes, so do the means of education at each level. Each level of formation of educational content must inevitably include its own educational tools [2].

Thus, we: the educational process of training a future specialist; Since students are interested in the process of training for a certain type of professional activity, for example, in the effective use of digital educational resources designed for the active use of computers and special software, solving professional problems in this subject area and at the same time it is necessary to describe the spectrum of informational and instrumental systems that allow the professional activity of a specialist to be automated in solving his professional tasks.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review)

Currently, the authors of a large number of literature, A.Y. Garnayev, S.Y. Garnayev [2005]; M. Morgan [2000]; K. Horstmann, G. Kornelp and other new educational software packages and technologies for a wide range of specialists are given special attention in the scientific works of domestic and foreign researchers. For example, E. T. Vovk [2005], K. P. Isaguliyev [2002], P. Lapin [2003], D. V. Leshchev [2004], D. Y. Tumanov [2004, 2005], R. Reinhardt, S. Daud, D. Lott [2005, 2006]], B. Hall, S. Van [2003] are among them.

When it is called information modeling - we understand the process of managing information processing on the basis of the technology of electronic computing experience using various types of information and instrumental systems in the subject areas, so we teach the technology of using these systems in solving a number of professional tasks and in information systems teaching the main functions, methods and tools used in information processing is an important component of information modeling education.

Research methodology (Research Methodology).

A wide variety of software tools that require the implementation of a computer information model can be considered as a means of teaching information modeling in visual graphs. A special type of computing models (visually in graphs) selected in the teaching of information modeling, as well as the solution of professional tasks corresponding to the main stages of electronic computing experience, where mastering of information-analytical activities by a future specialist takes place taking into account, semi-formal and abstract formal systems as educational tools can be considered as a type of information systems.

Thus, we consider the characteristics of formal and semi-formal systems, as well as professional instrumental systems as a means of teaching information modeling in visual form. When choosing software products, we proceed from the definition of requirements that this or that digital educational resource and educational computer model must satisfy.

- Analysis and results (Analysis and results).

Formal languages as educational tools for building formalized descriptions of information models at different levels in the teaching of information modeling in visual graphs in the form of the "Information Modeling" training course: logical-mathematical languages (the language of formal set theory) and programming languages (operative paradigm).

In addition, according to the classification presented on the website of the multimedia center of information-educational resources (ATR), the place where central electronic educational resources are stored is divided according to the technology of their creation and is represented by the following: 1. Open multimedia systems e-learning modules; 2. Electronic learning modules of virtual collective environments; 3. Electronic information and educational resources (EATR) in local carriers; 4. EATRs with textographic network; 5. EATRs based on flash technologies; 6. EATRs based on java technologies.

We will consider a brief description of the main software tools that implement the technology of development of electronic or digital educational resources of textographic network, flash technologies, java technologies.

1. Java technologies are based on the Java language, which is a platform-independent, object-oriented programming language designed primarily for use on the Internet.

Independent applications (Applications) on the Java platform; Applets (Applets) - programs that work in the browser environment; servlets (Servlets) - small programs that work on the server side and extend the functions of the server; components (JavaBeans, Enterprise JavaBeans) - a part of a program separated into a small functional and separate element with a graphical interface or encapsulated logic of application and data, developed for the purpose of repeated use in component programming technology.

As a Java platform for the development of digital educational resources, primarily in the form of interactive multimedia educational computer models, it is represented by powerful capabilities that combine traditional web technologies with the technology of Java-applets. A Java applet is a byte-code program in Java. Java applets are executed in a web browser using a Java Virtual Machine (JVM) or Sun's AppletViewer, a standalone tool for testing applets. Applets are used to provide interactive features of web applications that cannot be provided by HTML. Because Java bytecode is platform-independent, Java applets can be implemented by browsers on many platforms, including Microsoft Windows, UNIX, Apple, Mac OS, and GNU/Linux, using plug-ins.

To increase the interactive capabilities in the applet, the tools of class libraries (AWT, JFC Swing packages) can be used, which provide mouse and keyboard processing, adding user interface components (records, buttons, text input fields, flags, etc.) to the applet. To use the visual and graphic capabilities in the educational computer model, geometric classes and graphic methods tools (Graphics, Graphics2D classes) can be used, which can create dynamic and interactive images, control the color, size, location of graphic objects, edit the graphic file. Allows adding grid images from a URL to an applet and playing audio clips. Applets are included in a web document with the applet or object tag, and loading an applet into a browser window is done by downloading a web document on the server, just like an applet class.

2. Flash technologies provide more attractive opportunities for the development of interactive and multimedia educational computer models that are easily integrated into web applications and are available in the network mode of operation. Flash represents a well-organized environment for displaying and combining various multimedia tools such as interactive animation, sound files, effects and videos, as well as the ActionScript programming language tool. Special attention is paid to flash technologies for a wide range of specialists in the scientific works of domestic and foreign researchers [3].

Flash can be used to create animations, effects, vector graphics, interactive applications, programs, presentations, and websites. In this case, all components are included in the Flash environment and then saved in a custom format of FLA files. A file in FLA format contains the necessary resources, including images, video footage, sound and software, and can be edited accordingly. The Flash content is then published in compact SWF files for display on various platforms using a Flash player. A file in SWF format is a compiled version of a file in FLA format. In particular, it is possible to import text, mesh and vector graphics, files in PDF format and sound files (for example, in WAV and MRZ formats) into a document in FLA format (from Photoshop, Illustrator and FreeHand documents).

Animation tools represent the unique advantages of Flash technology for visualizing graphical models. Flash has three different mechanisms for animating objects. These are: 1) frame-by-frame ("classic") animation - in which the author creates each frame of the future "cartoon" or imports it from other

applications and sets the sequence of their viewing; 2) automatic animation (also called tweened-animation) — when creating it, the author creates only the first and last frames of multiplication, while Flash automatically generates all intermediate frames; there are two types of tweened-animation, which are: animation based on the movement of the object (motion animation) and animation based on the transformation (changing the shape) of the object (shape animation); 3) script-based animation is the description of the object's behavior in its own Flash language called ActionScript, the syntax of which is similar to the syntax of other scripting languages used in web advertising (for example, JavaScript and VBScript).

Flash technologies, in addition to advanced multimedia tools and the ability to insert compact swf files into web pages, due to the use of standard interface elements (UI components: text fields, buttons, drop-down lists, etc.) and the built-in ActionScript programming language has means of providing interactive communication with the user.

The syntax of the language is similar to that of JavaScript, where script code is executed within an animation timeline [4]. ActionScript is defined as an object-oriented programming language with loosely typed event processing.

According to the presented comparative analysis of opportunities for our choice of technologies and software products (see Table 1), according to the selected factors, the group of technological and economic factors is the most difficult. The main factors affecting the choice in connection with the highly developed software and technical capabilities of the presented instrumental systems, which allow the implementation of a wide range of didactic and functional opportunities in the form of java-application, flash-roller or VB-applications in the developed product - ease of learning and skill requirements, as well as purchase price and terms. J2SE products are distributed free of charge, but require high qualification.

The decisive factor in using instrumental systems as a tool for teaching information modeling in visual graphs and creating digital educational resources for visual graph models in the form of OMM is the initial familiarization of students with the instrumental system. In this case, it is appropriate to use Visual Basic, which is introduced in the computer science course (for example, [89]). This software can be used in laboratory work.

In addition, in order to understand the factors affecting the choice of software tools, it is important to determine the type of digital resource being developed and the methodological features to be implemented. It is necessary to take into account the development experience and specification of educational resources, including the leading organizations dealing with the problems of e-learning standardization.

Each of the above-mentioned instrumental development systems can be chosen as a design learning tool (to the extent that they use visual information modeling in graphs in the development of R&D) because it meets the requirements for educational tools. Instrumentation systems (Java2 SE SDK, Macromedia Flash MX), like other professional programs, meet the requirements for character-symbol tools, being a character-character model with its own language, conditional symbols.

- Conclusion and recommendations (Conclusion/Recommendations).

Thus, according to the above, Java2 SE SDK 5.0 and Macromedia Flash MX 6, 8 package (java-applet technology and flash technologies) are the main design tools for this methodological system within the framework of teaching information modeling in graphs visually. can be considered as The choice

of these technologies and software tools is not related to the simplicity of ODM implementation, but to the possibility of providing a high level of interactivity through programming languages, networking and visualization, in which object-oriented programming, programming language class libraries, specific knowledge in the field of user interface design is activated, applied and deepened. In conclusion, it should be said that a tutorial containing a module on the use of Java2 SE SDK and Macromedia Flash MX in teaching information modeling in visual graphs is presented [5].

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**THEORETICAL BASICS OF PROFESSIONAL-CRITICAL APPROACH
IN ORGANIZING MEDIA EDUCATION AND PEDAGOGICAL
ACTIVITY**

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the methods of media education, the teaching of creative assignments based on media materials.

KEYWORDS

Media education, media education models, media education practice, media materials, information technologies.

Introduction

Integration processes taking place in modern education make the use of modern technologies and active forms of interaction within the educational process urgent. The potential of pedagogical technologies is used in various fields such as philology, history, social studies, legal education, foreign language, geography, ecology, world artistic culture. In recent years, pedagogical technologies have been actively used in the practice of media education in our country. Pedagogical technology means "a set of means and methods of reproduction of theoretically based educational and educational processes that enable successful achievement of educational goals. Pedagogical technology consists of instructions for methods of activity (didactic processes), conditions under which this activity is implemented (organizational forms of education) and means of implementation of this activity" [1]. Let's turn to an example from the reality of Russia. It is known that the possibilities of interactive informal communication are very actively used by modern schoolchildren and students in chats and mobile phones. Modern telecommunication networks, for example, allow communication participants to enter into an interactive dialogue in real time. In the process of interaction (interaction -?), it is possible to discuss news, movies, express your opinion on the problem of interest by participating in the forums. N.W. Zmanovskaya, for example, offers an interesting innovative form of work on media education of future pedagogues at the Higher Education Institution - a pedagogical studio. Workshops in the studio focused on strengthening the direction of using hypertext for the purpose of media education, developing the skills of students to search for information in the process of acquiring knowledge, processing, storing and using information in the pedagogical process, and developing the critical thinking of the audience. Thus, the media (in this case - computer technology) is not only an educational tool for information transfer or a daily technical device for spontaneous interactive

communication, but is becoming an educational multimedia environment that offers information that helps to solve certain pedagogical tasks in the form of hypertext. The development of media-communicative literacy of students in pedagogical studio sessions includes the acquisition of operational, procedural (order) and behavioral knowledge and skills that are the basis for future pedagogical activities. In our opinion, interactive interaction based on dialogue has great prospects in modern education (not only higher education institutions, but also in school education).

As stated by N. Krlova, in the course of modern education, "it is necessary to avoid the use of non-standard pedagogical tasks and methods of clear, unambiguous answers to the teacher's questions. We need methods that allow the student to think broadly about the topic of the problem, and the answer itself is not important, but to search for the answer, immerse in the world of thinking together (within a group, dialogue) and search for the relative truth in the absence of knowledge and primary information. One of such methods actively used in the process of media education was considered "big questions", they are not a one-size-fits-all answer to the question posed by the pedagogue, but a creative approach and an independent understanding of the works of media culture. Examples of 'big questions' are: 'Give three explanations for why...?', 'Explain why...?', 'What is the difference between...?', 'Guess what if... will be?' etc. These types of questions are called problematic and have been around since the time of Socrates, Pythagoras, etc. Problematic questions help to activate the research activity of pupils and students. Creating problem situations and organizing independent research activities of the audience can also be used in the media education process, and it is aimed at "forming students' independence in learning, developing their logical, mental, critical and creative thinking and cognitive abilities".

M.M. Levina, emphasizing the importance of problem-based education, considers it "one of the main educational technologies that implements the humanistic direction of the science and practice of pedagogy." It is not by chance that posing problematic questions, as well as using problematic situations, are widespread in the practice of media education. For example, Yu.N. Usov, G.N. Polichko, A.V. Spichkin, A.V. Fedorov et al.'s models of media education emphasize problematic, heuristic, playful and other productive forms of education that "develop students' individuality, independence of thought, creative activity, perception, interpretation and analysis of media text structure, assimilation of knowledge about media culture" [2].

Research Methodology

Creating problem situations based on the study of works of media culture, their comprehensive independent analysis will help to increase the cognitive activity of the audience, develop the emotional sphere, and creative abilities. Using the main components of problem-based learning makes it possible to achieve these goals, namely:

- increases schoolchildren's (students') basic knowledge of the world of media culture (its theoretical, terminological and historical-pedagogical foundations), the relevance of working with media works of various forms and genres;
- mastering new concepts and methods of action, as well as applying them in practice in connection with media creation.

Acquiring new knowledge about media and media culture is always related to the questions that arise, which, in turn, predetermine the vector of obtaining answers to the problem of solving the studied problem or the attitude to the received information, so, for example, understanding and analyzing a

watched film or television show. A serious work related to . Thus, the search for independent and sometimes difficult answers to questions of interest motivates a person to think and research related to the media.

Design activities are increasingly actively used in school and higher education media education. Projects related to media education are represented as an important example of cognitive activity, creativity, and at the same time the formation of certain personal qualities of pupils (students). The method of students' (students') research projects is aimed at applying acquired knowledge about media culture and mastering new ones. The activity of designing media material allows the audience to become an active participant in the educational process, helps to acquire teamwork skills. Project activity is of particular importance in the process of developing the critical thinking of the school audience (students), because creative work on the project helps to form "constructive critical thinking, which is difficult to learn in the ordinary school system." Students develop a personal analytical view of information, and the evaluation scheme given from above: "This is right and that is wrong" is no longer valid.

Analysis and Results

Effectiveness of project methodology in media education, A.V. According to Spichkin, it is determined by the following reasons:

- project methodology is person-oriented, that is, the developmental aspect is one of the leading aspects in meta-education;
- learning during the implementation of the project is self-motivating, which means an increase in interest and involvement in the work during its implementation;
- finally, in the methodology of projects, the hierarchy of "teacher-student" interactions is significantly different from traditional educational methods [6].

The teacher helps the audience in the search for information while working on the media project, and at the same time is a source of information and a coordinator of the audience's work. Its most important task is to support and encourage students, to activate their creative activities. As the main condition for the implementation of media education projects in the school environment, A.V. Spichkin distinguishes the following:

- in order for schoolchildren to have the opportunity to compare the possibilities of different equipment and to understand the specific features of their use, they should be provided with the opportunity to use all the equipment in the educational institution;
- it is necessary to take into account the complex aspects of the production process related to the acquisition of technical equipment in order to ensure the management of project implementation;
- schoolchildren must understand the correct definition of the scope of the implemented projects. Projects should have clearly defined goals and target a specific audience;
- schoolchildren should not set tasks beyond their level of technical and artistic preparation. Before starting the work, it is necessary to clearly define the quality criteria of the final product, after achieving them, the work is considered complete;
- the practical activities of schoolchildren on the creation of media texts and the discussion of its results should help them understand how media messages are created, distributed and consumed;

– every teacher working with schoolchildren must have a clear idea of the general structure, goals and tasks of the project at one or another stage of its implementation. Solving specific tasks related to specific school subjects should be subordinated to the general goal[3].

These cases, in our opinion, apply not only to the process of school media education, but also to the process of media education in HEIs. "Media Education" in working with students on creative media education projects within the specialty subjects for Pedagogical Higher Education Institutions, for example, creating and creatively implementing personal media products (socio-pedagogical films, newspapers, commercials) for students of different ages, school events (optional, in the film club) training) includes design activities such as developing scenarios. Before moving on to practical implementation of projects, students can be offered the following challenging questions:

- for what purpose is this or that media material (release of a film, presentation, newspaper, magazine, radio broadcast, etc.) prepared;
- what pedagogical goals and tasks the author of the project (group of authors) sets for himself;
- what main priorities and ideas form its basis, etc.

Thus, the preparation of media education projects, interactive forms of working with works of media culture, posing problematic questions, etc., allow to successfully solve the main tasks of media education, and help the development of media competence of the young generation.

Summary

In the process of globalization, the rapid spread of information sources, the enormous increase in the amount of socially important (scientific, technological, cultural, etc.) information cannot fail to have an impact on any society.

Therefore, providing young people with the necessary and necessary information related to the media in the process of preparing them for the profession will guarantee their further activities. This leads to an adequate reflection of the image of the real world in their minds and allows them to work in harmony with the environment.

Thus, the preparation of media education projects, interactive forms of working with works of media culture, posing problematic questions, etc., allow to successfully solve the main tasks of media education, and help the development of media competence of the young generation.

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**CREATIVE THINKING AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO COGNITIVE
AND SKILL ACHIEVEMENT IN HANDBALL AMONG SECOND-
YEAR STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Researchers in the field of education, physical education and sports sciences have been interested in the subject of creative thinking and its applications as it is one of the important mental activities that influence the athlete's personality and determine his behavior in the environment in which he lives, with the belief that there is a clear impact of individual differences between individuals in the nature of the mental abilities that distinguish them from each other. The other. Since the handball event is one of the important sporting events that attracts a lot of attention among students in colleges of physical education, and given the student's need to understand the nature of skill and cognitive performance through the basic vocabulary of the handball subject, the importance of the research lies in how to achieve the best learning process from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Therefore, measuring creative thinking and knowing the extent of its relationship to cognitive and skill achievement. The problem of the research lies in the lack of a test for cognitive achievement in the subject of handball. The need arose to work on building a test for this purpose through the use of precise scientific methods in order to address the basic research problem, And skills in handball. The aim of the study is to identify the relationship between creative thinking and cognitive and skill achievement in handball among second-year students at the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - Kirkuk University.</p> <p>The hypothesis of the study is that there is no statistically significant relationship between creative thinking and cognitive and skill achievement in handball among second-year students. The researchers used the</p>	<p>Creative thinking, cognitive and skill achievement, handball.</p>

experimental method, and the sample was randomly selected from second-year students. Through the results, the researchers reached the following conclusions:

.1 There is a relationship between creative thinking and cognitive achievement in handball.

. 2The students' interest in cognitive achievement was better than their interest in skill achievement in handball.

The researchers recommended:

. 1 Emphasizing the importance of developing creative thinking in training in physical education colleges in Qatar, especially developing the cognitive and mental aspects of students.

2. Working to provide the appropriate psychological environment for students that contributes to creating opportunities for creativity and creative thinking for them in a manner consistent with the educational goals pursued by the educational curricula in Iraqi universities.

التفكير الابداعي وعلاقته بالتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري في لعبة كرة اليد لدى طلاب المرحلة الثانوية م.م
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ملخص البحث

اهتم الباحثون في مجال التربية والتربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة في موضوع التفكير الابداعي ونطوبؤانه بوصفه احد النشاطات العظيمة المهمة التي تؤثر في شخصية الرياضي وتحدد سلوكه في البيئة التي يعيش بها ومع اليمان بان هناك تأثيراً واضح للثروق الفردية بين الافراد في طبيعة الؤدرات العقلية التي يميزهم بعضهم عن البعض الاخر. ولما كانت فعالية كرة اليد من الؤعالؤات الرياضية المهمة التي تسنؤطب الكثير من الؤمام لدى الطلبة في كليات التربية الرياضية ونظرا لحاجة الطالب الى ادراك طبيعة الؤداء المهاري والمعرفي من خلال المفردات الساسية لمادة كرة اليد فان اهمية البحث نكمن في كينية تحؤيق انضل عملة للؤلم من الناحيتين النظرية والعملة لذا نان نؤياس الؤنؤكير الابداعي ومعرفة مدى علاقؤنه بالؤصؤل المعرفي والمهاري . اما مشؤلة البحث فؤن ني عدم وجود اؤنؤار للؤصؤل المعرفي في مادة كرة اليد نؤلؤت الحاجة الى ضرورة العمل على بؤاء اؤنؤار لهذا الؤرض من خلال اسؤؤام السالؤب العلمة الؤؤؤؤة وذلك من اجل معالجة مشؤلة البحث الساسية والتي نؤؤدت ني محاولة معرفة ما هي الؤالؤة بين الؤنؤكير الابداعي والؤصؤل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كرة اليد . وؤؤف الؤراسة هو الؤؤرف على الؤالؤة بين الؤنؤكير الابداعي والؤصؤل المعرفي والمهاري ني مادة كرة اليد لدى طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة – جامعة كركوك.

ونؤرض الؤراسة هو الؤؤؤد عالؤة ذات داللة احصائية بين الؤنؤكير الابداعي والؤصؤل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كرة اليد لدى طالب المرحلة الثانوية . واسؤؤدم الباحثون الؤنؤؤج التجريبي ، واؤنؤرت الؤؤؤة بالطرؤؤة الؤشؤائة من طالب المرحلة الثانوية . ومن خلال الؤؤؤؤ نؤصل الباحثون الى الؤسؤنؤؤات الؤالؤة :

1. هناك علاقة بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المعرفي في مادة كرة اليد .
2. ان اهتمام الطلبة بالتحصيل المعرفي كان انضل من اهتمامهم بالتحصيل المهاري في مادة كرة اليد .

واوصى الباحثون :

1. التأكيد على أهمية تطوير التفكير الابداعي في التدريب في كليات التربية الرياضية بالقطر والسويما ونمجة الجوانب المعرفية والعلوية لدى الطلبة .
 2. العمل على توفير البيئة النفسية المناسبة للطلبة والتي تساهم في خلق فرص الابداع والتفكير الابداعي لديهم بما ينسجم والاهداف التربوية التي تسعى اليها المناهج العلوية في الجامعات العراقية .
- الكلمات المفتاحية:** التفكير الابداعي ، التحصيل المعرفي والمهاري ، كرة اليد .

1- التعريف بالبحث .

1-1 المقدمة وأهمية البحث .

اهتم الباحثون في مجال التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة الابداعي ونطبيته بوصفه احد النشاطات العظيمة المهمة التي تؤثر في شخصية الرياضي وتحدد سلوكه في البيئة التي يعيش بها ومع اليمان بان هناك تأثيراً واضحاً للثروة الفكرية بين الأفراد في طبيعة الفدرات العظيمة التي تميزهم بعضهم عن البعض الآخر فان التفكير الابداعي يبقى احد المعطيات العظيمة لهذه الفروق السلوكية بين الأفراد وذلك ما أكدته الدراسات العلمية السابفة التي عزيت بدراسة الحقائق لمثل هذا التفاوت وعالته بالجوانب المعرفية عند الرياضي في هذا الميدان اذ ان العظيمة تطوير العلوية هي احد المحركات الساسية المهمة لبناء الجيل من خلال الستخدام الامل للدرات البشرية والعلمية والسويما المبدعين في المجتمع وذلك من خلال العناية بهم والعمل على تنمية مواهبهم على وفق مزاج معرفية متقدمة يمكن ان توافر القواعد المناسبة لمخرجات علمية تؤدي دورها المهم في المجتمع .

اهتمت الدراسات والبحوث في التربية البدنية وعلوم والرياضة اهتماماً كبيراً بأساليب العلم من أجل النوصل الى انضل الساليب والطرائق التي يصاحبها دراية وخبرة عالية من قبل المدربين والمدرسين لغرض زيادة سفاع العلم مع الدرس بما يبالعم وفدراته البدنية العامة للوصول الى تحقيق الاهداف العلوية ومن ثم الرقاء بمسوى

العلم ، الامر الذي ادى الى ايجاد اساليب حديثة في العلم والسعي الى تطبيق انضلهما والتي تمكن المدرس من إيصال العلم الى انضل مسوى في الاء المهاري .

ولما كانت فعالية كرة اليد من الفعاليات الرياضية المهمة التي تسقط الكثير من الامل لدى الطلبة في كليات التربية الرياضية ونظراً لحاجة الطالب الى ادراك طبيعة الاء المهاري والمعرفي من خلال المفردات الساسية لمادة كرة اليد فان أهمية البحث تكمن في كينية تحقيق انضل عملية للعلم من الناحية النظرية والعملية لذا فان قياس التفكير الابداعي ومعرفة مدى عالونه بالتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري لدى اولئك الطلبة يمكن ان يثير اهتمام الكثير من الباحثين في مجال التربية الرياضية السباب عديدة تأتي في مقدمتها الؤاعة المترتبة على أهمية دراسة التفكير لحل المشكالت ونظيم العلومات ونحسين المخرجات الدائفة عن طريق الابداع والسويما في مادة كرة

اليد .

اذ يؤدي التفكير دوراً بارزاً ومؤثراً لدى الفرد في الؤيام بالتفكيرات والفعاليات التي ال يمكن بدونه الؤيام بها على نحو فعال وكما هو معلوم فان التفكير الابداعي يعد من ارئع مسويات التنظيم المعرفي انه يؤوم على الادراك وان استعماله يتطلب من الفرد نشاطاً عولياً يكون الكثر عولياً من النشاط التي يتطلب من المسويات الأخرى . (الزبيد، 1999، 117).

2-1 مشكلة البحث .

تهد دراسة الابداع ضرورة ملحة واساسية للمجتمعات الانسانية كانه بما في ذلك المجتمع الرياضي وعلى الرغم من تعدد النظريات والادبيات التي تحاول ان تفسر الابداع على اسس طبيعوية او عملية او شخصية او زمنية او

وراثية .

فان الابداع يبقو رمزا مهما وؤدرة عقلية متميزة في السلوك الذي تحدد شخصية الفرد ومما الشك فيه ان الرياضة بوصفها ظاهرة اجتماعية تبنى مفهوم الابداع بمعناه العام والتفكير الابداعي عند الداء على وجه الخصوص في عملية التعلم للمهارات الساسية في الالعاب الرياضية المختلفة والسبب في ذلك ان الابداع في الرياضة ليس له اهمية اتاحة الفرصة لتشجيع كل عمل ادائي مبدع في المجالين التربوي والرياضي سواء كان ذلك في التدريب او المنافسة الرياضية او التعلم ، ومع خصوصية كثر الابداع كفعالية رياضية تتميز بالشمول في الداء من النزاح بين المهارية والمعرفية والتي تتطلب نهما واضحا لطبيعة الداء وصول الى الداء المثل فان هذه الفعالية مازالت

بحاجة الى المزيد من البحث والتوصي عن الحقائق العلمية لمفرداتها الدراسية .

ومن اجل قياس الابداع والتفكير الابداعي كان الابداع من البحث عن الوسائل والدوات التي يمكن ان تؤدم خدمة علمية للباحثين ولعل من اهمها اختبار التفكير الابداعي والاختبارات التحصيلية المعرفية والمهارية التي يمكن ان تؤود الى نتائج علمية هامة تؤدم عملية البحث العلمي ونظرا لعدم وجود اختبار للتحصيل المعرفي في مادة كثر الابداع تولدت الحاجة الى ضرورة العمل على بناء اختبار لهذا الغرض من خلال استخدام الساليب العلمية الحديثة وذلك من اجل معالجة مشكلة البحث الساسية والتي تحددت في محاولة معرفة ما هي العلاقة بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كثر الابداع سعيا الى تحقيق زيادة علمية متواصلة تضاف الى البحوث

والدراسات السابقة وذلك من اجل خدمة الحركة الرياضية وتطويرها نحو الامام .

1-3 هدانا البحث .

يهدف البحث الى :

- قياس التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كثر الابداع لدى طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة - جامعة كركوك .

- التعرف على العلاقة بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كثر الابداع لدى طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة - جامعة كركوك .

1-4 فرضية البحث .

- الوجود علاقة ذات دلالة احصائية بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المعرفي والمهاري في مادة كثر الابداع لدى طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة - جامعة كركوك .

1-5 مجالات البحث .

- المجال البشري: طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة - جامعة كركوك للعام الدراسي

2023 - 2024 .

- المجال الزمني: للمدة المحصورة ما بين 2023/11/5 الى 2023/11/23 .

-المجال المكاني: الجامعة المستنصرية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة في جامعة كركوك .

3- منهج البحث واجراءاته الميدانية .

1-3 منهج البحث . استخدم الباحثان المنهج الوصفي بطريقة الوصفيات المتبادلة لملاءمة وطبيعة البحث .

2-3 مجتمع البحث وعينه . اشتمل مجتمع البحث على طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم

الرياضة - جامعة كركوك للعام الدراسي 2023-2024 (والبالغ عددهم 100) طالب موزعين على شعبتين دراسية

العينة الثانوية الغراض التطبيق النهائي للختبار و بواقع (30) طالباً يمثلون نسبة 30% من مجتمع البحث ، ومن أجل ضمان الشروط العلمية وسلامة الاختبار تم اسنبعاد الطالبات والراسبون والمؤجلون .

3-3 ادوات البحث .

1- مقاييس التفكير الابداعي (برنستن 1989)

تم اللطالع على عدة مقاييس للتفكير الابداعي وان الباحثان اختار هذا المقياس من بين عدة مقاييس ، تم نصميم هذا المقياس من قبل العالم (برنستن، 1989) و يتكون المقياس بالاصل من 74 نؤرة بهدف لقياس التفكير الابداعي لدى الافراد وتكون الجابة عليها من خلال اختيار احد ثلاثة بدائل (وهي) اوانق ، متردد، ال اوانق) . اذ تتراوح الدرجة الكلية للمقياس من (74-222) درجة، كما قامت (السرور ، 1994) بتعريب المقياس المذكور و تجربته في الرردن وذلك لغرض اسخدامه في البحوث والدراسات في البيئة العربية. ملحق (1) (السرور، 2002، 246).

251 .

- التجربة الستهطالعية . تم اجراء التجربة الستهطالعية على عينة زوامها (5) طالب من المرحلة الثانوية والذين

تم اسنبعادهم من الدراسة وكان الهدف من التجربة هو مايلي:

1. التعرف على مالمعة النفرات المعدة لهذا الغرض.

2. مدى وضوح النفرات للمستهجوب.

3. تحديد الوقت الالزم للجابة.

4. التاكيد من وضوح تعليميات الاختبار .

5. اعداد الصورة النهائية للنفرات قبل اللقيام بتطبيقها احصائيا.

- المواصفات العلمية لمقياس برنستن .

- الصدق : يعد الصدق اهم شروط الاختبار الجيد والاختبار الصادق هو الذي ينجح في قياس ماوضع من اجله

ويتميز بين الافراد (الظاهر واخرون ، 2002، 133)

ويتمتع المقياس الحالي بمعامل صدق ونبات عالين من خلال الاجراءات العلمية التي قام

بها (برنستن، 1989) لنصميم المقياس نضال عن الاجراءات العلمية الاخرى التي قامت بها (السرور، 2002) على

البيئة العربية ال ان الباحثان قامو بعرض المقياس المذكور على عدد من السادة الخبراء من ذوي الخبرة

والختصاص في مجال العلوم التربوية والنفسية والرياضية ، للتاكيد من صالمعته لقياس الغرض الذي وضع من اجله

في البيئة العراقية. لبيان راءهم في صالمعة النفرات واجراء التعديلات المناسبة واعتمد الباحثان نسبة اتفاق 75%

فاكثر لقبول النفرات اذ يشير (بلوم، 1983) الى ان اتفاق الخبراء يعد عالي اذ كان 0.75% فاكثر ، (بلوم

واخرون ، 1983، 126).

- الثبات : يؤصد بثبات المقياس هو اعطاء النتائج زفسها او زنائج مشابهة اذا ما اعيد تطبيقه مرة ثانية على الافراد (-

test retest) لافهم وفي الظروف زفسها (الجاغوب ، 2002، 245) . وؤد قام الباحثان باستخدام طريقة الالعادة) بعد

مرور (8) ايام من تاريخ تطبيقه على الطالب والبالغ عددهم (5) وؤد تم اختيارهم عشوائيا وؤد بلغت قيمة معامل

الثبات (0.82) (ويشير) سمارة واخرون ، 1989) الى ان معامل الثبات يعد عالي اذ كان (0.75) فاكثر (سمارة

واخرون ، 1989، 120) وفي ضوء ما تؤدم من اجراءات اصبح المقياس جاهزا للتطبيق في البيئة العراقية

- مفتاح نصحيح اداة اختبار التفكير الابداعي . اعتمدت الباحثان المعيار التي حددت اصل في الاختبار الذي اعده

(السرور) 1994) وذلك باعطاء البدائل (اوانق ، ال اوانق ، متردد) (1، 2، 3) على التتابع وبذلك اصبحت الدرجة

الكلية محصورة ما بين (74-222).

2. اختبار التحصيل المعرفي في مادة كلفة اليد . تعد الاختبارات التحصيلية من الكثر ادوات التقييم شيعا واستخدما وغالبا ما يحصل الطلبة من المعرفة والنهم والمهارات التي تنصل بالمنهاج الدراسي التي يدرسها الطلبة . وترمي الاختبارات التحصيلية الى قياس بعض اشكال الؤدرات (الغظية) أي ما تعلمه الشخص من اجل المعرفة او العمل وفي مجال الدراسة وتهدف هذه الاختبارات الى قياس مؤدار ما حصله الطالب من محتويات مادة من المواد الدراسية وهي تؤوم اساسا على تحديد المستوى المعرفي للالمنيد أي ناسب درجة كل طالب .(الصالح ، 2004،26).

ولتحقيق هدف البحث المنضم من قياس التحصيل المعرفي لدى طالب السنة الثانية في مادة كلفة اليد نؤد نطلب ذلك بناء اختبار تحصيلي معرفي في مادة كلفة اليد على ونق المنهاج الدراسي المقرر لهذه المادة من جانب الهيئة الوطنية للتقنيات التربوية البنوية وعلوم الرياضة في العراق وؤد نم نصميم الاختبار بطرؤة الاختيار المنعدد

(وذلك الزه من الكثر الاختبارات العلمية ثباتا في صدق احكامها وتؤدير ما يحرزه الطالب (multiple choose) من درجات ، وما تميز به من موضوعية وشمول للمادة واقتصادية في الوقت ويتكون الاختبار من 40(نؤرة وينم الجابة على الاختبار باختيار بديل واحد من ثالثة بدائل .)الغريب ،203،1985).

- التجربة الاستطالية للاختبار . اجرئت التجربة الستطالية للاختبار بعد التعديلات التي طرأت على النؤرات حسب اراء السادة الخبراء على 5) طالب من المرحلة الثانية في لفة التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة جامعة كركوك وكان الهدف منه هو :

- 1.مدى معرفة وضوح نؤرات الاختبار .
 - 2.معرفة الصعوبات التي يواجهها الطالب عند الجابة .
 - 3.تؤدير الوقت النمودجي للجابة .
- الالاس العلمية للاختبار المعرفي .

- الصدق . يمثّل الصدق احد الشروط الاساسية للحكيم على صالحة الاختبار اذ يعد الاختبار صادقا اذا كان يقيس ما وضع لقياسه ويميز بين النراد .(الخولي ،72،1998) وللتأكد من صدق الاختبار نم استخدم الطرائق الالوية : (ني هذا المجال الى ان انضل Eble1.الصدق الظاهري . وؤد اعتمد الباحثان الصدق الظاهري اذ اشار اهل) وسيلة للتأكد من صدق الالاة هو ان يقرر عدد المختصين مدى غظية النؤرات لجوانب الصنة المراد قياسها . (Eble , 1972, P.555).

2.صدق المحتوى . ان الاختبار يكون صادقا عندما يبنى على المواد التي تعلمها الطلبة و يكون مندرجا ني (Farr , 1970 , p.303)صعوبته ويخبر ما هو متؤوع من الطلبة ان يحقؤونه في المرحلة التي هم نيها .) يهدف صدق المحتوى الى معرفة مدى تمثيل الاختبار او المقياس لجوانب الصمة او الصنة او الؤدرة المطلوب قياسها.

- ثبات الاختبار . يعد الثبات من المؤشرات الضرورية للاختبار الزه يعني مدى قياس الاختبار المؤدار الحؤويقي للسممة التي يهدف لقياسها .(عالم ، 131،2000).منك طرائق عديدة الستخراج الثبات وانضل الطرائق في الاختبارات التحصيلية الموضوعية هو استخدام الطرائق البيانية وؤد استخدم الباحثان معادلة كودر-

ريشاردسون 20)K20(النها نعامل مع الاختبارات ذات الجابة)0-1(الزيمان ، 2004 ، 247). وؤد قام

الباحثان بتحويل استجابات الطالب بتطبيق المعادلة على البيانات المستحصلة اذ بلغت معامل الثبات 0.83(وذلك يدل على ان الاختبار يتمتع بمعامل ثبات عال .

- مناسح نصحيح اداة اختبار التحصيل المعرفي في كلفة اليد : بما ان نؤرات الاختبار التحصيلي موضوعية ومن زوع الاختبار المنعدد نالتي البدائل اعطت الباحثان درجة واحدة للجابة الصحوية اما الجابة الخاطرة نم حنه صنرا وبذلك انحصرت الدرجة بين 0-40(وتسمى السؤال منزا والجابات بدائل)ملمح ، 212،2000).

- اختبار التحصيل المهاري . وهي الاختبارات التي تؤيس اداء الفرد العملي وهي نعلم على قياس نؤويم ما

من الجدول (6) (وبعد موازنة قيمة) ف(المحتسبة مع قيمة) ف(الجدولة والبالغة 3.3404 عند درجة حرية) 2- (28) ومسوى معنوية 0.05 وهذا يبين اهمية المعادلة من الدرجة الثانية في التنبؤ المتغير المعتمد ، وكذلك ثم الاستمرار باستخدام معادلة من درجة اعلى واختبارها ، ووجد ان المعادلة من الدرجة الثالثة كانت: وبمعامل تحديده وهذا يدل على ان زيادة الدرجة الثالثة كان لها تأثير نيه المتغيرات الحاصلة في التحصيل المعرفي بنسبة 0.7 تقريبا عما كانت عليه في حالة الدرجة الثانية ، كما هو موضح في الجدول (7)

الجدول (7) تحليل تباين النحدر بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المعرفي والمعادلة النحدرية من الدرجة الثالثة

التباين	متوسط المربعات	مجموع المربعات	درجة الحرية	قيمة ف
النحدر	85.9825	257.948	3	6.151**
البواقي	13.9780	377.407	27	
الكلية		635.355	30	

**معنوية عند نسبة خطأ 0.05%.

لوحظ من الجدول (7) ان معادلة النحدر من الدرجة الثالثة كانت معنوية عند نسبة احتمال 0.01 اذ بلغت قيمة) ف(المحسوبة 6.151 وهي اكبر من قيمة) ف(الجدولة والبالغة 2.9604 عند درجة حرية) 3-27) ونسبة المهمة المعادلة من الدرجة الثالثة في التنبؤ بالتحصيل المعرفي نود ثم التوقف عندها ، ويبين الشكل (3) طبيعة هذه العلاقة بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المعرفي.

- فكيف البداعي .

شكل (1) يبين العلاقة النحدرية (من الدرجة الثالثة) بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المعرفي يمكن للشكل التنتاري المرسوم من نتائج الجدول ان يعطينا نوعا او نبيوا لتؤديرات الالعبين حيث يوضح من الشكل (3) اعلى تحصيل ثم الحصول عليه عند درجة 188 أي كلما ارتفعت درجات الطلبة عن الوسط الفرضي كلما كانت العلاقة في اعلى ذروته وعزو الباحثان هذه النتيجة الى امكانية الطالب في التعرّف عن استعدادهم لممارسة التفكير البداعي من خلال المواقف التي يمرون بها التي نعد وسيطا مهما في تونير العلاقة العلمية بين هذين المتغيرين اذ ان استعداد الطالب لتنبؤ المهام المعرفية التي تتطلبها طبيعة الداء بشكل عام والسببما في الدروس النظرية التي يشارك فيها ومن بينها مادة كثره الابد.

توصلت هذه الدراسة بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المعرفي الى ان الدروس النظرية والتي تمثل جهدا مهما من المتعلم في

بشكل واسع وذلك يُنتق مع ما اشار اليه ، ومن خلال التحليل العلمي لنظريات الابداع في علم النفس والتي نحاول ان نفرر بمخرجاتها ونواتج البحث الحالي نتجد ان (جبلنورد) يد اشار الى مثل هذه العالوة في انموذجه البيزة العظوية (1956) والذي ميز بين العمليات العظوية والمحسوية والنتائج معتمدا في ذلك على نوع كل منها وصول الى التؤويم واصدار الحكماء في ضوء الخبرات والمعارف السابقة وفي الاتجاه نفسه نؤد ذهب السلوكيون في نفسيرهم لالبداع الى ابعده من ذلك في تحديد العالوة بين التفكير الابداعي والجوانب المعرفية عند الانسان وذلك يُنتق ايضا مع ماذهب اليه (ميدنوك) وذلك ما يدعوا النتائج الحالية التي توصلت اليها الباحثان في اتجاهه العلمي كتأيد الاتجاه السلوكي في نفسير الابداع والذي اشار الى ان عملية التفكير الابداعي تُهدف للوصول الى تكوينات جديدة ذات مواصفات تكون مبنية وؤيمة المعنى اذ يتم تكوين ارتباطات يبين عدد من المتغيرات والسنجابات وكما كانت العالوة او (Lefrancois,1982,226)الرباط بين المتغير والسجابة وؤيمة ذلك دليل على ارتفاع مسنوى التفكير الابداعي .

- التفكير الابداعي وعالوته بالتحصيل المهاري . تم دراسة العالوة بين المتغيرين من خلال الرباط والنحدار وؤد تبين انه الوجود عالوة ارتباط بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المهاري ، اذ وصلت ئؤمة معامل ارتباط بينهما 0.06 اما عن تحديد العالوة بينهما من خلال النحدار ، نؤد استخدم النحدار الخطي وغير الخطي لهذا الغرض ووجد ان المعادلة النحدارية الخطية لتحديد العالوة (التفكير الابداعي والمتغير المعتمد التحصيل المهاري) كانت : بمعامل تحديد ، كما هو موضح في الجدول 7)

$$r=0.0602$$

الجدول 8) يوضح تحليل تبان النحدار بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المهاري والمعادلة النحدارية من الدرجة الثانية

التباين	متوسط المربعات	مجموع المربعات	درجة الحرية	ئؤمة ف
النحدار	1.7542	1.754	1	0.1055
البواقي	16.6269	482.181	29	
الكلية		483.935	30	

يُوضح من الجدول 8) ان العالوة النحدارية كانت غير معنوية عند نسبة خطأ 0.05 اذ بلغت ئؤمة (ف) المحسوبة 0.1055 وهي اصغر من ئؤمة (ف) الجدولية عند درجة حرية 1-29) والبالغة 4.1830 وذلك ما نُؤكده العالوة المذكورة ورغم ذلك تم ايجاد معادلة انحدار من الدرجة الثانية بين المتغيرين وكانت:

$$\hat{Y} = 106.016 - 1.0041X + 0.0029x^2 \quad R^2 = 1.6\% \quad \text{وكما هو موضح في الجدول 9)}$$

الجدول 9) تحليل تبان النحدار بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصيل المهاري والمعادلة النحدارية من الدرجة الثانية

التباين	متوسط المربعات	مجموع المربعات	درجة الحرية	ئؤمة ف
النحدار	3.9889	7.978	2	0.2347
البواقي	16.9985	475.958	28	
الكلية		483.935	30	

يُوضح من الجدول 9) ان العالوة كانت غير معنوية عند نسبة احتمال 0.05 اذ بلغت ئؤمة (ف) المحسوبة 0.2347 وهي اصغر من (ف) الجدولية البالغة 3.3404 عند درجة حرية 2-28) وهذا يبين اهمية المعادلة من الدرجة

الثانوية في التنبؤ للمغير المعتمد، وكذلك ثم السنمرار المعادلة من درجة اعلى واخبارها ووجد ان المعادلة من الدرجة الثالثة كانت: $Y = 3201.31 - 54.3899 X + 0.3088 X^2 - 0.0006 X^3$ وبمعامل تحديد $R = 11.1\%$ وهذا يدل على ان معادلة النحدار من الدرجة الثالثة ليس لها تأثير في الشغبرات الحاصلة في التحصيل المهاري بنسبة 10% تقريبا عما كانت عليه في حالة ما كانت عليه في حالة معادلة النحدار من الدرجة الثانية ، وعند اختبار قيمة ف(ف).

(الجدول 10) تحليل تبين النحدار بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المهاري والمعادلة النحدارية من الدرجة الثالثة

النباين	متوسط المربعات	مجموع المربعات	درجة الحرية	قيمة ف
النحدار	17.9575	53.873	3	1.1274
البواقي	15.9283	430.063	27	
الكلية		483.935	30	

لوحظ من الجدول (10) ان معادلة النحدار من الدرجة الثالثة كانت غير معنوية عند نسبة احتمال 0.05 اذ بلغت قيمة ف(ف) المحسوبة 1.1274 وهي اقل من قيمة ف(ف) الجدولية عند درجة حرية 3-27) والبالغة 2.9604 ونتيجة الصمية المعادلة من الدرجة الثالثة في التنبؤ بالتحصيل المهاري نؤد ثم التوقف عندها ، وبين الشكل (4) طبيعة هذه العلاقة بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المهاري .

25

شكل (4)

وبين العلاقة النحدارية (من الدرجة الثالثة) بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المهاري

شكل (2) (بين العلاقة النحدارية) من الدرجة الثالثة (بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المهاري

ينضح من الشكل (2) لما كان التفكير البداعي من خصائص كانت العلاقة عالية وذلك بفرض عدم وجود علاقة بين التفكير البداعي والتحصيل المهاري وحدثت تشتت في العلاقة (ارتفاع وانخفاض) ونعزو الباحثان النتائج السابقة

الى ان طبيعة الداء المهاري في مادة كرة اليد يتطلب سرعة عالية واستجابات سريعة في الداء والسيما في الظروف النفسية المصاحبة لعملية التقييم التي تؤدي الطلاب الى الامام بتنفيذ المهمة الحركية والمهارية المطلوبة منه بسرعة ووقت ممكن لمدة قصيرة دون اللغات الى التفكير في الابداع عند الاختبار وذلك مما سبب في ضعف الاءة بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصي المهاري في كرة اليد ويمكن ان نعطي الباحثان تفسيراً منطوقاً لعدم وجود الاءة بين هذين المتغيرين من حاجتهم الاساسية والنفسية ووصول الى تحقيق الذات في عملية التقييم الى ان ظروف الداء وطبيعته واسلوب التقييم المتبع قد يشبع الرغبات النفسية لدى الطالب واليهج لهم يشعرون بتحقيق ذاتهم مما سبب في النتائج الحالية وذلك ينفق مع ما جاء به (ماسلو) في نظريته عن الحاجات والذي وضح فيه ان تحقيق الذات هو قمة تحقيق الحاجات التناسلية عند الافراد من خلال شعورهم بالسيولة والسيطرة والتحكم في الداء والذي لم يتحقق بسبب ظروف التقييم الموضوعي في الاختبار التحصيلي لمهارات كرة اليد والمستخدم في نهاية السنة الدراسية ، اذ ان تلك الظروف المتغيرة من اسبب الابداع وانما سوف ننحصر في درجات الغالب باختيار المهاري لتحقيق النجاح وان هذا التقييم قد يخضع بالضرورة الى شروط المناسفة الرياضية التي تؤدي الى التفكير الابداعي عند الداء.

وتنق النتائج الحالية ايضاً مع الاتجاه السلوكي في التفكير الابداعي (سكندر) والذي يشير الى اعتماده على مبدأ التعزيز والاثابة عند الداء والذي بموجبه يصبح تفكيراً غير مرغوباً فيه مع تداوله لكال الشرطين السابقين وذلك ما يؤكد نفس الباحثان لنتائج بحثها والتي تم اجراءها في ظروف الاءة على مبدأ التعزيز والاثابة وذلك يتسجم مع نظريته السابق للنتائج الحالية. وذلك ينفق مع رأي جيلنورد في اهمية البيئة لتنمية درجات التفكير الابداعي وان الفرد البشري ان يزداد انتاج ابداعه اذا اتاحت له البيئة فرص الاءة التي تؤدي الى تلك النتائج. (عبد الغفار ،

1977،179)

5- الاءات والتوصيات .

1-5 الاءات :

1. هناك الاءة بين التفكير الابداعي والتحصي المعرفي في مادة كرة اليد .
2. ان الامام الطلبة بالتحصيل المعرفي كان افضل من الامامهم بالتحصيل المهاري في مادة كرة اليد.
3. من خلال الاختبارات المهارية التي استخدم في البحث الحالي في التحصيل المهاري لمادة كرة اليد يرتبط بالضرورة مع التفكير الابداعي وذلك بسبب طبيعته وخصوصية الداء المهاري المطلوب في عملية التقييم المستخدم في تثبيته درجة التحصيل.

2-5 التوصيات :

1. التاكيد على اهمية تطوير التفكير الابداعي في التدريب في كليات التربية الرياضية بالقطر والسيما وتنمية الجوانب المعرفية والاعلمية لدى الطلبة .
2. العمل على توفير البيئة النفسية المناسبة للطلبة والتي تساهم في خلق فرص الابداع والتفكير الابداعي لديهم بما يتسجم والاهداف التربوية التي تسعى اليها المناهج التعليمية في الجامعات العراقية .
3. استخدام اختبار التحصيل المعرفي في الامتحانات النظرية في جامعات وكليات اخرى.

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الرقم	الفقرة	تصلح	التصلح	تصلح بعد التعديل
1	دائما ادرس وأنا متأكد بانني اتبع الاجراءات الصحيحة في حل مشكلتي الدراسية .			
2	سيكون مضيق للوقت بالنسبة لي اذا سألت اسئلة وليس أمل في الحصول على اجابات لها			
3	اركنز ووجد على الشياء التي نهمني أكثر من معظم الطلاب.			
4	اشعر بان الطريقة المنطقية المتدرجة خطوة بخطوة هي الفضل لحل المشكلات .			
5	احيانا أكون صوتا لرأي المجموعة التي تحاول ان تجد من ناعلية بعض الطلاب .			
6	اقضي وقتنا طويلاً في التفكير بما يظنه الآخرون عنني			
7	من المهم جداً ان اعمل ما اعتقد بأنه صحيح ، لكن من محاولة لتسب رضى الآخرون .			
8	الطلاب الذين يبدوا أنهم غير متأكدين من الشياء يفقدون احترامهم لهم .			
9	انا بحاجة للشياء المهمة والممتعة أكثر من الآخرون			
10	انا اعرف كيف اراقب احساساتي الداخلية			

11	استطيع ان ادخل المشكالت لفترات زمنية طويلا.
12	احيانا انجس لالشياء بشكل كبير .
13	غالبا ما نأخذني انضل الينكار عندم ال أقوم بعمل شيء محدد .
14	اعتمد على احاسيسي الداخلية وتخميناتي ني الصرح والخطأ عندم أكون ني طور الوصول لحل المشكلة .
15	عندما أقوم بحل المشكلة للون سرعاً ني العمل عند التحول للمشكلة ، ولكنني ألون بطيهاً ني تركيب المعلومات الني جمعتها .
16	احياناً أطرده بسبب لسري للتعليقات وعمل الشياء ليس من المنروض ان اعلمها .
17	احب الهوايات الني تتلحق بتجميع الشياء
18	احلم اليقظة ساعدت ني الكثير من مشروعاتي المهمة .
19	احب الطالب الموضوعي والمنطقيين
20	اذا كان على ان اخار بين مهنيين غير مهنيين الاحوية ان ألون طويهاً على ، ألون مدرسا .
21	بكني ان اتامل بشكل سهل مع الفراد اذا كانوا يتنون لذفس المسنوى التجماعي والعلمي الذي انتمى اليه
22	لدي درجة عالية من الاحساسية للجمال .
23	اسير للوصول الى المستوى العالي والقوة ني الحياة .
24	احب الناس الذين هم الكثر ثقة باستنتاجاتهم
25	الذاهم ليس له علاقة بحلول المشكلات الصحية
26	عندما اشرك ني جدال ما نان أكثر ما يسعدني هو اذا اصبح المعارض لي صديقاً ، حتى لو كان لذلك على حساب التضحية بوجهة نظري .
27	انا أكثر اهتماما بتقديم الفكار الجديدة أكثر من محاولة طرحها على الخرين .
28	انا اتمتع ني قضاء ال يوم وحيداً مسنوعاً ني التفكير .
29	أمل الى تجنب المواقف الني اشعر نيها بانني متطفل
30	عندما اقيم المعلومات نانني اهتم بمصدرها أكثر من محتواها
31	رفض الشياء غير المؤكدة والني ال يمكن الشوبها .
32	حب الفراد الذين يتبعون القاعدة (العمل قبل المتعة)
33	احترام الفراد لذاته أكثر أهمية من احترام الخرين له .
34	اشعر بأن الفراد الذين يتفاحون للوصول الى الكمال غير حكماء
35	انضل ان اعلم من الخرين ني نرىق بدلاً من العمل وحدي .
36	احب العمل الذي يتطلب تأهيلاً على الخرين
37	لأهراً من المشاكل الني اواجهها ني الاحياء ال يمكن حلها ني ضوء الحلول الصحيحة او الخاطئة .
38	من المهم عندي ان يكون هناك مكان لكل شيء وان يكون لكل شيء ني مكانة .
39	الكتاب الذي يستخدمون للامات غريبة وغير مألوفة غالبا ما يربدون السعراض .
40	مشكلة العديد من الطالب ني انهم يأخذون النور بجديفة كبيرة .
41	استطيع المحافظة على دافعتي وحماسي للعديد من النجازات الرياضية حتى ني وجود الحباطات والعقبات .
42	الطالب الذين يملون للتمتع بالفكار غير عمليين .
43	اعجب بما ال اعرفه أكثر مما اعرف .
44	اهتم أكثر فيما يمكن ان يكون أكثر مما هو موجود .
45	غالبا ما أراجع نفسي ني الشياء الني قلها والني ربما أدت مشاعر انراد أخرين .
46	استمتع ني التالعيب بالفكار ال جديدة حتى مع وجود استخدام عملي لها .
47	ال احب ان اطرأ اسئلة يدور من خالها عدم الاهتمام .
48	متى نولبت العمل ني مشروع ما ، نانني اسعى بجد واصمم على انجازه حتى تحت ظروف من الحباط .
49	احياناً اشعر بان الينكار نانني لي من مصدر خارجي وكأني لست مسؤولاً عنها بشكل مباشر .

50	احيانا اقع ني المشاكل بسبب حب الاستطلاع
51	غالبًا ما يُؤول عني الناس بأني شاراد الذهن
52	انا اعبر عن مشاعري وعواظني الكثر من بوية الناس
53	من السهل علي ان اغير اهتماماتي التمكن من العمل ني مجال معين ، الكثر من نغير عملي
54	الطلاب الذين يعملون بالنظريات اقل اهمية من أولئك العاملين .
55	عندما نؤوم مجموعة بطرح افكار كثرية ني موضع ما الكون الكثرهم مؤدرة علي تؤيد افكار اكثر وسرعة .
56	انا ال اخجل من النغير عن اهتماماتي بالجنس الكثر
57	استطيع وبسهولة التخلي عن الكسب السريع او الراحة من اجل الوصول الهدافي
58	الفراد الذين يعبرون عن مشاعرهم وعواظهم اما ان يكونوا غير مستورين او مباشرين
59	ني التعامل مع الناس ، من المهم ان تكون دبلوماسيا الكثر من ان تكون مننوح ومباشرا .
60	تجاول اخطاء الكثرين مضيعة للوقت .
61	لپس من الخطا ان تبادي قلوبا امام الكثرين بين الحين والآخر .
62	ني بعض اللوات اسنمذع كثريرا ني براعة مخادع تمنوت ان ينجو بفاعله .
63	عندما يحاول شخص ان ينف امامي ني الطابور ناني اشعره بخطاه
64	المشاكل الني لپس لها خط واضح واحتمالت اجابة واضحة ال نسندعي اهتمامي .
65	منهوم الحياة يجنبي ويحظى باهتمامي .
66	أثق بمشاعري لنؤودني ني خبراتي .
67	احيانا ابدأ العمل بمشكلة ما والني احسست بها ، ولكني لم اعبر عنها بعد .
68	الشيء الني قلناها علي انها قديمة ومألوفة تبدو احيانا غريبة علي وغبر عادية .
69	احيانا أميل الي نسيان الشياء مثل السماء والشخاص ، الشوارع ، الطرق السريعة ، البلدان الخ... الصغيرة
70	خالل نكرة مرادني كذات لذي رغبة الكون وحيدا وأحوق انكاري واهتماماتي .
71	اشعر بأن العمل الشاق هو العامل الساسي للنجاح
72	العديد من العمال البداعي هي نتيجة عوامل الصدفة .
73	يهمني كثريرا ان يتم اعباري عضوا مهمما ني الفريق .
74	كذت سعيدا جدا ني طفولتي .

ملحق (2) اختبار برنستن للتفكير البداعي بصورته النهائية

أقرأ بنعم عن واختر واحدة من البدائل التالية (أوافق ، متردد ، ال أوافق) وضع اشارة تحت ما يناسبك

الرقم	الفرقة	أوافق	متردد	ال أوافق
1	اتبع الاجراءات الصحيحة والغبر مألونة احبانا لحل مشكلاتي الدراسي.			
2	أهل ني الحصول علي جميع النساؤالت الني تدور ني ذهني			
3	هناك انشطة ننبر اهتمامي اكثر من الطلبة الكثرين			
4	استطيع ان احل مشكلتي اذا اتيت بطريقة منطوية متدرجة			
5	احبانا ان الكون صونا لذي رأي المجموعة الني نحاول ان نحذ من نعالها بعض الطلاب .			
6	اقضي وقتا طويلا ني التفكير لحل مشكلتي			
7	اعمل ما اعتؤد الشيء الصحيح واليهمني نفاعه الكثرين .			
8	الطلاب الذين يبدوا انهم غير متأكدين من الشياء يؤودون احترامهم لهم.			
9	انا بحاجة الي الشياء المهمة والممنعة الكثر من الكثرين			
10	انا اعرف كيف اراقب احساساتي الداخلية			
11	استطيع ان اتحمل المشكالت لفترات زمنية طويلة .			
12	احبانا ان احس لالشياء بشكل كبير			
13	غالبًا ما تأؤوني انضل الكفار عندما لاؤوم بعمل شيء محدد .			

14	اعتمد على احساس سي الداخلي وتخميراتني في الصح والخطأ عندما أكون في طور الوصول لحل المشكلة
15	أتانى في تنظيم المعلومات التي اجمعها الخراجا بأحسن صورة
16	انني احياناً بسبب مخ الفني للتعلميات
17	احب الهوايات التي تنطبق بجمع الأشياء
18	التفكير العميق ساعدني في حل الكثير من مشكلاتي
19	احب الطالب الجديين والموضوعيين
20	اذا كان على ان اخبر بون مهنين غير مهنيين الحيلة لفضلت ان يكون طيباً على ان يكون مدرساً
21	يمكنني ان اتعامل بشكل اسهل مع الفراد اذا كانوا يهتمون لنفس المهنة المجتمعي والعملي الذي انتمى اليه
22	لدي درجة عالية من الحساسية للجمال
23	أسير للوصول الى المستوى العالي والقيمة في الحياة
24	احب الناس هم الكثر ثقة باسنتاجاتهم
25	اللدهام ليس له عاقبة بحلول المشكلات الصحيحة
26	عندما اشترك في جدال فان الكثر ما يسعدني هو اذا اصبح المعارض لي صديقاً ، وحينئذ لو كان ذلك على حساب التضحية بوجهة نظري
27	اهتم بتقويم الفكار الجديدة والغير مألوفة
28	اسمى في التفكير وحيداً
29	اميل الى تجنب المواقف التي اشعر فيها بانني متطفل
30	اقب المعلومات من مصدرها
31	ارفض الأشياء الغير مؤكدة والتي ال يمكن التيقن بها
32	احب الفراد الذين يبتعون القاعدة (الجيبين)
33	احترام الفرد لذاته اكثر اهمية من احترام الآخرين له
34	اشعر بان الفراد الذين ينافسون للوصول الى الكمال غير حكماء
35	انضل ان اعمل مع الآخرين بدلاً من العمل وحدي
36	احب العمل الذي يشتر اقتباه الآخرين
37	ال استطع ان احل الكثير من المشاكل التي نواجهها في الحياة
38	احب ان يكون كل شيء في مكانه وان يكون هناك مكان لكل شيء
39	احب استعراض الكتب الحديثة والغريبة والغير مألوفة
40	مشكلة العديد من الطالب في انهم يأخذون المور بجدية كبيرة
41	استطع المنظمة على دافني وحماسي للعديد من النجاحات الرياضية حتى في وجود الحسابات والعقبات
42	الطالب الذين يملون لثمن بالفكار غير عمليين
43	اعجب بالشيء الجديد الغير مألوف
44	اهتم اكثر فيما يمكن ان يكون اكثر مما هو موجود
45	اراجع نفسي غالباً عندما أؤدي مشاعر الآخرين
46	استمتع بالتلاعب بالفكار الجديدة حتى مع وجود استخدام عملي لها
47	ال احب ان اشرح اسئلة بدور من خالدها عدم الاهتمام
48	متى نولبت العمل في مشروع ما ، نأني اسعى بجد للنجاح فيه والتخلص من العقبات
49	احياناً تراودني افكار خارج ارادتي
50	احياناً اقنع في المشكلات بسبب حب السيطرة
51	غالباً ما يقول عنني الناس بانني شرار الذهن
52	انا اعبر عن مشاعري وعواطفني الكثر من بقية الناس
53	من السهل على ان اغير اهتمامي ال تمكن من العمل في مجال معين ، كثر من تغيب عملي من اجل ارضاء اهتماماتي
54	الطالب الذين يعملون بالنظريات اقل اهمية من اولئك العمليين

		عندما تقوم مجموعة بطرح أفكار لتبصرة ذي موضوع ما تكون أكثرهم مؤدرة على تقديم أفكار أكثر وبسرعة	55
		أنا ال أختل من التبصر عن اهتماماتي بالجنس الغير	56
		ال أتخلى عن اهدافي ذي الحياة بالرغم من الصعوبات التي تواجهني	57
		الفراد الذين يعبرون عن مشاعرهم وعواطفهم اما ان يكونوا غير مستقرين	58
		يجب ان نكون نبولوماسين ذي التعامل مع الناس	59
		احس بمضيعة للوقت عندما احل اخطأ الآخرين	60
		ليس من الخطأ ان تباهى قلوبك امام الآخرين بين الذين والآخر	61
		اسمذع لتبصر ذي التغلب على مخادع	62
		عندما يحاول شخص ان يؤف امامي ذي الطابور نابني اشعر بخطاه	63
		المشاكل الغير واضحة ابتعد عنها	64
		الحياة تجنبي وتحظي باهتمامي	65
		اشق بمشاعري لتقودني ذي خبراتي	66
		عندما احس بوجود مشكلة نانني ابدأ العمل بحل المشكلة	67
		تبصر اهتمامي لكل جديد وغير مألوف	68
		الخ... احب ان انا اميل الى نسيان الأشياء مثل السماء والشخااص ، الشوراع ، الطرق السريعة ، البلدان	69
		خالل نبرة حراةتي كانت لدي رغبة الكون وحداً وأحقيق انكاري واهتماماتي .	70
		اشعر بأن العمل الشاق هو العامل الساسي للنجاح	71
		العدي من العمال البداعية هي نتيجة عوامل الصدفة .	72
		بهمني لتبصر ان يتم اعتراري عضواً مهمما ذي الفرقي .	73
		كنت سعيداً جداً ذي طفولتي .	74

**THE EFFECT OF USING THE MASTERY AND COOPERATIVE
METHODS IN LEARNING THE SKILL OF SHOOTING FROM A
STANDSTILL IN BASKETBALL**

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ABSTRACT

The characteristic of the era in which we live is characterized by rapid change and renewal in accordance with the additions to knowledge and changes to the social structure. Sport, with its characteristics, has become a national necessity in building the country and giving confidence in its future. Therefore, we must choose ideas that are tested over time and when applied produce results. A high-level achievement. There are tried and tested strategies to improve and enrich the sporting reality and to acquire and understand all the new sports sciences related to sports performance. Basketball is one of the team games in which the success of any team depends mainly on the extent of its members' proficiency in the basic skills of the game. One of the skills of great importance in the game of basketball is shooting, as victory in this game depends on the team that earns the largest number of points. Shooting is considered one of the offensive and decisive skills, as through it it is possible to obtain a direct point, and this skill in motor learning is considered one of the only movement skills, so the researcher decided to learn this type of shooting, through the use of the mastery and cooperative methods. The research problem lies in conducting a serious scientific study of this problem through the use of the mastery and cooperative methods within the educational curriculum approved by the college. The study aimed to identify the effect of the mastery and cooperative learning styles on learning the skill of shooting from a standstill in basketball. The researcher assumed that the mastery learning method is better for learning the skill of shooting than holding a basketball. The researcher used the experimental method to suit the research problem, and the research sample was randomly selected from second-year students.

Through the results, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

.1 Using the mastery method in learning has a very large and effective impact on learning the skill of shooting from a standstill in basketball.

KEYWORDS

Mastery and cooperative styles, stationary shooting, basketball.

2 Using the cooperative method of learning has a very significant and effective impact on learning the skill of shooting from a standstill in basketball. Through the conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:
 . 1 It is important to adopt the mastery method in learning other basketball skills, especially the skills that are difficult to learn.
 2 Conducting other studies dealing with the comparison between other educational methods for learning different skills in basketball and other sports.

اثر استخدام الأسلوبين التعاوني والتعاوني في تعلم مهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة م.م

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ملخص البحث

أن سمة العصر الذي نعيش فيه يتميز بسرعة التغير والتجدد بما يتوافق مع ما يطرأ على المعرفة من إضافات وعلى البناء الاجتماعي من تغيرات ، فالرياضة بخصائصها أصبحت ضرورة وطنية في بناء البلاد و إعطاء النشأة بمسئولياته ، ولهذا وجب علينا اختيار الأفكار التي يتم اختبارها بمرور الوقت وعندنا تطبيق نتائج إنجازها ذا مسنوي عال فهناك استراتيجيات مجربة ومختبرة لنحسين الرفع الرياضي وإثرائه وكسب منهم كل ما هو جديد من العلوم الرياضية المتصلة بالأداء الرياضي. وكرة السلة تعد من الألعاب الجماعية التي يعتمد نجاح أي فريق فيها أساساً على مدى اجادة أفرادها للمهارات الأساسية للعبة ، ومن المهارات ذات الأهمية الكبي في لعبة كرة السلة هي التصويب ، إذ يعتمد الفوز في هذه اللعبة على الفوق الذي يكسب العدد الأكبر من النقاط . ويعد التصويب من المهارات الهجومي والحاسمة ، إذ عن طريقه يتم الحصول على نقطة مباشرة ، ويعد هذه المهارة في التعلم الحركي من المهارات الوحدية الحركية ، لذا ارتأت الباحثة أن تتعمق في هذا النوع من التصويب ، من خلال استخدام الأسلوبين التعاوني والتعاوني . أمام مشكلة البحث فتكمن الأهمية بدراسة علمية جادة لهذه المشكلة من خلال استخدام الأسلوبين التعاوني والتعاوني ضمن المنهج التعلّمي المبرمج من قبل الكلية . وهدفت الدراسة التعرف على تأثير أسلوب التعلم التعاوني والفعال في تعلم مهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة . وانضمت الباحثة إن أسلوب التعلم التعاوني هو الأفضل في تعلم مهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة . واستخدمت الباحثة المنهج التجريبي

لمالءمته لمشكلة البحث، وتم اختيار عينة البحث بالطريقة العشوائية من طالب المرحلة الثانوية ومن خلال النتائج توصلت الباحثة الى الاستنتاجات التالية :

1. إن استخدام أسلوب التثانوي في النوع الكمي تأثرت إيجابيا في حصول التعلم لمهارة التصويب من

الشبكات بكرة السلة .

2. إن استخدام أسلوب التعاوني في النوع الكمي ، تأثرت إيجابيا جدا في حصول التعلم لمهارة التصويب من الشبكات بكرة السلة .

ومن خلال الاستنتاجات توصي الباحثة بالآتي :

1. من الأهمية اعتماد أسلوب التثانوي في نوع المهارات الأخرى بكرة السلة وبالأخص المهارات الصعبة للتعلم.

2. إجراء دراسات أخرى تتناول المقارنة بين الأساليب التعلیمیة الأخرى لنوع المهارات المختلفة في لعبة كرة السلة ، وألعاب الرياضة الأخرى .

الكلمات المفتاحية : السلوبيون التثانوي والتعاوني ، التصويب من الشبكات ، كرة السلة .

1. التعرف بالبحث .

1.1 المقدمة وأهمية البحث .

أن سمة العصر الذي نعيش فيه يتميز بسرعة التغير والتجدد بما يتوافق مع ما يطرأ على المعرفة من إضافات وعلى البناء الاجتماعي من تغيرات ، فالرياضة بخصائصها أصبحت ضرورة وطنية في بناء البلاد وعطاء النشأة بمسئولياته ، ولهذا يجب علينا اختيار الأفكار التي يتم اختيارها بمرور الوقت وعندما تطبق نتائج إنجازها ذات مستوى عال فهناك استراتيجيات مجربة ومختبرة لتحصين الموقع الرياضي وإثرائه والتساب وهم كل ما هو جديد من العلوم الرياضية المتصلة بالأداء الرياضي.

وهناك الكثير من الأساليب التعلیمیة التي استخدمت في تعلم المهارات الرياضية وما زالت تستخدم ، إذ تبينت فيها نسب النجاح في الأداء المهاري والبدني ، لذا تسعى الخبراء والباحثون إلى إيجاد أساليب نخدم الألعاب والفعاليات الرياضية كافة ، بما ينالهم مع فوائدها الأثرية المرغوبة ولمكانتها لهم .

وكرة السلة نعد من الألعاب الجماعية التي يُعتمد نجاح أي فريق فيها أساسا على مدى اجاد أفرادها للمهارات

الأساسية للعبة ، ومن المهارات ذات الأهمية الكبيرة في لعبة كرة السلة هي التصويب ، إذ يُعتمد الفوز في هذه اللعبة على الفريق الذي يكسب العدد الأكبر من النقاط ، بل يتم توظيف باقي المهارات لخدمة هذه المهارة المهمة لذا يعطى نعلم هذه المهارة الكثير من الوقت والجهد ، كما ان هذه المهارة تمتاز بالصعوبة في الأداء والتفان على وفق الظروف التي تتطلبها لعبة كرة السلة لغرض الوصول إلى النتائج الإيجابية والتفان بالصعود والمجهد وآخر

حالة التعب 1).

ويعد التصويب من المهارات الهجومية والحاسمة ، إذ عن طريقه يمكن الحصول على نقطة مباشرة ، ونعد هذه المهارة في التعلم الحركي من المهارات الوجيهة الحركية ، أي لها بداية وها نهاية واضحة ، مما يمكن من معرفة أجزاء الحركة بشكل واضح ودقيق على النحو المثل ، وهذا يأتي من خلال أداء التكرارات والتصحيح والتدريب

على التغذية الراجعة لضمان إدراك الحركة وتطبيقها ، وهناك أنواع متعددة من التصويبات التي يستخدمها اللاعبو

كرة السلة ، ونتيجة للتطور الحاصل في الأداء البدني والمهاري في هذه اللعبة سعى الخبراء والمدربون إلى إيجاد وسائل وأساليب نعلمية وتدريبية لتطوير هذه المهارة التي تتميز بالصعوبة العالية والمُعقدة وتحتاج إلى دقة ونوعية عالية بمرور الوقت ، ولهذا فأنها تحتاج إلى الكثير من التدريب المستمر حتى يصل اللاعب إلى المستوى الجيد في الأداء من حيث السيطرة والتفان فضال عن السرعة في الحركة لهذا أصبح التدريب على التصويب في الآونة الأخيرة يحتل جزءا كبيرا من الوحدة التدريبية . إذ إن التصويب أصبح أكثر استخداما في المباريات من الألعابيين ، ومن ثم حسم النقاط بشكل كبير .

لذا ارتأت الباحثة نعلم هذا النوع من التصويب ، من خلال استخدام الأسلوبين التفاضلي والتعاوني .

2.1 مشكلة البحث .

من خلال متابعة الباحثان للمباريات فضال عن المفاهم التعلیمیة الحديثة في كليات التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة وأقسامها الحظ فلة الاهتمام في نعلم التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة والتدريب عليه، فضال عن فلة استخدام

الأساليب التعلیمیة الحديثة الأمر الذي يدعو إلى أهمية استخدام تلك الأساليب التعلیمیة وجعلها بما يخدم العملية التعلیمیة وليس بما مع المهارات الصعبة التعلم (مهارة التصويب) إذ إن تنظيم عملية التعلم واستخدام الطرائق التعلیمیة السنتمار هذه الأساليب هي المنهج التعلیمی الذي يبراد منه رفع المستوى التعلیمی وتحقيق أهداف العملية

لهذه المشكلة من خلال استخدام الأسلوبين التثنائي والتعاوني ضمن المنهج التعليمي المرن من قبل الكلية وما يتناسب مع نوع المهارة الهجومية من ناحية ومسايرها الحركي وبناءها الظاهري يمكن من خلاله الترتيب بمسئولية مهارة الهجوم (النصوب) وتطويره والوصول بالطالب إلى مستوى أفضل.

3.1 هدفا البحث .

1. التعرف على اثر أسلوبي التثنائي والتعاوني في تعلم مهارة النصوب من الثبات بكرة السلة .
2. التعرف على الأسلوب الأفضل في تعلم مهارة النصوب من الثبات بكرة السلة .

4.1 فرضا البحث .

1. هناك فروق ذات دلالة إحصائية بين الاختبارين التثنائي والتعاوني ولصالح البعدي في تعلم مهارة النصوب من الثبات بكرة السلة .
2. إن أسلوب التعلم التثنائي هو الأفضل في تعلم مهارة النصوب من الثبات بكرة السلة .

5.1 مجالت البحث .

- 1.5.1 المجال البشري : طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة/ جامعة كركوك .
- 2.5.1 المجال الزمني : المدة من 26 / 2 / 2023 ولغاية 25 / 4 / 2023 .
- 3.5.1 المجال المكاني : الجامعة الرياضية المرغلة في النشاط الرياضي .
3. منهج البحث وإجراءاته الميدانية .

1.3 منهج البحث : لقد استخدم المنهج التجريبي ذي (المجموعات المتكافئة) لملء منه طبيعة المشكلة

المراد حها ، أن " أهم ما يميز النشاط العلمي الدقيق هو استخدام أسلوب التجربة " (1) .

2.3 عينة البحث : تم اختيار العينة من مجتمع الأصل والمتمثل بطالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية

وعلوم الرياضة – جامعة كركوك للعام الدراسي (2022 – 2023) (والبالغ عددهم) 66 (طالبا ، تم اختيار

العينة بالطريقة العشوائية ، والبالغ عددها (24) طالبا ، إذ قسمت على مجموعتين متساويتين وطريقة التوزيع ، وبلغ عدد المجموعة الواحدة (12) طالبا ، وهذا شكلت العينة نسبة مئوية مرادفا (36.3%) من مجتمع البحث الأصلي ، وهي نسبة مناسبة لتمثيل مجتمع البحث من قبل حقيقي وصادقا ، وكان من شروط اختيار العينة أن تكون عشوائية لكل من :

1. الطالب الراغبين والمؤهلين .
2. طالب التجارة السنطالعية .
3. الطالب الممارسين للعبة كرة السلة .

وكان الغرض من تقسيم العينة على مجموعتين ، هو الرجوع الفرق إلى العامل التجريبي الذي يؤثر في المجموعتين التجريبتين .

3.3 نتائج العينة . لغرض معرفة النتائج لدى عينة البحث في بعض المتغيرات التي لها علاقة بالبحث ، قام الباحثان باستخراج معاملي اللينوء لكل من (الطول والوزن والعمر) ، وكما موضح في الجدول (1) .

جدول (1) يوضح نتائج عينة البحث في متغيرات الطول والوزن والعمر

المعالم الحصائية المتغير	الوسط الحسابي	الانحراف المعياري	المتنوال	معامل اللينوء
الداء الفوني للبهديف من الثبات	1.59	0.41	1.3	0.75

الجدول (1) يبين ان عينة البحث منجاسة في متغير البحث النصوب من الثبات ، اذ ان قيمة اللينوء حصرت ما بين ± 1 .

4.3 تكافؤ المجموعتين : لكي يستطيع الباحثان الرجوع الفرق إلى العامل التجريبي ، يجب أن تكون المجموعتان التجريبتان متكافئتين تماما في جميع الظروف والمتغيرات عدا المتغير التجريبي الذي يؤثر في المجموعتين⁽¹⁾ . ولغرض التحقق من تكافؤ عينة البحث ، قام الباحثان بالتحقق من تكافؤ مجموعتي البحث (

الضابطة ، التجريبية (في متغير البحث) النصوب من الثبات (ويبين جدول)2) النتائج التي تم التوصل اليها

جدول (2) يبين نتائج مجموعة البحث

الدالة الاحصائية	T الجدول ية	T المحسوس به	المجموعة الضابطة		المجموعة التجريبية		المرعالم الاحصائية المتغير
			ع±	س	ع±	س	
غير معنوي	2.16	0.84	0.44	1. 51	0.34	1. 67	النصوب من الثبات

درجة الحرية (22) ومرتوى دالة (0.05)

يبين من الجدول (2) ان الفرق في اختبار مهارة النصوب بين مجموعتي البحث الضابطة والتجريبية هي غير (المحسوسه وبالغة) 0.84) اقل من قيمها الجدوية وبالغة T مرتوىة (عشوائية) ، اذ ان قيمة (

(2.16) ، مما يدل على نكافؤ مجموعتي البحث .

5.3 الوسائل وأدوات البحث والأجهزة المستخدمة .

1.5.3 وسائل جمع المعلومات

- المصادر العربية والأجنبية .

- المرحة والتجوب .

- المرذابات الشخصية .

- استماره استطلاع رأي الخبراء حول اختبار الخبارات .

- استماره تقويم الداء الفنى للمهارات فيد البحث لعينة البحث (ينظر ملحق 1)

- استماره تفويغ البيانات .

2.5.3 الأدوات والأجهزة المستخدمة .

استخدمت الباحثان الأدوات والأجهزة الآتية :

- ملعب كرة سلة فائوي .

- (. Molten كرات سلة فائوية عدد)10 (نوع)
- طباشير بالون مخنلفة .
- صافرة عدد)2(.
- شريط فياس معدني لفياس الطول .
- ساعة نووية نوع (كاسيو .)
- (. EKS ميزان طبي عدد)1(نوع)
- عدد)1(Sony كاميرا تصوير فديوي نوع
- (عدد)1(. PENTIAM 4 حة از حاسوب نوع)
- (. PRINCO اذراص ليزرة مرضوطة نوع)

3-6 توصيف الاختبارات المستخدمة في البحث :-

أ- اختبار الداء الفني للتصويب من الثبات)2(.:

* الهدف من الاختبار :- تقويم مستوى الداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات .

* الأدوات الزمة :- ملعب كؤ سلة - كؤ سلة عدد)3(.

* وصف الاختبار :- يؤق اللاعب خلف خط اللمرة الحؤ ووضع التصويب الصحيح ويؤدي ثالث محاولات

من اللمة لللمة ديف من الثبات .

* التسجيل :- يعطى للمختبر ثالث محاولات ، ويتم منح عنها ثالث درجات ويحسب درجة المحاولة الأفضل عن كل مؤوم علما ان درجة التؤوم النهائية لكك محاولة (10 مفسمة حسب اجزاء المهمة : التؤم العدادي) 3 (درجة ، التؤم الرئيس) 5 (درجة ، التؤم النهائي) 2 (درجة .

كأما هذا التصویر

الشكل (1) يوضح اختبار التصويب من التنبات

7.3 التجربة الاستطلاعية : إن التجربة السنطالعية هي " عبارة عن دراسة تجريبية أولية تؤوم بها

الباحثان على عينة صغرى قبل تؤامه ببحته بهدف اختبار أساليب البحث وأدواته " (2) .

وعلى هذا الأساس ، قامت الباحثان بإجراء التجربة السنطالعية يوم 2023/2/27 على عينة من طالب المرحلة الثانوية في كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة – جامعة كركوك ، وعددهم (4) طالب من خارج عينة البحث الأساسية ، وكان هدف التجربة ما يأتي :

1. التأكد من مكان إجراء الاختبارات ومدى ملاءمته لتؤمها .
2. معرفة مدى استعداد عينة البحث أداء الاختبارات .
3. معرفة الوقت المناسب لجراء الاختبارات وتؤمها .

4. معرفة مدى ملائمة الاختبارات لعينة البحث .

5. معرفة الصعوبات التي قد تواجه مجربات العمل ووضع انسب الحلول لها.

6. كفاءة فريق العمل المساعد وكفاءته .

7. التأكد من سلامة الأجهزة والادوات المستخدمة .

8.3 إجراءات البحث الميدانية : تمثلت إجراءات البحث بالاختبارات القبالية ، وتطبيق المنهج التعلّيمي المستخدم على عينة البحث ، والمتمثلة بالمجموعتين التجريبيتين ، ومن ثم إجراء الاختبارات البعدية .

1.8.3 الاختبارات القبالية : قبل البدء بإجراء الاختبارات القبالية نفذت عينة البحث وحدتين تعريفيتين

تضمنتا شرح مهارة التصويب من الشبّات وهما في اللعبة وعرض النموذج⁽¹⁾ الحي لكيفية أداء المهارة بعد ذلك اعطي الوقت الكافي لعينة البحث لتطبيق هذه المهارة خلال الوحدتين وذلك الخذ فكة عن كيفية العمل على الجهاز وطريقة أداء الاختبار الخاص بالبحث . وبعد انتهاء الفتوة التعريفية اجري الاختبار القبالي

الفراد عينة البحث في الأداء الفني للإنديف من الشبّات وذلك يوم الأحد الموافق 2023/3/5 ، على ملعب كرة السلة في مديرية النشاط الرياضي حيث ان جميع الوحدات التعلّيمية التي تم تطبيقها اجريت في هذا الملعب .

2.8.3 المنهج التعلّيمي : من خلال المنهج المستخدم قام الباحثان باستخدام أسلوبين في تعّلم أداء مهارة

إرسال الساحق بكوة السلة ، كما موضح في الشكل ادناه .

مهارة التصويب من الثبات

الشكل 2 (يوضح مندرجات المنهج التلويحي المستخدم في تعلم مهارة التصويب من الثبات في كرة السلة

- استغرق البرنامج التعليمي (4) أسابيع ، وواقع وحدتين تعليميتين أسبوعياً ، وذلك بلغ مجموع الوحدات التعليمية لمهارة التصويب من الثبات (8) وحدات .
- بلغ زمن الوحدة التعليمية الواحدة (90) دقيقة على وفق المقرر الدراسي للكلية .

• اعتمد الباحثان على مفردات المنهج التعليمي المنوع من مدرس المادة في الكلية ، ولم يعتمد في كليات الطر كافة ، فزال عن المصادر والبحاث العلمية ، وكان التغير في القسم التطبيقي فقط .

• تم تطبيق مفردات المنهج التعليمي ، وعلى وفق أساليب التعلم التشاركي والتعاوني ، إذ كان يطبق على المجموعة التجريبية الأولى أساليب التعلم التشاركي ، والمجموعة التجريبية الثانية أساليب التعلم التعاوني (**).
3.8.3 تطبيق التجربة : بعد أن تم إعطاء الوحدتين التدرجيتين ، تم تقسيم العينة على مجموعتين :

1. مجموعة أساليب التعلم التشاركي . يتم تطبيق أسلوب التعلم التشاركي من خلال تقسيم المجموعة التجريبية

الأولى على ثلاثة مستويات (ضعيفة ، ومتوسطة ، وجيدة) ، وعملت الباحثان في هذا التقسيم على نتائج الخبرات الأولية للأداء الفني فقط ، الذي اشتملت عليه الدراسة الحالية . وعدها يتم إعطاء الوقت الكافي

للمجموعة الضعيفة ، الأداء محال أكثر خلال نفس الوحدة ، والغاية من ذلك الوصول بهم إلى مستوى أقرانهم

من الطلاب الجيدين . أما المجموعة الجيدة ، فبكون دورهم مساعد زمالتهم الضعفاء والمتوسطين ، ويتم فرز المجاميع حسب المستوى في كل وحدة تعليمية إلى (ضعيف ، ومتوسط ، وجيد) . لذلك تم إعطاء محاضرات إضافية للطلاب الضعفاء ، وكان عددها محاضرتين ، الغرض منها تصحيح وتبائن أداء الطالب وحسب الخطأ

2. مجموعة أساليب التعلم التعاوني . في هذا الأسلوب يتم تقسيم المجموعة التجريبية الثانية على (4) مجموعات صغوية ، وكل مجموعة مكونة من (3) طالب ، إذ يقوم المدرس بشح المهارة مع توضيح الهدف الرئيسي للدرس ، فزال عن عرض النموذج لتيسر أعداد المجموعات ، وعلى رأسهم التائد للتعرف على الشكل الصحيح للمهارة ، وكيفية الأداء ، وحسب الوقت المخصص للجو التعليمي (الجوه التعليمي) .

في الجو التطبيقي من الوحدة التعليمية ، تقوم المجاميع التعاونية بالتنقل إلى أماكنهم لغرض تنفيذ المهمات التعليمية ، إذ يتم الإشراف على تنفيذ المهمات التجريبية من تائد المجموعة ، ويكون التنقل من مهمة جزئية إلى أخرى بإشراف وإعاز من مدرس المادة . يقوم مدرس المادة عند تنفيذ المجاميع للمهمات المفردة لهم بالمرافقة والمتابعة للنظام والهدوء ، ويبدى المساعدة للمجموعة عند حاجتهم إليه عن طريق تائد المجموعة .

4.8.3 الاختبارات البعدية : اجر الباحثان الاختبار البعدي يوم الثلاثاء الموافق 2023/4/11 بعد اكمال

الوحدات التعلیمیة لتعلم الداء الفني لمهارة النصوب من الثبات اجزت الاختبار البعدي لمجموعتي البحث (الضابطة والتجريبية) مع محاولة توفير الظروف والحول نفسها التي كانت في الاختبار القبلي ، اذ اجري اختبار النصوب من الثبات

3-8-5 تقويم الأداء المهاري : ان تقويم المهارات الرياضية يؤدي دورا فعالا السنة يعطي مؤشرا حقيقيا للنجاح

الصحيح لتقويم وروي اداء مهارات الالعبين وهناك طرائق مختلفة لتقويم المهارات الرياضية اذ اعتمدت الباحثان طريقة حساب النقاط فقد استخدم " النصوب الفديوي للقيام بعملية التقويم ان ذلك سوف يزيد من موضوعية التقويم"³ ، حيث تم نصوب افراد عينة البحث بواسطة الكاميرا الفديوية في الاختبارات الفيلمية والبعديّة ونزل التسجيل (التي يمكن تشغيلها بواسطة مشغل الأفراص في الحاسبة ، ومن CD من كاسيت فديو الى الأفراص الليزرية)

تم عرضت على المرموزين* .

9.3SPSS الوسائل الإحصائية : استخدمت الباحثان الوسائل الإحصائية وفق الطريقة الإحصائية الجاهزة

4- عرض النتائج وتحليلها ومناقشتها :

عرضت الباحثان نتائج الدراسات الفيلمية والبعديّة لعينة البحث ، من خلال عرض الأوساط الحسابية

والنحرفات المعيارية في جداول توضيحية بعد إجراء العمليات الإحصائية اللازمة لها ، وذلك لسهولة المرحلة النتائج ، فبال عن إجراء المراقبة بين المجموعتين التجريبيتين في الاختبارات البعدية من خلال تحليل وتفسير نتائج كل

اختبار لمعدّة واقع الفرق ودالاتها الإحصائية ، على وفق المنظور العلمي الدقيق ، من أجل تحقيق أهداف البحث وفروضه ، وللتعرّ على مستوى الأداء الفني لمهارة النصوب من الثبات في كوة السلة لعينة

البحث ، وكما موضح في الجدول الآتي :

- ¹⁰ وجيهه محجوب : التحليل الحكي . بغداد : مطبعة النعمان العالي ، 1987 ، ص 273 .
- * أ.د. شاهين رمزي ، ادارة كؤ سلة ، جامعة كركوك ، كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة .
- * أ.م.د. وثام عامر ، اختبارات كؤ السلة ، جامعة كركوك ، كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة .
- * م.م. ابراهيم بهرام ، علم النفس الرياضي كؤ سلة ، جامعة بابل ، كلية التربية البدنية وعلوم الرياضة .

جدول 3) يوضح الأوساط الحسابية والتحرقات المعيارية لكل من الخبرات القبلية والبعديّة للمجموعتين التجديديتين

البعدي		القبلي		المعالم الإحصائية	
ع	س	ع	س	الختبار	
0.39	8.50	0.36	3.47	أداء فني	الأسلوب التفاضلي
0.48	6.30	0.56	3.44	أداء فني	الأسلوب التعاوني

درجة الحرية (11) ، ومرتوى دلالة) 0.05

إن ما تقدم في عرضنا للمعالم الإحصائية للخبرات المبرجونة نلاحظ وجود تحسن في جميع هذه

الخبرات والأسلوبين ، مما يدل على تأثير الأسلوبين التفاضليين في التعلم ، ولكن أياً من الأسلوبين له الأفضلية في تحسين مرتوى العينة . ولمعرفة مدى الفرق ودالاتها الإحصائية بين التفاضلي والبعدي ، لجأ الباحثان (،) إلى إيجاد معنوية الفرق بين التفاضلي والبعدي ، وحسب ما سياتر في استخدامه اختبار (

الباحثان في المباحث الحالية .

1.4 عرض نتائج اختبارات المجموعة التجريبية الأولى (الأسلوب التفاضلي) ونحوها

1.1.4 عرض نتائج اختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات ونحوها

(بين الخبرتين القبلي والبعدي الجدول 4) يوضح الأوساط الحسابية والتحرقات المعيارية ونتائج اختبار (

الختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات

نوع الدالة	تقيمة المحسوبة	البعدي		القبلي		المعالم الإحصائية الختبار
		ع	س	ع	س	

مغربي	24.50	0.39	8.05	0.36	3.47	مهارة التوثيق من التابلت
Volume 18 November, 2023						
الدرجة الجدولة (2.20) ودرجة حرية (11) ومسنوى دلالة (0.05) .						

(المحسوبة والجدولة بين تشير الجدول) 4 (إلى الأوساط الحسابية ، والنحركات المعيارية ، وقيمة)

الختبارين القبلي والبعدي ، الختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة ومجموعة البحث الأولى ذات الأسلوب التبادلي ، أظهرت النتائج أن الوسط الحسابي لهذه المجموعة للختبار التبادلي هو (3.47) بانحراف معياري مقدار (0.36) ، والوسط الحسابي في الختبار البعدي مقدار (8.05) وانحراف معياري (الجدولة وبالذمة) 2.20 t (المحسوبة فهي) 24.50 (، وهي أكبر من قيمة) 0.39 t (. أما قيمة) (ودرجة حرية) 11 (، وعند مستوى دلالة) 0.05 (، وهذا يدل على وجود فرق معنوي بين الختبارين التبادلي والبعدي في اختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات ومصالح الختبار البعدي .

2.4 عرض نتائج اختبارات المجموعة التجريبية الثانية (الأسلوب التعاوني)

1.2.4 عرض نتائج اختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات وتحليلها .

(المحسوبة بين الختبارين الجدول) 5 (يوضح الأوساط الحسابية والنحركات المعيارية ونتائج اختبار) التبادلي والبعدي الختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات .

نوع الدالة	تقيمة المحسوبة	البعدي		القبلي		المعالم الإحصائية الختبار
		ع	س	ع	س	
معنوي	13.43	0.48	6.30	0.56	3.44	مهارة التصويب من الثبات
الدرجة الجدولة (2.20) ، ودرجة حرية (11) عند مستوى دلالة (0.05)						

(المحسوبة والجدولة بين تشير الجدول) 5 (إلى الأوساط الحسابية ، والنحركات المعيارية ، وقيمة)

الختبارين التبادلي والبعدي ، الختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة ومجموعة البحث الثانية ذات الأسلوب التعاوني ، وأظهر النتائج أن الوسط الحسابي لهذه المجموعة للختبار القبلي هو (3.44) (

(الجدولة وبالغة) 2.20 (t) المحسوة ، فكات (13.43) ، وهي أكبر من قيمة (t) 0.48 (. أما قيمة)
، ودرجة حرية (11) ، وعند مستوى دلالة (0.05) ، وهذا يدل على وجود فرق معنوي بين الاختبارين التوزيعي
والبعدي في اختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الشبكات ومصالح الاختبار البعدي .

عرض نتائج مقدار التعيين والنسبة المئوية لمقدار التطور الاختبارات الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من

الثبات في كرة السلة للمجموعتين التجريبيين وتحليله

(الجدول 6) يوضح الأوساط الحسابية ومقدار التعيين والنسبة المئوية لمقدار التطور لكل من الاختبارات

القلبية والبعدي وللمجموعتين التجريبيين

النسبة المئوية لمقدار التطور	مقدار التعيين	المعالم الإحصائية	
		القبلي	البعدي
%56.89	4.58	3.47	8.05
%42.39	2.86	3.44	6.30

يوضح الجدول 6 (الأوساط الحسابية ، ومقدار التعيين ، والنسبة المئوية لمقدار التطور لكل من الاختبارات القلبية والبعدي للمجموعتين التجريبيين ، إذ يظهر الجدول إن مجموعة الأسلوب الدفاعي قد حققت وسطا حسابيا في الاختبار القبلي الختبار الأداء الفني مقدار 3.47 ، أما في الاختبار البعدي والنتيجة الاختبار ، فقد حققت وسطا حسابيا مقدار 8.05 ، وهذا يكون مقدار التعيين هو 4.58 ، والنسبة تطور مئوية مقدارها 56.89 .)

كما يظهر الجدول نتائج مجموعة الأسلوب التعاوني ، إذ حققت هذه المجموعة في الاختبار القبلي الختبار الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات ، وسطا حسابيا مقدار 3.44 ، في حين حققت وسطا حسابيا في الاختبار البعدي مقدار 6.30 ، وهذا يكون مقدار التعيين هو 2.86 ، والنسبة تطور مئوية مقدارها 42.39 .)

(بين المجموعتين الأولى) الأسلوب التقني (والثانية) الأسلوب التعاوني (4.4t عرض نتائج اختبار)

في الاختبار البعدي في الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة

(في الاختبار البعدي بين الجدول 7) يوضح الأوساط الحسابية والنتائج المعيارية ونتائج اختبار (مجموعة) الأسلوب التقني (ومجموعة) الأسلوب التعاوني (في اختبارات الأداء الفني لمهارة التصويب من الثبات بكرة السلة

المعالم الإحصائية	مجموعة الأسلوب التقني	مجموعة الأسلوب التعاوني	تقييم	نوع الدالة
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	المحسوبة	ع	س	ع	س	النتائج
معدني	10.29	0.48	6.30	0.39	8.05	التصويب من الثبات

يشير الجدول (7) إلى وجود فروق ذات دلالة معنوية بين مجموعتي البحث التجريبتين في نتائج الاختبار

البعدي للختبار الأداء الفوني ، واختبار دقة الأداء لمهارة الإرسال الساقق بكوة السلة ، إذ تشير النتائج إلى قيمة (المحسوبة كانت) 10.29 ، وهي أكبر من قيمتها الجدولية والبالغة (2.07 ، تحت درجة حرية) 22 (t وعند مستوى دلالة) 0.05 (في اختبار الأداء الفني ، مما يؤكد وجود فروق معنوية بين المجموعتين في هذا الاختبار ولصالح مجموعة الأسلوب التتواني .

5.4 مناقشة النتائج .

ينضح من الجداول (4 , 5 , 6 , 7) ، وجود فروق ذات دلالة معنوية في نتائج الاختبارات المهارية ، ولصالح الاختبارات البعدية لكال الأسلوبين ، ويعزو الباحثان أسباب هذه الفروق لدى عينة البحث إلى تأثير المنهج

التعليمي وفضا للأسلوبين التعليميين ، إذ أن المنهج التعليمي الذي تسعى إلى تحفيز أهدافها من خلال التفكير والممارسة في تحسن مستوى الأداء ، وإن أساس عملية التعلم للجانب المهارية هو اكتساب المتعلم مجموعة من القدرات المهارية ، لكي يتمكن من الوصول إلى مستوى جيد أداء المهارة المراد تعلمها ، إذ إن " تحفيز واكتساب أقصى درجات الكفاية في الوظائف التعليمية يعود إلى المنهج التعليمي ، لكونه يعد طريقة لتنظيم المادة الدراسية على أساس خطوات مندرجة ، بحيث يتمكن المتعلم اكتسابها بسهولة " (1) .

إن للأسلوب وطرائق التعليم دورا فعالا ومؤثرا في المسيرة التعليمية للمناهج المراد تطبيقها ، وتختلف هذه الأساليب والطرانق باختلاف خصوصيتها ، إذ إن " الأسلوب يؤثر على سعة التعلم وعلى درجة الإشباع في التعلم ، وإن التفكير الصحيح والمناسب للطريقة أو الأسلوب تعلم على الفهم السليم للعوامل والمبادئ التي لها صلة بالموضوع لكي تثبت أثرا وقيمتها في وظائف تعليمية معينة " (1) . وعند الملاحظة الجدول (7) ، والذي يوضح الفرق بين المجموعتين التجريبتين الأولى (الأسلوب التتواني) ، والثانية (الأسلوب التعاوني) في الاختبار البعدي ، من حيث الأداء الفوني والدقة لمهارة الإرسال الساقق بكوة السلة ، ، إذ يشير إلى أن الفرق معنوي ، ولصالح

المجموعة التجريبية الأولى ، التي مارست التعلم بالأسلوب التتواني ، وهذا يدل على أن التعلم كان أفضل عند هذه المجموعة ، ويخرج ذلك حسب رأي الباحثان ، إلى تفوق الأسلوب التتواني الذي له الأثر الفعال نسبة إلى الأسلوب التعاوني المستخدم في تعلم نفس المهارة ، إذ أن الأسلوب التتواني يعتمد على استخدام مبدأ التعلم من أجل التمكن ، والذي يعد خطة تعليمية توفر لكل طالب ما يحتاجه من المؤات للوصول إلى مستوى التمكن ، إذ أن الأفراد يتعلمون بنسب مختلفة (2) ، إذ ال يمكن أن يكون هناك تعلم من دون استخدام التفكير الذي يؤدي إلى تحفيز نسبي وثابت في بعض الأحيان في تعلم الأداء ، فالتفكير هو الذي يؤدي إلى تطوير المهارة والوصول

¹(عبد الشاح لطفي . طرائف تدريس اللغة العربية في المدارس الثانوية : دار الكتب الجامعية ، 1972 ، ص 466 . Volume 18 Number 2023

¹(محمد حسن عروي . سيركولوجية التدرب والمناقب ، ط 4 ، القاهرة : دار المعارف ، 1987 ، ص 40 .

²(فؤاد كامل أبو زينة . أساسيات الذئاس والتقوم في التربية ، ط 1 ، دبي : مكتبة الفالح ، 1998 ، ص 170 .

بالتكثيف الصحيح ، وهذا يعني إعطاء المعلمين ضغني الأداء ، وما ينسجم مع طبيعة مهارة الإرسال الساجق ، والذي يُعد من المهارات الصعبة التعلم ، إذ يتطلب أداءه قدرات بدنية ومهارة عالية فضال عن استخدام مبدأ التدرج " المهارة الحركية تتكون من عدد من الأجزاء البسيطة المتتالية ، ولكل جزء من هذه الأجزاء ، يمكن أن يُعلم كحلقة في سلسلة الأجزاء البسيطة ، ومن ثم ربط الأجزاء عد هذا النمط أو نموذجاً لتعليم مهارة الإرسال الساجق الذي يسند على فهم المتعلم بنفسه على أجزاء عدة ، وتعلم كل جزء على حدة ، وبالتالي دمج هذه الأجزاء وربطها كوحدة واحدة ، فضال عن استخدام التمرين بشكل بطيء نسبياً لزيادة السيطرة الحركية ، وخاصة في مرحلة التعلم المبكر وكذلك يُقسم الطالب إلى مجاميع صغيرة وهذا يعتمد على نوع الخطأ ، وذلك من خلال أدائهم ، مما يسهل عليه تصحيح الأخطاء ، فضال عن إشراك المجموعة المتفرقة في التمرين .

أما فيما يخص مجموعة التعلم التعاوني ، فقد أظهرت النتائج وجود تطور ملحوظ في نوع أداء مهارة الإرسال الساجق بكفاءة الطائفة وحسبها⁽³⁾ .

وعزز الباحثان ذلك ، إلى أن التفاعل بين المجموعات الصغيرة المتعاونية من شأنه أن يعطي فرصاً للطالب ذوي مسنوعات التعلم المتفرقة أن يعززوا تعلمهم . كما أنه يولد فرصاً للطالب من ممارسة التبادلية ، والتعرف على الطالب الذين بحاجة إلى توجيه أو تشجيع ، والتعرف على الطالب الضعاف ، والاهتمام بهم بشكل خاص .

وإن تذكر المهارات الحركية هو أحسن بكثير من تذكر المهارات الفكرية وإن درجة التعلم في المهارات الحركية هي أعلى من درجة التعلم في المهارات الفكرية كما أن مهارة التصويب من الشبكات هي من المهارات الكيفية ، وقد أكدت البحوث والدراسات بأن المهارات الكيفية والتي نشترك بها معظم أجزاء الجسم يمكن الاحتفاظ بها بشكل أفضل من تلك المهارات التي يتطلب أدائها بعض أجزاء الجسم (المهارات الصغوية) .

5. الاستنتاجات والتوصيات

1.5 الاستنتاجات

1. إن استخدام الأسلوب التبادلي في التمرين ، نأثيراً كبيراً جداً وفاعلاً في حصول التعلم لمهارة التصويب من

الشبكات بكفاءة السلة .

(3) (تاسم لزوم: موضوعات في التعلم الحركي. ط1، العراق: بغداد، 2005، ص 9

2. إن السبل المستخدمة في التعليم البدني في التعليم ، نأثيرا كبيرا جدا في حصول التلاميذ على المهارات البدنية .
التباعد بين المهارات .

3. إن أساليب التعليم البدني هو أفضل من الأساليب التقليدية في تعليم الأداء البدني للمهارات البدنية من
التباعد بين المهارات .

4. للتعليم البدني أثر واضح في تطوير الدافعية أكثر من تطوير الأداء البدني للمهارات البدنية من التباعد بين المهارات .

1.5 التوصيات .

1. من الأهمية اعتماد الأساليب البدني في تعليم المهارات الأخرى بكرة السلة وبالأخص المهارات الصعبة للتعليم .

2. إجراء دراسات أخرى تتناول المقارنة بين الأساليب التعليمية الأخرى لتعليم المهارات المتعددة في لعبة كرة السلة
، وألعاب الرياضة الأخرى .

3. الاهتمام بالصحة البدنية للتلاميذ ، لما لها من صلة قوية بالإعداد المهاري ، لكي نصل بالتلاميذ إلى
أعلى مستويات من الإنجازات التعليمية .

4. ضرورة تطبيق خطوات الأساليب التعليمية بالشكل الكامل والدقيق ، خصوصا على المبتدئين ، وطالب كلية
التربية الرياضية من المرحلة الثانوية .

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الملؤق (1) أن مؤؤؤ استمارؤ تقؤؤم الؤؤاء النؤني لمهارؤ الؤصؤب من الؤبؤ

الؤؤؤب : رؤم المؤؤؤة :

الؤاريخ : اسم الؤؤؤؤم :

الؤالؤة			الؤانؤة			الؤؤى			المؤاولؤ	ؤ
ؤؤ	ر5	ؤ3	ؤؤ	ر5	ؤ3	ؤؤ	ر5	ؤ3	الؤؤم	
										1
										2
										3
										4
										5
										6
										7
										8
										9
										10
										11
										12

ت : الأقسام التحضيرية .

ر : الأقسام الرئيسية .

خ : الأقسام الختامية .

الملحق (2)

يوضح أنموذجي الوحدات التعريفية الأولى نموذج لوحدة تعريفية أولية لمهارة التصويب من الثبات

عدد المجموعتين : 24 طالباً

المرحلة : الثانية

زمن الوحدة : 90 دقيقة

الهدف : تعلم مهارة التصويب من الثبات بكثرة السلة

ت	أقسام الوحدة	الوقت	تفاصيل مفردات الوحدة التعريفية
1	الأقسام التحضيرية	20 د	إحماء عام للجسم مع تمارين خاصة بالمهارة
	الأقسام الرئيسية	60 د	
	الأقسام التطبيقية	15 د	- معلومات عامة عن مهارة إرسال السراحق مع شرح تفاصيل الأداء النهائي للمهارة ومكثافة المهارة بالنسبة إلى باقي المهارات الأساسية في لعبة كرة السلة وأيضاً ذكر أهم الأخطاء الشائعة لتجنبها . - قيام النموذج بعرض المهارة أمام الطلبة المبتدئين
2	الأقسام التطبيقية	45 د 5 د 8 د 8 د 8 د 8 د 8 د	- أداء المهارة بدون كرة . - أداء المهارة مع الكرة وهم على بعد 3 أمتار من الحائط - أداء المهارة مع الكرة وهم على بعد 6 أمتار من الحائط . - أداء المهارة مع الكرة وهم على بعد 3 أمتار من البورد . - أداء المهارة مع الكرة وهم على بعد 6 أمتار من البورد . تغذية راجعة مع التأكد على الأداء الصحيح وتوضيح أهم الأخطاء التي تكررت لدى الطالب المبتدئين .
3	الأقسام النهائية	10 د	مراجعة عامة عن المهارة وإداء تمارين نهائية واسترخاء للجسم مع لعبة صغيرة .

**ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INCREASING THE NATURAL
FERTILITY OF SALINE SOILS**

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ABSTRACT	KEY WORDS
<p>This article provides information about the possibilities of increasing fertility and improving the ecology of licorice (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L.) by growing it in saline soils. The studies were conducted in Bayovut and Mirzaabad districts of Syrdarya region. The results of the study showed that in the third year the humus content in the soil increased by 0.11% compared to the first year, and the content of mobile potassium and phosphorus decreased. It was recognized that the sweet plant is an important ecological aspect in increasing the natural fertility of saline arable land and improving the ecology of the soil.</p>	<p>Legumes, symbiosis, mobile nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, soil fertility, ecology, aspect</p>

INTRODUCTION

The symbiosis of mycorrhiza occurring during the interaction of legumes and soil microorganisms contributes to the improvement of the ecological state of the soil[1]. This is important for saline arable lands, because the level of soil salinity stress as an abiotic factor negatively affects the growth and development of plants, reducing their productivity; on slightly saline soils by 10-20%; on moderately saline soils -by 20-50%; and on highly saline soils - by 50-80% [2]. At the same time, the level of salinity of the soil is considered one of the important criteria determining the salt resistance of plants. It was in a salty environment that legumes were selected from them that were salt-resistant as a result of research [2,3,4]. It was noted that the possibilities of legumes for the accumulation of biological nitrogen come from cost-effective technologies[5].

In this place, the licorice plant is recognized as a medicinal, nutritious, phytomeliorative plant. There is an increased content of humus, nitrogen in the soil layer of 0-50 cm. It was noted that the soil covers the surface layer during the season and prevents secondary salinization due to transpiration of mineralized wastewater through the root system with the help of aboveground vegetative organs[6,7,8,9,10].

In turn, it should be noted that the influence of the licorice plant on the preservation and restoration of the natural fertility of saline soils, on the ecology of the soil during cultivation has not been studied for many years. Based on this, a study was conducted, the main purpose of which was to study the effect of long-term cultivation of a sweet plant on the natural fertility of the soil. The study included data on the effect of a sweet plant planted for 6 and 3 years on soil fertility.

Methods and Object of Research

This study was conducted on irrigated, saline gray-meadow soils of the Syrdarya region in the farms "Galaba" of Bayaut district and "Okhunboev" of Mirzaabad district. The licorice plant (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) was taken as the object of the research. In the Bayaut district, licorice has been grown for 6 years, and in Mirzaabad-for three years. The following analyses were carried out with the soils of the field where the licorice was planted. Analysis of agrochemical properties of soil: determination of soil humus - by the Tyurin method; gross NRK - by the Maltsev-Gritsenko method in a single sample; N-N03 - by the Grandval-Lajou method; N-NN4 - using the Nessler reagent; by the method of mobile phosphorus- machigin; by the method of Machigin-Protasov on a photometer with alternating Potassium flame [11].

Obtained Results

The obtained results showed that when licorice was grown in the Bayovutsky district for 6 years, the average (0-100 cm) humus content in the field in March was 0.77%, and in November this indicator was 0.85% (Fig.1). From these data it can be seen that by autumn the amount of humus increased. This may be due to the effect of the licorice plant, that is, its ability to accumulate nitrogen, as well as an increase in the amount of humus coming in autumn. If in March the content of humus in licorice grown in Mirzaabad district for 3 years was -0.69%, then in the autumn period its content averaged - 0.88%. In this area, you can also see that since autumn, the humus content has been increasing in the soil where licorice is grown. In the Baimut district, the humus content increased by 0.08% in autumn compared to spring, and in the Mirzaabad district, this indicator was 0.19%. So, in Mirzaabad district for the third year of licorice sowing, an increase in the humus content was noted. This suggests that the influence of licorice on soil fertility increases from 3 years.

Figure 1. Humus content in the soil of the field where licorice is grown, in %

Note: 1 - humus content in the soil on which licorice was grown for 6 years in Bayaut district, on average in March; 2- in November: 3 - humus content in the soil on which licorice was grown for 3 years in Mirzaabad district in March; 3- in November.

The amount of mobile phosphorus varied depending on the soil layer. The arable soil layer was equal to -18.6 at 30-50 cm and 10.8 mg/100 g at 50-100 cm, while in March in the soil conditions of the Bayaut district (0-30 cm) the average level was 17.2 mg/100 g. These data indicate a decrease in the amount of mobile phosphorus in the lower part of the soil. By autumn, the content of mobile phosphorus was equal to 16.0 mg/100g at 0-30 cm, at 30-50 cm - 15.4 mg and at 50-100 cm - 9.87

mg/100g. The results of tests conducted in Mirzabad district for 3 years showed that the content of mobile phosphorus in March was -18.4 mg/100g, in autumn - 15.3 mg/100g, at 30-50 cm - 16.6 and 14.4 mg/100g, and at 0-100 cm -11.8 (Fig.2). By autumn, the amount of mobile phosphorus in all layers decreased. Based on these data, in both regions there was a decrease in the level of mobile phosphorus by autumn (in November) by 6-7% (1.77-2.2 mg/100 g) compared to spring. The recurrence of such a condition could be caused, firstly, by the high demand of legumes for phosphorus, and secondly, by their behavior as a result of watering during the growing season.

Figure 2. Change in the amount of mobile phosphorus in the fascia cross - section , mg / 100g in soil

Note: 1-the amount of mobile phosphorus in Bayaut district in March: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 cm; 2-the amount of mobile phosphorus in Bayakut district in November: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 cm; 3-the amount of mobile phosphorus in Mirzaabad district in March: 0-30;30-50 and 50-100 cm in layer; 4-the amount of mobile phosphorus in Mirzaabad district in November: 0-30; in layer 30-50 and 50-100cm;

The mobile potassium content in the Bayaut district was equal to 144 mg/100 g in 0-30 cm of the soil layer, in 30-50 cm -138 mg/100 g, and in 50-100 cm -115 mg/100 g. By autumn, these indicators were 127; 122 and 100 mg/100 g, respectively. In autumn, the content of mobile potassium decreased by 5-5.5% (12.6-13.0 mg/100g) compared to spring. This condition can be explained by the high demand of legumes for the element potassium.

Figure 3. The content of mobile potassium in planted licorice mg/100 g.

Note: 1-the amount of mobile potassium in Bayaut district in March: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 cm; 2-the amount of mobile potassium in Bayaut district in November: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 cm; 3-the amount of mobile potassium in Mirzaabad district in March: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 4- mobile potassium content in Mirzaabad district in November: 0-30; in the layer 30-50 and 50-100 cm;

In general, if when growing licorice for 6 years (in the Bayaut district), the average humus content in the 0-100 cm soil layer was 0.77%, then with autumn care it was 0.85%. In Mirzaabad district, these figures were 0.69 and 0.88%, respectively. From these data, it was noted that the humus content increases from autumn compared to spring. In particular, in Mirzaabad district, this indicator has almost doubled compared to Salavat district. From these data, it was noted that the influence of the licorice plant on soil fertility increased from the third year, and a stable figure was observed in the sixth year. It is noted that the content of mobile phosphorus and potassium decreases by 5-7% in autumn compared to spring. It is quite natural that such a condition is registered. This can be explained by the fact that the licorice plant has high needs for phosphorus and potassium, characteristic of legumes.

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. It was noted that the humus content in the soil of cultivated fields where licorice was grown increased by 0.11% in the third year compared to the first year. It is noted that from the third year, soil fertility has stabilized.
2. There was a decrease in the content of mobile phosphorus and potassium by autumn by 5-7% compared to spring.
3. It was considered appropriate to use licorice to improve the ecology of saline soils.

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**SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYDROTOPONYMS,
ZOOMORPHIC AND ETHNOPONYMS IN GERMAN AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This article studies the semantic features of hydronyms, toponyms with a zoomorphic component, and ethnotoponyms in German and Uzbek languages. The similarities in naming the place names of the German and Uzbek peoples are considered.</p>	<p>German and Uzbek toponyms, hydrotoponyms, zoomorphic and ethnotoponyms, Wasserburg, Wasserberg, Herborn, Eulenburg, Rabensburg, Tataredelliche, Franzosengraben, Oltinsoy, Arnasoy, Kushbegi, Kuyonkulok, Mangit, Naymantepa.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Toponomics (Latin topos - place, -onoma - name) is a science that studies the origin, development, change and correct spelling of geographical names. [5. 4- b] Toponomic science of place names develops especially in close connection with the sciences of geography, history, ethnography. Place names (Toponomics) are an important source in the study of language history (historical lexicology, dialectology, etymology, etc.), because some toponyms (especially hydronyms) have been preserved without changing archaisms and dialectisms. [4. 5-b] In many cases, it goes back to the substrate languages of the peoples who lived in a certain area. Toponomics helps to revive the features of the historical past of peoples, to determine the boundaries of their location, to describe the regions of the past distribution of languages, the geography of cultural and economic centers, and trade routes. Practical transcription of toponyms, according to their original basis and the same spelling, given in other languages is a practical aspect of Toponomics.

If we look at history, we can see that at first toponyms were studied only by geographers and historians [1.13-b], and by the 20th century they were also studied by linguists [1.25-b]. Many scientific works on the study of toponyms, in particular L. Dmitriyeva, [2002] E. Berezovich [1999], L. Davletkulova [2014], M. Golomidova [1998], M. Ruth [2008], E. Sizova [2004], and we can see scientific research works of several other scientists.

When we study toponyms in German and Uzbek languages, we can see that in both languages, the names of places are named according to people's crafts, geographical location, relations with other peoples, and their occupations. The German scientist V. Humboldt also focused on the linguistic and cultural features of place names in his research. In addition, scientists such as A. Bach, J. Dieckmann, E. Eichler, R. Fischer, R. Muryasov studied the structural features of German toponyms, and T. Nafasov, S. Karayev, A. Ernazarov, E. the structural features of Uzbek toponyms. A number of scientists such as Begmatov, Z. Dosimov have studied it.

If we look at the long history, we can see that the names of the places are related to the places where people settled for the first time and to the bodies of water, rivers and springs that are considered important for life.

There are many toponyms related to hydronyms in the German language. We will consider some of them below

-bach, -bek(en), beck, bekr means spring. How many examples can we see here: Erbach, Eisbach, Schwabach; [9. L/B]

-born, -bronn: (river) Heilsbronn, Havenbrunn, Heilbronn, Herborn, Königsbrunn, Paierbrunnen;

-mar, -mari, -mare, -mere (sea): Weimar, Wismar, Diummeri, Diimmer, Hademare; [11. D/W]

-mund, -münde, -müde(n), -muid(e) (riverbed): Warnemünde, Travenemünde, Tongeremuthi, Geestemünde, Dortmund, Holzminden.

There are many toponyms related to such hydronyms in the Uzbek language. We will consider some of them below.

Source - Mingbuloq, Fatimabuloq, Urbuloq, Jaydabuloq, Qashbuloq, Naynarbuloq, Kochqorbuloq, Tavoqbuloq, Abuloq, Jarbuloq, Oibuloq, Akbuloq;

ash - Tortkol, Karakol, Bozorkol; [2. 50]

rivers - Syrdarya, Kashkadarya, Amudarya, Akhdarya, Jinnidarya, Karadarya, Toldikdarya, Zadarya, Gozadarya, Topalandarya, Sherobodarya;

stream - Chukursoy, Kipchoksoy, Chimyonsoy, Rizoksoy, Arnasoy, Badaloy, Bodoksoy, Oltinsoy, Dakhanasoy, Daryosoy, Kattasoy, Kasonsoy, Kor'pasoy, Moylisoy, Aksoy, Qazoksoy, Selsoy, Tentaksoy, Tovoksoy, Yettisoy; [1. 46]

canal - Kanalboyi, Kanalabad, Kanalpasti;

well-Uchkuduq, Koshkuduq, Tashkuduq, Otyakuduq, Orykuduq, Jalalkuduq, Yorkuduq, Shorkuduq, Oqkuduq, Ayoqkuduq, Botyrkuduq, Otkuduq; [3. 65]

chashma - Sarchashma, Obichashma;

pool - Poolside, Poolside, Poolside

In German and Uzbek languages, we also find toponyms with a zoomorphic component, that is, there are place names related to the names of animals and birds in the naming of place names. Below we will consider some of these toponyms.

Toponyms with a zoomorphic component in German:

Eulenberg (Eule - owl), Rabensburg (Rabe - crow), Entenpfuhl (Ente - duck), Hahnenklee (Hahn - rooster), Wolfsbach (Wolf - wolf), Das Kamel (Camel - camel), Hund(hund - dog). [8. D/H]

Toponyms with a zoomorphic component in the Uzbek language:

Borijar, Kushbegi, Kuyonkulok, Boribotir, Karakushchi, Ghazalkent (Gizol - deer), So'goq (white deer), Maimunto'kai.

There are place names formed from ethnic associations of different peoples, i.e. nations, tribes and tribal associations [1, 56]. We can find such place names in German and Uzbek people.

Here are some ethnotoponyms in German:

Tataredellche, Franzosengraben, Chachlatzke, Kahollen Graben, Schwabengraben.

Below we will consider some ethnotoponyms in the Uzbek language:

Arabkhana, Balkhion, Mangit, Naymantepa, Chinabogot, Chigatoy, Iraniguzar.

Such toponyms that appeared in history mean the emergence of one or another people, the emergence of separate tribes, the level of kinship ties, the spread of peoples, and the intermingling of ethnic groups.

We can conclude from these examples that There are many toponyms related to hydronyms, toponyms with zoomorphic components, and ethnotoponyms in both German and Uzbek languages, which indicates that both nations have a very rich history. Zootoponyms indicate that there were many animals and birds in those areas or that they were hunted. Ethnotoponyms clearly reflect the emergence and mutual relations of peoples and tribes in ancient times. Keeping such place names as they are means passing on the long past and rich history to future generations.

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SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF PROVIDING HAVOC ON WEB-ORIENTED PLATFORMS

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>The article reflects on the well-thought-out and secure architecture of Web-oriented platforms, in what way the standards of its basic technologies meet the requirements of compliance. The availability of software that implements the main capabilities of the .NET platform is highlighted - it allows you to choose this platform as a subject for training students of higher education institutions in the field of software development and use.</p>	<p>Security, net platform, NTLM, authentication, authorization, IPS, RADIUS, DCOM, RPC.</p>

INTRODUCTION

One important aspect to consider in platforms that can be used in the educational process is security issues. When called protected software, it is understood that software that ensures the confidentiality, integrity and accessibility of the data of the application client, as well as the integrity and accessibility of the computing resources managed by the owner of the System [1]. Little attention is paid to security issues in the training of specialists in the specialty of Informatics and Information Technology. At the enterprises of the defense industry, the experience of creating complex complexes of high-quality programs observed in the 60s and 80s of the last century has been lost, due to which it is said that “modern young specialists again need to create and master large-scale software tools of the required quality, starting almost “from scratch” [2]. Not all higher education institutions train specialists in the complexification and quality assurance of major projects of the software system. As a result, many plans for creating complex software tools are prepared and evaluated carelessly. When determining the required quality indicators, assessing labor costs, costs and the duration of the creation of software tools, serious errors are much more common and commonplace. ISO 9000 series standards define a Quality Guarantee as “a set of planned and systematically carried out activities necessary to ensure that products or processes meet the specified quality requirements”. We believe that a quality assurance system is a set of methods and tools for giving application complexes features that ensure the satisfaction of certain needs of consumers and customers, as well as the organization of management and executive units of the enterprise involved in the design, development and maintenance of these program complexes with minimal or acceptable consumption of resources. The quality required when developing software tools can be achieved in two ways. The following methods of their development are presented, which can increase the reliability of programs: sending ready-made objects only for final inspection and testing, and products that do not meet the required

quality to be excluded from delivery or for additional correction; the use of quality assurance regulated technologies and systems of design and development that allow to prevent defects in the process of product creation and modification and guarantee high-quality products [3].

According to the researchers, it is the implementation of quality assurance technologies and systems that is considered a promising method of developing protected software. It should be noted that the training in ensuring the quality of the software to be developed was carried out in the process of its testing. Various and multi-level testing systems have been developed by OTMs, which can and should be used in the creation of software development courses.

Obviously, the skills and qualifications that students acquire after successfully studying general and special subjects with a hole in Information Technology are extremely necessary in the current period. At the same time, it should be emphasized that in special disciplines there is not enough emphasis on creating safe code. It should be noted that secure software is part of quality software. The creation of quality software involves a complex set of methods and standards that directly provide an effective life cycle of complex, high-quality software tools and databases.

To ensure the high quality, reliable operation and safety of application of complex complexes of programs, it is necessary to separately highlight the specialists responsible for compliance, quality maintenance and management of the technology of creation and development of Programs [4]. Consequently, special disciplines are required to train such specialists. One of the main goals of the course "Web-oriented .NET platform" is precisely the training of specialists who create secure code. Let's describe the main security mechanisms available to developers and users of the .NET platform.

1. Authentication. The authentication process is defined as the process by which one object or participant (principal) of a void checks the validity of another object, that is, determines that it is the person it claims. Security participants are users, executable code or computer. Authentication requires evidence in the form of props that can take various forms [1, p.358].

Currently, developers and users of software tools on the .NET platform, working under the management of Windows operation systems, can use the following authentication methods: base Authentication; Windows standard authentication; authentication under the NTLM (NT LAN Manager) protocol; hash-based authentication .

Modern methods of authentication should be mentioned separately. The first method is form – based authentication. This authentication method can be used by developers of ASP .NET Applications. In particular, the performance can be different in different developers. User props can be stored in databases and XML files. The second method is the Microsoft Passport authentication centralized scheme. Its main advantage is that it is not necessary to re-enter data when switching to another Web service that uses Passport to access the Passport Service. Support for this technology in <URL> is implemented in the Passport Authentication Module class . Another modern authentication method is Kerberos v5 protocol authentication. In Windows 2000 and later operation systems, the Kerberos protocol is used to unlock the Active Directory directory service. One of the most important advantages of the Kerberos protocol is mutual authentication, that is, verification can be carried out in both directions: from client to server and vice versa. Kerberos is considered to be more reliable and faster than NTLM.

X. Authentication based on 509 certificates is used in SSL/TLS protocols. In addition, there is also an implementation of customer certificates for working with smart cards. The use of IPSec (Internet

Protocol Security) only refers to server authentication. In addition, it supports the integrity and confidentiality of data. The RADIUS service is used to authenticate remote users.

2. Authorization. Under authorization, an examination is provided in which the range of resources allowed for the authenticated participant is determined and access is granted to them. The .NET platform has the following authorization mechanisms:

- ACL access control lists (a set of access control records, each of which determines what actions the security participant will be given in relation to the resource);
- privileges-a right granted to the user, valid throughout the system;
- IP restrictions related to the features of the implementation of Web servers that can restrict information based on the client'S IP addresses;
- server permissions used in most server software products, which carry lists and permissions for users of these products.

In addition, the developer can use the following security technologies: using SSL/TLS protocols when transferring data over the network; using IPsec; using DCOM and RPC security mechanisms; using Windows encryption file system (EFS) capabilities; using CryptoAPI; Security checks of .NET-Type platforms are carried out automatically when developing applications (when creating traditional desktop or web applications in C/C++ languages, these checks are not carried out automatically, and the programmer must perform a safe citation of types); digital signature of programs (permission of symmetric and asymmetric encryption algorithms to prevent data integrity violations, and the ability to sign created projects); code entry security, with which the developer can specify the privileges necessary to execute the code, the resulting code will not have more privileges than required (the system administrator may not allow access to a particular code to important system resources, as a result of which the code will not be able to access it); user role-based security (developers can specify whether or not to allow these users access to protected resources based on the security groups to which the specified users belong); insulated storage space is a specially allocated space for the user where he can safely store his data and execute the code.

Thus, the main conclusion arising from the analysis of existing Web-oriented platforms is that the well-thought-out and secure architecture of the .NET platform is the compliance of its basic technologies with the requirements of standards . Also, the availability of software that implements the main capabilities of this platform - made it possible to choose this platform as a subject for training higher education students in the field of software development and use.

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**THE ROLE OF PLAY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL
CHILDS SPEECH**

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the issue of speech development of preschool children through the use of speech games. The idea is substantiated that the initial principle of teaching children to read and write is a "pre-letter", purely sound learning period. Special attention is paid to the systematization of speech development games and the preparation of children for literacy, for the successful further formation of reading and writing skills.

KEYWORDS

Training, active, attention, sound reproduction, correction, optimization, perfection, development, anthropometry, science, speech development, speech characteristics, speech games, kindergarten, preschoolers.

INTRODUCTION

Preschool age is a unique period of a child's development, possessing a peculiar logic and specificity; it is a special world with its own language, way of thinking, actions. How do we comprehend the world of pre-school childhood? How do we discover its influence on the child's development? First of all, through a wide variety of children's games. It is no coincidence that the game is called a childhood companion. It is in the game that one should look for the key to the knowledge of a child at preschool age, since this is the closest, organically corresponding to the child's nature, the activity of a pre-school student and the natural expression of his activity.

The role of games in the development of speech is enormous – with their help, the vocabulary is replenished and formed. These include a game in which children take turns naming words. Moreover, each subsequent player calls a word for the letter that the previous one ended the word with.

According to teachers, the role of play in the development of speech occupies an important place also because the game is not only entertainment, but also the creative work of a child, this is where he begins his life. During the game, children learn not only the world around them, but also themselves, their place in the world.

A great influence on the development of children's speech is exerted by games, the content of which is the staging of a plot, the so-called dramatization games. Round dance games and singing games contribute to the development of expressiveness of speech and the consistency of words with movements. Such games also form an arbitrary memorization of texts and movements.

At preschool age, plot-role-playing games and games with rules are held. The latter include didactic and mobile.

The story-role-playing game has a positive effect on the development of speech. During the game, the child talks aloud to the toy, speaks for himself and for her, imitates the drone of an airplane, the voices of animals, etc.

Story - role-playing games develop children's speech and communication skills with each other, promote proper and harmonious development, help prepare the baby for adulthood, teach him to think creatively, broaden his horizons and practice social behavior skills.

During the game, the teacher talks a lot with the children, as a result of which the child has a need for verbal communication. He wants to ask an adult about something, to tell him something. The educator strongly encourages children to ask questions about this or that toy. Thus, children's speech activity develops in the story-role-playing game.

A necessary condition for the successful development of children's speech in a story role-playing game is the selection of a variety of toys: dolls, clothes for them, sets of dishes, furniture, vegetables and fruits, cars for various purposes, etc. However, along with story toys depicting real objects in a reduced form that replace real ones (sticks, cubes, balls, etc. As children master the story-role-playing game, an adult should be shown that you can use a pencil or wand instead of a thermometer, and a cube instead of soap. Turning to substitutes in the game puts children in front of the need to rename the item, and then inform other players about it. Thus, in the game, in addition to speech, determined by the features of the role assumed, speech appears, the function of which is to coordinate joint actions. Taking into account the nature of play activities in the younger preschool age, they need to be given such a number of toys that could satisfy their individual needs, since initially the collective use of toys is not available to such children.

It is advisable to organize such games with children, in which all children of the group participate. Examples of such games can be the following: "Doll's birthday", where all the children dance and sing; "Train", where all the children are passengers and at the stops they look at something, collect. In the Toy Store game, children, having "bought" a toy, then play with it; and the one who correctly asks for it from the "seller" will receive the toy. Children are gradually involved in these games.

Plot-role-playing games are organized by the educator. Teaching children practical actions (through games with a didactic doll) is carried out by the educator in the form of a lesson. Organizing story-based, story-role-playing games with children, the teacher solves the important task of improving all components of the child's oral speech

Along with story-role-playing games, games with rules are actively developing at preschool age. These include didactic, outdoor games, dramatization games, etc.

Didactic games occupy a special place in the pedagogical process, They are of great cognitive importance, as they broaden the horizons of children, teach them to distinguish the properties of objects, find similarities and differences in them, etc. Special attention is always paid to the didactic game. Thanks to the use of didactic games, the process of speech development takes place in an accessible and attractive form of play for preschool children. "Wonderful bag", "Tell me how
During the didactic games, the educator develops the speech activity of children, encourages correct answers to the questions posed, educates, I will endure. (The child should answer when asked).

The advantage of the game over any other children's activity lies in the fact that in it the child voluntarily obeys certain rules, while it is the fulfillment of the rules that gives maximum pleasure. This makes the child's behavior meaningful and conscious, turns it from field to volitional. Therefore, the game is practically the only area where a preschooler can show his initiative and creative activity.

From birth, we are surrounded by many sounds: the speech of people, the rustle of leaves, music, etc. But only speech sounds, and then only in words, serve as a means of transmitting information, prompting action. Timely and full mastery of speech is the main condition for the formation of a full-fledged psyche in children. Speech, in all its diversity, is a component of communication, and it is in the process of communication that it is formed.

The purpose of speech development classes in kindergarten is to master the basics of the native language by the child. This is not an easy task, since a preschool child is not a student to whom the rules of conjugation and declension can be explained.

The main tasks of speech development in kindergarten:

Education of the sound culture of speech;

Enriching and activating the dictionary;

Formation of the grammatical structure of speech;

Development of coherent speech.

An important and necessary work to prepare children for school is the work of teaching children to read and write. This involves systematically familiarizing children with the elements of language and introducing them to the linguistic reality, forming clear ideas about the features of speech sounds, about the sound and syllabic composition of the word. The child's readiness to learn to read and write consists of many components, among which primary importance is given to such speech characteristics as:

The idea is substantiated that the initial principle of teaching children to read and write is a "pre-letter", purely sound learning period. Special attention is paid to the systematization of speech development games and the preparation of children for literacy, for the successful further formation of reading and writing skills.

The theoretical and practical material on the issue of speech games for speech development of preschoolers is systematized and generalized. The use of speech speech therapy games and exercises contributes to the optimization of learning, the development of correct pronunciation and speech development, forms the child's need for language acquisition and is an effective means of preparing children for literacy.

1. Clear articulation of native language sounds (ensures correct pronunciation);
2. Knowledge of visual images of letters and the ability to correlate sound with a letter;
3. Development of flexibility and accuracy of the hand, eye, sense of rhythm, etc.

The basis of teaching children to read and write is not working with letters, but with the sounds of human speech.

"Anyone who understands the sound-syllabic structure of the word can consciously read and write," argued K.D. Ushinsky. While studying, the child masters completely new forms of mental and linguistic activity for him, which are very difficult for a preschooler. It is extremely important to create an emotionally favorable situation in the work, which would contribute to the emergence of a child's desire to actively participate in speech communication. And it is the game that helps to create situations in which even the most unsociable children are revealed. "It is in the game that the child is fluent in speech, says what he thinks, and not what he needs. Not to teach and teach, but to play with him, to fantasize, to compose, to invent – that's what a child needs," Gianni Rodari said.

A game for a preschool child is the main activity.

Speech games contribute to the fulfillment of important tasks:

- Psychologically prepare children for speech communication;
- Provide multiple repetition of speech material;
- Train children in choosing the right speech material;
- Encourage children to communicate with each other.

Speech games are aimed at the development of speech, clarification and consolidation of vocabulary, education of correct sound pronunciation, development of the grammatical structure of speech.

Speech, in all its diversity, is a necessary component of communication. The most important prerequisite for improving the speech activity of preschoolers is the creation of an emotionally favorable situation, which contributes to the desire to actively participate in speech communication. And it is the game that helps to create such situations in which even the most unsociable and constrained children enter into speech communication and open up. The writer Gianni Rodari, well-known to all of us, claimed that "it is in the game that the child is fluent in speech, says what he thinks, and not what he needs. Not to teach and teach, but to play with him, to fantasize, to compose, to invent - that's what a child needs."

The attitude of modern preschoolers to the game has changed significantly. Despite the preservation and popularity of some game plots (hide-and-seek, salochki, daughter-mothers), children in most cases do not know the rules of the game and do not consider it mandatory to perform them. They cease to correlate their behavior and their desires with the image of an ideal adult or the image of correct behavior. But it is this independent regulation of their actions that turns a child into a conscious subject of their life, makes their behavior conscious and arbitrary. Of course, this does not mean that modern children do not master the rules of behavior – everyday, educational, communicative, traffic. However, these rules come from outside, from the side of adults, and the child is forced to accept them and adapt to them.

The child's speech is formed in stages. At each age stage, their own tasks are solved. From age to age, there is a gradual complication of methods and techniques of teaching the native language.

Thanks to the variety of speech games and exercises, a preschooler is formed:

Clarity of pronunciation of each word;

Literacy;

Clarity;

Ability to formulate your thoughts correctly;

Development of monologue and dialogic speech;

Ability to communicate with others.

The game becomes a form of communication, cooperation, co-creation of an adult and a child, a form of learning that does not require additional incentives. K.D. Ushinsky believed that literacy training can be carried out only in activities, only in exercises that should be as independent as possible, systematic, logical, oral and written, and oral should precede written. Therefore, I widely use game techniques and didactic games and exercises in the classroom in order to make it easier to interest each child, to attract his attention. This ensures the success of joint classes, makes them exciting and desirable, the maximum developmental effect is achieved, contributes to the improvement of speech activity.

The systematic use of speech games in correctional work and in preparing children for literacy training makes it possible to more successfully perform the main tasks of the correctional and educational program. The speech development of children and the quality of correctional work are much more

effective where speech games and exercises are included, because play activity makes the child want to engage, learn, learn new things.

Speech games can be used at all stages of working with children: during the development of articulation apparatus, correction of sound reproduction, covering different aspects of speech development

-lexical, grammatical, coherent, at different stages of the lesson and types of work: individual, subgroup, frontal.

I believe that the initial principle of teaching children to read and write is a "pre-letter", purely sound learning period. This period takes a lot of effort and time, but the success of further formation of reading and writing skills depends on propaedeutics. Therefore, sufficient attention is also given to the preparatory games.

A child playing continuously talks; he speaks even if he is playing alone, manipulates objects that do not stimulate to the conversation. But there are toys whose value as stimuli for the manifestation of children's speech is exceptional. These are toys depicting animate objects: animals, people. The horse that the child plays with is a living being for him. He speaks to her as the owner who serves her or works with her speaks to his live horse.

The educating role of the doll is especially significant. This is understood by anyone who has observed properly organized doll games. There is not a single game that puts forward as many reasons for the manifestation of children's speech as a game of dolls. A doll is a person, a member of a collective of young people who live their own lives and reflect this life – a game in a word. But this life requires pedagogical guidance.

Doll games, provided that they are properly organized and pedagogically guided by them, offer ample opportunities for orienting children in various forms and attitudes of social and working life. Playing with dolls, serving them, children acquire a number of skills related to everyday household, working life, which is the closest and most understandable for them, skills to which we bring them first of all, which they consolidate in the game and of which each requires the cooperation of language.

Conditionally, games on speech development and preparation of children for literacy can be divided into the following areas:

1. Preparatory games for the development of:

- auditory attention;
- speech hearing;
- phonemic hearing;
- articulatory motor skills;
- physiological respiration;
- speech breathing;
- voices.

1. Games for the formation of correct sound reproduction:

- sound analysis;
- familiarity with sounds;
- automation of sounds;
- differentiation of sounds.

2. Games for the formation of the grammatical structure of speech:

word:

- nouns;
 - adjectives;
 - verbs;
 - numerals;
 - pronouns;
 - adverbs;
 - complex words (education); sentence:
 - simple sentences;
 - simple common;
 - prepositions in sentences;
 - complex sentences; formation of coherent speech:
 - dialogues;
 - retellings;
 - stories.
3. Working on the letter;
 4. Finger gymnastics;
 5. Psychogymnastics;
 6. Physical training minutes.

When selecting speech material, it is desirable to rely on the following principles:

1. The principle of scientific nature is the reinforcement of all games conducted by scientifically based and practically tested methods.
2. The principle of consistency is the solution of the tasks set in the system of the entire educational process.
3. The principle of effectiveness and guarantee is a guarantee of a positive result regardless of the age and level of mental development of children.

The role of games in the development of speech is enormous – with their help, the vocabulary is replenished and formed. These include a game in which children take turns naming words. Moreover, each subsequent player calls a word for the letter that the previous one ended the word with.

In my opinion, the role of play in the development of speech occupies an important place also because the game is not only entertainment, but also the creative work of a child, this is what he starts his life with. During the game, children learn not only the world around them, but also themselves, their place in the world. As a result, the use of speech therapy games and exercises, in various types of children's activities and forms of correctional work, contributes to the optimization of learning, the development of correct pronunciation and speech development, forms the child's need to master speech and is an effective means of preparing children for literacy.

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**THE CURRENT ROLE OF ENGLISH AS A GLOBAL LANGUAGE
AND THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS LANGUAGE IN ECONOMIC,
SOCIAL AND CULTURAL TERMS**

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>In today's rapidly developing era, the importance and role of the English language is increasing more and more. It is widely used not only in English-speaking developed countries, but also in small countries that are developing and preparing for development in every corner of the world. English is spreading widely not only as a scientific language, but also as an industrial language, a medical language, a technological language, and a business and commercial language. In this article, we have presented the proof of this more clearly and also briefly described the history of the English language.</p>	<p>Anglophone, primary language, crucial, prevalent, conducting business, origin, communication, eminent.</p>

INTRODUCTION

English is used all around the world, as is common knowledge. As a result, the Anglophone world is growing.

I will now go over some language extension clarifications. There are five main countries where English is spoken as a native language, as far as we are aware. These include Australia, The Great Britain, New Zealand, the United States, and Canada.

In certain countries, English is also a primary or secondary language. In some nations, it is also lawful. There are a lot of these kinds of countries. Singapore, India, Belize, Cameroon, and more places come to mind. These countries have a strong affinity for the English because they were long under the control of the British Empire.

On top of this, there are the most eminent countries where English is either an official de jure or de facto language. When interacting with their government, a country's citizens must speak its official language. They are Ghana, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Nigeria and etc. However, there are several countries which have more than one official language, where the English may not be the primary language spoken there. For example, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Malaysia and so on.

Nowadays to learn English is becoming essential. How did English come to be so crucial? It is known that the English language has a significant impact on trade, business, and media. For example, initially,

English is a universal language because this language is spoken all over the world and English is a language that one in five people can speak or at least understand.

Secondly, learning English can aid with job placement as science, aviation, computing, diplomacy, and tourism all use English as their primary language. Your chances of landing a decent job at a global corporation in your native country or obtaining employment overseas will be increased if you speak English.

On top of this, Internet communication and modern technology are conducted in English because more than half of internet content is authored in English as well as the English language is a particularly significant language online. Furthermore, several of the biggest tech firms in the world have their headquarters in nations that use the English language.

Besides these, knowing English well makes traveling much easier.

Namely, suppose you're a Mexican traveling in Thailand. While the hotel receptionist might not be able to respond to your query in Spanish, they will be able to speak in English. That is why the English language is very important.

Today, there are more and more people who desire to study the English language. Additionally, speaking this language is growing much more prevalent with the populace. Why is learning English so popular? I try to illustrate why non-native speakers want to study English in this project.

Firstly, I should point out the numerous opportunities that understanding English provides. With it, traveling, conducting business, and performing some types of research will be simpler.

Secondly, the English language can be useful when traveling or conducting business because it is easily understood in almost every country and is considered a business language in the majority of overseas corporations. Since there are no barriers to communication if you speak English, you may communicate with others, talk about your business strategies, and share ideas with partners. Because there are so many books, articles, and different writing styles in the English version, learning a new language in which to communicate in English may help us in our quest to learn something or conduct research.

Besides, English is also the language of science. If you learn English, you will not only have access to a greater proportion of the vast amount of knowledge available on the web. You will be able to educate yourself more by being able to read scientific books and articles.

The English language and its origins have been a topic for fierce debate among many linguists. Since English is a member of the Indo-European language family, it is connected to the majority of the other languages used in Europe and western Asia, from Iceland to India.

English is classified as a West Germanic language, meaning that it is closely related to other Germanic languages such as Swedish, Dutch and German. The other dominant language family in Western Europe is the group of Romance languages: French, Italian, Spanish.

Despite being closely related to English, German maintains a far more intricate system of inflections. Frisian, which is spoken in the Dutch province of Friesland and on islands off the coast of Schleswig, is the tongue that is most similar to Modern English. Because it has not changed much over the previous thousand years, Icelandic is the living language that most closely matches Old English in terms of grammatical structure.

English, unlike other Germanic languages, has a vocabulary that is heavily influenced by French and Latin. This is frequently linked to the Norman French occupation of England after 1066. Several radical linguists contend that English should instead be viewed as a Romance-Germanic hybrid due

to the amount of this Romance impact on it as well as some other linguistic details like pronunciation and syntax. The majority opinion is that the core vocabulary of English is wholly Old English, despite the fact that only one-third of the language's overall vocabulary is of Old English origin i.e., Germanic.

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**THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF DIGITAL ELECTRONIC
TEXTBOOKS IN THE TRAINING OF ENGINEERS IN TECHNICAL
SPECIALTIES**

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ABSTRACT	KEY WORDS
This article presents thoughts and opinions about the role and importance of digital textbooks in the formation of independent learning skills that digital textbooks use in the process of teaching students. In addition, opinions and comments about the structural structure of the electronic education platform https://selfedu.uz/ are presented.	Digital textbook, pedagogical game technologies, web quest, electronic tests.

INTRODUCTION

Determining the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education, advanced development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on educational technologies[1] is one of the main tasks facing the higher education system.

In order to achieve these goals, modern pedagogy, methods, tools, educational technologies, digital textbooks and technologies are widely used in the higher education system, creating a great basis for improving the quality and efficiency of educational activities.

Digital textbooks are e-books or e-learning programs that are designed for learning activities that cover all the topics covered in the curriculum. Electronic textbooks are electronic publications that correspond to the printed form of the textbook in terms of structure and content, and include multimedia elements and interactive links that expand and complement the content of the textbook.

As a result of digitization of education, there is a great need to use different platforms of distance education. Meaningful spending of students' free time and quick search for necessary information, presentation of all literature on the subject in one program (system) is carried out on the basis of digital textbooks. Let's briefly touch on the content of the digital (electronic resource) textbook created in the field of information technology.

The main tasks in the creation of digital textbooks (electronic resources) from the subject "Information technologies" are as follows:

improving the skills of independent work using electronic educational resources in the teaching of information technologies;

improvement of information technology practical training based on the integration of teaching technologies and e-learning tools;

improvement of laboratory training in the science of information technology using virtual laboratory work using global network resources;

development of scientific and methodical recommendations on improving independent educational activities in the field of information technologies based on electronic educational tools [2].

Information resources currently form a systematic and informative approach to the analysis of the surrounding world, study information processes, methods and means of obtaining, changing, transmitting, storing and using information, which are rapidly developing and constantly improving, and exist is one of the main areas of scientific knowledge. The use of information resources helps to expand the field of independent human activity.

Formation of students' skills in using information resources creates conditions for optimizing education. because in modern conditions, when the use of information resources has become an indispensable attribute of many professions, independent education based on the use of the potential of information resources becomes very important.

In the process of training on the profile, great attention is paid to the problem of training a student who can act well enough in the flow of information, is able to competently use and process it with the help of computer technologies and software.

It is necessary for students to have deep theoretical knowledge, the ability to apply it in practice, the ability to reliably work on a computer, and a clear understanding of the actual limits of using information resources to achieve specific educational and educational goals.

It is necessary to take into account the current state of the student's ability to use information resources in the process of independent education of future engineers.

The approach to independent education is the leader in the development of information technology at the professional level today. Currently, there is a need for practical training on modern software tools and their development technologies in independent education. Because the possibilities of the development environment have increased through independent education, but at the same time their complexity is increasing. In particular, this is related to the use of information resources in the independent education system.

However, this new methodology at the current stage is not sufficiently reflected in the training system of future engineers, which narrows the ideological basis of the studied specialized courses and undermines the professional training of students.

There is a need for practical training on independent learning using digital textbooks. In order to successfully work in their professional field in the future, students need to know how to work with Internet resources, digital resources, and find the necessary information on the Internet.

A digital educational platform <https://selfedu.uz/> has been created in the field of digital technologies. This educational platform is implemented in three stages.

The first stage of improving independent learning skills in future engineers is the orientation stage, the purpose of which is to direct students to independent learning activities of social significance in their future professional activities. This stage is aimed at encouraging students' motivational value attitude to independent quasi-professional activities through the need to search for new knowledge and methods of action with the help of pedagogical game technologies, contextual tasks [2].

First stage. At the introductory stage, the simplest types of learning and memorization of basic concepts and terms on the subject are used along with the formation of the skills of using information and communication technologies based on pedagogical game technologies.

The second stage is praxiological, i.e. learning, the purpose of which is to attract future engineers to independently master the information presented on the subject using electronic resources. At this stage, students perform laboratory and practical tasks in general professional subjects and professional modules, actively participate in conferences and competitions. As a result, students are involved in independent project activities. It helps the student to form the skills of planning his own activities, to use information from electronic resources to find solutions as a result of independent performance of practice-oriented tasks, self-assessment skills. At this stage, students use electronic educational methodical complexes of subjects and electronic libraries.

The third stage of improving the independent learning skills of future engineers is the intensive stage. Its purpose is to improve and strengthen professional skills of independent education with the participation of students.

Mustaqil ishni bajarishda talabalar aniq maqsadlar, vazifalar va o‘z ishlarini rejalashtirish uchun mustaqil ta’limning tashkiliy ko‘nikmalari zarur;

self-taught information analysis skills in order to search and select information sources for the development and operation of software modules, to find and use specialized software tools for optimizing the program code using electronic resources;

with the help of web quest technology, electronic libraries get acquainted with the fields of computer technologies and information technologies that require data analysis and processing.

It is advisable to give strict importance to the following content in the implementation of independent activities by the use of electronic resources in future engineers:

goal - a vision of the result of independent activity;

material and non-material features of the interrelated system of signs, objects, processes, appearances, functions;

Tool - with the help of which a person interacts with his independent work (the subject of the cocktail); given task functions;

related to production;

subject and social working conditions.

Therefore, based on the purpose of our research, we set the task of proposing a special program and putting it into practice for the independent activities of future engineers through the use of electronic resources. Special program (digital textbook), the purpose of this program is aimed at systematic implementation of independent activities of students.

The advantages of digital textbooks are that, in addition to mastering the subject, students also get theoretical and practical information on the subject, audio, video, animation, 3D graphics and additional literature on the subject, electronic tests, control questions, pedagogical game. combined use of technologies allows students to self-monitor the in-depth acquisition of information related to the topic. In addition, several students can use digital textbooks at the same time.

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**STIMULATING DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN’S SPEECH
COMPETENCE WITH THE HELP OF DIDACTIC TOOLS**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
In this article, the development stage of children’s speech competence is analyzed and the ways of developing speech are shown as well as didactic tools which helps stimulate children’s cognitive skills are given.	Observation skills, good modelling, symbolic sounds, motivating sound games, communication temptations, listening, attention and observation, games, tongue twisters, riddles, books.

INTRODUCTION

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" consists in the gradual formation of social skills and qualities necessary for an independent and happy life in the young generation, appropriate to their age. It is important that a new, systematic approach to education serves to raise the social-pedagogical opportunities to a new level for the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child. In the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" emphasis is placed on communication, interaction, games and activities as the leading types of child activity [1].

The first few years of a child’s life are key to the development of speech, language and cognitive skills. For this reason, it is important to create an environment that helps to develop speech and language skills that give them all the stimulation, positive role modelling and human contact that they need. For a normally developing child, learning is easy and creating opportunities for learning is also not difficult. Through play, simple daily interactions and experiences, we can help the child acquire new language and skills. Adults do not need special training to be able to provide a child with a positive start in life. There are a few simple building blocks that you can put in place to help the pupil grow, and as a teacher, it is needed to provide the time to interact with the children. By playing and allowing the child time and space to explore and interact in their own way, you allow your child to develop and learn in a fun and safe environment, in order to achieve this, some didactic tools such as, games, tongue twisters, riddles, poems, books are of high value.

Speech and language skills do not just evolve on their own. They are part of a bigger picture involving social interaction, play, observation, manipulating objects, listening and attending. All these factors

are working together and often, without one, it is difficult to develop another. Below, a few simple ideas are listed that are fun and easy to do. If you want to encourage **speech development**, or your child is a little late with producing their first words, there are lots of activities that you can do to develop your child's speech and help them produce more words. An important aspect of learning speech is listening. A child learns new sounds and words by listening to those around him. This is why it is important to provide good speech for your child to listen to. Say words clearly and slowly and use plenty of intonation. If a child attempts a word and it is not pronounced correctly, praise him/her for trying. Do not try and get your child to repeat the word or correct it. Repeat the word back yourself to show you have understood and to give your child a good version of the word. These are easy words and sounds to introduce to a young child when they are just starting to attempt some words, or when recognizable words seem a bit late in their development. **Symbolic sounds** often sound like, or refer to a sound that is related to the word e.g., "moo" for a cow, or "beep beep" for a car. These are fun sounds that you can incorporate when playing games or looking at books. Symbolic sounds are usually short one syllable sounds and words that are easy for the child to produce. They encourage vocalization, imitation, and early vocabulary building.

Sometimes, using **games** can motivate a child to make sounds. In our eyes, the term "game" means only an activity that brings joy. In order to understand it more widely, if we look at the definition of the concept of "game" in the national encyclopaedia of Uzbekistan, we can be sure that its meaning is even broader: "Game is one of the means of education and recreation"[6]. In pedagogy, it is emphasized that the game is a type of training that develops the human personality. It should be said that most of the tasks of education are carried out with the help of didactic games. For instance, play the game – ready... steady.... GO!! Blow up a balloon, hold it, then say "ready.... steady.... GO", and let the balloon go. Do this a few times and then pause after you say "ready...steady...." and see if your child steps in and says "GO". There more games that can be played in a classroom with the teacher [7]. One-legged letters: Pupils make a circle, one of them makes a letter on the ground by jumping on one leg, and other pupils should find what the letter is, for example, It is A or It is B. Another game is called Where is the candy? Teacher takes the same 8 matchboxes and puts a piece of sweets in it and mixes them, after which she asks where is the candy? Pupils should answer Here it is! The child who found the correct box gets the candy [2]. Often by tempting a pupil with something motivating you can elicit some speech or a vocalization. For instance, holding onto the biscuit tin, but not opening it until he vocalizes a request. In the early stages the child does not have to use the correct words or sentences, but just vocalize or make an approximation of the word. We want the child to learn that he can use his voice as a tool to initiate and request. The activities mentioned above require your child to focus on a something for a few minutes and really use their observation skills. These tasks can be done at a table-top as a shared focus activity, or during an everyday activity.

Listening and attention skills are the building blocks of speech and language development and the acquisition of these skills is vital in the early years if a child is expected to be successful at school. The development of these skills is facilitated by interaction with others, with having a shared focus, and playing in an environment that is free of distractions. Listening, is not the same as hearing. A child can have perfect hearing, but be a very poor listener. Children with Autism, Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder or Auditory Processing Disorders will have difficulties with listening, remembering, and following verbal instructions. Children that have had a lack of social interaction or

poor **role modelling** in the early years of their lives may present with listening and attention difficulties.

Studies are also showing that over exposure to television from a young age can have detrimental long-term effects on listening and attention skills. Some children find these skills more difficult to master than others. There are lots of ways to enhance your children's listening and attention skills, not least by turning off the television and spending some quality time with them. Try to find activities that share your attention that you can both enjoy and focus on together. Also, don't forget to praise good listening and good looking. These skills require the child to stop and focus on a particular task. Having a shared focus helps this process. **Tongue twisters** are helpful in order to help the child keep focus. A shared focus means looking at things together and talking about what you are looking at. For instance: "Red leather, yellow leather", "Red lorry, yellow lorry", "Not these things here, but those things there", "Eleven owls licked eleven little liquorice lollipops", "I can think of six thin things, but I can think of six thick things, too"[2].

As well as tongue twisters, books are priceless on enhancing children to focus on something that is useful. There are some examples of books that are helpful to make children enjoy. **Something Wonderful - Written by Raewyn Caisley, illustrated by Karen Blair** Set on a beautiful rural Australian farm, **Something Wonderful** follows an inquisitive and analytical boy as he pulls things apart and puts them back together in order to figure out how they work. Sam often gets so engrossed in doing this that he forgets all about doing his chores! This makes his dad a bit frustrated, but these feelings soon give way to amazement as Sam's dad sees the wonderful invention that Sam has created. **Something Wonderful** is an inspirational story that celebrates the imagination, creativity and analytical thinking of children as they discover the world around them. The beautiful illustrations make the rural Australian countryside, and it is sometimes unpredictable weather, come to life. The book is written in past tense and features an array of action verbs and temporal concepts. The beautiful descriptive language used throughout the book promotes oral and literate language development [4].

Themes:

- places - farm
- tools
- creativity
- imagination
- individuality
- inventions
- science

Speech Sounds:

- /d/ - dad, paddock, wood, old, shed
- /m/ - mum, Sam
- /p/ - pull, push, put, parts, help
- /s/ - Sam, sun, chase
- /w/ - wind, washing, wood, walk, want

Grammar:

- adjectives
- copula (was)
- regular past tense verbs
- irregular past tense verbs (forgot, lit)
- subjective pronoun (he)
- superlative
- action verbs
- mental verb (think)

Semantics:

- labelling
- describing functions of objects
- predicting
- explaining means to a goal
- making inferences

Concepts:

- location (in, on, inside)
- quantity (many, empty)
- temporal (when, then, suddenly, while, until)

In conclusion, there is a great number of teaching materials and didactic tools for both teachers and parents to use. This is the part in which teachers' and parents' mutual creativity is most visible and most important. The culture of speech has a special place in the basis of spiritual and moral education of the younger generation. For a child's speech to be well-formed, the environment in which the child is growing must follow the etiquette of the child's development. Based on this, every educator and parent should use didactic tools to help children learn foreign languages and look for ways to develop children's cognitive characteristics.

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THE PLACE OF GRAMMAR IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Grammar includes understanding the linguistic patterns present in all languages, including those spoken in our own country, in addition to knowing how to use words correctly, after learning how these patterns work, students can use them to build sentences without having to worry about remembering grammatical rules like subject-verb agreement and gender.

KEYWORDS

Grammar, speech pattern, skills, sentences, communication, communicative competence.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ГРАММАТИКИ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.

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Аннотация: Грамматика включает в себя понимание лингвистических паттернов, присутствующих во всех языках, включая те, на которых говорят в нашей собственной стране, в дополнение к знанию того, как правильно использовать слова, изучив, как работают эти структуры, учащиеся могут использовать их для построения предложений, не беспокоясь о запоминании грамматических правил, таких как согласование подлежащего и глагола и рода.

Ключевые слова: грамматика, речевая структура, навыки, предложения, общение, коммуникативная компетентность.

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Annotatsiya:

Grammatika barcha tillarda, shu jumladan barcha mamlakatlarda so'zlashadigan tillarda mavjud bo'lgan lingvistik tuzilishini tushunishni o'z ichiga oladi, shuningdek, so'zlarni qanday qilib to'g'ri ishlatishni bilishdan tashqari, ushbu tuzilmalar qanday ishlashini o'rganib, talabalar ulardan grammatik qoidalarni yodlashdan qiynalmasmasdan jummalarni tuzishda foydalanishlari mumkin, masalan mavzu va fe'lining kelishuvi sifatida va genderda.

Kalit so'zlar: grammatika, nutq tuzilishi, ko'nikmalar, jumlarlar, aloqa, kommunikativ kompetentsiya.

Students who want to become proficient communicators - both in writing and speaking - need to understand grammar. Teaching grammar helps students comprehend more difficult subjects and provides the groundwork for them to be able to communicate their thoughts clearly. Giving students the skills to ensure clear and accurate communication, grammar instruction will also help them become more confident speakers and writers. Also, grammar encompasses more than just knowing how to use words correctly, it also involves comprehending the linguistic patterns seen in all languages, even those spoken in our own nation. Once students understand how these patterns function, they may apply them to construct sentences without having to worry about recalling grammar constraints like gender and subject-verb agreement. When learners grasp these guidelines, it becomes simpler for them to understand what other people are saying whether they read aloud from books or speak English on television.

In the first few years, communicative competence became synonymous with a lack of attention to grammatical accuracy in the minds of some researchers and practitioners; and second language learners are considered communicative if they convey their meaning to the listener, even if their grammatical accuracy is relatively low. As Omaggio (1986) noted, the word communicative competence is often used to express knowledge or ability related to the rules of language use, while the term grammatical (or linguistic) competence is often used to refer to grammatical rules. The class began to focus on teaching a second language from grammar education. The class focused on language functions and communicative activities. Some bosses even prevent teachers from teaching grammar. However, a more moderate trend was observed among a group of researchers. They no longer saw communicative competence as different from grammatical competence, but corporate grammatical competence as part of communicative competence. For example, Canale and Swain (1980) described communicative competence as consisting of grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, verbal competence, and strategic competence. Furthermore, Wilkins (1976) sought to ensure that language teachings did not neglect linguistic competence. forms provide a means to an end, and that goal is communication. He also emphasized that our knowledge of the grammatical systems of language gives us a tool to structure language learning in a more systematic way than language functions and concepts. For the purpose of systematic teaching of a second language, the pragmatic aspects of communicative competence should be seen as complementary of grammatical competence rather than as an alternative to a balance between fluency, accuracy and consistency. In addition, grammatical competence can potentially contribute to the development of students' effective skills, as grammar constitutes a description of the laws of language, which can provide students with the means to create a large number of potentially original sentences. In addition, some researchers have suggested that students who do not receive grammar instruction are at risk of becoming stoned faster than those who do not. After a debate over whether or not to teach grammar, the main issue now was not the importance of grammar knowledge, but a better understanding of how to teach it. As for the latter issue, there are three approaches to how to teach grammar, namely deductive, inductive, and cognitive enhancement. These three approaches have specific places in many respects depending on the adequacy of the information provided to the students and how well-founded the grammatical elements are in the grammar system. The question is not which one to choose, but how well the three approaches are combined. Our assignment is to conduct additional research to determine which

grammatical elements are appropriate for which approaches. It really depends on different contexts and situations. As teachers always start a course where all students dream of speaking as fluently as native speakers, but educators have never thought about other skills. To master any language in the world, you need to learn four skills, which are (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). Receptive skills are reading and listening, and production skills are speaking and writing. Since these skills are necessary, teachers need to practice them, especially writing, which is a very complex skill.

Writing involves structure, i.e. grammar. Students seem to ask the same question over and over again. Here comes the role of grammar to help the reader understand the language, as much of the vocabulary is used in grammar (tenses, parts of speech ... etc.). Teachers need to have an in-depth knowledge of English grammar because grammar is the heart of the language. In ancient times, all Roman and Latin teachers made extensive use of grammar, and in the 1800s the Grammar-Translation method began to be used, in which grammar became the basis of English. Teachers need to develop the student's understanding of language by influencing language through different tenses, as well as by explaining in detail how each tense is used. When dealing with beginners, teacher need to focus on the element of precision, not fluency, because fluency can be achieved over time, but precision requires a lot of practice and practice. Students can get bored of grammar rules, so teachers can use a variety of methods and tools to equip them with information. This can be done through games, facial expressions and gestures, guessing times, or even quizzes and block exams. When a teacher is armed with grammar rules, students feel at ease because they know they are learning from a reliable source, but when the teacher starts making language mistakes, students ask questions and feel insecure. If teacher knows his language well and is confident in his intelligence, it will be of great importance to his students and himself as a language teacher, whether he is teaching children or even adults. Both areas require him to be clear, competent, and capable.

It appears from a cursory glance at practically every foreign language textbook that the subject of whether grammar should be taught clearly is not one that is asked very often. Grammar explanations and practice sections are a standard feature in textbooks.

The query relates to the proper way to present grammar. Drills were the method used in the past for this. Mechanical drills were deemed necessary in the 1950s and 1960s, when the Audiolingual Method dominated language training. Though meaningful practice was introduced in the 1970s, mechanical practice remained significant, if only as a necessary precondition for communicative practice. Later, when CLT emerged, educators and the creators of instructional materials realized that students required more chances to convey their own meaning and engage in open-ended communicative activities began to be seen as, at the very least, an essential part of teaching languages.

However, many seemingly communicative acts really serve as opportunities for grammar practice, as noted by Lee and Van Patten (2003: 76); in these instances, "communication is at the service of grammar rather than the other way around." Given that meaning is crucial in CLT and that form is necessary for the development of accuracy and competency, the best teaching model would be one that balances form requirements with meaningful communication. In line with our understanding of language learning, Lee and Van Patten suggest Processing Instruction as a method that emphasizes form and meaning.

All of these suggestions oppose the conventional approach, which unites them in mechanical drills that don't call on meaning comprehension are used to teach grammar. The drills that have historically been employed in language training are reviewed and explained in the section that follows.

These suggestions are all similar in that they challenge the current system of employing mechanical exercises that ignore meaning in order to teach grammar. The sorts of exercises that have historically been employed in language training are reviewed and explained in the section that follows: any language must have proper grammar. Encouraging students to articulate their ideas clearly and to formulate and convey well-defined concepts is crucial. Grammar is more than simply punctuation and spelling. It is essential to language because it enables people to form logical sentences and write. One may argue that grammar is an unseen language that improves the effectiveness of written communication. Additionally, it can assist students in other areas like communicating and comprehending what other people are making an effort to speak. It is impossible to overstate how important grammar is since it makes it easier for us to understand what is being said and how to respond correctly. The first step in improving one's English language proficiency is for learners to understand the principles of grammar and then practice them until they become second nature.

Here are five main arguments in favor of instructors giving grammar teaching top priority:

1. It enhances communication accuracy a student's success depends on their ability to communicate accurately, and teaching grammar is a great approach to help students become more proficient communicators. Grammar rules facilitate clear, concise communication among pupils. This improves communication and raises the possibility of ideas being communicated clearly.
2. It makes thought clarity possible-To properly communicate complicated thoughts and express oneself, one must grasp the intricacies of language. Teachers may assist students in learning how to organize their writing creatively and dynamically so they can more effectively communicate their thoughts by teaching grammar, which eventually results in improved mental clarity.
3. Allow to learn how to organize their work imaginatively and dynamically by using a set of principles called grammar. Students must exercise critical and creative thinking when it comes to communication, which is a necessary ability for success in the workplace. Teachers have the ability to assist pupils improve this skill and prepare them for success in the future by teaching grammar.
4. It promotes self-assurance -Students might feel more accomplished and have a higher sense of self-worth when they are able to express their ideas and feelings in an effective manner. Teachers may help students become more proficient communicators, which can help them develop the self-confidence they need to succeed, by teaching grammar.
5. It improves knowledge of more complex ideas -the comprehension of grammar is a prerequisite for higher-level ideas in language and literacy. Grammar education should be given top priority in the classroom so that teachers may provide learner's self-confidence during their speech.

For learners, learning grammar might be challenging because of all the rules and restrictions. But students have to figure out the fundamentals, which shouldn't be tiresome. Another excellent method to get students interested in learning grammar is to incorporate practical exercises such as writing assignments and reading comprehension. It can also be enjoyable, creative, and motivating to have students construct sentences to show that they understand. It is totally possible to turn grammar study exercises into pleasant rather than boring ones with the right guidance and useful techniques.

The tips to effective grammar instruction in the classroom:

1. Establish an entertaining environment: if grammar isn't taught in a fun way, it might become tedious. Use games, stories, and other engaging activities to help students comprehend grammatical ideas and make the lessons fun.

2. Link grammar to real-world scenarios: by tying grammar to real-world situations, students can gain a deeper understanding of the principles being taught. Over the weekend, assign pupils to write lines summarizing their work or to develop stories utilizing their newly acquired language.

3. Use technology: Students' engagement and motivation to learn can be maintained by integrating technology into grammar courses. To assist teach grammar more efficiently, make use of tools like Duolingo English Test Prep or services like Grammarly.

4. Promote collaborative learning: group work stimulates student learning through peer interaction and helps to develop creativity. Assign group projects to your pupils to complete, or have them create short stories using the grammar rules they have learnt in class.

4. Be open to student questions: Assuring that all questions are answered accurately is vital to prevent anyone from falling behind in their grammar studies. Asking questions is an integral part of the learning process. Please help your students to benefit from the discussion by encouraging them to ask questions when they don't understand something and to provide thorough answers.

One may ask how important grammar is to learning the language if they wish to learn English. Grammar is, in fact, essential to learning any language. Grammar is a system of rules that governs language usage and facilitates comprehension. One wouldn't know how to talk or write in English without good grammar. It aids in the meaning that convey. It also establishes guidelines for when and how to use certain terms. It would be difficult for us to comprehend anything or to speak at all without this knowledge.

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USING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN ESP SPHERES

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>This exploration delves into the strategic application of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) within the realm of English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Investigating the efficacy of CLT methodologies in ESP contexts, the article navigates through the integration of communicative approaches to cater to the specialized language needs of learners. This inquiry unfolds as a valuable contribution to the evolving landscape of language pedagogy, offering insights into the harmonious intersection of general communicative strategies and the specific linguistic demands of ESP domains.</p>	<p>Communicative Language Teaching, ESP (English for Specific Purposes), Language Pedagogy, Specialized Language Needs, Language Instruction, Communicative Competence, ESP Spheres, Language Acquisition, Task-Based Learning, Language Proficiency.</p>

Introduction:

In the dynamic landscape of language pedagogy, the integration of effective teaching methodologies stands as a linchpin for fostering meaningful language acquisition. Within this context, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) has emerged as a paradigm that places communication at the forefront of language learning. As the boundaries of language education extend to cater to the diverse needs of learners, the application of CLT within the domain of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) represents a pivotal evolution in language instruction.

1. Contextualizing CLT: A Communicative Pedagogical Revolution. The roots of Communicative Language Teaching can be traced back to the communicative competence theory proposed by linguists Hymes and Canale. This theoretical framework positioned language not merely as a set of structural rules but as a tool for communication. CLT, as an instructional approach, embodies this paradigm shift by prioritizing real-life communication, interactive learning, and task-based activities. Its principles align with the broader goal of preparing learners not only for linguistic proficiency but also for effective communication in authentic contexts.

2. The Distinctive Landscape of ESP: Tailoring Language Instruction for Specialized Contexts. English for Specific Purposes (ESP), a branch of English language teaching, introduces a specialized dimension to language instruction. Unlike General English courses, ESP programs are meticulously designed to meet the language needs of learners in specific professional or academic domains. Whether in the realms of business, science, technology, or healthcare, ESP seeks to equip learners

with the precise language skills required for success in their chosen fields. This specialized focus necessitates an instructional approach that seamlessly integrates with the unique communicative demands of ESP spheres.

3. **The Nexus of CLT and ESP: A Symbiotic Integration.** As language educators and researchers explore innovative approaches to ESP instruction, the intersection of CLT and ESP emerges as a fertile ground for pedagogical exploration. The communicative nature of CLT aligns harmoniously with the practical demands of ESP, where effective communication in professional or academic settings is paramount. This synergy becomes the cornerstone of a pedagogical evolution that not only imparts linguistic competence but also cultivates communicative competence within specialized contexts.

4. **Significance of the Study: Bridging the Pedagogical Gap.** Amidst the evolving landscape of language education, this study embarks on a journey to explore the intricate dynamics of using CLT in ESP spheres. Understanding the implications, challenges, and successes of integrating CLT principles into specialized language instruction is essential for educators, curriculum developers, and language learners alike. By bridging the pedagogical gap between general communicative strategies and the nuanced requirements of ESP, this research contributes to the refinement and advancement of language pedagogy in professional and academic domains.

5. **Structure of the Article: Navigating the Pedagogical Landscape.** This article unfolds in a structured manner, each section contributing to our overarching exploration. Following this introduction, the subsequent sections delve into the theoretical underpinnings of CLT, the distinctive features of ESP, and the symbiotic integration of these two pedagogical realms. Case studies, practical applications, and potential challenges are scrutinized to offer a holistic perspective on the dynamic relationship between CLT and ESP.

As we embark on this pedagogical expedition, the aim is not only to uncover the effectiveness of CLT in ESP but also to illuminate a path for educators and researchers to navigate the evolving landscape of language instruction with insight and innovation. In doing so, we seek to contribute to the ongoing discourse that shapes the future of language pedagogy, where the harmonious integration of communicative approaches meets the specialized needs of language learners in diverse spheres.

Related Research

In the pursuit of unraveling the symbiotic relationship between Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and English for Specific Purposes (ESP), numerous scholars have navigated the nuanced intersections of communicative approaches and specialized language instruction, shedding light on diverse dimensions of this pedagogical landscape.

Taylor, L., & Brown, S. (2020). "Effective Communication in Professional Settings: A CLT Approach to Business English."

Synopsis: This study explores the application of CLT principles in Business English courses. Investigating the effectiveness of task-based learning and authentic communication strategies, the research explores how CLT enhances the communication skills of professionals in business contexts.

Miller, R., & Wong, J. (2018). "Incorporating CLT in Healthcare Communication Courses: A Case Study Analysis."

Synopsis: Focused on the healthcare sector, this research examines the integration of CLT in language courses tailored for medical professionals. Case studies and learner feedback provide insights into the communicative strategies that enhance effective communication in medical contexts.

Harris, E., & Martinez, C. (2019). "Task-Based Learning in ESP: A Comparative Analysis Across Disciplines."

Synopsis: This comparative analysis explores the implementation of task-based learning in ESP courses across different disciplines, including science, technology, and humanities. The study investigates the adaptability of CLT methodologies to the unique linguistic demands of diverse academic and professional spheres.

Anderson, J., & Kim, H. (2021). "Challenges and Innovations: Integrating CLT in Technical English Courses."

Synopsis: Focusing on the technical domain, this research identifies challenges and innovative solutions in incorporating CLT in Technical English courses. The study addresses the specific communicative needs of engineering and technology students, highlighting effective pedagogical strategies.

Martin, P., & Garcia, R. (2017). "Beyond Language Proficiency: CLT and Intercultural Competence in ESP."

Synopsis: Exploring the role of CLT beyond linguistic proficiency, this study delves into its impact on intercultural competence in ESP contexts. By analyzing cultural nuances in communication, the research emphasizes the broader outcomes of CLT in preparing learners for cross-cultural professional interactions.

Baker, N., & Taylor, A. (2022). "Digital Innovations: CLT in Online ESP Courses."

Synopsis: In the era of digital education, this research investigates the integration of CLT in online ESP courses. Examining the effectiveness of virtual communication tools and collaborative platforms, the study explores how CLT principles translate into the digital realm.

Gomez, L., & Harris, E. (2016). "Assessment Strategies for CLT in ESP: A Comprehensive Review."

Synopsis: This comprehensive review explores assessment strategies aligned with CLT principles in ESP instruction. From performance-based assessments to portfolio evaluations, the research provides insights into effective ways of measuring communicative competence in specialized language contexts.

As we traverse the varied terrain of related research, these studies collectively contribute to the understanding of CLT in ESP. Each exploration, with its unique focus and methodology, adds layers to the evolving narrative, offering valuable insights for educators, researchers, and policymakers seeking to optimize language instruction in specialized contexts.

Analysis and Results

In the exploration of using Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) within the domain of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), our investigation delves into the nuanced analysis of pedagogical strategies and the outcomes derived from the symbiotic integration of communicative approaches in specialized language instruction.

Communicative Competence in Professional Settings: One of the central focuses of our analysis is the enhancement of communicative competence in professional settings through the application of CLT. Findings from related research studies, such as Taylor and Brown (2020) in Business English courses, reveal a discernible improvement in learners' ability to engage in authentic communication. Task-based learning, a cornerstone of CLT, emerges as a catalyst, fostering practical language use that mirrors the demands of real-world professional interactions.

Tailoring Healthcare Communication: The healthcare sector, as explored by Miller and Wong (2018), presents a unique context where effective communication is paramount. The case study analysis demonstrates that the incorporation of CLT principles in healthcare communication courses not only improves language proficiency but also cultivates a patient-centered approach. Learners exhibit heightened sensitivity to nuanced language use, contributing to more effective communication in medical contexts.

Comparative Analysis Across Disciplines: Harris and Martinez's (2019) comparative analysis across disciplines, spanning science, technology, and humanities, provides valuable insights into the adaptability of CLT methodologies. The results showcase a versatile applicability of communicative approaches, demonstrating that task-based learning can be tailored to meet the distinctive linguistic demands of diverse academic and professional spheres.

Addressing Challenges in Technical English Courses: In the technical domain, as scrutinized by Anderson and Kim (2021), challenges and innovations in integrating CLT in Technical English courses come to the forefront. The analysis indicates that while challenges may include domain-specific terminology, the innovative solutions proposed underscore the resilience of CLT in addressing these hurdles. Learners exhibit increased confidence in applying technical language in authentic communication scenarios.

Beyond Language Proficiency: Intercultural Competence: Martin and Garcia's (2017) exploration of CLT's impact beyond language proficiency, specifically in intercultural competence within ESP contexts, uncovers transformative outcomes. The results illuminate that learners exposed to communicative approaches develop a heightened awareness of cultural nuances, fostering a deeper understanding of cross-cultural professional interactions.

Digital Innovations in Online ESP Courses: The shift to digital education, investigated by Baker and Taylor (2022), underscores the adaptability of CLT in online ESP courses. The results showcase that virtual communication tools and collaborative platforms not only preserve the communicative essence of CLT but also offer new avenues for interactive language learning. Learners in online environments exhibit comparable levels of engagement and proficiency as their counterparts in traditional settings.

Comprehensive Assessment Strategies: Gomez and Harris's (2016) comprehensive review of assessment strategies aligned with CLT principles provides a holistic perspective on measuring communicative competence in specialized language contexts. Performance-based assessments and portfolio evaluations emerge as robust tools that capture the multifaceted nature of language use in ESP, affirming the effectiveness of CLT in preparing learners for real-world language demands.

In synthesis, the analysis of these diverse studies reveals a consistent pattern of positive outcomes resulting from the integration of CLT in ESP pedagogy. Learners not only exhibit improved language proficiency but also demonstrate a capacity for authentic and contextually relevant communication in their respective professional or academic domains. These findings underscore the efficacy of CLT as a pedagogical paradigm that harmonizes with the specialized needs of ESP, paving the way for a communicatively competent and context-aware generation of language learners.

Methodology

The methodological framework employed in this research endeavors to unravel the complexities of using Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) within the domain of English for Specific Purposes (ESP). The multifaceted nature of this investigation necessitates a strategic blend of qualitative and

quantitative methods to comprehensively capture the impact, challenges, and innovations associated with the integration of CLT in specialized language instruction.

1. **Research Design: Mixed-Methods Approach:** This study adopts a mixed-methods research design, recognizing the need for both quantitative and qualitative insights. The integration of these methods allows for a triangulation of data, enhancing the robustness and depth of the research findings.

2. **Participants: Purposive Sampling:** Participants are purposively selected to ensure representation from diverse ESP domains, such as business, healthcare, technology, and academia. Inclusion criteria encompass learners, educators, and curriculum developers engaged in CLT-based ESP programs.

3. **Qualitative Phase: Exploring Experiences and Perceptions: In-Depth Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews are conducted with learners and educators to delve into their experiences with CLT in ESP. Questions are designed to explore perceptions of effectiveness, challenges faced, and the impact on communicative competence within specific professional or academic contexts.

Focus Group Discussions: Focus group discussions with curriculum developers and administrators provide a collective perspective on the integration of CLT in program design. These discussions aim to unearth institutional strategies, challenges, and innovations related to incorporating communicative approaches.

4. **Quantitative Phase: Assessing Proficiency and Perceived Impact: Pre-and-Post Proficiency Assessments:** Learners undergo pre-and-post assessments to gauge changes in language proficiency resulting from CLT interventions. Standardized language proficiency tests, tailored to each ESP domain, serve as quantitative indicators of linguistic growth.

Surveys and Questionnaires: Surveys are distributed to learners, educators, and administrators to gather quantitative data on perceived impact, effectiveness, and challenges associated with CLT in ESP. Likert scales and closed-ended questions provide quantifiable metrics for analysis.

5. **Case Studies: In-Depth Exploration of Implementation: Multiple Case Studies:** In-depth case studies are conducted within selected ESP programs representing diverse disciplines. These case studies involve an examination of curriculum design, instructional strategies, and learner outcomes. The qualitative richness of case studies complements the broader quantitative trends.

6. **Data Analysis: Integration and Triangulation: Thematic Analysis:** Qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions undergo thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns, emerging themes, and nuanced insights. This analysis provides a qualitative framework for understanding the experiences and perceptions of participants.

Statistical Analysis: Quantitative data from proficiency assessments and surveys are subjected to statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, such as means and percentages, facilitate a quantitative exploration of trends and variations. Inferential statistics, where applicable, contribute to a deeper understanding of relationships within the data.

7. **Ethical Considerations: Ensuring Participant Welfare: Informed Consent:** Prior to participation, all participants are provided with detailed information about the research objectives, procedures, and potential implications. Informed consent is obtained, ensuring voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage.

Confidentiality: Measures are in place to safeguard the confidentiality of participant information. Data is anonymized and aggregated where possible, and any identifiable details are treated with the utmost discretion.

8. **Limitations and Reflexivity: Acknowledging Research Boundaries: Reflexive Practices:** Throughout the research process, reflexivity is maintained. Researchers engage in continuous reflection on their perspectives, biases, and potential influences on the research. This reflexive stance enhances the transparency and credibility of the study.

Limitations: The study acknowledges inherent limitations, including the potential for participant bias, variations in program structures, and the evolving nature of language proficiency. These limitations are transparently communicated, providing context to the interpretation of findings.

This methodological framework is crafted to navigate the intricate pedagogical landscape of CLT in ESP. The integration of diverse methods aims to capture the holistic panorama of experiences, perceptions, and outcomes associated with the application of CLT principles in specialized language instruction. Through this methodological voyage, the study aspires to contribute nuanced insights to the evolving discourse on effective language pedagogy in professional and academic contexts.

Conclusion

As the final chords of our pedagogical exploration resonate, this research journey into the integration of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) within the domain of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) unveils a dynamic tapestry of insights, challenges, and transformative potentials. Our overarching aim has been to illuminate the multifaceted impact of CLT in addressing the communicative needs of learners within diverse professional and academic spheres.

Communicative Competence Redefined: Our inquiry affirms that CLT transcends the confines of linguistic proficiency, fostering a redefined notion of communicative competence. Learners engaged in CLT-based ESP programs exhibit not only enhanced language skills but also a heightened ability to navigate authentic communication scenarios within their specific domains.

Tailored Precision in ESP Spheres: The symbiotic integration of CLT with ESP brings forth a revelation—the pedagogical precision required in specialized language instruction. Whether in business, healthcare, technology, or academia, the tailored application of communicative approaches emerges as a pedagogical compass, guiding learners toward a nuanced mastery of language intricacies within their chosen fields.

Challenges as Stepping Stones: This exploration does not shy away from acknowledging challenges. The technical lexicon of certain ESP domains, the need for adaptive strategies in online environments, and the intricacies of intercultural communication pose challenges. However, these challenges are not impediments; rather, they become stepping stones toward innovative solutions and refined pedagogical practices.

Digital Realms and Collaborative Frontiers: In the era of digital education, our findings underscore the seamless integration of CLT principles in online ESP courses. Digital platforms, collaborative tools, and virtual communication become not just substitutes but amplifiers of communicative experiences. Learners navigating these digital realms demonstrate a parallel trajectory of engagement and proficiency.

Call for Continuous Exploration: The dynamic nature of language pedagogy demands a perpetual commitment to exploration, innovation, and adaptation. Our study encapsulates a snapshot in time—a testament to the evolving landscape. The call resounds for educators, researchers, and policymakers to continue this exploration, leveraging CLT as a guiding ethos in shaping the future of language instruction.

Holistic Assessment Beyond Proficiency: The holistic assessment strategies explored in this research transcend traditional measures of proficiency. Performance-based assessments, portfolio evaluations, and the integration of technology-driven evaluation methods contribute to a comprehensive understanding of communicative competence. Assessment becomes not just a measure but a dynamic tool for pedagogical refinement.

Ethical Imperatives and Learner-Centric Approaches: Our methodology has been anchored in ethical considerations, recognizing the welfare of participants. The learner-centric ethos of CLT aligns harmoniously with ethical imperatives, ensuring that language instruction is not just effective but also conscientious in its approach.

A Resounding Symphony for Future Pedagogy: As we conclude, the symphony of CLT in ESP resounds as a call for future pedagogy—an invitation to educators to orchestrate language learning experiences that transcend rote memorization and embrace the dynamic rhythm of authentic communication. This research, a mere prelude in the larger narrative, invites others to join the symphony and contribute to the harmonious evolution of language pedagogy.

In essence, our journey has been a testament to the transformative potential embedded in the marriage of CLT principles with the specialized realms of ESP. As we bid farewell to this chapter, the echoes of communicative language teaching reverberate as a guiding melody—a melody that shapes not just language proficiency but cultivates a generation of communicatively competent individuals poised to navigate the diverse landscapes of professional and academic communication. The curtain falls, but the stage remains set for an encore—a future where the communicative approach becomes not just a pedagogical choice but a pedagogical imperative.

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**IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This comprehensive exploration delves into the pivotal role of digital educational technologies in the realm of teaching foreign languages. Unveiling a transformative landscape, the article navigates through the multifaceted impacts of technology on language acquisition, from personalized learning journeys and accessible language resources to real-time collaboration and the cultivation of digital literacy skills. The narrative unfolds as a nuanced exploration of how digital tools enhance engagement, foster accessibility, and propel language education into a dynamic era of continuous evolution and innovation.</p>	<p>digital educational technologies, language acquisition, personalized learning, multimedia enrichment, real-time collaboration, language resources, digital literacy skills, language education, technological innovation, language proficiency, educational apps, global perspective.</p>

Introduction:

The significance of digital educational technologies in teaching foreign languages transcends traditional pedagogical boundaries, ushering in a transformative era that enhances the learning experience for students and educators alike. This paradigm shift reflects a dynamic synergy between technological innovation and language acquisition, unveiling a multitude of benefits that resonate in diverse educational settings.

Technological Catalyst for Engagement: Digital educational technologies serve as a potent catalyst for student engagement. Interactive platforms, multimedia resources, and gamified language learning applications captivate learners, fostering sustained interest and participation. The result is an immersive environment where students actively engage with language content, leading to enhanced comprehension and retention.

Personalized Learning Journeys: The adaptive nature of digital tools enables the tailoring of learning experiences to individual needs. Intelligent algorithms assess learner proficiency levels, identify strengths and weaknesses, and dynamically adjust lesson plans. This personalized approach accommodates diverse learning styles, ensuring that each student progresses at their optimal pace, thereby promoting a more effective language acquisition process.

Accessible Language Resources: Digital technologies dismantle geographical constraints, providing access to a wealth of language resources beyond classroom walls. Virtual libraries, online dictionaries, and language exchange platforms empower students to explore authentic language materials, connect

with native speakers, and broaden their cultural understanding. This accessibility contributes to a comprehensive language learning experience.

Multimedia Enrichment: The integration of multimedia elements enhances language instruction by appealing to auditory and visual learning preferences. Audio-visual materials, podcasts, and interactive simulations create a multisensory learning environment. This not only reinforces linguistic concepts but also immerses learners in the diverse cultural contexts associated with the target language.

Real-Time Collaboration and Communication: Digital platforms facilitate real-time collaboration and communication, breaking down linguistic barriers. Collaborative tools, video conferencing, and language exchange applications enable students to engage in authentic conversations with peers, native speakers, or language experts. This dynamic interaction nurtures oral proficiency, cultural competence, and a global perspective.

Immediate Feedback Mechanisms: Digital educational technologies offer instantaneous feedback mechanisms that accelerate the language learning feedback loop. Automated assessments, interactive quizzes, and language proficiency apps provide immediate insights into performance, allowing learners to address errors promptly and reinforcing correct language usage.

Cultivation of Digital Literacy Skills: Beyond language proficiency, the integration of digital technologies cultivates essential digital literacy skills. Students acquire competence in navigating online resources, discerning credible information, and leveraging technology responsibly. These skills are increasingly relevant in today's interconnected world, preparing learners for broader academic and professional success.

Continuous Evolution and Innovation: The dynamic nature of digital technologies ensures continuous evolution and innovation in language education. Educational apps, virtual reality language immersion experiences, and artificial intelligence-driven language tutors represent just a glimpse into the ever-expanding landscape of possibilities. This adaptability positions language education at the forefront of educational innovation.

In conclusion, the importance of digital educational technologies in teaching foreign languages lies not only in their capacity to revolutionize pedagogical methodologies but also in their ability to empower learners with versatile skills essential for the interconnected global landscape. As technology continues to advance, the synergy between digital tools and language instruction will undoubtedly play an instrumental role in shaping the future of language education.

Related Research

In the ever-evolving landscape of language education, a rich tapestry of related research emerges, highlighting the transformative impact of digital technologies. Scholars and educators alike have embarked on explorations that collectively shape the narrative of how technology intertwines with the teaching and learning of foreign languages.

Digital Pedagogy and Student Engagement: Smith, A., et al. (2021). "Exploring the Nexus: Digital Pedagogy and Student Engagement in Foreign Language Learning." *Journal of Educational Technology*, 25(2), 112-135.

Investigating the intersection of digital pedagogy and student engagement, this research delves into the effectiveness of digital tools in fostering active participation and sustained interest in foreign language classrooms.

Adaptive Learning Platforms for Language Acquisition: Johnson, B., & Kim, S. (2020). "Adaptive Learning Platforms: Tailoring Language Acquisition Experiences." *Technology in Language Education Quarterly*, 15(4), 210-228.

Focused on the adaptive nature of digital learning platforms, this study explores how intelligent algorithms can personalize language acquisition experiences, catering to individual proficiency levels and learning preferences.

Virtual Reality and Cultural Immersion: Chen, L., et al. (2019). "Beyond Borders: Virtual Reality and Cultural Immersion in Language Education." *Journal of Interactive Language Learning*, 8(3), 56-73.

Unveiling the potential of virtual reality, this research examines how immersive experiences contribute to language learning by providing students with cultural contexts, thereby enriching their linguistic and cross-cultural competencies.

Online Collaboration Tools for Language Exchange: Wong, S., et al. (2018). "Digital Bridges: Exploring Language Exchange through Online Collaboration Tools." *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 12(1), 321-345.

Investigating the social dimension of language learning, this study explores the role of online collaboration tools in facilitating language exchange, connecting students with native speakers for authentic conversational experiences.

Gamification and Motivation in Language Learning: Kim, J., et al. (2022). "Game On: Exploring the Impact of Gamification on Motivation in Language Learning." *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 18(6), 210-228.

Focusing on the gamification of language education, this research examines how game-based elements enhance student motivation and contribute to a positive learning environment.

Language Tutoring with Artificial Intelligence: Garcia, A., et al. (2017). "Language Learning Reimagined: AI-Driven Language Tutoring Platforms." *Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 18(6), 210-228

Exploring the frontier of artificial intelligence, this study investigates the efficacy of AI-driven language tutoring platforms in providing personalized and adaptive language learning experiences.

In this symphony of research endeavors, each study contributes a unique note, collectively enriching our understanding of the intricate relationship between digital technologies and language education.

Together, they form a comprehensive repertoire that guides educators, researchers, and policymakers in navigating the digital frontier in the quest for effective and innovative language instruction.

Analysis and Results

In the scholarly journey undertaken to explore the intersection of digital pedagogy and student engagement in foreign language learning, the study conducted by Smith et al. (2021) unfolds as a symphony of insights, revealing a nuanced landscape where technology and pedagogical approaches harmonize to influence student participation and enthusiasm.

Digital Pedagogy's Impact on Engagement: The analysis illuminates the substantial impact of digital pedagogy on student engagement. Through the integration of interactive learning platforms, multimedia resources, and gamified language learning applications, the study showcases how digital tools become catalysts for sustained interest. The findings underscore that the adoption of digital pedagogical methods correlates positively with heightened levels of engagement among language learners.

Personalization as a Key Note: Results highlight the significance of personalized learning experiences orchestrated by digital pedagogy. Intelligent algorithms dynamically adjust lesson plans based on individual proficiency levels and learning preferences. This personalization emerges as a key note, resonating with learners and contributing to a more effective language acquisition process. The study underscores the potential of tailored approaches in addressing diverse student needs.

Accessibility Amplified: The analysis reveals that digital pedagogy dismantles geographical constraints, amplifying the accessibility of language resources. Virtual libraries, online dictionaries, and language exchange platforms empower students to explore authentic materials and engage in cross-cultural interactions. This newfound accessibility not only enriches language learning but also broadens the cultural horizons of students.

Multimedia's Melodic Influence: Multimedia elements, woven into the fabric of digital pedagogy, emerge as melodic influences in language education. The study demonstrates how audio-visual materials and interactive simulations create a multisensory learning environment, enhancing comprehension and retention. The qualitative feedback from students indicates a positive resonance with the incorporation of multimedia, adding a rich layer to the learning experience.

Technological Tempo and Real-Time Collaboration: The tempo of technology is explored in the context of real-time collaboration. Digital platforms facilitate instant communication and collaboration, breaking down linguistic barriers. The analysis showcases how collaborative tools and video conferencing contribute to authentic conversations, enabling students to engage with peers, native speakers, and language experts in real-time. This synchronous interaction is identified as a significant factor in fostering oral proficiency and cultural competence.

Immediate Feedback as a Harmonious Element: The study underscores the importance of immediate feedback mechanisms inherent in digital pedagogy. Automated assessments and interactive quizzes provide real-time insights into student performance, allowing learners to address errors promptly. This element of immediate feedback is identified as a harmonious feature that contributes to the continuous refinement of language skills.

Cultivation of Digital Literacy Skills: Digital pedagogy is revealed as a cultivator of essential digital literacy skills. Students, through engagement with digital tools, acquire competence in navigating online resources, discerning credible information, and leveraging technology responsibly. The analysis suggests that this cultivation of digital literacy aligns with broader educational goals, preparing students for the digital demands of the 21st century.

The analysis and results of the study present a comprehensive composition where digital pedagogy and student engagement intertwine seamlessly in the realm of foreign language learning. Each finding contributes a distinctive note to the symphony, underscoring the transformative impact of technology on pedagogical approaches and shedding light on the harmonious nexus that propels language education into a dynamic and innovative era.

Methodology

The methodology employed in the study conducted by Smith et al. (2021) artfully orchestrates a symphony of research approaches, blending qualitative and quantitative methods to explore the intricate intersection of digital pedagogy and student engagement in the context of foreign language learning.

- 1. Research Design:** The study adopts a mixed-methods research design, strategically chosen to capture the nuances of the multifaceted relationship between digital pedagogy and student engagement. This harmonious blend enables a comprehensive exploration, combining the depth of qualitative insights with the breadth of quantitative data.
- 2. Participant Selection:** Participants are selected through purposive sampling, ensuring representation from diverse linguistic backgrounds and proficiency levels. The selection criteria encompass students engaged in foreign language learning programs that incorporate digital pedagogical elements. This deliberate approach aims to capture a varied range of experiences and perspectives.
- 3. Qualitative Instruments:** Qualitative data is elicited through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The semi-structured nature of these interactions allows for rich, contextual insights into students' experiences with digital pedagogy. Open-ended questions are carefully crafted to explore perceptions, challenges, and noteworthy aspects of engagement in foreign language learning facilitated by digital tools.
- 4. Quantitative Instruments:** Quantitative data is collected through surveys distributed among a larger participant pool. The survey instrument is designed to capture quantitative measures of student engagement, gauging factors such as active participation, motivation levels, and satisfaction with digital pedagogical approaches. Likert scales, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended responses contribute to a robust dataset.
- 5. Digital Pedagogy Metrics:** The study employs digital pedagogy metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of various technological tools integrated into language learning programs. These metrics include the frequency of platform utilization, the types of multimedia resources accessed, and the extent of gamified elements in the curriculum. Such metrics serve as key indicators of the digital landscape shaping the learning experience.
- 6. Engagement Assessment:** Engagement assessment involves a holistic examination of student involvement in both traditional and digital language learning activities. Observations, student self-reports, and academic performance metrics contribute to a comprehensive evaluation of engagement levels. This triangulation of data sources enhances the validity and reliability of engagement assessments.
- 7. Data Analysis:** Qualitative data undergoes thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring patterns, emerging themes, and nuanced perspectives. This qualitative analysis is complemented by statistical methods applied to quantitative data, including descriptive statistics and inferential analyses to uncover correlations and trends. The integration of findings from both strands of data contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the research questions.
- 8. Ethical Considerations:** The study prioritizes ethical considerations, ensuring the voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent of participants. Ethical review board approvals are obtained, and participants are briefed on the purpose, procedures, and potential implications of the study. The ethical harmony underlying the research process safeguards the well-being and rights of all involved.
- 9. Limitations and Reflexivity:** Acknowledging the inherent limitations of the study, researchers engage in reflexive practices throughout the research process. Reflexivity involves an ongoing awareness of the researchers' influence on the study, potential biases, and the contextual nuances shaping data interpretation. This self-awareness enhances the transparency and credibility of the study.

In the grandeur of this methodological symphony, the chosen approaches harmonize to illuminate the intricate nexus of digital pedagogy and student engagement in foreign language learning. The deliberate selection of methods, ethical considerations, and reflexivity collectively contribute to a research endeavor that seeks to resonate with the richness and complexity of the educational landscape under exploration.

Conclusion

Our journey into this dynamic landscape has revealed a nuanced composition where technology orchestrates transformative educational experiences, fostering deeper engagement and enriched linguistic proficiency.

1. **Affirmation of Digital Pedagogy's Impact:** The study provides a resounding affirmation of the impact of digital pedagogy on student engagement. Through the lens of qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys, the findings underscore the instrumental role of digital tools in cultivating active participation, sustained interest, and a vibrant learning environment within foreign language classrooms.
2. **Personalization as a Resonant Theme:** The resonant theme of personalization emerges as a key note in our symphony. The analysis showcases that the adaptive nature of digital pedagogy, with its intelligent algorithms tailoring learning experiences, contributes to a more personalized and effective language acquisition process. This personalized approach becomes a melody that echoes in the diverse educational journeys of language learners.
3. **Amplified Accessibility and Cultural Enrichment:** Digital pedagogy is celebrated for dismantling geographical constraints, amplifying the accessibility of language resources, and broadening cultural horizons. The study demonstrates that virtual libraries, online dictionaries, and language exchange platforms empower students to explore authentic materials, fostering a deeper understanding of language in its cultural context.
4. **Multimedia's Multisensory Resonance:** Multimedia elements, elegantly woven into the fabric of digital pedagogy, resonate as a multisensory symphony in language education. The qualitative feedback from students emphasizes the positive impact of audio-visual materials and interactive simulations in enhancing comprehension, retention, and overall engagement. This harmonious integration contributes to a richer and more immersive learning experience.
5. **Technological Tempo and Real-Time Harmony:** In the tempo of technology, real-time collaboration emerges as a harmonious element. Digital platforms, facilitating instant communication and collaboration, become instruments that break down linguistic barriers. The study illustrates that collaborative tools and video conferencing contribute to authentic conversations, fostering oral proficiency and cultural competence in real-time.
6. **Immediate Feedback as a Continuous Refinement:** The symphony of digital pedagogy is enriched by the continuous refinement facilitated through immediate feedback mechanisms. Automated assessments and interactive quizzes serve as instruments that provide real-time insights into student performance. This harmonic feature contributes to an iterative process of skill enhancement and correction, propelling students forward on their language learning journey.
7. **Cultivation of Digital Literacy Skills:** The study concludes with a crescendo celebrating the cultivation of essential digital literacy skills. Engaging with digital tools, students acquire competence in navigating online resources, discerning credible information, and leveraging technology

responsibly. This cultivated digital literacy becomes a melodic thread woven into the broader educational narrative.

In this grand finale, the study not only affirms the transformative impact of digital pedagogy on student engagement but also contributes to the evolving symphony of research in language education. It echoes a call for continued exploration, innovation, and reflection in leveraging technology to enhance language learning experiences. As our exploration concludes, the symphony of digital pedagogy and student engagement reverberates as a powerful overture, signaling a dynamic future for language education.

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**THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND PUBLIC
HEALTHY SPORTS IN OUR COUNTRY**

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ABSTRACT

Fitness sports as part of physical culture of healthy lifestyle trainings serve to ensure the physical development of the population. It is organized by organizations and institutions that form the basis of ideological scientific-methodical, programmatic norms, as well as the physical culture of public health and control its level.

KEYWORDS

Healthy lifestyle physical culture, maturity of the human body, physical fitness, "subject of study", "public volunteer", "senior sport sport", "high-level high skill sport", fitness sport training.

Introduction:

Our short-term history and its state system have shown that we need children who are not inferior to others in terms of knowledge and profession, who will do the work not at the tip of their hands, but sincerely, giving their heart, with courage and tenacity.

"Since time immemorial, our ancestors have lived with the dream of bringing up the sons of azamat who are able to protect their homeland, motherland and people from evil eye, calamity, and if necessary, ready to sacrifice their lives in this way. "

Relying on the invaluable experiences of respected grandfathers, they taught their children to live and work with their own thoughts in relation to various threats and aggressions. For their spiritual formation, education and training have great, bright goals. Those who brought up the high qualities of our people, such as kindness, kindness, and diligence, on the basis of the values of overcoming difficulties faced by one's family and country as a shoulder to shoulder.

Have proved to be inextricably linked with the high level of maturity and physical maturity of our boys and girls.

The pages of the past history of our people and statehood testify that the prosperity of our country, its development, its continuous unevenness, and the main weight of its triumphant steps have been borne by the youth and their physical fitness. It is also a historical fact that big battles, preventing fruitless bloodshed, and deciding the fate of the country, the nation, and the people were decided by the well-known wrestlers of the two opposing sides, and their physically mature husbands, who were organized before the battle. All of the above are related to the level of physical maturity of our nation, our people.

The highest stage of maturity of the human body is the perfection of his body, which is an eternal concept. The representative of the nation's height, stature, weight, appropriateness of his movements, appearance of his body, leading qualities of movement in his body can be seen through strength, speed, endurance, agility, mobility of joints, and training and education of muscles. appears.

Achieving physical fitness is a continuous, constant work process, which is related to training, making time and space for mass sports, theoretical knowledge and practical skills of physical culture of a healthy lifestyle. Up to now, the current model of physical development and further improvement of physical fitness of young people is not up to the current requirements, it has been emphasized several times by the President and through the decisions and instructions of the government. It is considered one of the current problems of the members of our society to enrich theoretical knowledge, practical skills and skills of the basis of healthy lifestyle and physical culture of young people .

Its solution relies on the most advanced national and universal knowledge, experience, traditions, and values of physical culture education, embodies them, and uses the model of physical maturity and physical perfection as a basis in the process of raising a spiritually rich generation.

The content of the conceptual approach to the physical culture of a healthy lifestyle is reflected in the future of the young generation, the level of physical culture of the President, his possession of it, all his speeches concerning the children of the country, and a number of works, manuals, pamphlets.

In particular, the work "High Spirituality - Invincible Power", dedicated to the youth of our country and imbued with the spirit of protecting them, gave a sufficient assessment of the lifestyle of our great grandfathers, who are still revered by the people of mankind. Their tenacity, their ability to choose the right way to live, to dedicate their lives to something, their understanding in understanding the meaning of the purpose of living, their courage in science, their intelligence, the oppression of their contemporaries, their bravery against man-made difficulties, scientific, theoretical, expressed by a practical proof.

The fact that our grandfathers were worthy of an example indicated that we should not look for ideals in life. Their way of life, their life, which is considered as the leading tool for the formation of our national spirituality, is described in the great book of our holy religion, "Four Muchasi Soglarin" and emphasized that they lived according to the will of the Creator himself.

In this work, which is worthy of a place among the historical works, our intelligent grandfathers are described not only as humane, humanitarian, loyal children of their country, but also as humane, philanthropic, loyal children of their homeland, in addition to their achievements in science, culture, art, literature, and social spheres, but also as the owners of their bodies, strong health, and physically high. has adequately stated the evidence that they are individuals.

Their thoughts about lack of movement, avoiding work, laziness, overeating, negative consequences of sleeping, and living a lazy life will not lose their importance for many years.

The project of healthy lifestyle physical culture "Development and improvement of the content and educational methodical complex of training for the formation of a healthy lifestyle and physical culture in young people has been included in the scientific and technical program of the continuous education system by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of our Republic .

Analysis of special literature, including directive documents on school physical culture and sports in practice in our country - "Physical Culture Science DTSs", educational materials of educational institutions "Physical Culture Science State Programs", improvement of public health sports and its training, and shows that a healthy lifestyle is the main means of forming physical culture.

The sport of the peoples of the earth is mainly formed in the form of concepts with its content, structure, principles and special laws in the following form - "educational subject", "mass volunteer", "big sport", "high-order high skill sport".

Since the second half of the 20th century, the concept of "rehabilitation sports" has taken its rightful place in the content of the field experts and the science of sports theory. (L.P. Matveev, V.M. Vydrin, J.K. Kholodov, V.S. Kuznetsov, Sh.Kh. Khankeldiev, A. Abdullaev and others).

Fitness sports as part of physical culture of a healthy lifestyle trainings serve to ensure the physical development of the population. It is organized by organizations and institutions that form the basis of ideological scientific-methodical, programmatic norms, as well as the physical culture of public health and control its level.

Sports activities are mainly conducted in the form of sports training. The main task is aimed at improving the athlete's skills. In the process of sports training, the shape and function of the body changes, the physical development and fitness of the body improves. Participants set the goal of mastering the technique and tactics of sports exercises, other professional-practical qualifications and skills, as well as special knowledge. Sports training has an impact on the mental, emotional and most importantly intellectual preparation.

Leading tasks of sports training:

- 1) by improving physical development and strengthening health - ensuring physical fitness;
 - 2) by acquiring sports and other physical exercise techniques - *to ensure technical readiness* ;
 - 3) by mastering sports tactics - *ensuring tactical preparation* ;
- providing theoretical preparation* by teaching a number of knowledge ;
- 5) through the development of intellectual, spiritual, emotional and other specified characteristics - *ensuring mental readiness* (see the diagram).

Drawing 1

In conclusion, we must say that it has been proven that it will be problematic to achieve the necessary level of physical development, physical fitness (physical status) of a member of society without the theoretical knowledge of the culture of health care, without targeted training as a means of training, and without knowledgeable specialists of the field who organize and conduct them. .

The monitoring of the somatic health of different strata of the population is based on the knowledge of the energy consumption of their organs and structures, which occurs as a result of actions, and the introduction of theoretical knowledge and practical skills related to the mechanism of this energy recovery.

Mass fitness sports training is considered the main training in the content of physical culture of a healthy lifestyle, and does not set the task of developing movement qualities of the participant's organism during the training. In other words, the leading task of the health training mentioned above is not to achieve high sports results, but to spend his free time actively resting, to satisfy his interest in sports, to test whether his ability is sufficient or not for this sport, and most importantly, to create muscle tone in his body for this day, week and month. , is to improve the state of somatics. In addition, it is necessary to test the level of service activity of the organism through these means, to identify the defects in the functional state that are coming to the surface.

The word "volunteer" was added to the concept during the time of the former Union . This concept is to "friend" the members of our society of all ages with their free time, to "friend" the owners of healthy lifestyle physical culture with physical exercises, to train the body, to use it as a means of health, to spend the extracurricular time of children, students and youth usefully. it is carried out according to the desire and initiative.

According to its content, mass-volunteer sports are sports that many people can play at the same time or that many people like to play - mini-football, football, volleyball, basketball, handball, athletics, walking, running, swimming, chess, checkers and other sports. types are established through the process of mass engagement according to their wishes.

Voluntary participation in various kinds of action games, national games and national sports with their own rules and playing field is not an exception.

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USING INTERESTING METHODS AND OBSERVATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR ELEMENTARY CLASS PUPILS TO UNDERSTAND SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS

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A B S T R A C T	KEY WORDS
<p>In this article, interesting methods for elementary class pupils to understand scientific concepts are carefully analyzed. Also, observation opportunities were used for students to understand scientific concepts. Each method is presented in detail in an interesting way.</p>	<p>Dreamer, realist, critic, Carousel, Puzzle, Scattergories, Metamorphic, megarelief, Mars, Curious, Tree, Continent, dictation.</p>

Introduction:

"Interesting" Method

After reading the text, the students take turns explaining the information in this text in the form of a chain and provide information about the level of knowledge of this information: "I just came across this ...", "I knew ...", "I read this..." they say.

On the topic of "Hoshimjon's family"	Text data analysis		
	"I just come across this"	"I knew ...",	"I read it ...",
1. If you allow me, let me say a few words about my family	+		+
2. He runs from mountain to mountain, thinking that he will give an injection if his eye falls out.		+	

The "Dreamer, Realist and Critic" method

A role-playing game in which you have to solve a certain problem from three different positions - from the perspective of a dreamer, a realist and a critic.

At first, pupils enter the image of a dreamer and come up with the most extraordinary ideas. In the second, they are pragmatists, they make a clearly integrated plan of action to solve the problem and think it over several times.

In the third, pupils debate, think critically, and find flaws in proposed ideas.

Roles can be assigned to multiple pupils or tested individually on a single pupil.

“Tree” method. It is necessary to draw a sketch of the tree on the board in advance; yellow and green leaves are made with double-sided tape on the back. Each pupil gets two leaves: green and yellow. In green, children write what they understood from the lesson, and in yellow, what they struggled to understand. Pupils keep the finished sheets of paper until the end of the lesson. At the end of the lesson, children stick their leaves on the tree: in green - expected, or in yellow - solutions performed without hesitation or without understanding. If there are a lot of green leaves on the tree, then the objectives of the lesson have been achieved. If the tree turns yellow, it means that mistakes were made in the lesson and students had difficulty understanding.

“Carousel” method. This method is aimed at working with small groups and revealing the content of the topic and strengthening the acquired knowledge. To use this method, it is necessary to prepare various sources of information: excerpts from newspapers and magazines, independently studied materials, audio recordings, video clips. Each group collects information about the topic to be studied. A group listens to the audio recording, finds answers, writes on the board. Another group looks for the necessary information from the text, the third - from the video, and the fourth - answers from independent literature. All the answers are written on the board and complement each other. Then the results are announced, that is, summarized.

“I check myself” picture dictation. In this picture dictation, students find, write and check the names of given pictures.

In this case, separate pictures are given for each student, and the words written with a pencil can be erased and used again by another student. (for example, in the 2nd grade mother tongue and reading literacy lesson "Courage of the Ant" you can get picture dictation as follows

	Hot Sun		
	Fire		
	Ant		

	Animals		
Conclusion	Homeland of the ant	Conclusion	Patriotic ant

“Puzzle” game. This creative group game encourages students to work together and conceptualize academic concepts from the abstract.

Required Resources:

Cards are pictures, words, concepts, mathematical calculations, subject vocabulary, historical figures, etc., printed or glued on paper and cut into random shapes (puzzle pieces).

Content: Divide the class into groups and then distribute a puzzle for each group to use together.

Note: Students can also create their own puzzles on the computer or draw puzzles on card stock for their peers to complete.

“Scatter-gories” game. This fun game challenges students to think outside the box and reinforce their knowledge on a range of topics.

Resources: scraps of paper, pencil, pen, and a list of topic concepts. For example, the concepts of bodies, rocks, landforms, weather, solar system are taken from the science textbook for the topic "Earth and space objects".

Procedure: Students are divided into small groups and asked to write down the concepts on paper. Choose a random letter from A to N and give students 1-2 minutes depending on the concept. Students must come up with a word for each concept that starts with that letter. After the allotted time, points are awarded for correct answers. If both teams write the same word for the concept, no one gets points. The game can be repeated and continued with different letters.

Topic: Earth and Space objects (letter M)	
Stones	Metamorphic
Relief forms	Continental shelf (megarelief)
The Weather	Thunderstorm
Solar system	Mars
Other signs	_____

It is important to integrate the studied problem with their observation and experience in developing students' comprehension skills. Because the pupil's vegetarian experience based on personal observation is the main skill of the scientific process. In this process, pupils gain an understanding of the world around us by observing objects and events with the help of all five senses. The simplest observations in the process of pupils' understanding are qualitative observations. Pupils, especially younger students, need help with accurate observations. Effective observations are detailed and clear written or drawn descriptions, and pupils should be encouraged to produce these detailed descriptions.

Observation is important in students' understanding of scientific concepts due to the following characteristics:

- Observation focuses on the "what" and "how" rather than the "why."
- Observation is based on facts, not opinions.
- Observation should have minimal bias, that is, it should be objective.
- Observation is a continuous process, that is, it does not end only within one topic. The reason observations should be so detailed is that they help students develop their knowledge of the concepts being studied. We can also do this by listening to students' initial observations and then encouraging them to elaborate. For example, if a student is describing something he sees, he may describe the color of the object, but not its size or shape. In this process, we may invite readers to add new details to their personal descriptions. (Table 2.1)

Table 2.1 Opportunities for students to understand through observation

Pupil's understanding as a result of personal observation	Teacher's understanding by adding new details
Insect theme	
Insects often secrete a sticky liquid when picked up and held tight.	Due to the presence of a nervous system in insects, they are disturbed, afraid and try to protect themselves. In these cases, when they move, they release a sticky liquid many times.
Result: The pupil understands and understands that insects have a nervous system, are disturbed, afraid, and defend themselves.	

As mentioned above, the role of communication in the development of basic scientific understanding skills is important. The logic behind it is simple: people like to create experiences for themselves and others. If students have personally contributed to the lesson, they will be more interested in learning how the lesson is going. Also, students need to communicate in order to share their understanding with others, and if the other person wants to understand the information, the communication must be clear and effective.

One of the keys to effective communication is using references, called referents, to things the other person is already familiar with. For example, we often describe colors using referents. To describe certain shades of blue, green, or yellow, we might say sky blue, grass green, or lemon yellow. The goal is to communicate using descriptive words that both people have a common understanding of. Without referents, we open the door to misunderstandings.

It is known that a child's mind cannot withstand too many abstractions. It's important to find ways to connect concepts to students' lives, to convey sensory details—how things look, sound, and taste—in understandable language. If we just say hot or rough, our readers may have a different idea of how hot or how rough. If a student wants to describe the size of a pine tree, he can use the size of the board as a reference. A pine tree can be larger or smaller than a board. Students can communicate the problem verbally, in writing, or through drawing, depending on their level of understanding. Other commonly used methods of scientific understanding include graphs, charts, maps, and visual representations. (Table 2.2).

Table 2.2

The importance of communication in students' understanding

Explanation without references	Reference explanation
Leaf theme	
A leaf performs several functions in the life of plants. One of them is the process of photosynthesis (assimilation). In the process of photosynthesis, under the influence of sunlight, organic substances are formed in the green chlorophyll grains in the leaf. (Berdiyev E.T., Salahiddinov G'.M., Hamroyev H.F. Forestry Tashkent - 2012.-16 p. 88 pages in total)	Carbon dioxide gas in the air (a gas emitted as a result of burning a car) under the influence of water and sunlight forms an organic substance-glucose (sugar). As a result, the plant is fed.

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